

Satu Huuhka (Editor)

Circularity in the Built Environment Proceedings of the 2025 conference

held in Tampere, Finland, September 16–18 2025

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Call for contributions

Committees

Organising committee members

Session hosts

Scientific committee members

Preface

Dear reader,

It has been my pleasure to chair the organisation of the 2nd International Conference on Circularity in the Built Environment (CiBEn 2025), which was held in Tampere, Finland, in September 16–18, 2025. The first edition of the conference was organised in the Netherlands in 2017 by the Recycling Laboratory of Delft University of Technology, in conjunction with the EU Horizon 2020 project ‘HISER’. At that time, the conference underwent with a different name, namely the ‘International conference on Advances in Recycling and Management of Construction and Demolition Waste’. The next conference, rebranded CiBEn, was scheduled to take place in 2021–22. Alas, it was first postponed and eventually cancelled due to the still raging COVID-19 pandemic. This way, CiBEn2025 in Tampere became the second conference in the series and the first one to actually bear the CiBEn title. I wish to express my sincerest gratitude to Professor Francesco di Maio and Assistant Professor Abraham Gebremariam from Delft University of Technology, who did not hesitate to trust their conference brand on the hands of a new team for the duration of the 2025 edition.

Like the very first conference, this one also came about thanks to an EU project. The conference was initially planned as the final event for the project ‘Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy’ or ‘ReCreate’ for short. ReCreate (EU Horizon 2020 Grant Agreement 958200) is an international research effort to push reuse of precast concrete elements, not originally designed for disassembly, towards market-readiness in the EU. However, over the course of the two years that it took to plan CiBEn2025, it became apparent that the timelines of the conference and ReCreate’s final event would diverge. While CiBEn2025 featured many contributions from ReCreate and provided an opportunity to present its findings, the project will continue for another year beyond the conference to finalise outstanding work.

Nevertheless, ReCreate inspired a structure for the call for contributions of the conference. The thematic structure of CiBEn2025 mimics the work package structure of the project (see Huuhka et al., 2023), influenced by a multi-level perspective on technological transitions (see Geels, 2002) and designed to address barriers to uptake of novel circular construction solutions beyond mere technology. To facilitate a circularity transition, it is imperative that researchers and practitioners increasingly understand that such a transition requires much more than a viable technology. While technology is foundational, once it exists, the hurdles to market uptake are usually anything but technological. Instead, they often pertain to human factors: industry and company cultures, value chain organisation, customer expectations (including prejudices), professional identities of the involved groups, regulatory lobbying, and education and knowledge (or the lack thereof), etc. It is my hope that the holistic approaches of ReCreate and CiBEn2025 could act as models for future circular construction endeavours how to address these aspects alongside the technological ones.

The call for contributions for CiBEn2025, which is available at the end of this proceedings book, was drafted not to exclude the more traditional focus of the first conference edition, i.e. management and recycling of waste materials from construction and demolition. To my delight, many of the submitted contributions nonetheless gravitated towards higher levels of circularity, such as extending lives of built assets or their structures, or reusing the latter in the same or a remanufactured state. In my view, this reflects advancements in the state of science since the first conference: in eight years, research into a circular built environment has broadened out from an exclusive waste/material perspective to include manifold approaches and question-settings.

In total, 145 contributions were submitted for review. The authors thereof were based in 30 countries, with all continents represented except Australia/Oceania and Antarctica. Of the submitted contributions, 115 made it into the conference as presentations. This proceedings book contains both abstracts and

papers of the presented contributions, as the authors were given the freedom to choose which type they submitted. All the contributions, except the keynotes, have been peer-reviewed in a double-blind setting by two independent reviewers. This book lists the contributions under each theme in the alphabetical order of the title, so no order of importance is implied. The proceedings have been put together from ‘camera-ready’ files delivered by the authors. Due to this, some discrepancies may appear in the graphical appearance and/or how the content is structured.

Heartfelt thanks to all organising committee members, keynote speakers, authors and presenters, session hosts, and scientific committee members, i.e. abstract and paper reviewers. Organising an international conference is very much a group effort, in which each of you had an essential role. I hope the conference can provide directions and inspiration for research into a circular built environment for years to come – at the very least until the next edition of the event, which is scheduled to take place at Guangxi University, China, in September 2027. Advancing science and practice through these kinds of events is crucial, as the urgency of the built environment sector’s circularity transition in the face of the global environmental crisis can hardly be overstated, and neither can the sector’s immense weight in it.

Prof. Satu Huuhka

Conference chair, CiBEn2025
Coordinator, ReCreate project

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Revision notes

This revised edition from October 2025 contains the following corrections:

- Preface edited to include the location and timing of the next conference (the current page),
- Two contribution titles corrected in the table of contents (pp. 5 & 7),
- Details of one abstract corrected (p. 159–160),
- The names of session hosts edited to rectify spelling errors and to reflect changed duties during the conference (pp. 342–344), and
- DOI link changed to the DOI version which represents all document versions, and which will always resolve to the latest one (pp. 2–349).

Circularity in the Built Environment 2025

Keynote lectures

Hope in Circulation: Places Where Circularity and Reuse Build Community and Spark Innovation

Jennifer S Minner*¹

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Keywords: Circularity, Built Environment, Reuse, Historic Preservation, Justice, Embodied Carbon

Circularity offers a powerful framework for seeing the built environment anew. As a set of ideas, practices, and technologies, circularity can spur imagination, generating new energy and creativity in caring for places. Circularity illuminates how we build, maintain, and demolish places under linear systems (Huuhka, 2023). It exposes the dark sides of this linear system of demolition and waste, while inspiring alternatives that reorder those material and social relationships into a more regenerative system (Heisel, 2022). Through a circular imagination, we can sharpen education and technology and their application in building a more sustainable and equitable built environment (Minner, 2021). Circularity can also encourage innovative forms of governance. In these ways, circularity becomes a magnifying glass for social systems and a projection of hope in building better futures.

This keynote speech shares stories from collaborative research on circular transitions in New York State over the past five years. The talk first foregrounds insights from collaborative research with community leaders, fellow researchers, and local and state officials within the Circularity, Reuse, and Zero Waste Development (CR0WD) network. Next, it will highlight insights from the creation of the *Embodying Justice in the Built Environment*. Following, the talk will spotlight the incredible creativity and drive of youth involved in learning about circularity and applying its ideas to their community. The talk will mention the development of analytical tools and methods for visualizing a spectrum of reuse in the local built environment in Ithaca, New York. The talk will conclude with an emphasis on the importance of bringing together the tools, methods, creativity, and insights from researchers around the world at the 2nd *Circularity in the Built Environment Conference*.

The Circularity, Reuse, and Zero Waste Development (CR0WD) Network

The CR0WD network brings together community leaders; reuse and heritage professionals; state and local government officials; professionals in planning, architecture, waste management, and the trades; as well as faculty and students, among others, who are engaged in re-envisioning the way the built environment is planned, constructed, maintained, repaired, and reused. The CR0WD network's origins are in a humble, but regular set of weekly Zoom meetings during the COVID pandemic. These sparked a substantial number of collaborations between community organizations, academics, and government agencies in conducting research and working toward change on the ground. Since then, the network has been conducting research about new economic and urban development opportunities for all sectors to redirect the flow of valuable building materials from landfills to community economic development efforts. The network builds on ties between heritage and reuse and the cultural, social, economic, and environmental benefits of prolonging the life of the built environment. The CR0WD network has produced local government guides, tours, exhibitions, toolkits and

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other resources that have inspired municipal resolutions and state-level legislation (Circularity, Reuse, and Zero Waste Development, 2023; CR0WD, n.d.; Minner et al., 2025).

One of the most important insights from work in this network is the rich collaborations that are transdisciplinary, bringing together city planning, architecture, heritage/historic preservation, waste management, and reuse, among other fields. Circularity has been an important way to articulate those connections and expand them into a wider network. We have observed important synergies between historic preservation (also known as heritage conservation) and reuse centers. The CR0WD network's collaborations has been inspired by visions of rethinking waste in heritage (see, for example, Ross and Angel, 2019) and bringing together the heritage trades and rehabilitation with the cutting edge in deconstruction practices (City of San Antonio Office of Historic Preservation, n.d.).

While deconstruction practices have been mostly unknown by the general public, CR0WD partners have observed that many people understand the value of thrift and regularly practice circularity and reuse through the sharing and purchase of secondhand clothing and household items. Some homeowners in the US already complete home improvement projects with salvaged materials, and some local developers already engage in the salvage, sharing, and reuse of building materials on an informal basis. We found examples in the local community of many different alternatives to demolition along what we began to call a building reuse to waste hierarchy (see figure 1). These alternatives to demolition included building maintenance and refurbishment, adaptive reuse and extension of buildings, and building relocation, in addition to salvage and deconstruction.

Figure 1. Building Reuse to Waste Hierarchy. Developed by Wyeth Augustine-Marceil and additional researchers in the Just Places Lab.

We noted that people were interested in these examples and created a mobile tour on a Pocket Sites App to share examples (Just Places Lab and Historic Ithaca, 2024). As a group, we gave many presentations together and noted how people appreciated tangible stories about a spectrum of reuse in the built environment.

Embodying Justice in the Built Environment

Collaborating researchers and I began to explore how social justice and equity could be more explicit in this work. With support from the Carbon Neutral Cities Alliance, we initiated the *Embodying Justice in the Built Environment* project, a multi-university and multi-city collaborative project that envisions how urban transformations in circularity and waste (Minner, et. al. 2024), and land use and zoning (Poe, et al., 2025), can be used to promote reparative planning in cities. The series began by analyzing existing work in justice and the built environment, as well as recommended policies in a framework called *City Policy Framework for Dramatically Reducing Embodied Carbon*, a resource for cities looking to adopt policies to reduce embodied carbon (Carbon Neutral Cities Alliance and One Click LCA, 2020).

Embodying Justice in the Built Environment Guides and Workbooks are aimed at helping governments and community organizations to center justice and equity in their work toward carbon neutrality. A key insight in the creation of the guides was how abstract ideas of justice and equity can become more explicit. Even more exciting were the many examples of Indigenous nations, local government agencies, and community organizations in North America that were already doing this work. Out of these examples, we drafted a series of practice stories that illustrate where progress is being made. More recently, we have begun to delve into similarities and differences with the efforts of cities in Europe, comparing notes with researchers at the Association of European Schools of Planning.

The Circular Visions of Youth

Circularity has proven to be a deep catalyst for community-based work in the Cornell Urban Research to Action – Youth (CURTA-Y). The program was dreamed up by a Cornell undergraduate student inspired by CROWD, and the program was incubated in the Just Places Lab. The youth program connects students at Cornell with high school students in the Binghamton tri-city region of New York to identify opportunities for creating a more circular and sustainable built environment in their community. In the course that I teach, which runs the program, university students learn about circularity and then teach related concepts and methods to the high school students.

The youth program has since supported multiple cohorts of high school students in exploring the embodied carbon and alternative potential paths for old buildings threatened with demolition. We have used research techniques such as Photovoice and zine-making to explore the potential for building and building material reuse to contribute to the community (Boghossian et al., 2025). In 2025, *Circular Visions: Binghamton through the Eyes of Youth* (see figures 2, 3) was produced, which presents observations of youth in CURTA-Y (Wang, 2025). From this video, one can see and hear the advocacy of young people and how they visualize principles of circularity as contributing to the beauty and sustainability of the city and its region.

Figure 2. Still from Circular Visions: Binghamton through the Eyes of Youth.

Figure 3. Still from Circular Visions: Binghamton through the Eyes of Youth.

Analytical and Visualization Tools to Communicate a Spectrum of Reuse

Finally, this talk will present insights from cross-disciplinary research conducted by the Just Places Lab in collaboration with Cornell's Realtime Urbanism Lab. Drawing from planning, architecture, and regional science, the research team used a range of analytical and visualization methods to explore local circularity and reuse strategies. These include agent-based modeling (Bower et al., 2025), 3D modeling, and life cycle analysis. In this work, we grappled with the challenges of modeling developer decision-making, social learning, and potential outcomes of urban development scenarios that were undergoing rapid change and in

one case controversial. Our findings highlight a productive tension: the use of sophisticated, data-intensive methods often contrasts with the need to communicate complex ideas clearly and in a timely manner to a broader public unfamiliar with the technical aspects of circularity.

Conclusions

In CR0WD, we continue to work toward a more circular built environment during a critical time of dimming belief in climate science. New York State and its local communities can rise to this challenge, applying concepts of circularity to realize more sustainable and inclusive urban development. CR0WD is only one of many regional, national, and international networks that are working to help communities and regions around the world apply circularity in the interest of progress in addressing not only climate change, but a myriad of other environmental, social, and economic challenges. The many diverse research projects and strategies are being showcased at the *2nd International Conference on Circularity in the Built Environment*. These many examples from around the world reflect a growing commitment across fields to reimagine care of the built environment. Your research projects and professional practices are developing the ideas, methods, and tools needed to spark change and keep hope in circulation.

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On the use of studying history in our aspiration to a more circular building economy

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This keynote lecture will start from the dispiriting observation that past building cultures have always been more circular than those of the present day. Taken as a whole, building projects from past societies systematically used more local materials, more bio-based and non-toxic materials, integrated more reused components, and often resorted to more refined forms of recycling than those of our present societies. These societies, in many cases, seem also to have been better equipped to erect structures that stood and still stand the test of time better than ours, for a wide range of reasons. A subsidiary observation is that the circular practices from the past were not ethically motivated. Instead, builders, commissioners, workforces, etc. resorted to circular practices for pragmatic reasons: it made economic sense, it was quicker, safer, it saved money. Those are exactly the same motivations that, in our current building cultures, make it so easy to resort to linear production methods for the built environment, and so difficult and costly to harken back to significant degrees of adaptive reuse, component reuse, or high-grade recycling.

That realization has led, in the past two decades, to an increased interest in circular practices from the past, exemplified by the question of building component reuse. This renewed interest emerged in the fields of archaeology, environmental history, architecture and construction history. The lecture will review some of the important pieces of scholarship in that new tradition, with a focus on what these studies can teach us. The lessons appear to have three layers of depth. A first layer reveals a gigantic gap between the pre-modern and modern economic and technological contingencies that frame the building industry. The second set of conclusions reveals that refined operational habits and formal procedures facilitated building component reuse in the past. These constitute a form of low-tech sophistication, largely eroded in the meantime, most of our contemporaries have no idea of, and which might, in some cases, be easily revived. The third, and more existential level of conclusions, is that tracing the history of circular practices through history reveals a story of regress instead of progress. In other words, it allows to interpret the evolutions of the socio-technical regimes that rule the production of architecture from an unexpected perspective. To put things differently, it allows, at last, to historicize the emergence of the linear building economy that safely departs from *progress* narratives; narratives which still hold a firm – and paralyzing - grip on our imaginaries of what transitioning the building sector might mean.

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The built environment as a living system: towards resource- and carbon-efficient cities

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Keywords: socioeconomic metabolism

ABSTRACT

Socioeconomic metabolism (SEM) conceptualizes societies as systems that draw resources from nature, transform them to meet human needs, and return wastes and emissions – much like a biological metabolism. The focus of SEM lies on the type and size of flows (materials and energy) that enter, circulate within, and leave societies as they sustain themselves.

Within the SEM framework, the built environment is a central component. It concentrates long-lived stocks of construction materials and represents a vast reservoir of secondary resources. Its characteristics—from composition to spatial organization—also shape the type and quantity of resources required to provide essential services. Understanding and characterizing the various roles of the built environment’s material stocks is therefore essential for designing pathways toward resource-, energy-, and carbon-efficiency.

Achieving this requires a detailed mapping of the built environment’s material stocks. This involves identifying what resources are embedded where, in what quantities, and with what expected lifetimes. Modeling at high spatial resolution is a complex task, but it supports predictive assessments of secondary resource availability and reveals drivers and patterns of material stocks across society.

Viewing the built environment as an active component of our socioeconomic metabolism allows us to analyze the impact of planning decisions at various scales. And as material stocks are increasingly understood, their spatial simulation becomes possible and highly relevant for exploring various neighborhood design solutions. Coupled with holonic thinking (i.e., systems units function both independently and as part of a larger whole), material stock simulations could help uncover and optimize interactions across scales, from buildings to cities. This would ensure that interventions for sustainability are aligned across all levels of the built environment.

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Circularity in the Built Environment 2025

Urban mining

A novel Spatial Urban Energy and Materials Model: preliminary empirical findings

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Keywords: buildings, transport, energy, materials, circularity, machine-learning.

ABSTRACT

The important contribution of urban areas to global energy use and greenhouse gas emissions is widely acknowledged, with over 65% and 70%, respectively [1]. The built environment, formed by two key energy-consuming urban sectors (buildings and transport) is largely responsible for cities' energy and carbon footprint [2]. Nevertheless, as renewable penetration and energy efficiency gain traction across the EU and beyond, with both the buildings and mobility sectors benefiting from improved standards, codes and investment (e.g. retrofits), there is on one hand a greater emphasis on embodied energy and carbon in materials (buildings and infrastructure), as well as on the material implications of a number of decarbonization strategies [3], feeding the rising circularity agenda at global level.

There is a vast body of research exploring the way that cities are built (i.e. urban form) and their energy implications (e.g. [4], [5], [6]). There has been limited work, however, exploring the material impacts of urban design and urban planning choices, as well as the respective synergies and/or trade-offs with energy. Similarly, there has been limited research exploring the existing interdependencies of these two resource dimensions across the two key urban sectors: buildings and transport. Studies tend to isolate energy (e.g. [7]) or the material dimensions (e.g. [8], [9]) or treat circularity as an aggregate city-wide metric ([10], [11]).

Bridging this gap requires a spatial methodological framework that can jointly analyze energy and material intensities for the two sectors, and understand existing patterns in the light of consistent urban descriptors (urban form, socio-economic drivers, behavioral patterns...). Building from past work focused on the links between urban form and energy [12], a novel "Spatial urban energy and materials model" (SUE2M) has been developed to assess the impact of urban design and development choices in energy and materials altogether, for both buildings and transport sectors. This modelling approach uses machine learning techniques (neural networks) to model high-resolution urban data at block or district level. It is being trained and tested in two different case studies at European level (Porto and Berlin), to validate the most relevant and best-performing metrics and indicators, as well as suitable model architectures, based on publicly-available datasets. The analysis focuses both on physical urban dimensions, i.e. urban form indicators which are cross-cutting to the buildings and mobility sectors (e.g. density, mix of uses, accessibility...); and on socio-economic and cultural dimensions (e.g. demographics, education, housing prices and household size). These are used to estimate energy and materials intensities of both buildings and transport infrastructure.

The preliminary empirical results of SUE2M highlight the relevant role of urban form to explain and predict materials intensities, as it happened for energy. In particular, the joint analysis captures geographical trade-offs hot-spots, through an urban planning lens, which is expected to inform integrated urban decarbonization and circular pathways in the future.

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Advancing Urban Mining by Identifying Circularity Patterns in Deconstruction and Renovation

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Keywords: Urban Mining, Early Stage, Eco-design, Reuse, Recycle

ABSTRACT

A central component of urban mining involves identifying and mapping material stocks across a given territory. In France, a newly introduced legal requirement—the Products, Equipment, Materials and Waste (PEMD) diagnostic—enables the early-stage identification of PEMDs that will be generated during renovation or demolition works, as well as their potential recovery pathways. This research is based on a new dataset of 341 diagnostics, analyzed to identify patterns in PEMD generation. By classifying each operation according to the type of work (renovation or demolition), and the former use of the building, emerging trends were identified regarding the recovery pathways applicable to the different types of waste produced, as well as the types of reusable materials identified. Future work will focus on creating archetypes that could help predict material stocks generated in a territory.

INTRODUCTION

The construction sector is the main contributor to waste production in France, up to 70% of the total production [1]. Therefore, legislation drives the sector's transition through a circular economy (CE) by encouraging reuse and recycling of construction elements. CE strategies can take other forms such as specific designs for reuse, disassembly, or reversibility, and does not only focus on material flows, as circularity can be applied to energy and water flows also. However, the French operational sector associates the CE mainly with selective deconstruction and other recycle and reuse strategies [2], [3].

The operational sector is encountering a wide range of challenges in implementing CE strategies. Among them is the lack of visibility on material availability, which complicates the development of urban mining. Additionally, incorporating CE strategies requires adaptation to new practices. As no standardized framework has yet emerged, coordination among the various stakeholders in a

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project is being more difficult. Therefore, one key factor in successfully implementing a CE strategy is to integrate objectives at the earliest stages of a project. [3]

In 2020, the AGEC law (anti-waste for a circular economy) established new objectives in various sectors, including the construction sector. An Extended Producer Responsibility was established for construction products, and a new diagnostic became mandatory: the Product, Equipment, Material and Waste (PEMD) diagnostic. The objective is to identify, as early as possible, the PEMDs that will be generated during demolition or renovation works, along with the potential recovery pathways for their treatment, enabling the integration of appropriate targets from the initial project phases. This diagnostic must be carried out during the early stages of a project, before submitting any required urban planning permit application. It is performed by an assessor commissioned by the project owner who meets the competency requirements set out by decree. A standardized official form issued by the French administration defines the data to be reported, and a dedicated material nomenclature has been established to ensure consistency in data collection. The completed form must be submitted to the Scientific and Technical Center for Building (CSTB). Diagnostics can be filled out digitally via the PEMD platform developed by the CSTB, or manually.

This research aims to analyze PEMD diagnostics to identify some patterns in the potential for reuse or recycling in deconstruction or renovation projects. PEMD diagnostics follow a standardized format, enabling a macro-level analysis of the data. Although several studies have performed macro-level analyses of waste production—providing ratios [4] or predictive models [5]—none had access to such a detailed dataset, which includes reuse information alongside other treatment pathways and encompasses all building types. Data limitations have often constrained the scope of previous research.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The data used in this research were sourced from the PEMD platform, made accessible through a data-sharing agreement with the CSTB. A total of 341 diagnostics were used and analyzed. Each diagnostic consists of two distinct sections: the Waste section, which describes waste generation assuming no elements are reused, and the PEM (Product-Equipment-Material) section, which provides detailed information on all reusable components. Table 1 presents the data available for each section of the diagnostic. The data marked with an asterisk (*) are mandatory, while the others may not be available for every diagnostic.

Table 1. Overview of Available Data in the PEMD Diagnostics

<i>PEM</i>	<i>Waste</i>
PEM type*	Waste type*
Quantity*	Weight*
Unit*	Volume
Dimensions	Reutilization % *
Assembly type	Recycling % *
Conservation quality	Quarry Backfilling % *
	Incineration (Energy recovery) % *
	Incineration % *
	Landfill % *

Additional information is available for each project, such as the type of work (renovation or demolition) and the building's former use (housing, offices, etc.). PEMs are described in various

units - such as linear meters (lm) or units (u) - since they are still considered products. Wastes, by contrast, are systematically reported in tons (t), making direct comparison between PEMs and waste quantities impossible without a conversion table. For this reason, both were analyzed separately.

For this preliminary study, a statistical analysis was carried out on the dataset to identify general trends and patterns. To explore whether distinct trends emerge, two criteria were considered: building usage and type of work (renovation, demolition, mixed). For waste, treatment distributions were averaged without weighting, so that each project contributed equally to the analysis. Atypical projects were excluded based on their Jensen-Shannon distance from the median profile — a metric well-suited to percentage-based distributions summing to 100. Using a fixed threshold of 0.5, 35 projects were excluded for each criterion separately, and 5 projects did not have any waste diagnosed. For PEMs, due to unit heterogeneity, quantities were not compared directly. Instead, the analysis focused on frequency of occurrence: each time a specific PEM appeared in a project, it was counted once, regardless of the amount; if absent, it was counted as zero. This approach allows for comparison across projects without requiring unit conversion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Waste

Figure 1 shows the average distribution of the total weight of waste in potential recovery pathways. This distribution is presented by type of work. The “Total” represents the distribution of the whole dataset, and the “Mix” category is for projects involving both renovation and deconstruction. The French Energy Transition for Green Growth Act (TECV) of 17 August 2015 set a target of 70% recovery of waste from construction sector by 2020. As reuse, recycling and quarry backfilling are considered recovery routes by French legislation, the target can be met for deconstruction. However, renovation projects produce more final waste in proportion, and do not appear to meet the target limits.

These results only reflect the theoretical potential and do not account for actual project implementation; as such, they are likely to be more optimistic than what is observed in practice. This trend is confirmed by comparisons with the data presented in a report on the recycling of waste produced by construction and public works activities [1].

The number of diagnostics used for each building type is indicated in brackets. Reuse recovery route in this section is different than the reuse potential of PEMs, as in French legislation reusing a waste is categorized differently from reusing a product, equipment or material.

Figure 1. Distribution of Potential Recovery Routes by Type of Work

It appears that the function of the buildings has an influence on the potential for recovery of the materials produced (see Figure 2). Industrial buildings in the sample achieve an average recycling rate of up to 64%, likely due to the presence of metal structures. However, this category may include both metal-framed and other types of industrial buildings. Identifying the main structural material of each building could help reveal more specific trends in circularity performance.

Figure 2. Distribution of Potential Recovery Routes by Building Types

Building types containing fewer than 15 diagnostics have been greyed out, as the result is too unreliable.

Figure 3. Distribution of Potential Reuse Across Macro-categories of PEM by Building Types

PEMs – Reusable components

As shown in the 'Total' line of Figure 3, the main macro-categories in which reusable components were identified—listed in decreasing order of frequency—are 'Sanitary installations', 'Partitioning', 'Façades and external joinery', 'Networks', 'HVAC systems', and 'Furniture'. Collective housing, which accounts for 41% of the analyzed diagnostics, follows a similar pattern. For office buildings, the most frequently identified categories of reusable components—also presented in decreasing order—are 'Partitioning', 'Networks', 'Sanitary installations', 'Floor, wall and ceiling coverings', 'Furniture', and 'HVAC systems'. Overall, office buildings appear to generate reusable PEMs more frequently than collective housing. However, this trend should be confirmed by using a larger sample of office projects, as the present analysis is based on only 34 diagnosed cases. Reusable elements are rarely identified in the macro-categories 'Lifts and indoor transport equipment', 'Foundations and infrastructure', and 'Local electricity production equipment'.

Discussion

This statistical analysis shows that circularity potential trends vary depending on both the building's former use and the type of work undertaken. Renovation projects generate less recoverable waste than deconstruction projects. This is likely because they do not involve the removal of structural components such as concrete or metals, which are commonly recovered - although often for low-grade applications - and represent a significant share of the overall demolition waste mass. While the building's use significantly influences the circularity potential of waste generation, a more detailed analysis that also accounts for the main structural materials would allow for more accurate results. Office buildings appear to yield more reusable components than residential ones, which may be explained by the fact that offices are more frequently subject to renovation and therefore tend to contain materials in better condition. Data on other building use types would help identify the main sources of reusable material stock.

FUTURE WORK

This approach serves as an initial attempt to explore the potential of reusing and recycling materials in deconstruction and renovation projects. Future work will focus on refining this analysis by comparing the PEM and Waste sections through a standardized unit of measurement. A conversion table is currently being developed to express the data in weight units, which will allow for a more comprehensive comparison of reusable components and recyclable materials in these projects across France.

Moreover, additional data will become available and manually completed PEMD diagnostics are being converted into digital format. Upon completion of each project, an inspection form is required, documenting the effective material flows and end-of-life treatments followed during the operation. Analyzing these data alongside the PEMD diagnostics could provide valuable insights into the progress still needed toward circular practices. This will show the gap between theoretical diagnosis and actual implementation.

The ultimate objective of this ongoing work is to develop a predictive model capable of estimating the types of reusable components likely to be found in each project, as well as identifying potential recovery pathways for the different types of waste. This will be complemented by an assessment

of actual reuse feasibility, based on existing reuse guidelines and expert insights, to determine whether materials diagnosed as reusable at the deconstruction stage can indeed be reclaimed and reintegrated into new projects. This step is essential to account for technical, regulatory, or market barriers that may limit reuse.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of 341 diagnostics made it possible to identify certain criteria that influence the nature of material flows generated on deconstruction or renovation sites. Building type and type of work - renovation or deconstruction - are key parameters, but other factors such as construction year or primary structural material should also be examined in future research. Further research will aim to create a robust model and include the potential of reclaiming materials.

Since PEMD diagnostics is a relatively new practice, the quality of the data from this initial dataset may be questioned. Therefore, an update should be carried out in the coming years to monitor the evolution of trends and further investigate the causes behind these changes.

This study does not aim to provide stakeholders with specific recommendations on which elements should be recycled or reused, especially during the early stages of a project, when there is limited knowledge about potential material flows. Circular economy strategies will inevitably vary from one project to another, depending on technical, regulatory, and contextual constraints. However, the findings presented here highlight the potential for emerging sectors within the circular economy - whose development would help scale up and mainstream circular practices across projects. These results will be instrumental in early-stage Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), particularly when no project data is available and when the project is still flexible. They will help stakeholders assess the potential impacts of applying circular strategies and provide valuable insights into their environmental and economic implications.

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Approaching building lifetimes and hazard rates through demolition patterns

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Keywords: building lifetime, building stock, dynamic modeling, hazard rate, industrial ecology, urban dynamics

Despite their relevance in building stock modeling, building lifetimes are poorly understood and tend to form the weakest link in forecasting energy use, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, waste generation, and resource use. Here, we develop a methodology to trace building lifetimes for cohorts in two central areas built up after fires in the 1840s. Using Geographical Information System (GIS) data of the current building stock and archival material, we determined yearly hazard rates for buildings within the cohort 1841–1845 in the historical center of Trondheim, Norway. We find that hazard rates are very sensitive to events ranging from global to hyperlocal scales and that demolition rates have slowed down significantly since the 1980s when municipal preservation policies came into effect. In contrast, age-based lifetime approaches fail to capture the effects of such events as they only account for the delay between construction and demolition. We discuss the use and limitations of hazard rates to better reflect changes in demolition that are not correlated with building age. Our study underscores that building lifetimes are a property of a wider system rather than an attribute of individual structures. In that sense, hazard rates are a more suitable approach to capture spatiotemporal changes of building stocks and could be further used in scenarios in dynamic models.

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Assessing Carbon Payback Time of Replacements and Refurbishments in Zurich's Residential Buildings (2001–2019) Using Stock-Level CRLCA

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Keywords: building replacement and refurbishment; consequential replacement LCA (CRLCA); carbon payback time; residential buildings; range-bound analysis; per capita metric.

ABSTRACT. Under Switzerland's *inward development* policy, building replacement (BR) has become a prevalent strategy to urban renewal—yet its assumed advantage in delivering greater carbon savings over refurbishment is increasingly questioned. Refurbishment, defined as the preservation and continued use of existing buildings, is commonly framed as a circular economy practice. To identify the environmentally preferable strategy, this study evaluates the carbon payback time (CPBT) of replacement versus refurbishment in Zurich's residential buildings, using Consequential Replacement Life Cycle Assessment (CRLCA). CRLCA, as proposed by Huuhka et al. (2023) [1], isolates the post-decision carbon emissions resulting from replacement or retention choices by excluding historical and unaffected ones, enabling comparisons that reflect outcomes subject to strategic influence. This study extends CRLCA to the building stock level to enable a more representative evaluation than individual-building assessments. To operationalize this extension, two modeling methods are introduced: using a unified decision year to align projects with varying implementation timelines, enabling consistent evaluation of how decision timing influences CPBT outcomes; and estimating carbon emissions under optimistic and conservative assumptions, reflecting lower and upper bounds of key emission factors, to assess the sensitivity of CPBT outcomes. Moreover, a per capita metric complements the conventional per area approach, capturing both building-level and user-level carbon intensity.

The analysis draws on 335 residential BR projects completed in Zurich between 2001 and 2019 as the baseline scenario, and constructs two counterfactual refurbishment scenarios for comparison. The system boundaries follow the post-decision logic of CRLCA and include embodied (A1–A5, B5, C1) and operational (B6, B7) emissions related to heating demand, as defined by EN 15978. Four reference years (2010, 2013, 2016, 2019) are tested to explore the effect of policy timing, with 2013 closely aligning with actual implementation. Results show that CPBT is highly sensitive to both decision timing and metric selection. BR consistently exhibits the highest embodied and lowest operational emissions on a per-unit basis. Even under optimistic assumptions, BR only achieves payback before 2019; after that, it fails by either metric as decarbonization erodes the operational advantage of new buildings. This pattern extends to public buildings, where higher embodied impacts from more intensive construction, combined with lower operational demand per unit area, further disadvantage BR. Refurbishment proves more climate-conscious, overturning the assumption of greater carbon savings from replacement. Moreover, per capita metrics consistently yield more conservative results than per area metrics under identical conditions, demonstrating how metric choice shapes outcomes. The result highlights the value of per capita analysis in revealing individual carbon responsibility and fostering participatory, citizen-focused policymaking. Taken together, the study underscores the time-critical nature of construction policies for climate mitigation and adaptation, calling for continual reassessment as conditions evolve. It further emphasizes that the climate benefit from lifespan extension within circular construction is vital to advancing sustainability.

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Deriving temporal and spatial evidence of buildings from aerial orthophotos using computer vision

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Keywords: building stock, dynamic modeling, machine learning, industrial ecology

The built environment stock and its development are crucial to cover human needs but also have a substantial impact on the environment. Both have been studied extensively in the past, where research often focuses on the stock's material and typological composition, spatial patterns, services, or dynamics. Due to the long lifetimes of buildings and infrastructure, their stocks have high inertia, making it necessary to look at decades or even centuries to properly assess changes and trends. Obtaining evidence for these time spans is naturally challenging, especially since buildings and infrastructure were historically mostly subject to local governance, making systematic documentation for supralocal scale research scarce. Historical aerial orthophotos can, in principle, fill this niche: high-quality coverage can be found for almost the last century and follows the built environment in density. We demonstrate its value as evidence for mapping building stocks (dynamics) by applying machine learning to aerial orthophotos in Norway.

For this purpose, we use a convolutional neural network designed to detect building footprints. We use public domain data to train the network for colored and black and white images, predict the presence of buildings on images between 1937 and 2024, convert the predictions to building polygons, demonstrate the analysis across layers, and showcase the use for the comparison of stock dynamics across Norwegian cities. This proves the usability of historic orthophotos for obtaining spatially and temporally explicit evidence for building stocks at the level of individual buildings, not only in the case of Norway but anywhere such photos are available. Future applications of this data can build on our framework to assess spatiotemporal development patterns like lifetimes or land use at high resolution at any scale.

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Exploring the Role of City Information Modeling in Material Stock and Flow Analysis: A Literature Review

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Keywords: City Information Modeling, Material Flow Analysis, Material Stock Analysis, Urban Mining, Urban Circular Economy

ABSTRACT

In pursuing sustainable urban development, the circular economy (CE) concept has gained significant attention among academics, urban planners, and policymakers. Part of the urban circularity, the urban metabolism concept analyses flows and stocks of resources in cities, including material and energy flows. Holding the potential to tackle diverse challenges, cities are analyzing their metabolism through a circular approach, seeking solutions towards sustainable urban development. Acting as catalysts for sustainable and circular transitions, information technologies have emerged as potential tools to achieve sustainability goals. City Information Modeling (CIM) is one promising approach to assessing sustainability and circularity within cities. This study explores the application of CIM to assess material flows and stock. Through a critical literature review, this study examines whether CIM has been used for MFA and MSA calculations tools currently in use, and future research directions.

INTRODUCTION

In a world more and more urbanized, tackling climate change and challenges for sustainable development may be strategically focused on cities [1]. Cities hold a pivotal role in sustainable development, acting as catalysts for transformation and offering opportunities to enhance the quality of life [1-3]. As a pathway to sustainable development, the Circular Economy (CE) concept has been adopted by cities, seeking circular strategies to close loop systems [4]. Understanding that in a circular approach, nothing is “waste”, and everything is potentially a “resource”[1], it is necessary to comprehensively look at the urban systems as a whole, evaluating the environmental impacts of socio-economic systems, by accounting and analyzing resource flows [5]. This is one of the key principles of industrial ecology, in which the concept of urban metabolism can be understood as the flow of resources gathered by cities, their retention and/or transformation, and discard [3]. This analysis of flows, stocks, and the metabolism of cities plays a crucial role in a city’s environmental performance [3], [6]. Considering that the built environment is responsible for 35-45% of global material flows and 25% of global waste generation [7-9], analyzing construction materials flow and stock is essential to “closing, slowing, and narrowing” the cycle of materials and effectively managing resources [7], thus, understanding urban metabolism and promoting sustainable development. Since the first definitions of urban metabolism were introduced in the 1960s, methods have been developed, and research in the field has gained significant attention. However, despite the growing interest and developments, urban metabolism has not been widely used to support urban planning and management. In this regard, innovative technologies have the potential to support analysis and promote a holistic approach [6]. Digital tools, such as City Information Modeling (CIM), offer a promising approach for analyzing and calculating materials flows and

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stock [7]. CIM has been recognized as a multidisciplinary approach that integrates diverse data sources, technologies, and analytical tools to create an intelligent city model [10]. With diverse urban elements, this intelligent modeling approach allows a comprehensive analysis and creation of sustainable urban plans [11-13]. It facilitates collaboration among stakeholders, enabling informed decision-making towards a more circular and sustainable urban future [14], [15]. CIM leverages rich geospatial information and up-to-date databases within 3D models [12-16]. Some authors stated that the CIM concept is analogous to Building Information Modeling (BIM) but applied to the city context [12], [14], [15], [17]. Additionally, many studies have pointed out CIM as a useful tool to help implement sustainable strategies in cities [14], [16-19].

Despite the growing interest in CIM capabilities and its promising approach for analyzing and calculating material flows and stock, the literature lacks studies that have associated the use of CIM for MFA and MSA, thereby promoting the implementation of the circular economy in cities. In this regard, this study presents a critical literature review to identify whether CIM is actually applied in MFA and MSA, the definitions in use, and the practical challenges that remain. Ultimately, this paper aims to initiate a discussion and explore future directions of CIM capabilities and functionalities within the urban CE concept.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employs a critical literature review to understand the relationships between CIM, MFA, and MSA, including their current definitions, challenges, and potential future research directions. By addressing the following research question: “Is City Information Modeling currently defined and used in the context of Material Flow and Stock Analysis?”, we intend to understand how and if CIM is applied in MFA and MSA.

To perform the literature review, the academic databases of Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus were selected. These two databases were selected because both are larger databases of peer-reviewed, high-quality, and high-impact-factor journal articles. The exact search string was used for both databases: (city information model* AND material analysis) AND (urban metabolism OR circular economy). For WoS, the search criterion was ‘*All Fields*’, and for Scopus, it was ‘*Article title, Abstract, Keywords*’. This criterion differentiation is due to the nature of the search databases. WoS does not allow the option to include ‘*Article title, Abstract, and Keywords*’, as it does in Scopus. However, using ‘*All Fields*’ in Scopus yields an enormous number of articles, most of which are not directly related to the core of the research. The papers were screened to eliminate duplicates and those not related to the research question.

Ultimately, although this review employs a structured approach, its limitations should be noted. Firstly, the databases are well-known and major academic databases. However, it can omit relevant studies found in other repositories, such as Google Scholar or grey literature. Secondly, the chosen keywords and Boolean operators may not capture all relevant studies due to terminological variation. Finally, even though adopting a semi-systematic approach, the screening process involved researcher judgment, which may introduce a degree of subjectivity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The literature search revealed a total of 75 papers, of which 14 duplicates were removed. After the screening for relevance and eligibility, 19 papers were selected for a full-text analysis.

In almost the totality of papers, City Information Modeling has not been mentioned. However, the use of GIS and/or BIM tools, core tools for CIM, is widely studied in the literature [20-31]. Overall, the studies examine the application of digital tools (e.g., AI, BIM, machine learning, life cycle assessment tools, etc.) as enablers for the bottom-up approach to calculating materials building stocks. The papers also discussed the concepts separately, such as the use of MSA for

CE implementation, or the integrations of digital tools (e.g., AI, geospatial technologies, and machine learning) for building stock analysis, using MFA, and LCA [23], [28]. GIS tools have been widely explored for MFA and/or MSA [21-37]. These tools can estimate material stock and flow, map their spatial-temporal patterns, help in the identification of building typologies, and are considered reliable sources of information and data acquisition. Concerning BIM, existing BIM models are rich databases of materials [27], in addition to their capability to manage complex information throughout the building lifecycle [20].

Interestingly, only one study [7] specifically presented the concept of CIM, using the MFA principle to create a material cadaster map. By applying the concept of CIM, which integrates GIS and BIM, the authors discussed a materiality-based city information modeling (mCIM). The authors proposed that the primary roles of GIS tools for modeling the built environment and BIM tools are to capture the building's characteristics and life cycle perspectives [7]. In the line of studying the integration of BIM and GIS, but without mentioning CIM as a concept, Parezanović et al. (2025) [27] have developed and applied a method for assessing building material stock and material intensity coefficients using BIM and GIS tools. Existing BIM models and GIS cadasters are combined to assess types and quantities of embedded material in buildings. Similarly, Triantafyllidis et al. (2025) [20] used georeferenced BIM models for MSA. As further developments, the authors highlighted that linking these BIM models with GIS tools can enhance spatial analysis and planning. Once again, no mentions of CIM were made.

CONCLUSIONS

The critical analysis of the literature indicates that CIM remains a novel and emerging concept. Although the literature indicates that CIM has a wide range of potential applications, its use for MFA and MSA remains unexplored. Considering that only one paper explicitly referred to the concept of CIM, it can be concluded that, while CIM is emerging as a valuable tool, it is not yet fully recognized or adopted in the academic literature. On the other hand, the core components of CIM – GIS and BIM are widely applied, including for MFA and MSA. Understanding CIM as the integration of BIM and GIS, its applicability can be amplified once the majority of the analyzed studies evaluate the potential of these tools, mainly individually, for material flows and/or stock analysis.

Furthermore, as many studies effectively incorporate elements of CIM, namely the integration of BIM and GIS, without explicitly naming or framing them as such, it suggests that a terminological gap exists. This may be due to the novelty and lack of a standard definition and widespread adoption of CIM.

Ultimately, the results suggest a clear research gap in systematically applying CIM to MFA and MSA. This represents an opportunity to pilot CIM applications in city-scale material analysis, guided by the synergies between BIM and GIS, as already presented in the literature. Future research directions could seek to clearly define CIM in the context of material analysis, exploring its application and benefits for MFA and MSA. By developing methodological frameworks that integrate BIM and GIS for dynamic MFA studies and testing CIM approaches in pilot urban settings, new insights can be unlocked.

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High-resolution material stock modelling of UK buildings for a circular built environment

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Keywords: bottom-up material stock analysis (MSA), building stock, circular economy, circularity, embodied carbon, high-resolution.

ABSTRACT

Around a quarter of emissions from UK buildings are in the form of embodied carbon, with this proportion expected to rise to more than half by 2040 (UK Green Building Council, 2021). To meet decarbonization targets, the UK construction sector must transition to a more circular economy in which resource extraction, waste generation and associated embodied emissions are minimized through increased reuse and recycling. The BuildZero research program (The University of Sheffield, 2024) will explore the extent to which the UK's future building needs may be met with zero material extraction, zero waste and zero carbon emissions. Doing so relies upon an accurate and high-resolution understanding of the location, built form, use-type, age and material content of each building in the UK. To date, no such model exists, with previous attempts often being based upon unverified asset inventories and/or material intensities with insufficient spatial and temporal resolution (Drewniok et al., 2023; Wiedenhofer et al., 2024).

This presentation documents the development of a high-resolution building stock model of the UK, combining neighborhood-level statistical data and building-resolution GIS mapping to successfully predict location, built form, use type and age. This is supplemented with temporally-explicit and layer-disaggregated material intensities, providing an accurate estimation of the material content of UK buildings at the individual components level. In addition to the resulting stock model, this presentation will provide insights on intended and potential-future applications within the BuildZero research program and beyond.

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Predicting Building Demolitions in Switzerland Using GIS and Deep Learning

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Keywords: Building demolition, circularity, deep learning, explainable AI, GIS

ABSTRACT

In Switzerland, more than 4,000 buildings are demolished annually, generating over 16 million tons of construction waste and exceeding 110,000 tons of CO₂ emissions. Within the framework of a circular economy, minimizing demolitions and encouraging the reuse of entire structures, components, and materials are critical for reducing environmental impacts and enhancing resource efficiency. Predicting when, where, and which buildings are likely to be demolished can support proactive urban planning, resource management, and circular economy strategies. This study presents a predictive approach for building demolition that integrates Geographic Information Systems (GIS) with machine learning techniques. A comprehensive dataset was established by integrating GIS-based spatial data with various building characteristics, such as construction period, typology, and location, along with contextual socio-economic indicators including mobility quality, urban density, and employment levels. Using this dataset, we trained and evaluated various deep learning models, including Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks and Transformer-based architectures, to predict building demolitions across Switzerland over different time horizons. To enhance model interpretability, we employed the explainable machine learning method Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) to quantify the contribution of individual features to the predicted demolition risk. This analysis offers insights into the key drivers of demolition, examining the influence of both intrinsic building characteristics and external factors on demolition decisions. Furthermore, the model enables the spatial prediction of future demolition risks across different urban areas. This study contributes to the advancement of data-driven methods for sustainable urban planning by offering a scalable and interpretable framework for anticipating building demolition trends and enabling informed, forward-looking decision-making.

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Mapping the Current Building Stock of Precast Concrete Structures in Sweden: An Integrated GIS and BIM Approach

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Keywords: building stocks, circular economy, urban mining, precast concrete, reuse

ABSTRACT

Precast concrete systems had widespread proliferation in Europe during the post-war era. In Sweden, a wide variety of industrialised buildings were developed mainly in the 60s and 70s as part of the so-called ‘Million Programme’. Although many of these buildings may still be in good material condition, outdated standards and socio-economic factors have contributed to their accelerated obsolescence. Reusing concrete allows for the largest environmental savings, compared to demolishing or recycling, while the high modularity of precast systems facilitates disassembly and transport. Therefore, reconsidering this building stock as an asset for future construction can significantly reduce the footprint of new buildings.

This paper presents a novel approach for mapping and quantifying the current stock of prefabricated concrete buildings applied to the Drottninghög neighbourhood in Helsingborg. This is done by reconstructing the original drawing information in a BIM environment with geospatial information (GIS) to quantify the current stock of prefabricated concrete structures in a three-step automated workflow. First, known instances of precast buildings were identified in cadastral databases, and their footprints were then segmented using the modules of each target system. Length and width were divided by the characteristic module size, and a deviation threshold of $\pm 10\%$ was applied to discard poor matches. Height data, corrected for pitched roofs when present, provided an estimate of storey numbers. The resulting module counts served as input for parametric BIM generation. Second, historical construction drawings were digitised, creating simple BIM models of the system element was modelled once as a reusable template. Third, the geospatial layer was enriched with component-level quantities derived from the BIM instances, producing an integrated GIS-BIM dataset covering both building footprints and their internal element inventories.

Integrating geospatial and BIM environments offers a scalable alternative to conventional building-by-building surveys. The modular-fitting algorithm takes advantage on the strict regularity of industrialised systems, enabling rapid building stock assessments at district scale. While performance may decline in cases of missing technical drawings or atypical layouts, the ability to flag high-uncertainty cases ensures that manual verification can be focused where it is most critical. The result is a detailed database of the precast building stock at the building component level. This geospatial dataset offers valuable input for reuse assessment in future projects, while integration with BIM models serves as input for the design process. The proposed workflow is transferable to other contexts, provided that basic system parameters and reliable cadastral data are available.

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On Modeling Dynamic Flow of Finnish Building Stock

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Keywords: building stock modeling, hierarchical system, network analysis.

Abstract: The development of a building stock has been studied for example by Aksözen et al. (2017) and Bradley (2019). Kurvinen et al. (2021) have modeled building stock development. We are constructing an automated method for processing time dependent building stock data into social network form. Social networks have been used to analyze biological interactions. As buildings are not static entities but change through time as a result of human activity the same methods can be applied to them as well. The method produces a graph in which the individual buildings are represented as nodes. The edge lengths are derived from the similarity of the buildings using Jaccard distance on buildings' features. The Jaccard distance was chosen solely for its relative simplicity. But as the building stock evolves the changing hierarchical system can be parameterized with time resulting in dynamical flow. The aim is to be able to recognize patterns in building life events and outcomes they lead into. Thus allowing efficient maintenance of standing building stock as well as a forecast of material coming available through demolitions.

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Modelling material stocks, embodied carbon and circular economy potential in UK building services

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Keywords: building services, building stocks, circular economy, embodied carbon, material stocks, material stock analysis (MSA)

ABSTRACT

The built environment contributes 25% of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the UK, with embodied carbon from the construction and refurbishment of buildings making up 20% of built environment emissions (UK Green Building Council, 2021). With increasingly energy efficient systems and associated reductions in operational emissions, there is a growing need to explore solutions to reduce embodied carbon emissions. Research in embodied carbon quantification and reduction often overlooks building services in comparison to other building shearing layers (e.g. structure, skin and space), with this often only considered in terms of operational carbon emissions. Although typically comprising fewer materials and embodied carbon emissions than the structural layer (London Energy Transformation Initiative, 2020), building services are often replaced multiple times during a buildings lifespan (Pushkar, 2015). This higher replacement leads to potential significant material consumption, waste generation and embodied carbon.

The BuildZero research program (The University of Sheffield, 2024) will explore the extent to which the UK's future building needs may be met with zero material extraction, zero waste and zero carbon emissions. As part of the research program, the first step to explore circular economy solutions in the UK building construction is to develop a national material stock model. As part of this, a framework is developed to facilitate the quantification of residential material stocks across the structure, skin, services, and space layers. Using this framework and a suite of novel material intensities, a detailed estimation of material stocks and embodied carbon within building services material stock is obtained for a case study borough within London, UK. The framework disaggregates building elements across six hierarchies to retain and allow users to query diverse information such as building layer, use, specification and material composition. Therefore allowing the relative impact of building services and other building layers to be assessed and the impact of the assumed lifespans investigated.

The primary aims of the study presented are to (1) introduce a derived set of novel material intensities for UK residential building services, (2) demonstrate how the framework and developed material intensities enable stock estimation of building services, (3) compare the material quantities, embodied carbon and replacement rates of residential building services and other building layers, (4) predict the material stock and embodied carbon associated with upgrading and replacing building services in the transition to lower operational carbon solutions.

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Softmax Similarity Weighting for Bottom-up Building Stock Modelling: Application to Building Replacements in Zurich (2001–2019)

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Keywords: bottom-up approach; similarity weighting; Softmax; generalizability; interval-dependent shifts; building replacement.

ABSTRACT. The building material stock plays a pivotal role in the circular economy by reducing reliance on virgin resources through material reuse and recovery. Realizing this potential requires accurate mapping of urban material flows, yet such efforts are often hindered by missing material-specific data in cadastral and GIS records. Among bottom-up estimation approaches, Similarity weighting (SW) is a novel method that infers unknown building properties from known samples via similarity-based averaging. While SW addresses the oversimplifications of conventional archetype models, it remains limited by subjective parameter selection, a coverage–accuracy trade-off, and reduced efficacy in high-dimensional contexts—all constraining its generalizability. To overcome these challenges, this study proposes Softmax Similarity Weighting (SoftmaxSW), a reformulation of classical SW method (inverse-distance-weighting) into a probabilistic similarity-based approach. This shift improves generalizability by enabling adaptation to diverse data conditions, enhancing numerical stability, and ensuring consistent performance across varying feature dimensions, while maintaining high coverage and accuracy. Additional branches integrate a radius scaling function to account for real-world interval-dependent shifts, such as temporal variations in material usage patterns. The method is applied to building replacements (BR) in Zurich City (2001–2019), estimating structural material use and embodied carbon emissions for 6,115 demolished and constructed buildings. Validation on 48 Swiss sample buildings shows 100% theoretical applicability and over 75% accuracy. SoftmaxSW matches the overall performance of Support Vector Machine and outperforms it in material-specific predictions. Results highlight slabs and walls, concrete, and multi-residential and office buildings as key areas for circularity within the BR context. Overall, SoftmaxSW provides a generalizable bottom-up framework for scalable interpolation of localized assessments, including material quantities and carbon emissions, and further extends to technological performance and other context-specific aspects relevant to urban-scale applications.

INTRODUCTION

Building stock modelling (BSM) is commonly classified into two approaches: top-down and bottom-up. Top-down models summarize entire stocks using macroeconomic statistics [1] but lack resolution to capture building-level characteristics. In contrast, bottom-up approaches are considered better suited to supporting the circular economy, as they enable detailed stock analysis and facilitate investigation of potential reuse of stockpiled materials as secondary resources [2]. Bottom-up approaches typically consist of two methods: building-by-building and archetype approaches. The former offers high resolution but demands rich, detailed data. Although advanced techniques such as remote sensing and computer vision have been developed to enhance data collection capabilities, these methods are primarily suited for existing buildings and exterior components, and are not applicable to demolished buildings or interior elements. Archetype approaches represent building cohorts through archetypes and extrapolate findings across the stock using up-scaling factors. However, cohort categorization often relies on expert judgment, and propagation through up-scaling assumes homogeneity in material composition,

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intensity, and other characteristics within each category. Archetype-based approaches are therefore criticized for oversimplifying models [3], homogenizing datasets, and resulting in a loss of heterogeneity [4]. To address these issues, Fivet and team [5] introduced a novel bottom-up approach in 2024, using a *similarity-weighting (SW)* function to estimate unknown properties of stock buildings through weighted averages of similar samples, with weights linearly derived from feature-based differences (Figure 1, left). However, this method presents several limitations: (1) **Subjectivity**: Defining similar samples through similarity boundaries often requires manually setting threshold values, which introduces subjective assumptions. Moreover, a fixed and uniform boundary fails to capture real-world variations and nonlinear behaviors—for example, the evolving historical trajectories and time-dependent adoption patterns of different materials; (2) **Trade-off in coverage vs. accuracy**: A wider boundary allows broader comparisons but reduces accuracy, while a narrower one ensures stricter similarity but limits comparable samples and lowers validation coverage. This challenge is particularly acute in the building sector, where sample data is often limited and sparse; (3) **High-dimensional ineffectiveness**: Euclidean distance is more effective as a similarity measure in low-dimensional spaces (1–3D). In higher dimensions, the phenomenon of “distance concentration” can easily occur—relative differences among inter-point distances diminish, and the ratio between the nearest and farthest distances approaches 1—thereby weakening discriminative power and undermining similarity measures based on absolute distances between features.

Therefore, this study tackles these limitations by developing a generalizable bottom-up method designed to overcome subjectivity, improve validation coverage and accuracy, and maintain performance across diverse feature spaces. This method quantifies and maps the in-use stock, demand, and release of distinct building materials, along with their associated embodied carbon, to better inform circular strategies targeting material circularity. Central to the approach is a SW scheme incorporating the *Softmax* function, a widely used and effective similarity technique, providing a robust framework for detailed stock modeling. In addition, the method accounts for the nonlinear behavior of different materials, particularly their historically incremental phase-in and phase-out patterns. Finally, this study traces conceptual origins of SW and examines its applicability and limitations in the BSM context.

METHODS

Softmax Similarity Weighting for Generic Cases

The core principle of SW originates from the *inverse-distance-weighting (IDW)* interpolation method developed in the 1960s at Harvard’s Computer Graphics Laboratory [6]. It estimates the value at an unobserved geographical point as a weighted average of known points, where weights decay with distance following a power law, thereby assigning greater weight to closer points. This method has broad applications across environmental science (e.g., air quality), geology (e.g., mineral exploration), and economics (e.g., real estate pricing). Assuming this interpolation applies to BSM, the general formula is expressed as:

$$M(j) = \frac{\sum_{i \in C(j)} w(i, j) M(i)}{\sum_{i \in C(j)} w(i, j)}, \quad (1)$$

where $M(i)$ and $M(j)$ represent *interpolable properties* of sample i and stock building j , such as material quantities, emissions profiles, or technology-specific effects. An *interpolable property* refers to a characteristic determined by objective conditions, excluding behavior- or policy-dependent attributes like lifespan. The sample and stock sets are denoted by $\mathcal{I} = \{i\}$ and $\mathcal{J} = \{j\}$. Let $C(j)$ denote the subset of samples within \mathcal{I} that satisfy eligibility conditions (e.g., matching use category or industrial zone) for comparison with stock building j , over which the summation index i runs. The weight $w(i, j)$ quantifies similarity based on distance $D(i, j)$ in feature space. The denominator $\sum_{i \in C(j)} w(i, j)$ acts as a normalization factor, ensuring that the weights estimate $M(j)$ sum to 1. While the SW method proposed by Fivet *et al.* [5] uses a **linear decay weighting** scheme (Figure 1, left)—equivalent to IDW with a power parameter of

Figure 1. Diagram of weight assignments for stock building j : (left) a linear weighting in SW, derived from Fivet *et al.* [5]; (right) an exponential weighting in SoftmaxSW. In SW, only samples within the boundary contribute (active), while others are ignored (inactive). SoftmaxSW assigns weights to all samples (all active). 1—and manually defined elliptical boundaries that constrain the comparison scope, this study instead employs an **exponential decay function** to assign weights that decay smoothly with increasing feature distance (Figure 1, right), expressed as:

$$w(i, j) = e^{-\sigma D(i, j)}. \quad (2)$$

Combining Eqs. 1 and 2, the normalized weighting function follows a *Softmax* mapping, widely used in Large Language Models to convert distance-based measures into smooth, differentiable similarity weights [7]. This design offers several advantages: (1) **Adaptive behavior**: The exponential decay amplifies differences by assigning higher weights to nearby samples and rapidly downweighting distant ones, removing the need for predefined similarity boundaries and enhancing coverage and robustness. The hyperparameter σ controls sensitivity to distance; larger values produce sharper decay and more focused weights; (2) **Numerical stability**: Typical IDW can become unstable when distances between samples approach zero, as the weight expression diverges—a phenomenon known as “weight explosion”—which may lead to numerical errors such as undefined values (*NaN*) or overflow (*Inf*). In contrast, Softmax produces bounded and smooth weights, and further improves stability through the LogSumExp trick; (3) **High-dimensional robustness**: IDW is vulnerable to the “distance concentration” effect, where distances become indistinguishable and weights tend to equalize or become discontinuous. Softmax can amplify relative weight differences by introducing σ , making it robust for distinguishing samples in high dimensions. Critically, the transformation from IDW to Softmax reframes absolute distance-based interpolation as probabilistic similarity assignment, enabling a weighting scheme with greater generalizability: namely, adaptability, stability, and scalability.

The separation between stock and sample buildings are quantified by the Euclidean distance

$$D(i, j) = \sqrt{\sum_k (\Delta F_k(i, j)/\tilde{F}_k)^2}, \quad (k = 1, 2, \dots, n), \quad (3)$$

where F represents the features used for similarity comparison, indexed by k . Feature selection is context-dependent and should reflect the mechanisms or correlates of the interpolable property. It may include numerical attributes (e.g., year, size, coordinates) and categorical attributes (e.g., functionality, district), with categorical features converted into binary form via one-hot encoding. Each feature difference is normalized by a scaling factor \tilde{F}_k —set to 1 for binary features and based on distribution metrics (e.g., standard deviation) for numerical features—to remove unit effects and balance contributions. Categorical attributes are either used as prerequisites to filter samples i sharing the category of j in Eq. 1 to define the comparison set, or incorporated in one-hot encoded distance metrics, depending on the application. Hence, the method proposed is called **Softmax Similarity Weighting**, abbreviated as **SoftmaxSW**.

Extension with Dynamic Similarity Boundary for Interval-Dependent Behavior

The basic SW principle in IDW assumes a smoothly distributed dataset. However, real-world phenomena often exhibit **nonlinear behavior with interval-dependent shifts**, where behavior varies across conditions or ranges and may change abruptly at critical points. For instance,

material elasticity varies with stress levels, and biological growth rates shift with age. In buildings, material usage does not always follow a continuous trend, with discontinuities such as structural material per unit area surging beyond certain heights [8] or materials phasing in and out at key technological milestones. These patterns challenge the smooth distribution assumption underlying SW-based methods, necessitating alternatives. A *piecewise function* effectively captures variations in feature F_k across distinct intervals [9], fitting transitions driven by temporal dynamics or contextual shifts. To ensure similarity estimation respects this piecewise behavior, a **similarity boundary** is introduced to constrain comparisons within the same behavioral regime. This boundary corresponds to the piecewise structure: if interval thresholds remain stable, the boundary stays fixed; but when thresholds evolve, it must be dynamically adjusted—forming a **dynamic similarity boundary** that adapts to evolving piecewise regimes. For example, the adoption pattern of a specific material in stock buildings evolves over time, leading to dynamic adjustments of the corresponding similarity boundary. A narrow boundary indicates early or limited adoption phases, where the material appears in few cases and exhibits inconsistent features, requiring stricter similarity criteria for reliable comparison. Conversely, a wider boundary reflects broader adoption, where the material is used across varied contexts and features tend to stabilize and diversify, allowing greater variability tolerance while preserving meaningful similarity. Applying a uniform boundary across all measured indicators and materials risks overgeneralization, as observed in the SW application by [5].

To mathematically characterize and dynamically adjust the similarity boundary associated with a specific feature F within the SoftmaxSW framework, a *radius scaling function* $\gamma(\cdot)$ is introduced. This function defines a similarity boundary radius for feature F , dynamically scaled by the value of F in stock building j , denoted as $\gamma(F(j))$. Specifically, the distance function (Eq. 3) is modified, subject to the constraint:

$$(\Delta F(i, j) / \tilde{F})^2 \leq \gamma(F(j)). \quad (4)$$

A dynamic similarity boundary is needed only when interval-dependent shifts must be explicitly captured—for instance, when material types phase in or out over time due to technological evolution. In contrast, essential and time-invariant intrinsic properties like spatial size or total mass are well captured by SoftmaxSW for generic consideration without such boundaries.

APPLICATION AND VALIDATION

The SoftmaxSW method is applied to building replacements (BR) in Zurich City from 2001 to 2019 to estimate the inflow and outflow of structural materials and associated embodied greenhouse gas emissions (EGHGEs). The stock dataset comprises 3,359 demolished buildings dating from 1780 to 2018 and 2,756 newly constructed buildings between 2001 and 2019. The sample dataset, derived from [10], comprises 48 Swiss buildings: 32 residential (R) and 16 non-residential (NR). Detailed investigation data cover structural components (slabs, beams, walls, posts, roofing frameworks, and covers), excluding foundations, stairs, and balconies. Construction materials—reinforced concrete, metals, timber, and masonry—are assessed in terms of volume, mass, and EGHGE (phases A1–A3 per EN-15978) using KBOB.

Prerequisite condition. The attribute of functionality is selected as the prerequisite in Eq. 1.

Figure 2. SoftmaxSW-based bottom-up workflow transfers observed properties from limited samples to the broader stock; the red box marks the interpolated target.

This work adopts two coarse-grained groups, residential (R) and non-residential (NR), as the basis for similarity matching, restricting comparisons to buildings within the same category.

Similarity comparison. Comparison features, including built year, footprint, and building height, are chosen for their availability and relevance to the estimated properties.

Parameter selection. The parameter σ in weighting function is empirically set to 0.8, achieving a local minimum mean absolute percentage error and producing a slower decay rate compared to the standard exponential setting of 1. The normalization factors \bar{F} for construction year, footprint, and height are determined based on their standard deviations across the datasets.

Material-specific scaling functions. Compared to the SW application in [5], this study refines material-specific estimation in SoftmaxSW by introducing distinct radius scaling functions γ for three materials, capturing their respective historical evolutions and adoption rates. Concrete, metal, and timber and masonry correspond to γ_c , γ_m , and γ_{ts} , respectively.

Cross validation. All methods are validated by cross-predicting each sample building's quantity from the remaining ones, with performance evaluated using mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) and model coverage (Table 1). For SW and SoftmaxSW, leave-one-out cross-validation is applied. SoftmaxSW achieves full coverage, while SW reaches 87.5%. SoftmaxSW also provides more accurate estimates, with overall accuracy between 75–80%. Further compared with Support Vector Machine (SVM), a classic machine learning effective for training on small to medium datasets. MATLAB's `fitrsvm` with automatic hyperparameter tuning is called, which defaults to 5-fold cross-validation. Results show SoftmaxSW matches or outperforms SVM. As estimation granularity increases for breakdown materials, both methods see rising error rates, with SoftmaxSW generally performing better. A higher presence of zero values in the sample set correlates with increased error rates, particularly for metals, where the high errors observed in SoftmaxSW are attributed to exceptionally high quantity estimates in several samples where metals were present, leading to a steep rise in overall error rate. Since the total quantity of metals is small, the impact on the total estimation error remains limited.

Correlation between measures. The high cosine similarity and Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) between the estimated measures (volume, mass, and EGHGE) confirm strong correlations, further validating SoftmaxSW. Additionally, PCC values are higher for new construction than for demolition, indicating better model performance for new construction.

Table 1. Model performance on the sample dataset using cross-validation across SW, SoftmaxSW, and SVM.

Estimated measures	Number of 0 value in sample library	SW [5]		SoftmaxSW		SVM	
		Coverage↑	MAPE↓	Coverage↑	MAPE ↓	Coverage↑	MAPE ↓
EGHGE	0	87.5%	26.74%	100%	20.58 %	100%	20.08%
Volume	0	87.5%	31.21%	100%	25.75 %	100%	37.26%
Mass	0	87.5%	33.98%	100%	26.71 %	100%	26.42%
concrete mass	3	—	—	100%	44.96% ($+\gamma_c$)	100%	89.19%
metal mass	36	—	—	100%	453.71% ($+\gamma_m$)	100%	399.32%
timber mass	31	—	—	100%	46.64% ($+\gamma_{ts}$)	100%	132.94%
masonry mass	26	—	—	100%	63.90% ($+\gamma_{ts}$)	100%	41.76%

RESULTS

This study uses the SoftmaxSW method to estimate material quantities and embodied carbon emissions for BR projects in Zurich (2001–2019), achieving 90% coverage; the remaining 10% of building entries lacked complete data. The results show that while new constructions had 2.44 times the total volume of demolished buildings, their structural volume, mass, and EGHGEs (A1–A3) were 2.26, 2.53, and 2.24 times higher, respectively. Structural EGHGEs per unit (in $\text{kgCO}_2\text{eq/m}^2$) for residential buildings (211 for demolished, 218 for new) were slightly above the 25th percentile structural GWP (around 200, A1–A3) in the deQo database [11], likely due to excluding foundations and staircases. A more detailed breakdown reveals three key patterns. First, the distribution of EGHGEs across structural components is similar between demolition and new construction in BR, with slabs and walls dominating—accounting for over 85% and 92% of total EGHGE, respectively. Except for beams, the absolute EGHGE of each

component is higher in new construction. Second, concrete is the primary structural material, increasing from 84.5% in demolitions to 99.5% in new constructions. Third, demolished concrete structures mainly originate from multi-residential, office, and industrial buildings, whereas new construction is dominated by multi-residential and office buildings, accounting for 75.7% and 15.2% of total structural concrete use, respectively. These findings highlight slabs and walls, concrete, and multi-residential and office buildings as key focus areas for investigating circularity in structural components, materials, and building types within the BR context.

DISCUSSION FOR METHODOLOGY

SoftmaxSW provides a generalizable bottom-up approach, demonstrating robustness to data variability, reliable numerical behavior, and consistent performance across low- and high-dimensional feature spaces. These qualities enable its effective extension to diverse urban contexts and datasets. SoftmaxSW proved effective even with limited samples, highlighting its suitability for BSM, where data are often limited and sparse due to manual collection. Its accuracy improves with sample size. SW-based methods rely on the assumption of smoothly varying data, making them suitable for domains governed by stable industry trends or objectively defined technologies, such as structural and envelope assemblies. In contrast, user-driven assemblies such as finishes exhibit higher variability and greater uncertainty in SW assignment. Although the radius scaling function captures real-world interval-dependent behavior, it remains a conceptual abstraction and warrants further investigation. In conclusion, SoftmaxSW enables accurate bottom-up mapping of material flows and emissions, supporting circular resource planning in construction. It supports scalable interpolation of localized assessments across physical, technological, and other domains relevant to urban-scale applications.

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**The city of flows:
Mechanisms behind urban building stock development and how construction
and demolition manifest in morphological changes and material flows.**

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Keywords: Building stock research; Construction and demolition; Material stocks and flows; Urban morphology; Urban planning

ABSTRACT

Urban building stocks are the backbone of societal activities as they provide homes, spaces for education, healthcare, work, and more. Simultaneously, the extraction of natural resources to feed the material-intensive construction sector poses profound constraints onto the natural environment. Despite a growing body of literature investigating urban material stocks, there is relatively little awareness for the factors and mechanisms that drive and shape the dynamic evolution of urban building and material stocks.

In my doctoral dissertation, I investigated the building stocks of the two Finnish cities Tampere and Vantaa and how they evolved through construction and demolition between 2000 and 2018. Through a spatially explicit and temporally dynamic analysis, I investigated over seventy residential and non-residential building types with regards to urban morphological aspects. The results of this analysis showed greenfield development and replacement as the predominant spatiotemporal development patterns. By linking these patterns with population growth, economic structure, geographical features, and other contextual factors, I observed some of the potential determinants that shape the structural differences in both cities' building stock compositions. Geographical limitations in Tampere stimulated a more efficient land use approach which led to a more compact housing stock. The cities' economic profiles, on the other hand, profoundly influenced the composition of their non-residential building stocks.

A notable contribution of this dissertation is the development of material intensity coefficients for Finnish residential buildings. This data set enabled to link findings of Vantaa's housing stock development with the respective material consequences. For example, the ongoing densification of already built-up city districts led to above-average material usage. In contrast, the new low to medium-density neighborhoods on former greenfield land accommodate a large proportion of the growing population and manifested in less severe per capita material flows.

This doctoral dissertation demonstrates how cities of a similar size experienced notably different developments which manifest in structural differences of their building stocks. Given the differences in material contents by building type, distinct building stock compositions translate into qualitatively and quantitatively distinct stocks and flows of materials. For this reason, it is of critical importance to understand the mechanisms and drivers behind urban building stock development. Such knowledge can help planners to get a better understanding of their work's material consequences which aids the development of more material-conscious urban planning approaches.

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Urban Forest Material Stock and Flow Analysis: Turin, Tartu and Rotterdam

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Keywords: circular value chain, flows, model, stocks, timber, wood

ABSTRACT

Timber is one of the most promising sustainable construction materials for the built environment. As the demand for timber is projected to increase in the coming decades, it is crucial to use wood products more efficiently, by maximising cascading use and developing circular value chains. This would reduce waste generation, raw material consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, while at the same time reducing pressure on forests to supply the expected growing demand.

The WOODCIRCLES project aims to develop new circular value chains for the wood stock accumulated in existing buildings, referred to as Urban Forest materials. To better understand the capacity and impact of these circular value chains, knowledge of the quantities and qualities of the Urban Forest materials is necessary. In WOODCIRCLES, we are quantifying the stocks and flows of the Urban Forest materials at European and local level in the partner cities of Turin, Tartu and Rotterdam. Here, we outline the proposed methodology for the Urban Forest Material Flow and Stock Analysis at city level. In particular, the wood material stock model for mapping the quantities and qualities of the Urban Forest. The model is a static bottom-up parametric model with incremental capability and uncertainty characterisation. The data collection is based on mixed method strategies and based on building typology classification and type of wooden construction materials. The aim of the model output is to provide sufficient information with quality data to enable the management of wood materials released from the demolition of buildings, prioritising their cascading use as high value materials. The study is currently ongoing, and the results will support the development of the new circular value chains, such as engineered wood products and insulation products made with reclaimed wood. The research methods and models are being documented to enable the future adaptation to other cities and contexts.

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Circularity in the Built Environment 2025

Circular decommissioning of buildings and infrastructure

A standardized approach to evaluating the reuse potential of building components

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Keywords: assessment, audit, case studies, deconstruction, reuse, Switzerland, tool, USA

ABSTRACT

Assessing the reuse potential of building components is a key step toward sustainable construction practices. However, existing evaluation methods lack consistency, leading to subjectivity and variability in results. A review of 21 assessment procedures from Europe and the USA (2001-2021) highlights critical gaps, including inconsistencies in data collection and a lack of standardized criteria. To address these challenges, this study presents a structured and adaptable assessment method aimed at providing a systematic approach to evaluating the reuse potential of building components.

The proposed framework enables an initial evaluation based on basic building data, excluding the need for site visits or extensive specifications. It allows initial evaluation of the time and budget required for deconstruction, transformation, and sale. The assessment is automated, supported by defined archetypes and scenarios, and customized as the user adds inputs. Indeed, the method is designed for iterative refinement, progressing through four phases—rough, adjusted, refined, and bespoke—by integrating additional data and criteria as they become available, thereby enhancing accuracy and reliability over time.

The tool's effectiveness is demonstrated through two real-world case studies: one in Ithaca, NY, USA, and another in Vaud, Switzerland. These applications showcase how the methodology can be implemented in different contexts, validating its practical relevance and adaptability. The comparative analysis of both case studies provides insight into the challenges and benefits of reuse-oriented deconstruction and highlights the method's ability to support informed decision-making.

By offering a standardized yet flexible approach, this assessment framework provides industry professionals with a practical tool for evaluating and planning the reuse of building materials. It contributes to the advancement of circular construction practices, promoting resource efficiency and reducing environmental impact.

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Disconnecting and reconnecting in case of reuse of precast concrete elements

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Keywords: Concrete, Connections, Retrofit, Reuse

ABSTRACT

The reuse of precast concrete elements, as considered in the ReCreate project, has a benefit for sustainability goals. In this research, the focus is laid on the disconnection and reconnection of precast concrete elements. One of the difficulties is that current structures have not been designed with future demounting in mind. This leads to the need for careful consideration of the method of deconstruction. The method of deconstruction may alter the elements compared to their original conditions, leading to complications when trying to reconnect them in a new structure. This research focuses on three aspects of reuse: (1) disconnecting, (2) connecting elements with the original conditions, and (3) connecting elements whose conditions have been altered due to deconstruction. Disconnecting (1) has a substantial impact on the ability to reconnect afterwards, so different techniques are investigated to determine its influence. As for now, sawing is the most commonly used technique, but sawing through reinforcement may prevent the use of this reinforcement bar for reconnecting purposes. Some more recently developed techniques, such as water-jetting, may prove useful when reinforcement bars are preferably kept intact. Of course, there are more parameters that influence the required disconnecting techniques, such as damage probability, tolerance, ease of use, time restrictions, etc. This means it is often very beneficial to know already which reconnecting option is desired to reuse the elements. When this is unknown, the correct technique can be determined for each connection type to allow for most reconnecting options. The new connections have been developed with the additional criteria of being demountable and, where possible, to fit elements with the widest possible range of dimensions. Connections developed for the aspect (2) can be used to connect new elements and elements that have been deconstructed carefully, through which no alterations to the elements have been made. Two connections are developed for aspect (2), relating the connection between two hollow-core slabs. Connection (C1) is designed to prevent horizontal movement over the joint between the slabs, while (C2) limits vertical differential deformation of the joint, both include experimental and numerical research. Connections developed for aspect (3) can also apply to a certain extent for unaltered/ new elements. For aspect (3), three connections are developed. (C3) is a connection concept to retrofit columns and beams, which was only studied numerically. (C4) is a connection to transfer tension forces in wall elements and increase friction in the joints. (C5) connection concept looks into preventing in-plane movement between elements, which can be applied to slabs and wall elements. (C4) and (C5) both include numerical and experimental research.

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Integrating Demolition into the Construction Project Lifecycle

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Keywords: lifecycle model, demolition project, material reuse and recycling

ABSTRACT

The construction industry must transform significantly to meet the EU's carbon neutrality targets. While new strategies like design for disassembly are emerging, vast urban areas shaped by outdated design principles will remain for decades. This raises the question of how these existing structures can be effectively utilized today. A more comprehensive lifecycle model is needed, one that goes beyond the traditional linear approach. Although circular economy frameworks, such as the Butterfly Diagram by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation [1] and the Loop Model [2], have been applied to the construction sector, these models are not yet fully integrated into formal lifecycle standards for buildings or construction materials [3], [4]. This study addresses how demolition can be repositioned as a strategic and integral part of the construction lifecycle, rather than a final step.

This study examines the development of construction project lifecycle models through a literature review and semi-structured interviews with eight professionals from both contractor and client sectors. The aim is to identify best practices for implementing circular construction—defined here as the use of recycled materials and strategic material recovery during demolition—and to validate a proposed lifecycle model. The interviews draw on insights from Finnish pilot projects and broader professional expertise in sustainable construction. The study analyzes how lifecycle models have evolved internationally, identifies expert views on future directions, and highlights practices and innovations not yet widely applied in Finland.

This study introduces a new construction project lifecycle model that prioritizes material reuse and recovery at a strategic level, while outlining the practical steps required for implementation in real-world contexts. The proposed model defines the necessary connections and scheduling to facilitate effective collaboration between demolition and new construction activities. In doing so, it demonstrates how these processes can progress in parallel, rather than in isolation. The model functions as a strategic instrument to support organizational alignment and the identification of context-specific best practices within the Finnish construction sector.

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Evaluating the Deconstruction Process of Precast Concrete Elements Intended for Reuse in Four Pilot Projects

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Keywords: Concrete elements, Deconstruction design, Renovation, Repair, Reuse, Sustainability.

ABSTRACT

Reuse of precast concrete elements is more sustainable than recycling crushed concrete in landfills. New detaching techniques as well as new lifting accessories has been developed in ReCreate project. Deconstruction pilots in each country provided extensive experience in detaching and lifting the elements. An accurate deconstruction plan with alternative options for temporary bracing and shortening, as well as alternative disconnecting options for elements, is necessary. Different temporary bracing systems and detaching techniques for elements were tested, and lifting accessories for hollow core slabs were successfully developed.

INTRODUCTION

The Finnish building stock is relatively young compared to many European countries. Based on Statistics Finland (2025) 70% of all residential buildings and 80% of floor area have been built since 1960's. Despite the relatively young age of these buildings, approximately 8000 buildings are demolished annually. The primary reason for demolition is new construction (91%) due to cities planning for more or different permitted building volumes in areas where buildings already exist. Consequently, demolition occurs most actively in regions where new construction is prevalent, such as the capital area, Tampere, Turku and Oulu.

Residential buildings have the longest service life before demolition. On average block of flats are demolished when they reach 62 years old, while warehouses and industrial buildings are demolished at an average age of 37 years, and commercial and office buildings at 39 years old. (Huuhka & Lahdensivu 2014)

Reuse of precast concrete elements has been studied in EU funded international ReCreate project, where experimental building practices are implemented. Precast office building made of concrete elements have been deconstructed in Finland, the Netherlands and Sweden, and block of flats in Germany and Sweden. Salvaged elements are reused in new constructions.

Structural precast concrete elements are connected using force-transferring connectors. In block of flats, these connections are mostly reinforcement and grouting, while connections between columns and beams commonly use bolted joints. Hollow core slabs are standard intermediate floors in all concrete buildings and are typically reinforced and grouted. In Germany, most connections are welded together. Generally, these connections are permanent and labour-intensive to dismantle, often requiring cutting or breaking to remove elements from their place. Studies conducted by Tampere University (Lahdensivu et al. 2015) found that

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columns, beams, and TT-slabs are the easiest to detach, while intermediate and exterior wall elements and hollow core (HC) slabs reinforced connections must be broken.

Old buildings are usually demolished, and materials recycled when no longer needed or when there is a need for a larger building at the same location. Therefore, large-scale deconstruction techniques for reusing salvaged precast elements have not been widely developed. This paper discusses considerations for deconstructing buildings intended for reusing precast elements that were not originally designed for deconstruction and reuse.

RESEARCH DATA AND METHODS

The research data consist of technical drawings, deconstruction plans, and experiences of detaching elements in ReCreate pilot buildings. The deconstructed precast concrete buildings are thoroughly presented in Vullings et al. (2024). The main salvaged elements in each pilot are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Salvaged elements for reuse in pilots.

Element type	Number of elements			
	Finland	Sweden	The Netherlands	Germany
column	95	50		
beam	45	19		
hollow core slab	134	7	549	
massive floor slab	3	24		192
interior walls	3	20	67	116
bearing exterior walls	3		409	120
non-bearing exterior walls	3			
staircase			18	
staircase landing			26	36

Research methods employed include case studies, research by design and active participation observation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Deconstruction plan. A structural deconstruction plan provides a detailed description of how precast concrete elements should be detached while maintaining the structural integrity of the building and ensuring a safe working environment for the workers. The structural deconstruction plan contains at least the following elements:

- Requirements for stripping before deconstruction, including removal of harmful substances
- Labelling of the precast concrete elements for later tracing
- Detailed design of a temporary support system to ensure structural safety during deconstruction
- Description of disconnecting the concrete elements safely and without damaging them
- Instructions for safe lifting of the elements, and the structural design of special lifting accessories for deconstruction, if needed
- Instructions for visual inspection of the elements, as well as for their safe transport and storage.

A qualified structural engineer must author the structural deconstruction plan. It is highly recommended that the plan be developed with the deconstruction company, as there might be specific considerations for lifting or disconnecting the elements or special tools available by the company. The deconstruction methods, planned techniques, and important issues related to quality assurance of reclaimed elements must be thoroughly communicated to all workers. This is crucial for avoiding damage to the elements during deconstruction and for identifying any defects that might prevent the safe reuse of the reclaimed elements.

Disconnecting elements. Most of the connections need bracing. At least some of the concrete must be removed to gain access to the actual connection parts. Reinforcement or welding might to be cut, and nuts removed from bolt joints. For example, hollow core slab tie bars to exterior or intermediate walls need to be opened and cut before the element can be safely lifted, see Figure 1. In most cases, cutting was done with a diamond saw. Practical experience from deconstruction pilots indicated that the structural deconstruction plan should also specify the maximum depth and extent of cuts to avoid damaging adjacent elements.

Figure 1. Cutting the connection between a façade element and HC slab (left) and cutting the welded steel ties from column-beam connection (right).

Another issue discussed before disconnecting the elements and before installing the temporary support system for elements was whether elements should be cut to the right dimensions during sawing. For example, hollow core slabs could be cut for right length during disconnection phase, if the new required length is known beforehand. The advantage of this approach is reduced handling afterwards since the element needs to be cut only once. However, the disadvantage is that the temporary support system must bear higher loads during disconnection and therefore needs to be stronger than used in the pilots.

Lifting the elements. The main issue when handling heavy concrete elements is safety. The elements must not slip out of the lifting system, transport vehicle, or storage rack during the process. During construction, the original lifting lugs are mostly cut off or damaged. Therefore, alternative lifting systems are likely needed in deconstruction projects. Several lifting systems for hollow core slabs were developed in Dutch and Finnish pilots, see Figure 2. The special lifting accessories usually used for new hollow core slabs could not be used because of the grouted concrete between the slabs. Additionally, in the Dutch pilot, the 60 mm reinforced concrete on top of hollow core slabs was another obstacle.

The developed and tested lifting systems for hollow core slabs required a lot of drilled holes. When these hollow core slabs are installed in new buildings, the holes must be patched, causing extra work and costs. A lifting system that does not require additional drilling or patching was developed in the Finnish pilot, see Figure 3, but it was not produced or tested.

Figure 2. Developed lifting accessories for hollow core slabs. The Dutch version on the left (source Lagemaat) and the Finnish version on the right (source Ramboll Finland Oy).

Figure 3. Developed lifting system for hollow core slabs (source Ramboll Finland Oy).

Lifting by drilling holes in elements was widely used in wall elements despite newly developed lifting systems. For columns, lifting was performed using a system similar to the original, except the lifting hole was bigger than original.

CONCLUSIONS

Deconstruction pilots in each country provided extensive experience in detaching and lifting elements. An accurate deconstruction plan with alternative options for temporary bracing and shortening, as well as alternative options for disconnecting elements, is necessary. Workers are typically not used to detaching elements, so it is crucial to develop detaching techniques collaboratively and ensure they are suitable for the contractor's equipment.

Different temporary bracing systems and detachment techniques were tested, and lifting accessories for hollow core slabs were successfully developed. However, each project still requires a qualified structural engineer to initiate the workers in detaching process and conduct visual quality checks of reclaimed elements before transportation to storage.

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Salvaging load-bearing steel and reinforced concrete building elements for open-destination reuse - a case study

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keywords: concrete reuse, steel reuse, structural reuse, environmental benefits, life-cycle assessment, sustainable construction

ABSTRACT

The production of building materials significantly contributes to global greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) and natural resource depletion. Reusing structural elements in construction can mitigate these environmental impacts by reducing the demand for primary resources, reducing building waste and avoiding new emissions. This paper presents the process of salvaging structural steel and concrete elements from buildings planned to be demolished, specifically focusing on generic or open-destination reuse. Using an office building in Basel, Switzerland, as a case study, the research highlights the necessary steps to identify potential structural elements for generic reuse and examines three parameters from within the process of reuse that can influence the definition and selection of these elements.

A systematic literature review was used as a base to identify potential elements that can be reused from a donor building. Through expert interviews the reuse process was parameterised and the main parameters influencing the effectiveness of the reuse process were identified. The sequence and implications of the dismantling process was modelled through expert interviews and a site visit. Different specification documents were examined and consolidated into a catalogue of criteria for identifying and specifying elements for publication and exchange through a market-place.

The research produces a systematic approach for scanning existing buildings and identifying reusable structural elements. The results show that standard road transport dimensions and weight should be taken into consideration when defining elements for extraction. Thus, contributing to the development of praxis grounded solutions to the global challenges of climate change and resource scarcity.

INTRODUCTION

The production of construction material is a major emitter of global GHG-emissions and a driver in natural resource depletion (UNEP YCEA 2023). The reuse of building material reduces the demand for primary resources and mostly avoids new GHG-emissions (Xiong et al. 2024). A great potential lies within the structural elements with high embodied energy (Al-Najjar and Malmqvist 2025, Berglund-Brown and Ochsendorf 2025).

The reuse of structural building elements was a common practice in the past (Stricker 2026:17-31). It has recently been taken up again by pioneering projects. Currently most proceed by individual peer-to-peer reuse: single elements are identified in different donor buildings and are integrated into one new building during the planning phase. In contrast, little information and guidelines are available for the process of salvaging entire buildings on a large scale in order to extract elements for structural reuse and distribute them through a market-place, with a generic, open-end reuse destination.

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The process of reusing steel or reinforced concrete components differs. Steel can be reused multiple times without losing its structural integrity or strength, making it a circular material (Berglund-Brown and Ochsendorf 2025). Reusing steel significantly reduces (Cappel 2021) carbon emissions (25% from primary steel), energy consumption (30 – 35% from primary steel), and the demand for virgin raw materials. Compared to concrete, steel is easier to salvage and reuse as it is often assembled rather than permanently joined, allowing for simpler disassembly or separation from other materials (Kanyilmaz et al. 2023).

In contrast, the reuse of reinforced concrete is challenging. Cast in-place concrete is not designed for disassembly, with wet connections forming a monolithic mass that bind it integrally to other building elements. The process of extracting concrete elements is labour-intensive, technically demanding and often leads to irregular, non-standardized components that complicate their integration into new structures (Grangeot et al. 2023). Despite these difficulties, proof-of-concept projects have demonstrated that it is possible to reuse cut elements from cast-in-place concrete for new load-bearing applications (Devènes et al. 2022).

The office building, serving as a case study was constructed in the 1970s and is located in Basel, Switzerland. Further background remains confidential. The building is an 8-floor hybrid structure of cuboidal shape composed of a steel skeleton, steel profile composite floor decks, reinforced concrete cores and shear walls. An additional, separate ground-floor auditorium is covered by a steel canopy structure. The concrete underground floors are not available for reuse.

This led to the research questions, what are the main parameters influencing the effectiveness of disassembling the load-bearing structure of a building and how to identify structural elements for open-destination reuse. To validate the results a case study was used, focussing on the reuse of structural steel and reinforce concrete elements.

METHOD AND MATERIALS

A first part analyses what necessary practical steps need to be followed when examining a building with the aim of identifying structural elements suitable for open-end reuse. A systematic literature review was conducted with the key words „Deconstruct“, „Reuse“, „Process“, „Building“ on the databases Scopus, Web of Science und Google Scholar on 16.11.2024 at 16:40 Uhr. Two seed papers were added to the research string for focus: Arora et al. (2021) and Kpfer et al. (2024).

Parameters of influence for determining and specifying elements to be salvaged

Between the offer provided by a donor building and the demand in a beneficiary building, the entire process of reuse seems to influence the determination and specification of the elements to be salvaged. In a second part, three factors of influence within the practical phases for reuse as described by Abegg et al. (2021) were retained within the scope of this study (Fig.1):

Figure 1. Potential parameters of influence for determining and specifying elements to be salvaged (own illustration)

a) The process of dismantling for reuse

The influence bearing from the process of dismantling and extraction was investigated through expert interviews. Four persons from the construction industry representing demolition companies or consultancies were chosen for their pioneering role within the Swiss context and expertise on the subject. Questionnaires were sent a week prior to the semi-structured one-hour interview. The registered and transcribed exchange is analysed using the software MASQDA.

b) Specification and identification of building components

To be able to identify and advertise salvaged elements in a market-place, a data sheet or material passport is necessary. In order to determine what specifications are useful for the desired marketability and transfer of information from donor to beneficiary, a comparative analysis of four different catalogues of past reuse projects was conducted: Swiss-Inv Inventar, Bauteilkatalog Gruner AG, Bauteilkatalog Immobilien Basel Stadt, Bauteilkatalog Zirkular GmbH.

c) Transport and logistics

A literature review of relevant Swiss norms was used to determine dimensions and weight for a standard road transport. In addition, a site visit of the pioneering project Lysbüchel in Basel, Switzerland is conducted on 25.2.2025 and documented, followed by a non-structured interview of the chief engineer in charge of salvaging reinforced concrete elements for reuse by dismantling the multi-storey logistics parking facility.

RESULTS

Parametric workflow for identifying reuse potential

Figure 2. Parametric workflow for identifying reuse potential (own illustration)

The systematic literature research produced 14 relevant papers, where procedures for an initial building survey and the determination of structural elements suitable for reuse were described. These have been consolidated in a decision making flow chart shown in Figure 2.

This consolidated decision-making flow chart allows an initial classification of the building structure into distinct areas: *S* with potential for reuse as load-bearing elements, *NS* with potential for reuse as non-structural elements or *X* not suitable for reuse.

Parameters of influence for determining and specifying elements to be salvaged

a) The process of dismantling for reuse

The interviews confirmed that the process of extraction will have implications on the final size and geometry of salvaged elements, depending on material and technique. The following key points were revealed: The gradual de-constructing of the load-bearing system follows preceding constructive logics, ensuring the structural integrity throughout. Extra openings for hoisting elements will reduce availability for reuse.

Obtaining panels from cast-in-place reinforced concrete slabs or walls often reduces the initial dimensions and may compromise their structural integrity. The different cutting tools require operational space and result in additional margins: diamond saw cutting, wire sawing or water jetting. The cutting of thicker slabs requires additional parallel twin cuts to prevent interlocking when lifting.

Steel constructions may usually be disassembled more easily and with higher precision. Successful unscrewing is rare but bolted connections may be oxy-fuel cut without affecting the load-bearing element itself. Welded assemblies require thermal or mechanical cutting methods, will therefore produce an off-cut and hence reduce the initial portion available for reuse.

b) Specification and identification

Examining the four databases produced a combined list of 55 criteria. Mirroring these with the case study building X revealed that gathering this information is time-consuming and costly. A contradicting requirement exists between the donor and the beneficiary: the first seeks to reduce cost, whilst the second needs comprehensive data for planning and minimising risk.

As a consequence the 55 identifying criteria were subdivided into three tiers of priority, following an increasing level of detail that may be added successively upon advancement of the planning process on either the donor or beneficiary side. The first tier comprising the attributes "material, dimension, available quantity, identification number, contact information" is deemed sufficient for an initial publication on a market-place.

c) Transport and logistics

Swiss federal traffic regulations (471.11 Verkehrsregelnverordnung § 64-67) define maximum overall dimensions for standard road transport by semi-trailer truck with a width of 2.55m, a height of 4.00m (§66) and a length of 16.50m. On a European standard semi-trailer truck this results in maximum load dimensions of $w=2.55\text{m}$, $h=3.00\text{m}$, $l=13.60\text{m}$. The overall weight for a standard transport is limited to 40.0 metric tons, including the semi-trailer truck and the total load. Any excess of these dimensions and weight necessitates extra permits, increasing complexity and cost. The site visit and interview confirmed these results and added a maximum weight capacity for standard construction site cranes of 6.00-7.00 metric tons, implying this as an ideal maximum weight for each single element intended for reuse.

DISCUSSION

The newly elaborated decision-making flow chart for the survey procedure expands on the previous results by Devènes (2002:16). The proposed guideline seems suited for non-experts of the reuse procedure and readily applicable in practice for salvaging on a larger scale. The difference in procedure was only limited to steel and reinforced concrete due to the material composition of the case study. Thus, further research is needed to identify the validity of the results for other construction systems like masonry and timber.

The investigation of the dismantling process revealed useful indications on the sequence, and the different processes together with their implications. However, it does not allow to establish generally applicable guidelines nor measures. Too many factors vary with circumstances within the donor building and technique. This shows that buildings currently being dismantled have not been designed for de-construction resulting in a complex and costly process. Further research into the potential of robotics in the dismantling process might be useful.

Limiting dimensions of elements for reuse to standard road transport sizes is generally most cost- and time-efficient and supports the practicability of reuse, according to an expert interview. On the other hand, according to Brütting (2020) choosing largest possible salvaging dimensions and hence retaining structural components intact may allow to safeguard the highest structural value to be re-employed. The first statement focusses on favouring conditions for reuse of structural elements on a larger scale, while the second on maximising the reduction of grey energy on an individual element level. As the process may become applied more widely, both statements may merge.

CONCLUSION

The research established a systematic approach for scanning existing buildings and identifying reusable structural elements through a literature review. Using a case study as practical reference point allowed to develop praxis oriented solutions.

Consolidating numerous criteria of different catalogues produced a list of specifications for identifying structural elements for publication and exchange through a market-place, arranged in a scale of priority tiers.

Investigating the dismantling process, allowed to show a practical sequence and elucidate potential implications of different extraction techniques. However no generally applicable guideline could be defined.

The study reveals the dimensions of reuse elements have an implications on the complexity and cost of logistics. Therefore, in some cases it might be preferable to select most common dimension and characteristics to stay within standard transport sizes and favour marketability; in other conditions, it might be recommendable to extract elements for their best structural or material capacity. The establishment of a broad and open market-place for reuse elements can allow to develop more precise guidelines and increase the effectiveness of reuse of building components.

Case study confidentiality

Due to pending building permits, the identity and further detail regarding the donor building may currently only be provided conditionally upon request.

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Circularity in the Built Environment 2025

Circular supply chain management in construction

A decision framework for circular management based on enablers and obstacles of construction waste logistics in Hong Kong

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Keywords: Circular economy, Construction disposal waste management, Construction waste logistics, Value stream mapping

ABSTRACT

The circular economy (CE) has brought new vitality to the construction industry, and reverse logistics of construction waste has become an important way to circular practices. However, the value chain in construction disposal waste management (CDWM) is too long, and CDWM involves too many facilities, processes, and stakeholders. Many issues have arisen in the logistics of CDWM, such as unreasonable facility allocation, repeated transportation processes, and high empty load rates, resulting in secondary waste. Therefore, this study aims to identify the enablers and obstacles of CDWM in the Hong Kong construction industry and propose a decision framework to promote the efficiency of CDWM and implement the concept of CE.

This study first conducted a content analysis of the current literature on CDWM research and identified the current enablers and obstacles in CDWM in Hong Kong. The study found that although the Hong Kong government has several recycling policies, supports and initiatives for infrastructure network construction and logistics management, no single enabler can be effectively implemented in the application. In addition, due to obstacles such as the limited land, shortage of recycling facilities and lack of recycling functions in Hong Kong, CDWM needs clearer strategic guidance.

These problems are also reflected in the data analysis of CDW logistics records provided by the Hong Kong government. Therefore, this study combines the above content with the results of big data analysis to propose three management strategies: 1) Effective utilization of vehicle capacity; 2) The improvement in the recycling rate; 3) The avoidance of peak hours for waste collection and transportation. Based on the above three strategies, the multi-objective value stream mapping evaluation method (i.e., time, cost, environmental emission, transportation efficiency) was revised and improved. Specifically, it is reflected in the correction of various value calculation formulas through the integration of several specific conditions, such as trucks with different capacities and actual transport loads, and the processing processes of facilities under different operating periods. A heatmap of each value under each specific improvement strategy is given for visualisation of decision making, and a CDWM management decision-making method for optimizing multiple values is proposed by combining the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) method.

Finally, this study combined the CDW logistics big data provided by the Hong Kong government and applied the framework to a case study in Tuen Mun, Hong Kong. This method provides decision-makers with a new CDW logistics management tool and helps further implement the transformation of Hong Kong's construction industry to the CE.

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A Taxonomic Framework for Structured Databases of Reusable Precast Concrete Elements

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Keywords: Circular economy, Taxonomy, Building database, Reuse.

ABSTRACT

The Architecture, Engineering, and Construction sector (AEC) is undergoing a fundamental transformation driven by the principles of circularity, sustainability, and digitalisation. One promising approach within this shift is the reuse of precast concrete elements sourced from end-of-life buildings, enabled by the increased availability of digital tools. However, a major obstacle in scaling up such reuse strategies lies in the absence of a consistent, standardised method for identifying, classifying, and documenting existing precast elements and systems. To address this gap, this study examines the development of a taxonomy for precast elements and systems, to facilitate identification, traceability, and interoperability by providing a consistent identification between physical elements and their corresponding documentation. The proposed taxonomy is based on a faceted classification approach integrated with hierarchical categories, where facets can be combined to form unique identifiers, enabling detailed descriptions and comparisons across contexts. This hybrid classification is based on the standard for management of terminology and classification development (ISO 22274), the standard for construction classification systems (ISO 12006-2), while complying with information management standards for BIM (ISO 19650). Each precast element or system is classified across multiple independent facets, such as geometry, structural function, manufacturing provenance, production year, and intended application.

At the element level, the taxonomy distinguishes between class-level definitions (generic element types) and instance-level records (specific components from donor buildings). This distinction enables the consistent modelling of precast systems with BIM while allowing individual elements to be documented, evaluated, and reused based on their specific characteristics and history. At the system level, the taxonomy captures broader architectural and structural logics, including typological, structural, and historical developments. The taxonomy has been validated through a range of historical case studies across Europe. It integrates existing documentation, facilitates semantic search and comparison, and provides the foundation for structuring extensible databases of precast concrete elements available for reuse. By systematically organising both class-level definitions and instance-level data, it allows for the continuous enrichment of the database as new components are documented, surveyed, and characterised. Thus, the proposed taxonomy constitutes a critical enabler for circularity in the built environment, providing a methodological foundation for the classification and modelling of precast components, supporting the implementation of reuse in circular construction workflows.

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An organizational framework to upscale the reuse of construction materials

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Keywords: technical performance, reused materials, reuse protocols, tracking and tracing, digital information management, chain management.

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an organizational framework aimed at upscaling the reuse of construction materials in the Belgian building sector. Despite clear environmental benefits, reuse remains limited due to technical, legal, and procedural barriers. In collaboration with Buildwise and general contractor Democo, a structured framework was developed, consisting of material-specific protocols, a digital tracking system, and predefined typical applications. The system supports traceability, risk minimization, and quality assurance by combining objective data with practical expertise. A proof of concept was tested through pilot projects, including the construction of a rooftop pavilion using reclaimed timber and mineral wool. While the framework offers a practical tool for validating reused materials, further research is needed to ensure broader industry adoption and evaluate its financial viability in circular construction ecosystems.

INTRODUCTION

One key strategy in the circular economy is material reuse, which retains value and prevents downgrading to raw materials or energy recovery through incineration [1]. The environmental benefits of reuse can be substantial, depending on the material's original production impact. For instance, reclaimed structural wood can reduce environmental impacts by 63% [2], while reusing ceramic tiles can yield an 83% reduction [3]. Despite its sustainable potential, material reuse in European construction remains marginal, with rates below 15% [4].

Lambec et al. identify a critical gap in the literature concerning the practical implementation of deconstruction and reuse practices [5]. There is limited insight into the operational procedures involved—from identifying reusable materials, organizing deconstruction, transport, and storage, to verifying technical performance, integrating materials into new designs, and final on-site installation. Each step involves multiple stakeholders and added costs, complicating the creation of scalable business models. Hobbs et al. studied the challenges and opportunities to increase reuse and explain the challenge of legal ambiguities - such as defining when a material is waste versus a product, and clarifying responsibility for performance guarantees. They further conclude that many of the challenges to reuse are connected to the availability and robustness of data [6].

This paper presents an organizational framework developed for a Belgian general contractor to address these barriers and procedural uncertainties. The framework provides material-specific protocols for each process phase, a digital system for tracking material information, and mechanisms to foster trust-based collaboration within an ecosystem. This framework aims to

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make reuse more accessible and economically viable. It has been developed for two material types - mineral wool insulation and wooden beams - and is currently being tested in multiple pilot projects. The paper describes the framework and discusses its potential for sector-wide application in Belgium.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data analysis from previous experience

Buildwise, Belgium's research and innovation center for the construction sector, has been engaged in reuse-related research and pilot projects for over a decade. Its activities include testing reclaimed materials such as wood, bricks, insulation, and raised floors. The organization has authored key national reference documents, including guidelines for reuse inventories, technical performance assessment frameworks, and practical manuals for contractors [7][8][9][10]. Since 2021, the general contractor Democo has integrated reclaimed materials into projects. They have conducted reuse inventories, sought partnerships for material uptake, and collaborated with social enterprises for careful dismantling and storage of elements such as wooden floors, marble, insulation glass, wooden beams, zinc sheets, and sanitary components. Democo has also worked with deconstruction companies and conducted over seven site visits in the Brussels region to map material availability and study dismantling processes. Their systematic documentation offers insights into practical barriers, economic viability, and the time investment needed for dismantling. Data and lessons learned from both organizations, together with the existing theoretical methodologies and identified challenges mentioned in the introduction, formed the basis for the development of a practical organizational framework to scale up material reuse.

Stakeholder interviews, workshops and multicriteria analysis

To test the applicability of the framework, stakeholder interviews and design workshops were held. Three workshops brought together Democo, key subcontractors, architects, consultants (EPB and acoustics), Buildwise experts (in fire safety, circularity, acoustics, and structures), and material producers. These sessions led to the co-creation of circular designs strategies for partitioning walls and floors including reused materials. Only designs deemed likely to become "typical solutions" were retained. For their evaluation, a multicriteria analysis was done considering the costs, cross-project applicability, degree of substitution of new with reclaimed materials, and future dismantlability.

Pilot projects

Three active construction projects by Democo serve as pilots for implementing and testing the framework. Each procedural step is evaluated through stakeholder interviews and by monitoring product quality and associated costs. The documents from the protocol and forms for the data management system are adapted and improved on an iterative basis based on feedback and lessons learned from each of the pilot projects.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The organizational framework

To develop an effective organizational framework, it is essential to identify the process phases and the types of companies involved. Six phases were defined: Pre-deconstruction, Deconstruction, Measuring and Testing, Storage and Transportation, Design Measures, and On-site Installation (**Figure 1**). These phases, and the actors involved, vary per project. Some services—like inventory, deconstruction, and storage—can be offered by one single providers, while other stakeholders engage briefly in only one phase. This variability highlights the need

for a flexible framework and a digital information management tool, enabling all participants to log their interventions and support traceability and quality control of reused materials. In order to have confidence in the determination of the technical performance and to be able to validate the technical suitability of the reused material, the framework is composed of three main parts:

- 1) **Protocols which describe the “way of working”** that is expected from the companies in each phase of the process.
- 2) **Standardized information and data transfer** in each phase of the process.
- 3) **Predefined typical design applications** for reused materials, allowing an easy “fit-for-purpose” check

Figure 1: Schematic overview of the standardized process. Each phase uses digital tracking and protocols, and material validation occurs by comparing the technical properties of the Reuse-ID sheet with technical requirements of “typical” design solutions.

This allows for a controlled process, minimizing risks and creating confidence in the quality of the reused materials **combining objective data** (e.g. data sheets with year of production, measurement of the density, previous application) **with the practical ‘know-how’ based on the protocols** of the companies involved (e.g. exclusion of wooden beams with signs of insect infestation). To further simplify the process we work with a number of **predefined typical design applications** (e.g. internal wall within an apartment, non-high-rise) for which the technical requirements are well known and the suitability of the reused material can easily be verified (e.g. density of the mineral wool should be at least the value mentioned in the acoustic reference test report). As a result, companies do not need to assess all possible applications and requirements themselves. Instead, they can rely on high-potential, predefined solutions where reclaimed materials are more likely to meet the criteria.

1) Reuse protocols per phase and per material

Given the involvement of different companies at various stages of the reuse process, a separate protocol was developed for each phase and each material type. While the structure is consistent, the content is material-specific. For instance, wood requires detailed visual inspection for insect damage, moisture, or fungi, whereas this is less critical for mineral wool from interior office partitions. However, for mineral wool, production date is essential, as fibres manufactured before 2000 may pose health risks [11].

Each protocol outlines procedures to minimize quality degradation and ensure accurate assessment of technical properties. The relevant company receives the protocol and is expected to adhere to it. This commitment ensures that materials are properly identified, examined, dismantled, tested, stored, or transported following standardized practices. These protocols, endorsed by Buildwise, Belgium’s construction reference center, provide assurance to all stakeholders that reuse processes meet accepted quality standards.

2) Standardized information and data transfer

In addition to standardized procedures, consistent data collection and transfer are essential. Prior to dismantling, key information—such as construction year, building context, or technical datasheets—is collected per batch of materials with shared origin and characteristics. During deconstruction and storage, additional data (e.g., insulation thickness, thermal conductivity via lab tests) are gathered. All data are tracked across phases and compiled in a final document: the “Reuse ID-sheet.” Comparable to a material passport, but designed for reclaimed rather than new materials, this ID-sheet reflects the decentralized reuse process and the distinct roles of stakeholders and data sources involved.

Building on the literature review of Markou et al. [12], a platform-based methodology was identified as most suitable. Within the Mined2Rewind research project, a proof of concept was developed using Airtable [13]. Structured forms per phase, completed by involved companies, are linked via a unique ID-code assigned to each material batch. This code facilitates traceability throughout the reuse chain. Once the process is complete, all data—each annotated with its source (e.g., lab test, datasheet, or manufacturer info)—are consolidated in the Reuse ID-sheet. This enables transparent quality evaluation and supports informed reuse decisions.

3) Predefined typical design solutions

To simplify and economically support reuse practices, we propose working with predefined typical applications. In collaboration with general contractor Democo, we identified standard construction elements frequently used in their projects that could incorporate reclaimed materials. Specifically, four types of internal walls were defined, along with a list of materials suitable for substitution. For each wall type, a document was created detailing relevant technical requirements—such as fire reaction, fire resistance, and acoustic performance—and specifying the minimum performance criteria for reclaimed materials within that specific application. In some cases, requirements remain unchanged with reuse; in others, clear thresholds (e.g. minimum thickness or test values) or test reports are needed. These documents provide clarity on what is required per material. Using this approach, contractors can consult a material’s “Reuse ID-sheet” and compare it with the predefined criteria for the typical application. This allows for a straightforward assessment of whether a batch of reclaimed materials meets the necessary standards, as illustrated in Figure 1.

First pilot project: rooftop pavilion

To refine the protocols and further develop the digital tracking system, pilot projects are conducted within real-life construction sites by general contractor Democo. The first pilot involved constructing a rooftop pavilion on a new apartment building (**Figure 2**). Reclaimed laminated beams and wooden beams were tested and used for the roof structure and façade

framework. Reclaimed mineral wool, with verified lambda-value, was applied in the façade elements. This implementation allowed for in-depth evaluation of technical requirements and informed updates to the protocols for pre-deconstruction and deconstruction of structural timber. On-site installation revealed specific attention points, such as fiber orientation of insulation, avoiding penetrations in critical zones, screw hole positioning, and material compatibility with finishes. These findings highlighted the need for a technical installation guide for reclaimed materials, which will be added to the organizational framework and further developed through upcoming pilot projects. Finally, the subcontractor noted that milling the reclaimed beams increased costs by up to 20% compared to using new beams, underlining the importance of assessing the framework not only technically, but also from an economic perspective.

Figure 2: Rooftop pavilion, with reclaimed laminated beams and reclaimed wood for the roof structure and reclaimed wood and mineral wool in the façade modules.

Feedback from companies involved indicates that the protocols and tracking system are sometimes perceived as complex, rigid, or incompatible with their existing workflows. The final version must therefore balance practical feasibility, cost efficiency, and quality assurance. As current feedback was limited to stakeholders in Brussels, broader consultation across the Belgian construction sector is needed.

While the framework enables transparent assessment of the technical suitability of reclaimed materials, questions remain about who bears responsibility for validating this suitability. The framework is conceived as an open system, allowing market actors to define roles. Responsibility could lie with the material bank selling the reclaimed product, or with the contractor, provided this aligns with their circular business model.

Today, the usability of the framework has not yet been fully proven, only parts of the framework have been tested in the first pilot. Other pilots are needed to fully evaluate the potential of the framework.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a practical and scalable organizational framework to facilitate the reuse of construction materials through clear protocols, structured information tracking, and predefined

typical applications. The first pilot project demonstrated that technical validation of reclaimed materials is feasible, provided there is adequate documentation and collaboration between stakeholders. However, successful implementation depends not only on technical procedures but also on the willingness of market actors to adapt their practices. Feedback highlights the need for simplification and better alignment with existing workflows. Moreover, the question of who assumes responsibility for validating material suitability remains open and must be addressed within evolving circular business models. The next step in this research should be to investigate the costs involved in each phase and investigate how different companies can get organized in an ecosystem to make a promising business case out of the reuse of construction materials. As such, the framework offers a strong foundation for upscaling reuse practices, while emphasizing that economic viability, role definition, and practical applicability are key to long-term success.

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Analyzing the spatial logistics of construction materials for a circular economy

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Keywords: Built Environment, Circular Economy, Network Analysis, Spatial Logistics

ABSTRACT

The construction, operation, and maintenance of the built environment account for over 40% of the UK's carbon footprint and 62% of its total waste by mass. A shift to a circular economy (CE) is thus urgently required to limit primary material demand, increase reuse of construction waste, and reduce associated embodied carbon emissions. Despite this, there remain critical barriers to the widespread implementation of CE in the manufacturing, construction and waste sector due to the lack of infrastructure necessary to store these bulky and heavy building materials. Otherwise, most of the materials reclaimed from building demolition are downcycled into products of less value. This project therefore aims to address the key barrier to the adoption of CE in construction in terms of storing material for future reuse, in order to prolong their use cycles. This requires an understanding of how spatial dimensions affect the relationships between material supply and demand to evaluate the environmental impacts of the built environment.

The key motivation of this work is to fill in the research gap in the current literatures where the focus is usually on the business models, and reintegrating existing waste streams, but very little studies on the viability of CE as a function of the availability of intermediary reuse hubs in space and time to link material supply and demand. Hence, this work seeks to examine how location and capacity of intermediary storage hubs affects ability to reduce virgin material consumption and overall carbon footprint. Firstly, a hypothetical network model of material flows is used to study how varying numbers, location and size of hubs affects the carbon impact of CE logistics based on dynamic building demolition rates and new local area housing targets as proxies of waste material supply and demand. By overlaying storage hub locations and sizes with transport networks, a network analysis will be applied to optimize the number and location of material storage hubs required across different scales. As such, transport distances, emissions and economic costs are minimized, while promoting material reuse and reductions in raw material extraction, waste generation and associated embodied carbon emissions.

This will be followed by a UK-based case study to develop a map of suitable distribution and storage networks. The network model will be applied to the UK to establish material flow networks using supply and demand data over time, as well as incorporating stakeholder input on current storage facilities available. This overlaying map of material flows and storage hub locations will be combined with transport networks for optimizing the logistic distances to ensure environmental and economic benefits of reuse are considered. The results will contribute to the development of the UK's map of material storage and reuse network embedded in the existing infrastructure network to improve resource efficiency and environmental practices across the supply chain, reducing overall economic cost and carbon footprint.

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Cross-Regional Traceability and Circularity in Construction: The Role of Digital Product Passports

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Keywords: Circular Economy, Construction, Digital Product Identity, Digital Product Passports.

ABSTRACT

As the construction sector accelerates its transition toward circularity, the need for verifiable, high-quality information about materials and products across their lifecycle has become urgent. From emissions accountability to material reuse, the traceability and characteristics of building components are becoming key drivers of both compliance and value creation. Digital Product Passports (DPPs), structured digital records that document a product's composition, origin, and sustainability characteristics - essentially, constructing a Digital Product Identity - are emerging as essential infrastructure to meet these demands.

This paper explores the role of DPPs, traceability technologies, and supporting digital infrastructure in enabling circular supply chain management for the built environment. With tightening regulations across both Europe and Asia, such as the EU's Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and China's national mandate on product traceability, a cross-regional data layer is imminent. This implies aligning and harmonising digital systems and standards to enable the secure exchange of material and product data across jurisdictions, especially where supply chain transparency remains limited.

We present a framework for applying DPPs within construction ecosystems to unlock circular value. Rather than focusing on specific materials, we highlight how the framework facilitates the measurement of traceability and circularity metrics for diverse material streams, including reclaimed aggregates, recycled metals, and bio-based materials. Core technologies include digital identifiers (such as QR and RFID), blockchain-based audit trails, and cloud-based data repositories, which establish an unbroken link between the physical and digital worlds, leading to verifiable and immutable record-keeping. The framework is iteratively developed through multi-stakeholder pilot deployments across the Europe-Asia corridor.

We further assess how AI-enhanced methods, such as anomaly detection, semantic data structuring, and cross-referencing across datasets, can verify green claims, flag inconsistencies, and improve the overall reliability of lifecycle information. These tools are especially relevant in supply chains where documentation may be incomplete or unverifiable.

The paper concludes by outlining key recommendations for construction industry stakeholders seeking to operationalise circularity through digital information management. These include requirements for technical interoperability, robust data governance, and the active engagement of upstream and downstream actors. By embedding digital product identity into material management, DPPs can support compliance while enabling new forms of collaboration and verifiable circularity at scale.

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Node-Based Canvas Editor for Digital Product Passport Creation

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Keywords: Canvas Tool, Circular Economy, Digital Product Passport, Visual Programming.

ABSTRACT

Achieving a circular economy requires robust tools for managing and exchanging detailed product lifecycle data. As initiatives such as the European Union's Digital Product Passport (DPP) move forward, significant challenges persist, particularly in integrating data from diverse sources and making DPP tools accessible to non-technical users. This paper introduces the alpha version of the DPP editor system, a visual, node-based canvas tool that simplifies the creation and management of DPPs. Users can construct DPP workflows through drag-and-drop interactions using either template nodes or customizable nodes that support integration with databases, IoT devices, REST APIs, and file systems. By abstracting technical tasks into intuitive visual components, the tool lowers the barrier to DPP adoption and supports flexible, real-time data interaction for circular economy applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital Product Passports (DPPs) have emerged as a strategic tool for supporting the circular economy by enabling structured, transparent documentation of product lifecycle data[1]. By capturing and sharing information on material composition, origin, usage, and environmental impact, DPPs facilitate reuse, recycling, and informed decision-making across the value chain [2]. As regulatory momentum builds, especially through initiatives like the European Union's DPP framework, the demand for effective tools to create and manage these passports is growing rapidly.

Despite their potential, existing DPP solutions often pose significant technical barriers. Many require users to possess advanced programming skills or domain-specific knowledge in data integration, which limits accessibility for a broader range of stakeholders, including small manufacturers, recyclers, and regulatory bodies [4]. Furthermore, integrating heterogeneous data sources, ranging from manufacturing systems and supply chains to compliance records and IoT devices, remains a complex and error-prone task [4], [6], [6].

To address these challenges, this paper introduces the DPP editor system: a canvas-based visual design tool that enables intuitive and flexible creation of DPPs. The system is built on a modular, node-based architecture that allows users to construct DPP workflows using drag-and-drop interactions. Diverse nodes support integration with diverse data sources and schemas, enabling tailored workflows without requiring programming expertise.

By abstracting technical complexity into a user-friendly interface, the DPP editor system lowers the barrier to DPP adoption while supporting rich data modeling and workflow design. Key features include a visual editor for workflow construction, multi-source data integration (including databases, file uploads, REST APIs, and IoT streams), and export functionality for sharing and review. This paper presents the system architecture, core functionalities, and a

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simple case study demonstrating its application in a wood-based product lifecycle context. The system contributes a novel combination of domain-specific templates, a plug-in-based data architecture, and an intuitive canvas interface that together enable accessible, flexible, and scalable creation of DPPs across diverse user groups and data environments.

2. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

2.1 Major Functions

The DPP editor system comprises three primary functions, which are summarized in Figure 1 and detailed below:

Figure 1. Screenshot of the editor's home page highlighting key core functionalities.

Figure 2. Screen shot of the editor page with a simple example.

- **DPP Editor:** The Editor is the primary design environment for creating DPPs, featuring an intuitive drag-and-drop, node-based interface. As orange box marked in *Figure 2*, the editor consists of three main panels: 1) the node library panel on the left, which includes pre-configured template nodes, customizable dynamic nodes, and other node types; 2) the main canvas panel in the center, where users can drag nodes from the library and connect them to define the flow and organization of product information; 3) the property editor panel on the right, which displays detailed information about the selected node and allows users to edit its content and configuration. This three-panel layout is designed to support a highly efficient and user-friendly workflow: the left panel offers quick access to building blocks, the central canvas provides a visual overview of the product passport structure, and the right panel enables immediate, context-sensitive editing.
- **DPP Viewer:** The Viewer provides a sophisticated interface for examining completed DPPs by automatically transforming complex DPP data from the canvas into structured, accessible presentations organized through intuitive tabbed sections.
- **Data Management:** The Data Management module supports the creation and maintenance of reusable product data templates, custom schema definitions, bulk data import/export operations, and DPP management.

2.2 Technical Architecture

This architectural approach reflects three fundamental design principles essential for user adoption and future enhancement.

- **Modularity:** Each component addresses distinct functional domains while maintaining clear interfaces
- **Scalability:** The modular design supports the addition of new node types, export formats, and integration capabilities.
- **User-Centricity:** Visual design paradigms reduce complexity for domain experts who may lack technical background.

Figure 3. Technical architecture for the node-based canvas tool.

Based on above principle, we designed the architecture as Figure 2 illustrates, the DPP editor system utilizes a centralized architecture where a canvas engine serves as the primary workspace for creating DPP through visual design. This central component coordinates with six interconnected subsystems: the user interface enables stakeholders to interact with the system through familiar drag-and-drop operations across multiple workspace panels; the state manager ensures data consistency and provides complete change tracking with rollback capabilities; the node library offers both standardized templates for common industry scenarios and flexible custom node creation for specialized requirements; the group manager facilitates organizational hierarchy through intuitive grouping mechanisms that mirror real-world product relationships; and the export engine generates industry-standard outputs including data interchange formats, programming interfaces, and regulatory documentation.

2.3 Core Node Design Principles

The core design of the DPP editor is grounded in the concept of nodes as autonomous, intelligent data entities that encapsulate discrete aspects of product lifecycle information while maintaining seamless interoperability with other system components. This modular approach reimagines DPP creation not as a monolithic documentation task, but as a dynamic, interconnected ecosystem of specialized data collection and processing units. Each node functions as a self-contained service within the broader canvas architecture, equipped with its own data validation logic, processing capabilities, and integration protocols. This design allows nodes to operate independently while contributing to the overall functionality and intelligence of the

system. Nodes can validate their own data, initiating automated processes, communicating with external systems, and adapting their behavior in response to the context of the surrounding workflow. As a result, the editor promotes scalability, flexibility, and maintainability in complex product passport workflows.

The editor is built upon a comprehensive node library, systematically organized into categories that address the diverse requirements of DPPs. For instance, nodes within the Product Information category capture essential product attributes and specifications, while Supply Chain nodes manage data related to sourcing, transportation, and logistics. The strength of the system, however, lies in its ability to support a wide range of node types that accommodate varying levels of complexity, interoperability, and data integration. Figure 4 shows the screen shot of some example node; the details will be introduced afterwards. This flexible architecture enables the modeling of both simple and advanced product scenarios. Since each node type is designed as an independent, self-contained module, decoupled from the internal logic of other nodes, the system remains highly extensible. New node types can be added seamlessly without disrupting existing functionality, allowing the editor to evolve alongside emerging regulatory requirements, data standards, or industry-specific needs. The following section introduces several representative node types that we consider foundational for the effective development and implementation of DPPs.

3. SPECIALIZED NODE AND CAPABILITIES

In this section, we introduce several node types (as Figure 4 shows) employed in the editor; the details are provided below:

Figure 4. Gallery of example nodes

Template Nodes are pre-configured components designed for common DPP use cases. These nodes come with predefined properties and built-in functionality, allowing users to quickly populate standard data fields without the need for customization. Typical categories include Product Data (e.g., Basic Product, Advanced Product), Supply Chain (e.g., Material Source), Regulatory (e.g., Compliance Check), and Lifecycle (e.g., Carbon Footprint), and so on. For example, the Basic Product node includes default fields such as product name, description, and price. Users can simply drag these nodes into a workflow and enter relevant data. If modifications are needed, users can select the node and update its contents directly through the property panel, ensuring a seamless and intuitive editing experience.

Custom Nodes, in contrast, are user-defined components that provide flexibility beyond the scope of predefined templates. Created through an interactive dialog interface, custom nodes allow users to define the node's metadata such as name, description, icon, color, and category—and specify its properties, including data types like text, numbers, dropdowns, dates, attachment, etc.. Once added to a workflow, custom nodes function like template nodes and can be edited at any time through the property panel. This approach enables tailored workflows while maintaining the platform's usability and consistency across both standard and specialized DPP scenarios.

The **File Upload node** is a specialized visual programming component designed to streamline the integration of essential product documentation into DPP development workflows. Recognizing that DPP creation typically requires diverse file types containing critical product information, including evaluation reports, certifications, compliance documents, etc. This node provides a unified interface for importing and processing these heterogeneous data sources. The node automatically handles various document formats such as PDFs, Excel spreadsheets, XML certificates, JSON data files, and images, making it easy for users to upload the necessary documentation through a simple drag-and-drop interface. This component serves as the essential entry point for bringing external product documentation into DPP workflows, enabling manufacturers, suppliers, and compliance teams to quickly integrate their required files into the digital passport creation process.

The **database node** is a specialized visual component within the editor framework, designed to facilitate seamless integration and real-time visualization of database connections and query results within workflow diagrams. This node offers a unified interface for configuring connections to various database systems (e.g., MySQL, PostgreSQL, MongoDB), executing queries, and presenting both schema metadata and sample data directly within the design environment. To enhance reliability, the node incorporates a robust connection testing mechanism that verifies database credentials and query syntax prior to establishing persistent connections, thereby minimizing the risk of runtime errors during workflow execution. Once connected, the database node dynamically displays structural information about the linked database, including column names, data types, and key relationships, along with a preview of representative data rows. This immediate visualization enables researchers and developers to understand data sources and their structure without leaving the workflow context. The interface supports an expandable view that toggles between a compact summary (showing metrics such as column and row counts) and a detailed display of the database

schema and sample data. Additional features include automatic data type detection, visual indicators for connection status, configurable auto-refresh for live datasets, and standardized ports that allow the database node to connect and interact seamlessly with other components in the canvas system. Together, these capabilities support a more intuitive and integrated approach to data-driven workflow design.

The **REST API node** constitutes a vital component within modern workflow automation systems, acting as a bridge between internal canvas processes and external web services. This node addresses the core challenge of API integration in visual programming environments by offering a comprehensive interface that abstracts the complexity of HTTP communication while preserving full configurational flexibility. Through a structured, tabbed interface, users can systematically define request parameters, authentication methods, and data formatting options—enabling seamless interaction with a wide range of web services without requiring in-depth knowledge of HTTP protocols. The implementation includes real-time validation and testing features that provide immediate feedback on connectivity and response handling, thereby accelerating development cycles and minimizing integration errors. The node architecture supports both synchronous and asynchronous communication models, allowing for diverse integration scenarios—from straightforward data retrieval to more intricate, multi-step API workflows. To enhance usability, the node incorporates visual feedback mechanisms such as color-coded status indicators and expandable response viewers, improving transparency and debugging effectiveness. This design approach promotes the democratization of API integration, making advanced web service connectivity accessible to users with varying levels of technical expertise, while maintaining the reliability and flexibility necessary for production-grade workflow automation.

The **IoT Node** is a node component designed to enable seamless integration and real-time communication with IoT devices within canvas-based workflow environments. It adopts a multi-protocol architecture that supports MQTT-over-WebSocket, HTTP/REST, WebSocket, and CoAP, enabling platform-independent connectivity without requiring native software installations. The node offers robust device management features, including dynamic topic subscription, message filtering, authentication handling, and Quality of Service (QoS) configuration. It also includes integrated real-time data visualization, message history tracking, and basic statistical monitoring to support data-driven analysis. By leveraging a drag-and-drop interface, the IoT Node abstracts underlying networking complexities, allowing both technical and non-technical users to build IoT-enabled data flows and orchestration logic with ease. Its modular design supports extensible configuration management, automatic reconnection strategies, and parsing of diverse data formats such as JSON, XML, and binary. These capabilities make the IoT Node well-suited for a range of application domains including sensor networks, industrial monitoring, and smart infrastructure, reinforcing its role as a flexible and user-friendly building block within the DPP editor system.

The **Data Transformer Node** is a node component that enables users to perform data processing tasks within Extract-Transform-Load (ETL) workflows. Operating in a node-based canvas environment, it allows users to visually construct data pipelines by connecting transformation logic with other nodes, eliminating the need for traditional

coding. The node supports a wide range of transformation operations, including data type conversion, duplicate removal, field mapping, aggregation, and custom rule design through JavaScript coding. These capabilities facilitate the cleaning, filtering, formatting, and restructuring of heterogeneous datasets into standardized formats suitable for analysis or integration. For instance, data retrieved from a Database Node may contain redundant or irrelevant information, which can be filtered out by linking it to the Data Transformer Node and configuring the appropriate filter rules. This visual approach lowers the technical barrier for non-specialists while providing the flexibility needed for complex, enterprise-scale data integration projects.

4. DPP CREATION PROCESS

4.1 Drag-and Drop, Connect and Layout

The visual programming interface features a central, infinite canvas where users construct DPP workflows through intuitive drag-and-drop interactions. Nodes can be selected from the Node Library and placed onto the canvas, where they are visually arranged to represent the block of product lifecycle data. Users create logical connections between nodes by dragging from a source handle to a target handle, with real-time visual feedback and connection validation ensuring data flow integrity. The canvas supports zooming, panning, multi-node selection, and grid snapping for precise alignment, while automatic layout algorithms help organize complex workflows. Nodes can be repositioned freely, and right-click context menus allow for quick actions such as copy, paste, or delete.

4.2 Property Editing and Configuration

The property panel serves as a dynamic, context-sensitive interface that provides tailored editing capabilities for each node type within the node library. When a node is selected, the panel automatically adapts to present the appropriate configuration interface. For instance, a comprehensive, multi-tabbed form for REST API nodes, covering basic settings, authentication, headers, parameters, and request body configuration, along with integrated real-time testing; a connection and query editor for database nodes; and a standardized property editor for template and custom nodes. The latter displays schema-defined properties using input controls designed to support 19 distinct data types, including text fields, numeric inputs (integers, floats, and range sliders), Boolean toggles, date/time pickers, email and URL validators, single- and multi-select dropdowns, file uploads, and others. The panel enables real-time synchronization of all edits made to the selected node and enforces robust input validation, incorporating type-specific constraints to ensure data integrity. Additionally, the panel provides contextual help, validation feedback, and visual cues to indicate data types, guiding users through the configuration process with clarity and efficiency.

4.3 Hierarchical Organization and Grouping

The group and ungroup functions in the DPP editor system offer advanced hierarchical organization capabilities, enabling users to model complex structural relationships within their DPP workflows. The Group Manager features an intuitive drag-to-group interaction, allowing users to establish parent-child relationships by simply dragging selected nodes onto existing group containers. This mechanism supports unlimited

nesting levels, effectively mirroring real-world product hierarchies such as assemblies, sub-assemblies, and individual components. To preserve both structural and visual integrity, the system automatically calculates and maintains spatial relationships among nodes when grouped, ensuring a coherent layout that reflects the logical organization of the workflow. The Ungroup function complement this by enabling intelligent disassembly of group structures through a context-aware dialog interface. Users are provided with clear options: either to remove the entire group along with its child nodes or to preserve the child nodes and reassign them to appropriate hierarchical levels. When ungrouped to the top level, nodes are repositioned using absolute coordinates to maintain layout accuracy; when reassigned to existing groups, their parent relationships are preserved accordingly. Together, these functions provide a flexible and robust framework for workflow restructuring, enabling domain experts to organize and manage complex product information in alignment with industry-specific logic and regulatory requirements.

4.4 View, Export and Integration

The **DPP Viewer** module provides a structured and interactive dashboard for reviewing completed product data workflow developed through the node-based interface. Each logical group within the canvas is presented as a dedicated section, allowing users to navigate through the DPP in a clear and organized manner. The view interface supports real-time updates, automatically reflecting changes made to the underlying nodes or input data, thereby ensuring data consistency and up-to-date visualization throughout the product lifecycle.

The **Export** functionality supports the generation of standardized DPP outputs in multiple formats to accommodate diverse regulatory and operational requirements. Users can export the finalized DPP content as JSON for system integration, PDF for human-readable documentation, or via API endpoints for direct interaction with external systems. Additionally, the export process can generate QR codes or digital identifiers to facilitate traceability and accessibility, enabling seamless information exchange with regulatory bodies, supply chain stakeholders, and end users.

5. CASE STUDY

Figure 4. Example of DPP for wood manufacture stage

A structural solid wood beam was selected as a representative use case due to its relevance in both the construction industry and circular economy strategies. Wood, as a renewable and recyclable material, offers high potential for reuse, resource efficiency, and carbon sequestration, making it a compelling subject for DPP creation. This case

study was chosen to demonstrate the DPP editor tool's capacity to handle detailed, domain-specific product data across the entire lifecycle of a material intended for multiple use phases. As figure 5 shows, the DPP created for this example only includes information from forest to manufacture stage for simplicity, while covers data such as quality, standard, transportation etc. Note that the data used in this case study are illustrative and intended solely for demonstration purposes.

6. CONCLUSION

The DPP editor system represents a significant advancement in enabling user-friendly, visual creation of DPPs by lowering technical barriers and supporting modular, scalable design. Future work will focus on expanding the system's capabilities through the addition of more specialized node types, the design and integration of domain-specific large language models (LLMs) to assist users in creating and interpreting DPPs, and the incorporation of international regulatory systems and ongoing standardization efforts. Enhancements will also include multi-user collaboration features such as real-time editing and version control, as well as deeper integration with technical systems including ERP, PLM, and cloud platforms. These developments aim to position the tool as a comprehensive and intelligent infrastructure for supporting circular economy practices and digital sustainability.

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Smart Logistics for Reuse: Tracking precast concrete in Circular Construction

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Keywords: building information modelling (BIM), circular construction, circular supply chain, logistics, Near Field Communication (NFC), precast concrete

This research presents the outcomes of Task 3.2 of the ReCreate project, which explores smart logistics for the reuse of precast concrete elements reclaimed from existing buildings not originally designed for disassembly. Effective logistics and traceability are crucial enablers of circular construction, supporting quality management and the reuse of reclaimed building components. The deliverable associated outlines the logistical workflows tested in four pilot projects in each country cluster (Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany), spanning from deconstruction to storage, refurbishment, and reuse on new construction sites. The logistical arrangements depended on which actors perform certain tasks, and at which step in the reuse process.

A core component of this task was the application of data carriers, such as QR (Quick Response) codes, Radio frequency identification (RFID) or Near Field communication (NFC, a subset of RFID), and any other technology and practical approach, to identify and track individual precast elements throughout the process. The deliverable reviews these technologies, their integration with Building Information Modelling (BIM), and the establishment of digital identification and linking between physical components and their digital counterparts in BIM and/or databases. Another relevant feature of this process is the gathering of relevant information from the quality assurance process and the refurbishment of the elements. Key logistics aspects are discussed, such as workflows for embedding QR/RFID data into BIM models, data flow using APIs and Common Data Environments (CDE), identification of elements according to precast concrete taxonomy.

The pilots provide insights into practical challenges, decisions around actor responsibilities, and how product data quality evolves over time. Lessons learned inform more efficient and scalable logistics models that support concrete reuse, with broader applicability to other materials and construction contexts. This deliverable contributes to the systemic integration of smart logistics in circular building practices.

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Supporting Circular Economy in Building Construction Through Product Data and AI assistance: Retailers' Perspective

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Keywords: AI assistance, Circular economy, Product data, Sustainable sourcing

ABSTRACT

Retailers play a crucial role in circular construction process as the product data originates from the producers but is needed by their customers. The retailers can support builders and consumers in choosing sustainable options that align with circular economy principles by providing data about the materials, manufacturing processes, recycled content and recyclability of their products.

EU regulation regarding product data and sustainability information creates real challenges to follow all the obligatory and voluntary regulations, which are complicated and still developing (Adisorn et al., 2021). With fluent digital data flow, the end users can utilize product data to track the carbon footprint and circularity data of construction materials and ensure transparency in sourcing. The challenges in data flow, such as data accuracy, consistency, and integration, can hinder these efforts. AI can address these challenges by enhancing data processing capabilities, automating data collection, and providing predictive analytics for better inventory management and more accurate and automatic sourcing (Abioye et al., 2021).

An AI assistance system was developed in the project to support the procurement process. AI systems used by construction product retailers sometimes generate false or inconsistent results, particularly in product naming and material specifications. This can lead to confusion and inefficiencies in sourcing and inventory management, where precise terminology is essential. To mitigate this, preliminary naming dictionary was created with help of AI-tools (e.g. Microsoft copilot) and further curated by expert evaluation. The expert evaluation included searching for information from the producers and retailers web pages and focused interviews. Finally the product consistency was validated by cross-checking the information sources. With the curated data, the AI assistance system could learn the correct terms, ensuring accurate identification and classification of products. These efforts enhance the reliability of AI in business applications and contribute to a circular economy by improving transparency and trust.

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The transition to a circular construction practice – lessons learned from living labs: collaborate, innovate & create value

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Keywords: Circular Concrete, Collaboration, Systemic Transition & Innovation, Urban mining, Value creation

ABSTRACT

The transition toward circular economy practices in the construction sector is impeded by several systemic barriers [1]. These include a prevailing preference for short-term financial gains, risk aversion to innovative or alternative technical solutions, limited trust and collaboration among value chain actors, and a fragmented stakeholder landscape that varies from project to project—making it difficult to replicate circular practices. Additionally, there is often a lack of urgency or commitment from clients.

To address these challenges, several Living Lab projects were initiated. These labs provide an experimental environment to test and develop solutions, generate insights, and create practical tools that support the transition to circularity. Buildwise’s involvement in these Living Labs focused on four key domains: circular concrete, collaborative deconstruction, digital data and tools, and the role of specific actors as ‘bridges’ to broader knowledge and practice. From these initiatives, it became evident that technical advancements must be accompanied by non-technical developments—particularly in roles, workflows, and attitudes toward innovation. Within the Living Labs, various instruments were developed to foster collaboration, stimulate innovation, and enhance value creation.

Collaboration can be considered at multiple levels. At the project level, contractors are often involved too late in the process. This delay can lead to misaligned expectations, increased costs, and limited opportunities for circularity. Involving contractors earlier allows for co-definition of ambitions and realistic reuse scenarios. In more conventional settings, public tenders can incentivize recycling and reuse through selection and award criteria. On a broader scale, collaboration can be supported through the creation of digital ecosystems. For example, a digital platform for circular concrete was developed to connect stakeholders, facilitate knowledge exchange, and spark new initiatives.

Given the long-term responsibilities (often exceeding 10 years) and significant risks (e.g., structural integrity, health, and safety), stakeholders are understandably cautious about adopting innovative solutions. To bridge the so-called "valley of death," Buildwise has developed several instruments. One such tool is an attestation system that helps clients assess the residual risks of innovative concrete solutions, enabling informed decision-making. Another is a preliminary screening process that allows concrete producers to demonstrate performance in limited applications and gain market entry.

Ultimately, the success of circular initiatives hinges on individuals who take initiative and responsibility. These ‘bridge’ figures—whether architects, contractors, or clients—play a crucial role in driving progress, maintaining momentum, and transferring knowledge across stakeholders. Bringing together people, knowledge, and experience creates shared value and accelerates the transition to a circular construction sector.

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Circularity in the Built Environment 2025

Quality management of reused building parts and recycled construction materials

A timeline of hollow-core slabs in Finland – Reviving past knowledge for circular construction

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Keywords: building component reuse, circular construction, history of construction technology, urban mining, precast concrete, hollow-core slabs

ABSTRACT

The large-scale adaptation of reuse as a circular economy strategy is hindered by lacking knowledge of past building technology and systems (Huuhka et al., 2023; Küpfer et al., 2023). Better historical knowledge is needed to provide both a starting point for reuse projects and to help with knowledge and technology transfers between different contexts and over country borders.

In response to this, one of the tasks within the ReCreate project has been gathering and analysing various material on past precast systems and methods of construction, using an archival and historical research approach (Schrag, 2021; Wang, 2013). The material gathered includes original manuals, catalogues, patents, and building drawings among other types of sources, with an aim to form an open database of precast component and connection types.

From the Finnish materials, as a ‘sliver’ of the yet to be finished work, a timeline of the development of hollow-core slabs in Finland up to the present day will be presented. Hollow-core slabs are both the core component of the by far most prevalent precast concrete construction system in Finland, the still in use BES, as well as the most important Finnish building sector export product and technology during the 20th century (Hytönen & Seppänen, 2009), and as such the presentation is hopefully of interest to international audience as well.

Among the collected material appear products with varying cross-sectional geometries, approaches to reinforcement, load-capacity curves, naming conventions, etc. Knowledge on all these parameters help in speeding up the design process for a new building with reused components and avoiding unnecessary testing. Findings will be presented as a narrative historical overview supplemented by images of and collected data on the investigated products.

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Application of the ECOV method for assessing the load-bearing capacity of existing structures

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ABSTRACT

Within circular construction, an important aspect is the assessment of existing (used) structural elements and their possibility of reuse. Nevertheless, many uncertainties must be accounted for when assessing the remaining load-bearing capacity of existing reinforced concrete elements, especially when only limited information is available. This work aims to explore a method for assessing the resistance of an existing reinforced concrete structure, accounting for uncertainties in a simplified way. This method is based on the ECOV method (Estimation of Coefficient of Variation), which provides an estimate of the variance of the structural resistance based on limited model evaluations. The procedure is illustrated by application to hypothetical reinforced concrete beams, where the assumed limit states are bending and shear. The influence of different input variables on the maximum allowable load is estimated based on the ECOV method. Different scenarios of data availability on the layout, reinforcement composition and material properties are considered.

INTRODUCTION

In circular construction, there is a significant focus on reusing existing structures or their structural elements. To evaluate the possibility of reuse, the resistance of these elements needs to be assessed. Nevertheless, when assessing the load-bearing capacity of existing structures or structural elements, there are many uncertainties, for example, due to a lack of information. Probabilistic analyses can be applied to deal with these uncertainties [1]. Distributions are assigned to different variables in the resistance models, resulting in a distribution of the load-bearing capacity. Depending on the available information, the distributions of the variables in the resistance models can be more vague or informative. This influences the final estimate of the remaining load-bearing capacity of the structure and the associated uncertainty. These probabilistic analyses often require a considerable computational effort and are therefore often not applied in practice to assess existing structures. Hence, in this work, a simplified method will be applied to estimate the remaining load-bearing capacity of an existing structural element and the corresponding uncertainty on this estimate. This method will be based on evaluating uncertainties by application of the ECOV method (Estimation of Coefficient of Variation), which requires only a limited number of model evaluations. This method also allows for determining beforehand, based on the available information, which variables will most influence the uncertainty on the load-bearing capacity of a reinforced concrete element under investigation. This will be illustrated by application to simply supported reinforced concrete beams.

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EXAMPLE APPLICATIONS

The method is illustrated by application to two simply supported reinforced concrete beams subjected to a uniformly distributed load. The first beam has a length of 7800 mm, a width of 350 mm, and a height of 660 mm. The longitudinal bottom reinforcement consists of 4 bars of 25 mm diameter, and the stirrups have a diameter of 8 mm with a spacing of 320 mm. The second beam has a height of 1000 mm, a width of 500 mm, and a length of 6000 mm. The longitudinal bottom reinforcement consists of 6 bars of diameter 25 mm, i.e., one layer of 4 bars and one layer of 2 bars. The concrete cover is 40 mm, and the diameter of the stirrups equals 12 mm, spaced every 500 mm. For both beams, the concrete quality is C30/37, and the reinforcement steel strength is BE500S. The maximum allowable load on the beams is determined based on the limit states related to bending and shear. For the first beam, the bending and shear limit states are close to each other, whereas for the second beam, shear is clearly the governing limit state.

The resisting (M_R) and acting (M_E) bending moments are evaluated according to equation (1).

$$M_R = \theta_{R,M} A_s f_y (h - d_1) \left(1 - \frac{0,514 A_s f_y}{b(h - d_1) f_c} \right); M_E = \frac{(q + 25bh)L^2}{8} \quad (1)$$

The resisting (V_R) and acting (V_E) shear forces are evaluated according to equations (2) and (3) [2].

$$\rho = \frac{A_s}{b(h - d_1)}; k = \min \left(2; 1 + \sqrt{\frac{200}{(h - d_1)}} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$V_R = \theta_{R,V} \max \left(b(h - d_1) \left(0,18k(100\rho f_c)^{\frac{1}{3}} \right); 0,035k^{1,5} f_c^{0,5} b(h - d_1); 2 \frac{A_w}{1000} 0,9(h - d_1) f_y \right); V_E = \frac{(q + 25bh)L}{2} \quad (3)$$

The limit state equations corresponding to bending and shear failure are respectively given by equations (4) and (5).

$$g_M(X) = M_R - M_E = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$g_V(X) = V_R - V_E = 0 \quad (5)$$

Based on these limit state equations, the resistance of the beam under investigation can be derived as the maximum allowable load q . The mean value and standard deviation of this resistance are determined based on the ECOV method. The mean value is determined based on the mean value of all relevant basic variables, inserted in equations (1) to (5). The prior distributions of the considered variables are given in Table 1. All distributions are assumed to be lognormal to avoid negative and hence unrealistic values. The beam dimensions (b , h , and L) are assumed to be deterministic.

Table 1. Prior distributions of variables influencing the maximum allowable load

Var.	Symbol	Distr.	Mean	Stdev.	Ref.
Steel section longitudinal reinforcement	A_s	LN	$A_{s,provided}$	$0,02A_{s,provided}$	[3]
Steel section shear reinforcement	A_w	LN	$A_{w,provided}$	$0,02A_{w,provided}$	[3]
Centre of gravity of reinforcement with respect to bottom of beam	d_l	LN	$d_{l,provided}$	$0,02d_{l,provided}$	[4]
Concrete compressive strength for C30/37	f_c	LN	36 MPa	3 MPa	[4]
Steel yield strength	f_y	LN	560	30 MPa	[4]
Model uncertainty bending	$\theta_{R,M}$	LN	1,2	0,18	[3]
Model uncertainty shear	$\theta_{R,V}$	LN	1,2	0,18	[3]

The coefficient of variation of the resistance, V_q , can be calculated according to equation (6) based on the ECOV method [5], [6].

$$V_q^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(q_m - q_{\Delta i})^2}{q_m^2} \frac{\sigma_i^2}{(\Delta i)^2} = \sum_{i=1}^n V_{q,i}^2 \quad (6)$$

In this equation, i refers to the different variables influencing the maximum allowable load (i.e., the variables in Table 1), q_m is the maximum allowable load when for all variables the mean value is applied, $q_{\Delta i}$ is the maximum allowable load when changing the variable i with an increment Δi , and σ_i^2 is the prior variance of the variable i . The finite variations Δi are evaluated as $\Delta i = \mu_i(1 - \exp(-2,15V_i))$, according to [5]. Here, μ_i is the mean of the variable i and V_i is its coefficient of variation (COV).

When applying the ECOV method, the mean value of the resistance equals 53,4 kN/m for beam 1 and 156,4 kN/m for beam 2. The values $V_{q,i}^2$ for the different variables are given in Table 2 for beam 1. When looking at the geometric and material properties, the contribution of the uncertainty on the steel yield strength to the total uncertainty is the largest. Hence, when one wants to achieve a more accurate estimate of the remaining load-bearing capacity, measurements of this property will provide the largest reduction in uncertainty, under the current assumptions. Under different assumptions, these conclusions may vary. An increased prior uncertainty for the concrete compressive strength may vary its importance in the standard deviation of the load-bearing capacity. For example, if the standard deviation of the concrete compressive strength is increased to 12 MPa (and other assumptions are retained), its importance increases from 2.7% to 27.2%, whereas the contribution of the steel yield strength reduces from 8.3% to 6.2%.

It should be pointed out that the ECOV method could be applied considering both the bending and shear limit states together (as is done for achieving the results of Table 2). Nevertheless, when, due to a change in the assumed probabilistic distributions, there could be a shift in the failure mode depending on the size of the finite variations Δi , the ECOV method should be applied considering both limit states separately, i.e. applying it once to the bending limit state and once to the shear limit state.

Table 2. Contribution of the different variables to the total uncertainty on the maximum allowable load based on ECOV for beam 1

Variable	$V_{q,i}^2$ [-]	Percentage of total uncertainty [%]	σ_q [kNm/m]
A_s	5,24e-5	0,17	0,39
A_w	0,00018	0,59	0,73
d_I	1,15e-6	0,0037	0,06
f_c	0,00085	2,73	1,56
f_y	0,0026	8,30	2,72
$\theta_{R,M}$	0	0	0
$\theta_{R,V}$	0,028	88,2	8,88

Based on the ECOV method, the standard deviation of the allowable load q equals 9,46 kN/m for beam 1 and 30,7 kN/m for beam 2. When combining the mean value μ_q and the standard deviation of the remaining capacity of the structure, the design value can be derived. This design value is assessed as $q_d = \mu_q \exp(-\alpha_q \beta V_q)$, assuming a lognormal distribution. In this equation, α_q is the sensitivity factor, taken equal to 0,8 as a resistance is considered. The reliability index β equals 3,8 for a consequence class 2 and a reference period of 50 years. When applying this equation, the design value of the load under the current assumptions equals 31,2 kN/m for beam 1 and 86,1 kN/m for beam 2.

The results of the ECOV method are also compared with those of a Monte Carlo (MC) sampling method. Here, the distribution of the allowable load is determined with MC sampling (100 000 samples) of the distributions provided in Table 1 and inserting them in equations (1) to (5). From the resulting distribution of the allowable load q , the mean value, standard deviation, and design value are determined. These results are summarized in Table 3 for beam 1. Here, it can be seen that the ECOV method gives a good approximation in relation to the Monte Carlo simulation results.

Table 3. Comparison of ECOV and Monte Carlo Sampling for beam 1

	ECOV	Monte Carlo Sampling
μ_q [kN/m]	53,43	54,44
σ_q [kN/m]	9,49	9,16
q_d [kN/m]	31,14	32,65

INFLUENCE OF AVAILABLE DATA

Based on the ECOV method, the influence of additional information on the considered variables can also be derived. In the abovementioned analyses, the distributions are based on literature and hence represent the scatter generally present in the design. Nevertheless, for the assessment of existing structures, more or less prior information can be available, depending on the situation. To investigate the influence of the availability of information, different scenarios are considered:

- 1) Reinforcement plans are available, and the strength class of the concrete and steel is provided on the design drawings.
- 2) No reinforcement plans are available; the strength class of the concrete and steel is provided on the design drawings.
- 3) Reinforcement plans are available; the strength class of the concrete and steel is not provided on the design drawings.
- 4) No reinforcement plans are available, and the strength class of the concrete and steel is not provided on the design drawings.

These scenarios more or less align with the scenarios mentioned in [7], varying from no record of the original construction to a complete archive of documentation.

Scenario 1

In the first scenario, two situations are considered, assuming different distributions for the reinforcement sections A_s and A_w and the corresponding effective depth d . In the first situation, there is high confidence that the reinforcement plans are correct. Therefore, the COV of the distribution of the reinforcement section is assumed equal to 0,01. In the second situation, the reinforcement plans do not correspond with the actual structure. This could originate from different causes such as the reinforcement plans available do not correspond to the as built situation, or errors have occurred during construction, inducing incorrect reinforcement locations or wrong reinforcement diameters. Hence, in this situation, a larger COV is assumed and taken equal to 0,20 (based on engineering judgement, if more detailed information is available, this value could be determined more accurately). The mean value is also reduced, since it is less likely that more reinforcement will be present than indicated on the design plans. The mean value is reduced to the average of the minimum expected reinforcement and the amount indicated on the design plans. For both situations, a distribution for the maximum allowable load can be retrieved. These will be weighed with the probability of occurrence of each of the situations. In this work, it will be assumed that there is a 75% probability that the reinforcement plans are correct, and a 25% probability that the reinforcement plans were not followed during construction.

For beam 1, it was found that the ECOV method should be applied to the bending and shear limit states separately. For the first situation, i.e., where the reinforcement plans are assumed to be correct, the mean of the estimated load is 53,4 kN/m, the standard deviation equals 9,4 kN/m, and the design value is equal to 31,3 kN/m. For the second situation, i.e., where the reinforcement plans are assumed not to be correct, the values are 53,5 kN/m, 16 kN/m, and 21,6 kN/m, respectively. The resulting weighted design value is evaluated as 28,9 kN/m. For beam 2, for situation 1 (i.e., reinforcement plans are assumed to be correct), the mean value of the allowable load is 156,4 kN/m and the standard deviation equals 30,5 kN/m, leading to a design value of 86,5 kN/m. In the second situation (i.e., reinforcement plans are assumed not to be correct), the mean value of the load equals 134,0 kN/m, the estimate of the uncertainty on the allowable load increases to 40,3 kN/m, and the design value decreases to 53,7 kN/m. When the resulting weighted design value is evaluated, this equals 78,3 kN/m.

Scenario 2

In this scenario, it is assumed that there are no reinforcement plans available. Hence, assumptions should be made on the reinforcement that is present in the section. One assumption is to perform the analysis assuming the minimum value of the reinforcement that should at least be present based on the design guidelines at the moment of construction of the considered building. Another option is to try to determine the loads that were taken into account during design (e.g., based on calculation reports, notations on the construction plans, or based on the intended use of the building and the original permanent loads which could be derived from the architectural plans). Based on these loads and the design guidelines from the time of construction, the required amount of reinforcement could be derived. It should be pointed out that both strategies will likely always result in lower-bound conservative estimates of the resistance, leading to a 'downscaled design'. For the beams under investigation, assuming design according to the current generation of Eurocodes [2], the required reinforcement ranges from 339 mm² to 1963 mm² for beam 1, and from 700 mm² to 2945 mm² for beam 2. Hence, a distribution with a mean value of the average of the upper and lower bound will be assumed, and a standard deviation will be determined such that the difference between the minimum reinforcement and the mean value of the distribution equals 3 times the standard deviation. The distributions for the lever arm and for the shear reinforcement are adjusted correspondingly.

For beam 1, this results in a design value of the maximum allowable load of 21,5 kN/m (mean value 53,5 kN/m and standard deviation 16,1 kN/m). For beam 2, this scenario results in a

design value of the maximum allowable load of 70,6 kN/m (mean value 134,0 kN/m and standard deviation 28,2 kN/m). Hence, besides deriving a reduced design value compared to scenario 1, the ECOV method provides an indication of the expected mean and standard deviation of the maximum allowable load, more accurately accounting for uncertainties in the available information.

Scenario 3

In the third scenario, again, two situations are considered with respect to the reinforcement layout, similar to scenario 1. However, in contrast to scenario 1, now the material properties are not known. Regarding the concrete strength, it is assumed that the actual applied concrete class will range from C20/25 to C30/37. Hence, the mean value is assumed to correspond to the mean value of strength class C25/30, i.e., 33 MPa, but a large uncertainty is assumed with a standard deviation of 12 MPa. Similar for the yield strength, the mean value is reduced to an average for BE400S and BE500S. For beam 1, this leads to a weighted design value of the maximum allowable load of 12,1 kN/m (situation 1: mean 49,9 kN/m, standard deviation 22,1 kN/m, and design value 13 kN/m; situation 2: mean value 48,2 kN/m, standard deviation 25,8 kN/m, and design value 9,5 kN/m). For beam 2, for the first situation, the design value equals 33,7 kN/m, resulting from a mean value of 141,4 kN/m and a standard deviation of 66,7 kN/m. For the second situation, the design value equals 24,2 kN/m, resulting from a mean value of 120,9 kN/m and a standard deviation of 64,0 kN/m. The weighted design value equals 31,3 kN/m.

Scenario 4

In the last scenario, there is no information on the strength properties or the reinforcement layout. The distributions for the reinforcement are the same as those assumed for scenario 2. For the material properties, the distributions from scenario 3 are considered. This results in a design value of the maximum allowable load of 9,5 kN/m for beam 1 (mean value 48,2 kN/m, standard deviation 25,7 kN/m). For beam 2, this results in a design value of the maximum allowable load of 28,0 kN/m, with a mean value of 120,9 kN/m and a standard deviation of 58,2 kN/m.

Discussion

In Table 4, the resulting design loads for the different scenarios and the two beams are summarized. Here, it can be seen that the maximum allowable load is smallest when there are no reinforcement plans available and there is no information on the material properties (scenario 4). When there is information on the reinforcement, the estimated design value of the allowable load increases by 27% for beam 1 and by 13% for beam 2. When only information on the material properties is available, the design value increases by 127% for beam 1 and by 154% for beam 2. When both types of information are available, the maximum allowable load is highest, i.e., an increase of 204% compared to the situation with no information for beam 1 and with 182% for beam 2. Scenario 1 gives an increase of 139% compared to the situation where there is only reinforcement information for beam 1 and an increase of 150% for beam 2. Finally, scenario 1 leads to an increase of 34% compared to the situation where there is only information on the material properties for beam 1 and an increase of 11% for beam 2. Hence, for the specific investigated situations and the assumed uncertainties, the information from the material properties is more valuable than the information with respect to the reinforcement layout.

Table 4. Summary of the different scenarios

Scenario	Beam 1				Beam 2			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
q_d [kN/m]	28,9	21,5	12,1	9,5	78,3	70,6	31,3	27,8
Reinforcement plans	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Material information	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a simplified method is proposed to determine the distribution of the load-carrying capacity of a reinforced concrete beam, together with the resulting design value. The method is based on the ECOV method, providing an estimate of the variance. The advantage of this method is illustrated by its application to four different scenarios, considering a varying amount of available information. From the analyses, it could be concluded that a main advantage of the ECOV method is that it not only provides an estimate of the design value of the load carrying capacity, but also of the mean value and the uncertainty on the prediction. Moreover, from the examples considered in this work, under the assumptions made here, it was found that, in general, information from material properties is more valuable compared to information on the reinforcement layout. This might be beneficial, since these are easier to test in an existing structure. It should be pointed out that all analyses in this work assume that no non-destructive test methods for estimating material properties and reinforcement configurations are accounted for. However, the prior estimation of the most influential parameters when evaluating the uncertainty in the estimated load-carrying capacity allows us to determine which parameters the uncertainty will preferably be reduced. As such, decisions can be made to implement additional (non-destructive) testing where necessary.

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Application potential of a nature trail design concept using salvaged timber

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Abstract: In Finland, nature trails across wetlands are typically built using new, long timber boards from large, straight trees. To support circular construction and better use of wood resources, an alternative design has been proposed, which uses locally salvaged timber, mainly off-cuts from local production, connected with nails to form modular elements for a nature trail pathway. This approach has been demonstrated through full-scale prototypes intended for outdoor use. However, their mechanical performance under prolonged outdoor exposure has not yet been evaluated. As a continuation of this work, this study conducts four-point bending tests on the prototypes that have been exposed to outdoor conditions for three years. The test results demonstrate the potential of implementing this concept in practical applications.

Keywords: salvaged timber, nailed connection, bending capacity, modular element, outdoor exposure, sustainable trail construction

INTRODUCTION

In Finland, nature trails across wetlands are typically built using new, long timber boards sourced from large, straight trees (Figure 1). To support circular construction and better use of wood resources, an alternative design concept was proposed using locally salvaged timber. Similar to nailed-laminated timber (NLT) [1], we suggest to nail short, salvaged timber together to form elements for a nature trail pathway. This approach has been applied in our previous study [2], which has been developed into two versions via using: (i) wooden nails, which is predominately led by a timber-only concept [3, 4], and (ii) steel nails, which primarily pursues lower fabrication costs [5]. The driving motivation of this approach is to form a localised production model where salvaged timber materials are collected, assembled, and placed on sites that are in proximity (see Figure 2 (left)), offering an alternative to incineration.

Figure 1. Typical nature trail across wetlands in Finland.

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Figure 2. On-site collection of salvaged timber at a local timber housing company in Kouvola (left) and prototypes newly fabricated at the same company using the collected materials (right).

To demonstrate this concept, a collaborative project between Aalto University and the City of Kouvola was initiated, where steel nails were applied for fast and cost-efficient trail productions at a local housing company. Prototypes were constructed using on-site sourced salvaged timber and prepared for outdoor use (Figure 2 (right)). The constructed prototypes were not applied for public use but placed outside (piled up on pellets without protections from the elements) for three years of Southern Finnish weather, to endure the natural environmental conditions. In the present study, the mechanical performance of the prototypes is examined and the potential of implementing this trail design concept in practical applications is evaluated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used for prototype fabrications were collected from the material pile shown in Figure 2. Timber cut-offs with a thickness of 45 mm were found most suitable considering issues such as durability and material degradation [3] and therefore utilised for this project. Steel nails with 75 mm-length and 2.8 mm-diameter were used for connections. To assemble the prototypes, a universal assembly rule was defined (see Figure 3):

- Step 1: Select suitable timber boards from the material collection and arrange them to form a 2-meter span layer, which allows gaps of up to 50 mm between adjacent boards in the length direction.
- Step 2: Connect one layer to another using two nails at every $a_1 = 100$ mm along the length. The two nails are placed with a distance of $a_2 = 50$ mm in the depth direction. If the nailing position has a distance to the end of timber board shorter than $a_3 = 100$ mm, no nails are placed. Every two adjacent timber boards in the width direction need to have at least 200 mm overlapping length for nail connection.
- Step 3: Repeat the same nailing approach for other layers. A shift of $d_n = 25$ mm for nailing position in every adjacent layer is adopted to keep the minimal spacing required by EN 1995 [6]. To stabilise the prototype, the timber boards are arranged so that at least two layers with the same maximum depth (d_s) are positioned at support areas.

The prototypes have a total length (L) of 2000 mm and a clear span (l) of 1800 mm. The prototypes consist of either 10 or 11 layers, resulting in widths (w) either 450 mm or 495 mm, as each layer has a thickness of 45 mm. Some prototypes may include timber boards that span the full length. The dimensional information for each prototype is listed in Table 1. After three years' exposure to outdoor conditions, six prototypes were randomly selected for preliminary bending tests. The prototypes were directly collected from outdoor before sending to the experimental loading tests. Although the moisture content was not measured, the wood from such outdoor conditions was in a wet state as may be expected from a real-world scenario.

Figure 3. Design of the specimens.

Table 1. Design parameters of the specimens.

Specimen Number	Span l (mm)	Number of layers (Number of full-span layers)	Width w (mm)	Max. depth at support d_s (mm)
S#1	1800	10(1)	450	120
S#2		10(2)	450	191
S#3		11(0)	495	120
S#4		10(1)	450	171
S#5		10(2)	450	123
S#6		10(2)	450	193

Four-point bending tests were conducted on simply supported specimens. Vertical loads were applied via two I-beams positioned at one-third ($l/3$) and two-thirds ($2l/3$) of the span, using an additional I-beam mounted on the tip of the loading cylinder. The specimens were loaded at a constant rate of 8 kN/min until failure. Displacement and applied load data were directly recorded from the loading cylinder and loading cell, respectively.

TEST RESULTS

The load-displacement curves of the specimens are shown in Figure 4. A maximum load of 61.3 kN is reached by specimen S#2, leading to a maximum bending moment of 18.4 kN·m. The lowest load bearing capacity (22.4 kN) is performed in specimen S#3, which results in a bending moment of 6.7 kN·m. Both wood and nail failures were observed, with specific failure modes (Figure 5). Specimens S#1 and S#3 failed at the nails, showing large displacements. Specimens S#2, S#5 and S#6, each composed of two full-span large timber boards, showed bending failure in the wood. In specimens S#2 and S#6, failure was attributed to large knot clusters, while specimen S#5 performed wood failure near the nail connections. Specimen S#4 performed a wood splitting failure near the pith of the timber.

Figure 4. Force-displacement curves obtained from the bending tests.

Figure 5. Failure modes of the specimens: S#1: nail failure; S#2: wood failure due to the existence of a large knot cluster; S#3: nail failure; S#4: wood splitting failure close to the pith of the timber; S#5: wood failure near nail connections; S#6: wood failure due to the existence of a large knot cluster.

DISCUSSIONS

The test results showed a promising load bearing capacity of the trail prototypes under bending, indicating their potential for practical applications. The load bearing capacity of even the weakest prototype suggests a sufficient capacity beyond what may be needed for such applications as a nature trail. By applying the same assembly rule, it is feasible to extend the span beyond the tested 1.8 m for broader use cases. Although the mechanical behaviour of the structural system is more complex compared than that of a traditional trail design (Figure 1), it is advantageous to utilise an edgewise loading configuration of the timber boards, largely due to the higher stiffness that results in. With two full-span boards included, the load bearing capacity can be significantly enhanced compared to configurations without full-span boards. The design concept also allows for flexible fabrication process and strategic placement of

available timber boards, enabling boards with defects to be positioned in areas subject to lower loading demands.

From an architectural and social perspective, the intricate, random surface patterns generated from a simple assembly rule not only create a visually distinctive appearance [7] but also can invite user engagement and convey a narrative of sustainable design and thinking, adding to the social value of the structure. However, this concept also faces limitations, including restricted local material availability, challenges in establishing a localised production model, and difficulties related to disassembly (nail separations) and subsequent reuse of the structures.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, six modular elements for a nature trail pathway, which have been originally developed for localised trail construction, were fabricated using locally salvaged timber and experimentally tested after three years of outdoor exposure. Four-point bending tests were conducted on the simply supported specimens. A promising bending capacity was obtained, indicating the potential for practical applications. The bending behaviour of the prototypes varies, influenced by factors such as specimen depth and number of full-span boards. Both nail and wood failures were observed: nail failure occurred in specimens with no or only one full-span board, while wood bending failure was observed in specimens with two full-span boards. Furthermore, the design concept offers advantages in terms of fabrication, architectural expression, and social influence, while limitations in, e.g., material availability and disassembly of structure, can also be identified.

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Condition investigation in reuse quality management process

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Keywords: Concrete elements, Precast concrete, Reuse, Condition investigation, Quality

ABSTRACT

Before reuse of precast concrete elements, it is necessary to determine the actual material properties and condition of the elements with systematic structural condition investigation. The research data consist of structural condition investigation of four precast concrete buildings' structural frame built 1982 (A), 1989 (B), 1995 (C) and 1981 (D). Technical properties and possible deterioration have been studied according to Finnish national guideline by42 and fib Bulletin No 111. The procedure of systematic condition investigation consists of gathering and analyzing of relevant information from documents and visual inspection of structures, carrying out field investigations with necessary measurements and sampling, laboratory tests of samples and finally analysis of results and reporting. According to desktop studies concrete grade of reusable elements in case A was C25/30 (columns and beams) and in case B C20/25 (intermediate walls). Concrete grade of hollow core (HC) slabs was not known. All elements have been in warm and dry indoor environment, so no degradation mechanisms were expected. Compressive strength and rebound hammer test results are shown in Table 1. The variation of compressive strength is relatively low. In case B serious quality problems was revealed. Case A and D proceeded to actual reuse project.

Table 1 – Results from laboratory and rebound hammer tests.

Case	element	density (kg/m ³)	compression strength (cores) (MPa)		compression strength (rebound hammer) (MPa)	
			range	mean	range	mean
A	column	2230-2290	60,6-70,3	62,3	64-75	68
	beam	2230-2270	46,4-57,6	52,1	58-70	59
	HC slab	2356-2459	71,8-87,7	78,0	59-75	68
B	wall	2070-2210	11,8-33,5	21,3	36-56	41
	HC slab	-	-	-	61-77	66
C	HC slab	-	-	-	28-59	41
D	HC slab	-	64,6-89,0	81,9	-	-

Cracking of concrete and any other defects were visually inspected from all elements aiming reused. In the case C few hollow core slabs had cracks and were rejected. Most of the elements were plastered and painted after installing, thus possible original defects were not observed. Surfaces were inspected again after removing the surface layers. Few elements were rejected in this secondary inspection before actual refurbishment.

Material properties and condition of structural elements must be studied with suitable methods and extensively enough to obtain reliable values for structural redesign with current Eurocodes. Non-destructive testing should be considered as the first option in all testing to minimize cost as well as damage to elements. Results must be verified with destructive tests. It is highly recommended to use parallel investigation methods for all needed properties because of the variation between accuracy, applicability and reliability of the methods.

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Correlating Non-Destructive and Semi-Destructive Test Results with Mechanical Properties of Reclaimed Timber

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Keywords: circular construction, non-destructive testing, reclaimed timber, semi-destructive testing, structural wood reuse

ABSTRACT

The reuse of wood components in construction has become a growing area of interest, both from an environmental and structural standpoint. This study explores how combinations of non-destructive (NDT) and semi-destructive (SDT) testing methods relate to key mechanical properties of reclaimed solid wood timber. Specimens are softwood timber C24 48 mm x 98 mm with length of 2000 mm. The NDT tests will be carried out in controlled lab conditions using five portable testing devices: 1) Fakopp Portable Lumber Grader (dynamic MOE), 2) Pundit PL-200 (ultrasonic velocity), 3) IML-RESI PD400 (drilling resistance), 4) Fakopp Screw Withdrawal Meter, and 5) Hitman HM200 acoustic stiffness tester. Finally, each specimen will be subjected to destructive bending tests to verify the NDT results. The objective is to examine which NDT methods offer the best predictive performance.

The method selection should match the property of interest. Vibration-based MOE and ultrasonic velocity have shown strong correlation with bending strength (Chen & Guo, 2016; Gupta et al., 2021; Calderoni et al., 2010), whereas compression strength aligns more closely with internal resistance profiles and surface withdrawal resistance captured by micro-drilling and screw pull tests (Kloiber et al., 2017; Íñiguez-González et al., 2015). These, or their combinations, are expected to offer practical compromise between accuracy and field efficiency.

The study contributes to developing assessment protocols for reclaimed wood and timber. The methods are expected to allow practitioners to begin with rapid screening, while more detailed analysis can be applied when necessary. This supports safer reuse and regulatory consistency in circular construction.

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Data-driven approaches for predicting mechanical properties of structural steel

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Keywords: Mechanical property prediction; Data-driven approaches; Structural Steel; Circularity

ABSTRACT

Structural steel plays a significant role in contemporary construction due to its high strength, durability, and economic ability. With the increasing demands for improving the circularity of steel, the accurate and efficient prediction of the mechanical properties of steel (MPS) has become increasingly critical. Steel's mechanical properties such as tensile strength, yield strength and fatigue resistance directly influence the design parameters and service life of structural components. Traditional methods for MPS analysis employ linear regression methods for MPS prediction. However, these models often require large amount of experimental data and are insufficient for capturing the complex and nonlinear interactions among multiple influencing factors such as chemical composition, thermal processing conditions, and microstructural characteristics. To address these challenges, data-driven approaches such as machine learning (ML) methods have emerged as a promising alternative for MPS prediction due to its capability of uncovering patterns and relationships in large amount of data.

This study provides a comprehensive review of the application of ML techniques to the MPS prediction by employing the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework to ensure the reviewing transparency. In this paper, the performance of typical ML algorithms including support vector machines, decision trees, random forests, artificial neural networks, and ensemble learning methods have been evaluated based on literature. These models demonstrated superior accuracy and generalization capability compared to traditional regression-based methods. Most ML models commonly achieved prediction accuracies exceeding 90%, which is to attain utilizing linear regression method on the same dataset. Moreover, the optimal choice of ML algorithms often depends on the type of steel and selected input features, as ML behavior varies with different influencing factors. In addition to improving prediction precision, ML approach significantly reduces reliance on physical experiment, thereby offering economic and environmental benefits. Compared with traditional methods, ML generally required fewer experimental experiments to achieve similar levels of accuracy.

A typical ML-based MPS prediction workflow begins with the collection of raw data, which is mainly obtained from experimental results, published literature, and industrial datasets. Relevant features in the collected data include mechanical test results, chemical composition, grain size and heat treatment parameters. The next step involves data preprocessing, including normalization and feature engineering techniques to identify the most relevant variables and reduce dimensionality. The collected data is divided into training, validation and testing subsets to ensure unbiased model training and performance evaluation. Evaluation metrics such as the coefficient of determination (R^2), mean squared error (MSE), and mean absolute error (MAE) are employed to assess the model's predictive performance and guidance for optimization.

Furthermore, ML contributes to the circularity of structure with predictive accuracy and efficiency by exploring the possibility of reusing existing structural steel through predicting their residual mechanical performance. For example, the volume reduction of steel under specific environmental conditions can be reliably forecast by ML algorithms. This enables

rapid assessment of recycled structural steel's mechanical performance based on the existing dataset, avoiding the need for exhaustive and extensive physical testing, thereby reducing waste and enforcing the steel's circular use.

Derivation of Appropriate Design Values for Reused Precast Concrete Elements through Adjusted Eurocode 2 Partial Factors

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Keywords: concrete, partial factors, reinforcement, reliability, shear, structural design

ABSTRACT

Sustainable construction practices are increasingly critical as the built environment generates excessive volumes of construction and demolition waste (CDW) and associated embodied CO₂ emissions. Within the EU, high waste recovery rates are achieved through various recycling and downcycling modalities, yet direct reuse of building elements offers markedly greater environmental benefits by extending the service life of existing components. However, reusing deconstructed elements introduces new uncertainties in material properties, design compliance, and condition. EN 1992-1-1:2023 currently defines four partial factors in the design of concrete structures – concrete material properties (γ_C), steel reinforcement (γ_S), shear and punching resistance in members without shear reinforcement (γ_V), and the modulus of elasticity of concrete (γ_{CE}). To support circular construction, γ_C , γ_S , and γ_V must be recalibrated to capture the added variability inherent in reclaimed precast elements, for constituents such as the in-situ concrete compressive strength, reinforcement yield strength, effective depth, geometric tolerances, and aggregate gradation. This research defines four knowledge levels (KLs), reflecting the variability of available design information across reuse projects. KL1 and KL2 describe situations lacking any design documentation from the original donor building, with varying degrees of manufacturer information. Under these conditions, extensive material and non-destructive testing (NDT) is required to evaluate the element properties and geometry. Five comprehensive NDT databases are compiled from a total of 142 published studies, including 6,103 ultrasonic pulse velocity (UPV) tests, 10,428 rebound hammer tests, and 3,299 SonReb tests for the concrete compressive strength, and 2,679 covermeter tests and 784 ground-penetrating radar (GPR) tests for mapping the reinforcement design. Since no geometrical information is available, element dimensions must be measured independently during or post-deconstruction. A new Tolerance Class 3 is proposed, calibrated to a lower-bound manual measurement approach, supplementing existing deviations from EN 13670:2009. At KL3 and KL4, ample element specifications are available, allowing for a simplified verification procedure of the design properties. This multi-layered knowledge framework is then applied through a semi-probabilistic perspective to each partial factor, and new values are presented for the design of reused elements. The revised partial factors depend on several key parameters, such as the choice of NDT, sampling sizes, and material production periods. This tiered approach across each partial factor delivers a coherent package for structural designers, asset owners and contractors, enabling the reliable reuse of precast concrete elements.

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France evolution of reinforced concrete structures norms for reuse

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Keywords: Building code, Construction history, reinforced concrete reuse

In the wake of environmental concern, the construction sector searches for ways to build with lower energy consumption, carbon emissions and transition from a linear economy to a circular economy. One strategy is the reuse of concrete elements from deconstruction that occur because of socio-economic obsolescence. Previous reuse projects have shown that concrete elements are still structurally performant at the end of the life of constructions. Reuse raises quality and quantity concerns. The former problem is reinforced by both the lack of documents and the possible non-conformity to the current building code. Concrete is not a consistent material throughout time, nor has its normalization been always the same. In France, prior to the first building code on RC published in 1906, more than 250 patents had been filled mixing concrete and steel. Revision of building code introduced new subjects such as toxic substances, thermic regulation, or the notion of the lifespan of a structure.

The aim of this work is to provide a framework for assessing deconstructed elements by knowing the bare minimum they had to comply with when they were built. To this aim, building codes in France from 1906 until now are gathered, 8 of them in total, in order to identify the potential of deconstructed elements to respond to current building code.

It could also highlight the key elements that need to be looked at in greater depth when assessing reuse of a building with an uncertain date of construction, such as concrete cover depth, compressive strength, and the presence of toxic substances. This work shows that the evolution of building codes is tied to the evolution of society. The 1906 building code fixed parameters focused on safety measures because its writing followed the breaking of a pedestrian bridge during the Universal Exhibition of 1900, a major event in France. Later in the century, as discoveries were made about concrete and durability became important, criteria to ensure concrete durability evolved. In 1906, concrete cover depth had to be at least 15 to 20 mm, regardless of the environment of the concrete. A distinction between coastal construction and non-coastal construction was introduced in 1934. Eurocode, published in the early 2000s, set exposure classes and structural classes that prescribed specific minimum cover for each situation, widening the classification and the range of minimum cover. This retrospective of building code will put RC elements in their context as well as reflect on hypotheses made while designing those elements. It aims to help engineers working on the sourcing of buildings with a view to reusing elements of structures.

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Hazardous substances in reusable building components

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Keywords: hazardous substances, reuse, hazardous substance assessment, impurities

ABSTRACT

The basic requirement for the reuse of building components is that they can be used safely in new construction. The basis for this is the identification of hazardous substances and impurities, thorough and systematic examination, and their careful removal. The aim of the study "*Hazardous Substances in Reusable Building Components, 2025*" was to develop an accurate understanding of which hazardous substances have been used in reusable building components and how these substances affect the reusability of the components. The study also examined the need for changes in current hazardous substance assessment practices (RT 103501, 2022) considering the demands associated with the reuse of building components.

Building components suitable for reuse are structural load-bearing elements or other distinct parts that can be clearly detached from the structure. From the perspective of reuse, interesting materials are surface materials and coatings of building components, impurities that have contaminated the components, or hazardous substances that may have been absorbed from the surface materials. Examples of these include hazardous substances found in plasters, paints, and adhesives of surface materials, PCB and PAH compounds stored into building components, and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) generated during the degradation of plastic-based flooring materials and their adhesives.

The study utilized an extensive literature review as well as statistical analysis on data consisting of 175 asbestos and hazardous substance investigations conducted by Ramboll Finland Oy. The studied buildings were built between 1860 and 1990, while most of the buildings were from 1950s to 1990s. The literature review provided a detailed understanding of which hazardous substances have commonly been used in construction materials. According to literature and the gathered data, the use of hazardous substances has been the most substantial during the 1960s and 1980s. With the information gathered from the data through statistical analysis it was possible to identify the hazardous substances linked to building components suitable for reuse and to analyze how factors such as the construction time, structural system, and purpose of use of the building affect their occurrence. The most significant finding from the data was the prevalence of asbestos and heavy metals: asbestos had been used in 70% of the buildings in the dataset, and heavy metals in 50%. On the other hand, PCBs were present in only 14% of the buildings.

The study found that current hazardous material investigation practices do not fully meet the needs of assessing the reusability of building components. The most significant areas for improvement in current practices relate to the assessment of the microbiological condition of components, the investigation of chemical compounds, and a more comprehensive examination of commonly occurring hazardous substances by component from a reuse perspective. The hazardous materials assessment of reusable building components should incorporate elements from the systematic approach currently used in moisture and indoor air quality investigations.

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Non-destructive condition assessment of degraded timber beams in view of their reuse.

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Keywords: Non-destructive testing, Timber reuse, Ultrasonic pulse velocity, Vibration analysis

ABSTRACT

To enhance sustainable construction, effective reuse of construction materials such as timber beams is crucial. However, accurately assessing the mechanical properties of such beams remains challenging due to natural heterogeneities, prior use, and potential degradation. This study investigates wave-based non-destructive testing (NDT) methods, including ultrasonic pulse velocity (UPV) and vibration analysis, as tools for evaluating the stiffness of reclaimed timber beams. A total of 24 reclaimed beams were tested, and half of them were further subjected to environmental decay and mechanical damage. The NDT methods were compared to traditional visual grading and evaluated by four-point bending tests. Findings show that, unlike visual grading, UPV testing is a reliable stiffness predictor. Vibration testing also provided accurate results when analyzing the first bending modes. While environmental exposure had minimal impact, mechanical damage significantly reduced stiffness. These results demonstrate the high potential of wave-based NDT methods as reliable tools for assessing timber beam stiffness, supporting their reuse in structural applications.

INTRODUCTION

To evolve towards a more sustainable society, a circular construction sector is essential. Reducing energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in construction requires both recycling and reuse of building materials. Timber beams, commonly sourced from floors and roof trusses, are particularly suitable for reuse due to their availability in large volumes. Effective reuse, however, necessitates knowledge about the beams' stiffness and strength, as mechanical damage or environmental decay can alter their properties [1]. Reliable assessment of these remaining mechanical properties is challenging due to the lack of adequate non-destructive testing (NDT) tools. Hence, this research explores the potential of evaluating degraded timber beams with wave-based NDT techniques.

Due to the annual rings and heterogeneities of wood, structural analysis of timber beams is challenging. The strength and stiffness properties of timber depend on the clear wood properties as well as on the heterogeneities [2, 3]. As a result, visual grading is commonly used to assess timber elements, wherein visible defects are evaluated and correlated with standardized strength classes. The use of different national standards for visual grading across Europe makes it difficult to compare results between studies [4]. While some researchers found reductions of beam stiffness for lower grades [5, 6], others showed that visual grading underestimates load-bearing capacity [2, 7]. Nevertheless, it is recommended to perform additional NDT to obtain a more comprehensive overview of the beams' condition [4].

Besides visual grading, wave-based NDT methods such as ultrasonic pulse velocity (UPV) tests and vibration analysis are often performed for condition assessment of timber beams.

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Ultrasonic pulsing is a technique in which an elastic wave is transmitted from a transducer through the timber to a receiver. Typical testing frequencies range from 20 to 500 kHz [8]. The wave's travel time provides valuable insights into the specimen's condition, with high attenuation often indicating deterioration or a lower modulus of elasticity. Kim et al. [9] found a clear decrease in UPV after accelerated ageing, and several other authors have noticed a good correlation between UPV results and static stiffness [6, 7, 10, 11]. However, UPV testing is subject to several challenges, including its dependence on the testing frequency, the transducer coupling and the influence of beam characteristics, such as geometry, ring orientation, preservative treatments, mechanical loading, temperature, and moisture content [8]. Vibration analysis is based on the beams' natural frequencies, which are influenced by their stiffness. Several studies [10, 11] have compared the dynamic modulus of elasticity derived from vibration analysis with the static stiffness, demonstrating strong correlations. Moreover, Roohnia et al. [12] detected damage after drilling holes into timber elements, resulting in a reduced stiffness and corresponding decrease in natural frequencies.

This research aims to address the challenges of evaluating reclaimed and degraded timber beams by exploring the potential of wave-based NDT techniques, specifically UPV and vibration analysis. Comparison with traditional visual grading and evaluation by four-point bending testing is performed to provide a comprehensive and evaluated assessment strategy of timber beams in view of reuse.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of 24 reclaimed timber beams, with dimensions of approximately $200 \times 9 \times 6 \text{ cm}^3$ and an unknown origin, were experimentally tested. Half of the beams were left in their original condition as reference beams, while the other half were subjected to further damage mechanisms, including environmental decay and mechanical damage. Environmental decay was induced by exposing six beams to outdoor conditions for two months during winter (-5°C to 15°C with a total rainfall of 137 mm), simulating the uncovered storage of reclaimed materials. Three other beams were mechanically damaged by drilling horizontal ($\varnothing 1.8 \text{ cm}$) holes and the final three beams were drilled vertically ($\varnothing 1.2 \text{ cm}$), all with spacings of 20 cm.

Prior to inducing additional damage, visual grading, UPV testing, and vibration analysis were conducted. Visual grading was performed according to Belgian standard NBN EN 1611 [13], which classifies timber from G2-0 (best) to G2-4 (worst), and the Belgian technical specifications STS 04 [14] ranging between S4 (worst) and S10 (best). After damage was introduced, UPV testing and vibration analysis were repeated to allow for a comparison of the results. Before performing each NDT, the beams were conditioned for five days at 30°C . Finally, destructive bending testing was performed according to NBN EN 408 [15] with three load cycles between 1 kN and 4 kN at a rate of 0.25 mm/s, for all 24 beams.

A Matest (C372M) UPV tester was used, which allows saving incoming ultrasonic waves and enables detailed signal analysis. Sensors operating at frequencies of 24, 55, and 150 kHz were employed to measure the pulse velocity along the longitudinal axis of all specimens and investigate the influence of wave frequency. The measured arrival time of the wave was enhanced through signal analysis, by employing the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) algorithm [16], resulting in a coefficient of variation (CoV) of 1.3% across six repeated measurements. The UPV-based dynamic modulus of elasticity was estimated using the wave velocity V and material density ρ , according to Equation 1 [5-8].

$$E_{UPV} = V^2 \cdot \rho \quad (1)$$

During vibration testing, free-free boundary conditions were created by suspending the beams with elastic bands. The beams were excited with an instrumented impact hammer in the vertical, horizontal, and axial direction. Three accelerometers measured responses along different axes, each attached near the beam ends. The accelerometers had 0.1 V/g sensitivity, and data was sampled at 3304 Hz. A combined deterministic-stochastic subspace identification (CSI) method was employed for identifying the natural frequencies from the accelerations [17]. The vibration-based dynamic modulus of elasticity was calculated for the first vertical bending mode (B1) and first lateral bending mode (L1). Across six repeated measurements, the CoV was found to be 0.088% for B1 and 0.14% for L1. The first compression mode and first torsional mode are not considered here as their natural frequencies could not be accurately captured due to interference with other modes. Although there is no exact analytical solution to relate natural frequencies to beam stiffness, Equation 2 provides an accurate approximation for bending modes based on Euler-Bernoulli's beam theory [18].

$$E_{X1} = \frac{(2\pi f_{X1})^2 \rho b h L^4}{4.73^4 I} \quad (2)$$

E_{X1} is the dynamic stiffness [Pa] and f_{X1} is the first natural frequency [Hz], both corresponding to the considered mode. L is the beam length [m], ρ is the material density [kg/m^3], b is the width of the section [m], h is the height of the section [m] and I is the moment of inertia [m^4]. The moment of inertia is determined with respect to the testing direction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since this research focuses on the reuse of timber beams, assessment of the stiffness properties is vital to agree with the serviceability limit state (SLS). Hence, the NDT results are analysed and compared to the static stiffness (E_{stat}) in order to evaluate the accuracy of the employed techniques. An overview of the results is provided in Figure 1.

In addition, the wave-based NDT techniques allow for comparison of the beams' stiffness before and after introducing damage. This comparison is particularly useful for assessing the sensitivity of each method to changes in structural integrity. A summary of these results is provided in Table 1, with a detailed discussion of each testing method presented thereafter.

Figure 1. Overview of NDT results compared to the static stiffness (E_{stat}).

Table 1. NDT-based stiffness assessment before and after introducing damage.

	Beam Label	E before damage [GPa]			E after damage [GPa]			ΔE [GPa]		
		E_{UPV}	E_{B1}	E_{L1}	E_{UPV}	E_{B1}	E_{L1}	E_{UPV}	E_{B1}	E_{L1}
Horizontal holes (HH)	HH1	11.09	6.79	7.12	10.74	6.65	6.52	-0.35	-0.14	-0.60
	HH2	11.67	6.76	6.87	9.70	6.55	6.28	-1.97	-0.22	-0.60
	HH3	12.53	-	-	10.76	-	-	-1.77	-	-
Vertical holes (VH)	VH1	14.55	9.72	9.71	14.57	9.02	9.58	0.03	-0.70	-0.13
	VH2	14.90	9.13	9.09	14.22	8.47	9.00	-0.68	-0.66	-0.09
	VH3	14.53	9.80	9.79	13.58	8.78	9.36	-0.95	-1.01	-0.43
Environmental decay (ED)	ED1	14.09	7.82	7.92	11.97	7.83	7.92	-2.12	0.02	0.00
	ED2	13.16	8.60	8.74	13.18	8.68	8.84	0.02	0.07	0.09
	ED3	12.79	8.16	8.29	12.64	8.28	8.45	-0.15	0.12	0.16
	ED4	11.48	7.17	7.71	11.81	7.06	7.55	0.33	-0.11	-0.16
	ED5	10.50	6.98	7.46	11.69	6.98	7.39	1.19	0.00	-0.06
	ED6	12.68	6.74	7.01	13.06	6.70	7.00	0.38	-0.04	-0.01

Four-point bending. During four-point bending tests, both the bending strength (f_m) and static stiffness (E_{stat}) are evaluated in accordance with NBN EN 408 [15]. The bending strength is based on the maximum force reached during loading, while the static stiffness is calculated as the average slope over three elastic loading cycles between 1.5 and 3.5 kN. According to NBN EN 338:2016 [19], the reference beams can be classified as C30 since their characteristic bending strength equals $f_{m,0.05} = 30.8$ MPa. Figure 1a shows the correlation between bending strength (f_m) and static stiffness (E_{stat}) for all 24 beams, with the coefficient of determination equal to $R^2 = 0.47$. This value is considered rather low, which is most likely caused by the differing influences of heterogeneities on both E_{stat} and f_m [3]. Stiffness is mostly affected by clear wood properties, while failure in structural timber is influenced more by material variability and local defects from growth characteristics, handling, and manufacturing [2].

Visual grading. The twelve reference beams are visually graded based on their knots, fissures, annual ring width, etc. [13, 14], and their grade is compared to the static stiffness in Figures 1b and 1c. Based on the large scatter of the results and the low coefficient of determination, visual grading is found not to be a reliable assessor of the static stiffness for the tested timber beams.

UPV-based stiffness assessment. After application of AIC to the UPV results measured with 55 kHz, a correlation was found between the UPV-based stiffness (E_{UPV} in Equation 1) and static stiffness (E_{stat}), with $R^2 = 0.86$ as seen in Figure 1d. Hence, UPV testing proves to be a reliable stiffness predictor.

Comparison between the results with different pulsing frequencies (24, 55, 150 kHz), which are not reported here for the sake of brevity, showed that measurements at 24 kHz are unreliable. Taking the average pulse velocity in timber as $V = 5500$ m/s, the corresponding wavelength at a frequency of $f = 24$ kHz equals $\lambda = V/f = 23$ cm, which is substantially larger than the beams' lateral dimensions of 6 and 9 cm. The large wavelength most likely contributes to inaccurate results. Results from both 55 kHz and 150 kHz sensors are very similar, indicating that when consistent measurements are obtained, pulse frequency has no significant impact on the results of this experimental program.

Furthermore, UPV results before and after introducing damage are compared in Table 1. The UPV-based stiffness showed an average decrease of -0.95 GPa due to horizontal or vertical holes, demonstrating the potential of UPV measurements for detecting changes in structural integrity. Environmental decay, however, showed inconsistent changes in stiffness.

Vibration-based stiffness assessment. Finally, Figures 1e and 1f show that the static stiffness of the reference and damaged beams is accurately estimated by their natural frequencies through Equation 2, with $R^2 = 0.97$ and 0.95 for modes B1 and L1, respectively. Mode B1 is expected to represent the static stiffness the best, since similar deformations are induced during vertical, flexural vibration and static four-point bending.

From Table 1, it can be seen that the beams exposed to environmental decay showed insignificant changes in vibration-based dynamic stiffness. In contrast, beams with drilled holes exhibited clear changes. The average decrease in E_{B1} for beams with horizontal holes was -0.18 GPa while E_{L1} reduced more significantly with -0.60 GPa. For beams with vertical holes, the average decrease in E_{B1} was -0.79 GPa while E_{L1} decreased by -0.22 GPa. Hence, the damage direction has an important impact on the elasticity tensor of the anisotropic wood.

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the potential of wave-based NDT methods, specifically UPV and vibration analysis, for assessing the stiffness of reclaimed timber beams intended for reuse in construction. While traditional visual grading was found to be unreliable, both UPV and vibration-based techniques provided strong correlations with static bending stiffness.

UPV testing at 55 kHz yielded a coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.86$, indicating that approximately 86% of the variation in static stiffness can be explained by the test results, and resulted in successful detection of stiffness reductions caused by mechanical damage. Higher pulsing frequencies (150 kHz) provided similar results while lower frequencies (24 kHz) were found to be unsuitable due to the large wavelength. Hence, testing frequency within a reasonable range had a negligible influence on the wave velocity and stiffness prediction. Vibration analysis proved to be the most accurate method, with dynamic stiffness from the first vertical bending mode showing a strong linear relation with static stiffness ($R^2 = 0.97$). This method also captured the directional effects of mechanical damage and revealed that vertical holes caused more pronounced reductions in vertical bending stiffness than horizontal holes. Based on UPV and vibration analysis, environmental decay by outdoor exposure for two months was found to have an insignificant impact on timber stiffness, suggesting that short-term outdoor storage of reclaimed timber under similar climatic conditions may be feasible without compromising structural performance.

Overall, wave-based NDT methods, particularly vibration analysis, offer a reliable methodology to assess the mechanical condition of reclaimed timber. Their use enhances the safe reuse of timber in structural applications, contributing to circular construction.

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Quality Management Process for Reclaimed Concrete Elements: Best Practice from ReCreate

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Keywords: Concrete elements, ReCreate, Reuse, Quality

ABSTRACT

Quality is a fundamental factor in the reuse of concrete elements. The reuse process includes stages that virgin concrete elements do not undergo, such as sampling, deconstruction, storage, and refurbishment. The first service life, together with these additional stages, can cause deterioration and defects to the elements, thereby reducing quality. The quality requirements of the elements are determined by their further use, as different exposure conditions and loads lead to different demands. To achieve sufficient quality for reuse, these factors must be considered in the quality assurance process (QAP).

The QAP is one of the many aspects of concrete element reusability studied in the ReCreate project. The project includes four real-life pilots in Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands and Germany, where experiences are gathered and concluded to establish best practices for reuse. The process discussed in this abstract is based on the findings from the ReCreate pilots and considers only the timing and criticality of the stages in the QAP for reuse. The abstract identifies the most critical stages in the QAP and proposes best practices for reuse.

Seven main stages of the QAP were identified: pre-deconstruction audit, structural investigation, deconstruction, full-scale testing, redesign and reassembly, product approval and authorization, and visual inspections. In pilots, the execution of these QAP stages differed in terms of scope, timing, and methods. The pre-deconstruction audit was similar in each pilot, but the amount of data collected varied. This variation influenced the scope and timing of subsequent structural investigations. In Finland, damage and missing data of the elements led to further full-scale testing to ensure reliability of the elements. The deconstruction and redesign varied depending on the element type, although the timing and criticality remaining similar in each pilot. Additionally, visual inspection measures were done more often in Finland than in other pilots.

It was found that visual inspections and supervision throughout the reuse process are critical measures of the quality assurance process, as small defects can significantly reduce reusability and may be easily missed without expertise. The missing data and damage during deconstruction can lead to further expensive tests. Sampling should be taken before deconstruction, while careful visual inspection should be performed after deconstruction and during storage. As soon as testing needs are identified, better reliability, safety, and cost efficiency can be achieved.

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Reuse of insulated concrete façade elements in Denmark: Using historical knowledge to evaluate reuse potential.

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Keywords: Circular economy, precast concrete, insulated concrete façade elements, building regulation, reuse, standards

Abstract

This study examines the possibilities for the reuse of insulated concrete façade elements from a perspective of the evolution of Danish construction standards from 1950 to 2025 and the implications for reuse. While some properties, such as cover layer thickness, have remained consistent, others—like compressive strength, water-to-binder ratio and insulation requirements—have become more demanding, limiting the reuse potential of older elements. The findings highlight a conflict between sustainability goals and regulatory compliance, emphasising the need for updated frameworks that support safe and effective reuse.

Introduction

The UNEP Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction 2024/25 [1] reveals that the sector is falling short of its climate responsibilities. It contributes 34% of global energy-related CO₂ emissions, 32% of energy demand, and about a third of global waste—making the sector pivotal in meeting the Paris Agreement targets. The report stresses that annual progress must nearly double compared to 2015 levels.

While circular economy practices are emerging, most progress is within recycling. Recycling, however, still consumes energy and virgin materials, limiting its effectiveness. A more impactful strategy is reuse [2], which retains the embedded energy and resources in materials. Studies show that reuse can cut upfront emissions by 80% [3] and reduce climate impact by 75–82% [4]. Prioritising the reuse of high-impact materials like concrete, steel, and insulation is the logical next step.

Insulated concrete façade elements contain these materials and are the focus of this contribution. These elements are prefabricated concrete elements consisting of a base panel made of reinforced concrete, an insulating layer made of mineral wool and a facing panel made of a thinner layer of reinforced concrete or bricks, as shown in Figure 1.

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Figure 1. Conceptual drawing on an insulated concrete façade element (right) and a picture of such element in use in the Northwest quarters of Copenhagen (left).

Regulatory barriers are highlighted as impacting the extent of reuse seen in the industry, as found in [5]. The article finds that existing regulations do not support reuse, requiring actors to obtain approvals and dispensations, creating a bureaucratic burden for construction projects. It also highlights that additional resources are needed in the design phase due to the uncertainty of building with reused materials, which requires adaptable designs.

To enable greater reuse of elements from our existing building stock, it is crucial to document knowledge about the materials used. This documentation should track changes in practices over time to inform actors across the construction value chain about reuse potential as early as possible in the process. This contribution investigates the reuse of insulated concrete façade elements in Denmark through a historical perspective. By deep diving into former standards, previous building requirements, and the changes in common practice, this contribution aims to shed light on the variations of insulated concrete façade elements from different decades that our building stock is expected to embody. Further, it seeks to answer the question of to what extent these elements can be reused today.

Materials and methods

To inform an evaluation of reuse potential through time, three main questions were posed to form the basis of this literature study: How have insulated concrete façade elements been used historically? What requirements determine proper function throughout the elements' lifetime? How have these requirements changed over time?

Based on the questions, the literature study was divided into three categories: historical use, functional requirements, and changes in standards and regulations. Each category required its own search strategy, which is explained in the following.

Historical use

It became apparent that the scientific literature does not cover historical records of use, making it necessary to consult alternative sources.

Teaching material from 1984 [6] was examined to obtain background knowledge about how the elements have been used and produced since their emergence on the market. To supplement the written material, information has also been obtained through conversations with a demolisher with many years of experience [7].

Functional requirements

To establish the information base needed for implementation in contemporary building designs, the functional requirements for present-day use were determined by examining product specifications for the elements and earlier teaching material [8].

Changes in standards and regulations

A list of relevant standards was established for each functional requirement defined in the previous section, and current and prior versions were examined to determine changes.

Results and discussion

Historical use

From the 1950s to the 1980s, Danish multi-story construction shifted dramatically due to post-war housing shortages and innovations like steel-reinforced concrete and crane access. The industry moved from artisan-built brick and timber structures to industrialised prefabrication of concrete elements, peaking in 1973 with 55,000 completed dwellings [6].

This shift spurred the development of a prefabrication industry and innovations across the construction value chain, including new production methods, design approaches, and regulations. As a result, today's precast concrete building stock varies widely, despite the method's relatively short period of use [6].

Insulated concrete façade elements have mainly been used in two structural systems: one with load-bearing façade and longitudinal walls, and one with load-bearing transverse walls. Thus, insulated concrete façade elements exist in both structural and non-structural forms, differing in base panel thickness and material strength [6].

Today, such elements are used in residential, commercial, industrial, agricultural, public buildings, and warehouses.

Functional requirements

This paper identifies key properties of insulated concrete façade elements and the standards governing them to highlight expected variations in Denmark's existing building stock. The properties were mainly chosen based on information from [8] and diving into product declarations.

The main functional requirements are structural capacity, durability, insulation, and geometry [8]. Table 1 outlines these functions and their essential properties. Structural capacity is linked to concrete compressive strength. Durability, defined as a 50-year service life, relates to water-to-binder ratio and cover layer thickness. Insulation ensures energy efficiency, while geometry ensures the usability of indoor spaces. It is recognised that many more functional properties, especially regarding the quality of reinforcement steel, are equally as important, even though they have not been the focus of this study.

Table 1. Functional requirements, essential properties and relevant standards for insulated concrete façade elements.

Function	Property	Standards/regulations
Structural	Minimum concrete compressive strength	DS/EN 1992-1-1 DK NA:2021 [9], DS/EN 1992-1-1 DK NA:2017 [10], DS/EN 1992-1-1 DK NA:2013 [11], DS/EN 1992-1-1 DK NA:2011 [12], DS/EN 1992-1-1 DK NA:2007 [13], DS 411:1999 [14], DS 411:1984 [15], DS 411:1949 [16]
Durability	Maximum water-to-binder ratio	DS 206:2024 [17], DS/EN 206 DK NA:2023 [18], DS/EN 206 DK NA:2020 [19], DS/EN 206 DK NA:2019 [20], DS/EN 206 DK NA:2018 [21], DS 2426:2011 [22], DS 2426:2009 [23], DS 2426:2004 [24], DS 2426:1999 [25], DS 481:1999 [26], DS 411:1999 [27], Basisbetonbeskrivelsen 1986 [28], DS 411:1984 [29], DS 411:1949 [30]
	Minimum thickness of cover layer	DS 206:2024 [17], DS/EN 206 DK NA:2023 [18], DS/EN 206 DK NA:2020 [19], DS/EN 206 DK NA:2019 [20], DS/EN 206 DK NA:2018 [21], DS 2426:2011 [22], DS 2426:2009 [23], DS 2426:2004 [24], DS 2426:1999 [25], DS 481:1999 [26], DS 411:1999 [27], Basisbetonbeskrivelsen 1986 [28], DS 411:1984 [29], DS 411:1949 [30]
Insulating	Maximum U-value	BR18 [31], BR15 [32], BR10 [33], BR08 [34], BR95 [35], Bygningsreglementet 1985 [36], Bygningsreglementet 1982 [37], Bygningsreglementet 1977 [38], Bygningsreglementet 1972 [39], Bygningsreglementet 1966 [40], Bygningsreglementet 1961 [41]
Geometrical	Minimum modular ceiling height	DS1000:1958 [42]

Changes in standards and regulations

Figure 2 shows a timeline from 1950, when the Danish construction sector started using precast concrete elements, until writing time in 2025. The changes in the properties explained in the previous section are also mapped. Three of the properties, thickness of the concrete cover layer, water-to-binder ratio and the compressive strength of concrete, depend on the exposure class of the element, which is divided into passive exposure class and aggressive exposure class. These two classes were chosen because the facing panel falls under the class of aggressive exposure, and the base panel falls under the class of passive exposure. In cases where the requirements are conditional, the most critical option is presented.

As shown in Figure 2, the requirement for a minimum depth of the cover layer has remained stable for both exposure classes, whereby some consistency in the building stock regarding this property can be expected. Also related to durability, changes to the requirements for water-to-binder ratio have undergone some changes. The requirement for the aggressive exposure class became more stringent in 1973, indicating a risk for durability issues before this time. However, the requirement for a maximum water-to-binder ratio for elements in the passive exposure class was removed in 1984, perhaps due to a constricting of the requirement for compressive strength, which also influences the durability of concrete.

The requirement for a minimum compressive strength was not introduced until 1984 for both exposure classes and subsequently made more lenient for the passive exposure class. This indicates that elements produced before 1984 could have load-bearing capacity and durability issues. U-value requirements have become more stringent, reflecting increased energy efficiency demands. This means that even if the structural and durability criteria are met, the insulating performance of older elements may fall short, limiting their reuse in new constructions without additional interventions.

The reuse potential of these elements depends heavily on their compliance with current functional requirements. Many older elements may not meet today's stricter standards, particularly for insulation and durability.

Reuse potentials

When looking at Figure 2, it becomes apparent that only elements produced after 2010 can be expected to live up to today's standards for the selected functional requirements due to the U-value requirement being lowered this year. If the elements are not reused in an insulating function, the elements can be expected to live up to current standards since 1984.

A key question arises: Should reused construction materials be required to meet today's requirements? From a sustainability perspective, allowing some flexibility in standards could significantly increase reuse rates. However, this must be balanced against safety, performance, and energy efficiency concerns. The most sustainable buildings are the ones that last for the longest time. For a building to stand the test of time, it requires that it is well-made, well-thought-out and durable, often requiring additional resources and energy. The most sustainable building practices, however, are the ones that have the lowest impact on our planetary boundaries by emitting the least amount of greenhouse gases and using the least amount of virgin materials. This introduces the *sustainable building dilemma*.

The industry needs a way to reuse in a way that is well-made, well-thought-out and durable. Compromising on the safety, performance, and energy efficiency of our buildings should not be the way, and it is apparent that new regulations stating how reused construction materials can fit into the market safely and reliably are of great importance to increase circularity in the construction sector. The answer might lie in increased testing of the materials intended for reuse. With increased testing, the industry can reuse the elements to their highest functionality and avoid incorporating faulty building elements into new buildings.

While a new regulatory system is put in place, some opportunities for reuse might be found in renovation and transformation projects, where the requirements are more lenient, and the choice of investing in our existing buildings has already been made.

Figure 2. Development of requirements for essential functional properties

Conclusion

The evolution of Danish construction standards reveals both opportunities and challenges for reusing precast concrete elements. While some properties, like cover layer thickness, have remained stable, others—such as compressive strength, water-to-binder ratio and insulation requirements—have become more stringent, limiting reuse potential. Balancing sustainability with safety and performance is essential. To increase circularity, the industry must adopt clear regulations and robust testing protocols that ensure reused materials meet functional demands without compromising quality.

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Reusing Insulation Materials: Dismantling and Performance Assessment of Naturally Aged Thermal Insulation from 1990s Social Housing

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ABSTRACT

Thermal insulation materials are crucial for the performance of our buildings, yet these are often discarded during demolition, contributing to global waste challenges. This study evaluates the reusability of insulation materials from two social housing units. By examining the dismantling process and assessing the damage and performance of recovered insulation, their reuse potential is determined. The findings indicate lower reuse potential for cellular glass in flat roofs and stone wool in façades without air cavity. Other types such as mineral wool, XPS, and PUR exhibit significant reuse potential; however, microbial contamination and degradation of certain properties must be taken into account.

Keywords: Dismantling; Performance; Reuse; Thermal insulation

INTRODUCTION

Insulation materials are essential for achieving the thermal performance standards for buildings. Yet, during demolition or renovation, the existing insulation is often discarded [1][2], contributing to the estimated 30% of global solid waste generated by construction and demolition activities [3]. While this waste is typically dominated by heavy materials like concrete and steel, the environmental impact of lighter materials such as insulation should not be overlooked. Investigating the reuse of insulation materials is therefore crucial to enhancing circularity and minimizing the environmental burden of the building sector [4]. However, there is still a considerable lack of knowledge today to promote the reuse of insulation materials. On the one hand, there is limited understanding of how to carefully dismantle these materials and the extent of damage incurred during this process. On the other hand, little is known about the overall performance of such materials after their first life cycle. Therefore, this study investigates the dismantling process and the remaining performance of various insulation types from different applications in two Belgian social housing projects to assess its reuse potential.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this research, insulation materials from two social housing projects, constructed between 1993 and 1995 and scheduled for demolition, were examined. After a visual inspection, various insulation materials from different applications (see Table 1) were dismantled together with a contractor. Each application will now be considered a 'case' characterized by the type of insulation and the estimated year of production (e.g., PUR93 is polyurethane from 1993). The dismantling process and the resulting damage to the insulation is described in the dismantling and damage assessment along with a discussion of potential hazardous substances. Several samples were then taken to evaluate the remaining performance of the dismantled insulation. Given that representative samples could not be obtained from cases SW93 and CG93 because of too much damage, tests were conducted only on the four remaining cases. The most relevant performance metrics were selected for each case. For all four cases, density, thermal conductivity (EN 12667), and short-term (EN ISO 29767) or long-term (EN ISO 16535) water absorption were measured. Specifically, for cases PUR93 and XPS94, dimensional stability (EN 1604) and compressive strength at 10% deformation (EN ISO 29469) were also tested. To assess potential performance degradation, the results were compared with threshold values described in the original technical datasheets, approvals, or certificates.

Table 1. Information for every case of insulation dismantled from the social housing.

<i>Case</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Application</i>	<i>Attachment</i>	<i>Thickness</i>	<i>Current age</i>
GW93	Glass wool	Pitched roof	Loose between rafters	15cm	32 years
SW95	Stone wool	Pitched roof	Loose between rafters	12cm	30 years
SW93	Stone wool	Façade	With cavity anchors	4-7cm	32 years
PUR93	Polyurethane	Façade	With cavity anchors	3cm	32 years
XPS94	Extruded polystyrene	Floor	Loose under screed	3cm	31 years
CG93	Cellular glass	Flat roof	Glued on both sides	5cm	32 years

DISMANTLING AND DAMAGE ASSESSMENT

Glass wool in pitched roof (GW93). The glass wool blankets were easily dismantled from the attic. However, the glass wool tended to separate from the attached paper foil vapor barrier. Dismantling from the interior side (Fig. 1) was slower due to the need of removing the plaster first, but this method better preserved the paper foil. Additionally, the reuse potential is significantly reduced due to frequent damage and microbial contamination by mice and moisture infiltration, which often results in grey staining (Fig. 2). Furthermore, dismantling releases a large amount of dust and glass wool fibers, which is not ideal in a reuse scenario.

Figures 1 (left) and 2 (right). Pictures of the dismantling and the damage effects for case GW93.

Stone wool in pitched roof (SW95). The stone wool was easily removed from between the rafters (Fig. 3). On the attic floor, this could be done without damaging other building elements. However, on the sloped and vertical sections of the roof, the plaster and vapor barrier had to be removed first. The triangular stone wool pieces remained largely intact, with some dust and black moisture stains observed, but no microbial contamination was detected (Fig. 4).

Figures 3 (left) and 4 (right). Pictures of the dismantling and the damage effects for case SW95.

Stone wool in façade (SW94). First, the brick façade was removed destructively, a labor-intensive process that occasionally damaged the stone wool insulation (Fig. 5). Once exposed, the insulation pieces were carefully slid off the wall ties. However, the stone wool was contaminated and damaged, making it unsuitable for dismantling and reuse (Fig. 6). This was mainly due to mouse tunneling and moisture infiltration, as no draining air cavity was present.

Figures 5 (left) and 6 (right). Pictures of the dismantling and the damage effects for case SW94.

Polyurethane in façade (PUR93). First, the brick façade had to be destructively (Fig. 7), after which the wall ties were cut to dismantle the interlocking PUR panels. The panels remained largely intact; however, perforations were visible (Fig. 8), and the exterior surface was slightly damaged due to brick removal. Additionally, minimal damage to the panels' tongue-and-groove system was observed and some areas of the pink facing showed dirt and moisture stains (Fig. 8). Finally, cell gas analysis revealed the presence of an ozone-depleting substance (ODS) as a blowing agent, which does not make reuse impossible, but does require careful consideration.

Figures 7 (left) and 8 (right). Pictures of the dismantling and the damage effects for case PUR93.

Extruded polystyrene in floor (XPS94). First, the floor tiles and screed had to be removed using a mechanical breaker, making the process highly labor-intensive. Once exposed, the PE-foil between the insulation and screed could be easily removed, allowing to dismantle the XPS panels (Fig. 9). The foil largely helped to keep the panels intact. However, the unavoidable damage was the imprint left on both sides due to the screed (Fig. 10). In this case, an ODS is also present as a blowing agent and must be taken into account when considering reuse.

Figures 9 (left) and 10 (right). Pictures of the dismantling and the damage effects for case XPS94.

Cellular glass in flat roof (CG93). For flat roofs, the roofing must first be removed by cutting and pulling it away from the insulation (Fig. 11). It was observed that the cellular glass was strongly bonded to both the roofing layer and the concrete subfloor. Dismantling tests showed that the cellular glass blocks could not be successfully removed due to these adhesives and their brittle nature, leading to frequent breakage and significant adhesive residue (Fig. 12).

Figures 11 (left) and 12 (right). Pictures of the dismantling and the damage effects for case CG93.

PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

Density. Calculating the density is straightforward and offers a useful indicator of moisture control during deconstruction, transport, and storage. Here, the average density was calculated by measuring and weighing each sample used in this research (see Table 2). The slightly higher standard deviation for cases GW93 and SW95 could be due to the higher compressibility and potential measurement errors of the samples. Notably, the density of GW93 is relatively low, which may be attributed to damage caused by mice.

Table 2. The number of samples (#s), the average density (ρ_{avg}) and the standard deviation (σ).

Case	#s	ρ_{avg} [kg/m ³]	σ [kg/m ³]
GW93	21	11.78	1.81
SW95	18	44.42	2.47
PUR93	19	40.61	1.02
XPS94	15	31.98	0.46

Thermal conductivity. One of the key parameters for insulation materials is thermal conductivity (λ). This was measured using a heat flow meter (EN 12667) on at least 2 to 6 samples per case. Table 3 compares these values with historical declared values (λ_d) and default values set by Flanders' energy performance regulations (λ_{EPB}). For cases GW93, SW95, and XPS94, the results are consistently below the original declared values ($\Delta\lambda_d$). For case PUR93, the original declared value was difficult to determine, but given the gas-tight facing, it should not exceed 23 mW/m.K. However, degradation has occurred, as the average result ($\lambda_{m,avg}$) is significantly higher. This may be due to gas exchange, where air infiltrates the panels, increasing the partial pressure in the cells and leading to a higher thermal conductivity over time [5]. If the results are compared to the default value in absence of a technical datasheet ($\Delta\lambda_{EPB}$), a 22 to 31% difference is observed with measured values. This suggests that a lower default value could reduce the excessive use of overly thick insulation layers.

Table 3. The average measured ($\lambda_{m,av}$), declared (λ_d) and EPB (λ_{EPB}) thermal conductivity along with the difference between the declared value ($\Delta\lambda_d$) or the EPB value ($\Delta\lambda_{EPB}$).

Case	$\lambda_{m,avg}$ [mW/m.K]	λ_d [mW/m.K]	λ_{EPB} [mW/m.K]	$\Delta\lambda_d$	$\Delta\lambda_{EPB}$
GW93	37.75	40	50	-5.62%	-24.49%
SW95	34.67	35	50	-0.95%	-30.67%
PUR93	27.00	23*	35	+17.40*	-22.85%
XPS94	30.77	34	45	-9.49%	-31.61%

*This value is an estimation, since no information on a specific declared value was found.

Water absorption. The product standard for mineral wool (EN 13162) prescribes a short-term (24h) water absorption test with partial immersion (EN ISO 29767), expressed in kg/m². In contrast, the standards for PUR (EN 13165) and XPS (EN 13164) specify a long-term (28d) test with full immersion (EN ISO 16535), expressed in vol%. For cases GW93 and SW95, at least 16 samples were tested, whereas for cases PUR93 and XPS94, 6 samples were tested. The results shown in Figure 13 reveal that naturally aged glass wool and stone wool exhibit much higher water absorption than allowed, due to the degradation of mineral oils and binders on the fibers [4][6]. Conversely, samples from cases PUR93 and XPS94 maintain their strong water-repellent properties, staying well below the threshold value. For naturally aged PUR and XPS insulation, similar results can be found in previous research [7].

Figure 13. Average short- or long-term water absorption by partial or total immersion and its variation between the minimum and maximum results.

Compressive stress. The results of compressive stress at 10% deformation (EN ISO 29469), shown in Table 4, indicate that the average values consistently exceed the reference value by more than 30%. However, in the case of PUR93, a notable standard deviation in the measured values is observed. This variation could be attributed to local weakening of the top layer of the foam due to the use of outdated production technologies. In the case of XPS94, a high compressive stress at 10% deformation is observed, indicating no degradation.

Table 4. The average result of the compressive stress at 10% deformation (CS(10/Y)), the standard deviation (σ_m), the reference value (Ref.) and the difference with it ($\Delta Ref.$).

Case	CS(10/Y) [kPa]	σ_m [kPa]	Ref. [kPa]	$\Delta Ref.$
PUR93	166.3	43.1	≥ 120	+38.61%
XPS94	262.7	3.5	≥ 200	+31.33%

Dimensional stability. For cases PUR93 and XPS94, dimensional stability (EN 1604) was measured in all directions (length, width, and thickness) under cold (-20°C) and warm (70°C, 90% RH) conditions. The results at -20°C indicate minimal dimensional changes compared to the threshold values (see Figure 14), posing no risk at cold temperatures. Conversely, the results in warm and humid conditions show that samples from case PUR93 expand up to 1.5 times more than the threshold in width and length direction, and closely approach the threshold in thickness direction (see Figure 15). This may be due to degradation of the PUR foam or poor adhesion with the facing, attributed to older production processes used at the time. The results for case XPS94 meet all threshold values (which are less stringent than those for PUR).

Figure 14 (left) and 15 (right). Dimensional stability in thickness ($\Delta\epsilon_t$), length ($\Delta\epsilon_l$), and width ($\Delta\epsilon_w$) direction, measured at -20°C (left) and at 70°C with 90% relative humidity (right).

CONCLUSION

A first indication of the reusability is provided by investigating the dismantling process and the damage assessment. This assessment shows that the reuse potential is lowest for cellular glass in the flat roof and for stone wool in the façade without an air cavity. In contrast, XPS in the floor and PUR in the façade demonstrate significantly higher reuse potential, despite the more labor-intensive dismantling process and the presence ODS as blowing agents. Glass and stone wool in the sloped roofs, were easy to dismantle but differed in reuse potential: the stone wool remained largely intact and reusable, while the glass wool was damaged and contaminated due to mouse activity and moisture infiltration, making high-quality reuse nearly impossible. It should be noted that this assessment is project-specific, so while general acceptance criteria for deconstruction and reuse are essential, they must always be tailored to the specific context of each project, taking into account factors such as the age, condition, and initial application. Based on the performance assessment, a further estimation of the reusability can be made. Generally, these naturally aged insulation materials perform well, but there are specific

parameters that need to be reconsidered for each type of insulation material. For glass wool and stone wool from the pitched roofs, it can be concluded that while these insulation materials still perform thermally adequate, they do lose their water-repellent characteristics. Therefore, when choosing a reuse application, it is important to consider an application with little to no risk of moisture infiltration, as otherwise this insulation will quickly absorb a lot of water. The XPS insulation from the floor meets all limit values sufficiently. Despite these panels being more difficult to dismantle, they have a high reuse potential in terms of performance. The PUR from the cavity wall, on the other hand, shows some degradation for certain parameters. Firstly, an increase in the thermal conductivity can be observed, especially for PUR panels with a gas-tight aluminum facing. However, compared to other insulation materials, this is still a good value. Additionally, there is considerable variation in the compressive strength at 10% deformation in these panels, despite meeting the limit values. Finally, these old PUR panels are dimensionally very unstable in all directions. All this implies that it is not recommended to reuse these naturally aged PUR panels in applications where point loads and especially high temperatures and humidities occur, such as flat roofs.

Ultimately, this research offers valuable insights into assessing the reusability of both current and future insulation materials extracted from our buildings, with case studies serving as key references for improving dismantling and reuse practices.

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Securing indoor air quality in circular buildings using an emissions barrier

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Keywords: Circular building, contamination, emissions barrier, indoor air quality

Circular building implies a way of reducing carbon dioxide emissions. However, previously used building materials may contain disturbing or harmful contaminants which may be emitted into the indoor air. Here we show that the surface emissions trap (cTrap), an emissions barrier developed at Lund University and described in a doctoral thesis in 2014, may solve the problem. The cTrap cloth is a chemical-free laminate of one adsorbent layer and one VOC (volatile organic compounds)- and air-tight hydrophilic polymer layer. The cloth is attached indoors at surfaces from where the emissions are spread, whereby the emissions leave the building to be stored in the adsorbent; particulate emissions are also stopped, whereas water vapor passes through with almost no resistance at all (*Markowicz P, Larsson L, 2012, 2015*).

The cTrap was used to control chloroanisoles (from previous use of chlorophenols as pesticides), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH, from the use of creosote as moisture protection), and 2-ethylhexanol (a hydrolysis product from certain floor adhesives, *Pitkäranta M, Lehtimaa T, 2020; Larsson L, Mattsson J, 2022*). The chloroanisoles/chlorophenols results are from a summer cottage with a musty smell where the air in a room whose walls, ceiling and floor were covered with cTrap was compared to an adjacent room without cTrap. The PAH results are from previous use of creosote in a building before and after approximately 75% of a suspected contaminated surface was covered with cTrap. The results for 2-ethylhexanol

Results from cTrap installations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ air)

The chloroanisole/chlorophenol results are from a collaboration with J. Lorentzen

Emissions	Without cTrap	With cTrap
2,4,6-Trichloroanisole	0.0049	n.d. (<0.0018)
2,3,4,6-Tetrachlorophenol	0.14	0.0094
2,3,4,5-and 2,3,5,6-Tetrachlorophenol	0.0068	n.d. (<0.00091)
Pentachloroanisole	0.0081	n.d. (<0.00091)
PAH	1.726	0.139
2-Ethylhexanol	63	1.0

(directional measurement against PVC flooring on concrete) are from a townhouse where the residents had complained of skin irritation, problems which disappeared after the cTrap installation (*Larsson L, Mattsson J, 2022*).

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Standardization for reuse of structural elements and other construction products – experience from Återhus 3.0 project in Sweden

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Keywords: Circular construction, Reuse, Standardization,

ABSTRACT

The reuse of structural components in construction is gaining momentum as a strategy to reduce environmental impact and resource consumption. In Sweden, the construction and demolition sector generate approximately 14.6 million tonnes of waste annually. To address this, the Återhus 3.0 project, coordinated by RISE Research Institutes of Sweden, has played a pivotal role in developing technical frameworks and standards to enable the safe and scalable reuse of prefabricated concrete elements.

A central outcome of the project is work on the Swedish standard for reuse of prefabricated concrete products based on the Norwegian standard NS3682:2022, originally developed for hollow-core slabs (HDF). The Swedish version expands the scope to include all prefabricated concrete products and introduces several key enhancements including: (i) Differentiated procedures based on CE-marking status, (ii) Statistically grounded sampling protocols linked to element type and uncertainty levels, (iii) Non-prescriptive service life assessments based on in-situ testing, (iv) Characterization of reused elements in accordance with relevant manufacturing standards. The standardization process was based on an extensive testing across multiple demonstration projects within Återhus and achieving the project goals as:

- 1) Reuse $\geq 70\%$ of prefabricated concrete and minimum 50 % of in-situ concrete structures,
- 2) Climate impact thresholds aligned with Boverket's 2025 and 2030 targets (e.g., ≤ 200 kg CO₂eq/m² gross floor area),
- 3) Reduced volumes of construction demolition waste $> 10\%$.

The standardization work under Återhus 3.0 demonstrates that structural reuse can meet both safety and performance requirements when supported by robust technical protocols. It also provides a replicable model for other countries aiming to embed reuse into their regulatory and construction practices.

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Circularity in the Built Environment 2025

Circular design, construction materials and products

A game method for testing the feasibility of an adaptable housing system based on core dwellings, switch-rooms and spillover-rooms

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Keywords: design for adaptability, gamification, housing, spatial circularity, spatial sufficiency

ABSTRACT

Housing demand – and therefore price – is inflated by a growing number of vacant or under-occupied homes. Yet, policy responses of the UK and other ‘home-owning democracies’ in the Global North have been to ‘oil’ the market by increasing the supply of new homes, rather than deal with these underlying distributional problems. Architecturally, this supply-led approach usually means building smaller dwellings to maximise unit numbers, often without attention to adaptable features and their role in helping occupiers cope with changing spatial needs, thereby risking premature demolition and waste.

One sufficiency-oriented alternative is to build or retrofit adaptable multi-family housing in which the amount of habitable space in the control of any one household can be adjusted over time, by adding or removing rooms. This room-based approach to circular design requires a spatial composition consisting of core dwellings that may be joined to adjacent ‘switch-rooms’ or supported by nearby ‘spillover-rooms’. We argue that if switch-rooms and spillover-rooms were only available for *rent* rather than sale, there would be a monthly incentive to downsize. In this case, tenure would become the ‘engine’ or ‘pump’ that keeps available living space and materials therein circulating around the system, for the benefit of other households. This role for tenure, however, is missing from the literature and, consequently, there is no research into the commercial risks to the entity that owns and manages these switch-room elements.

To quantify these risks and opportunities, we advance a novel tabletop game method that simulates residents’ strategic behaviour, given different floor plan arrangements and life-course scenarios. Our scoring system records instances of overcrowding, under-occupancy, party wall alterations and unwanted switch-rooms, allowing the evaluation of outcomes for households, planet and switch-room owner(s). Building on a theoretical design-game (published in an earlier methods paper), we describe a simplified format and rules, designed to be replicable by others. After several iterations with various existing switch-room schemes, we have abstracted one Swiss example into our game format. This has been refined over four half-day sessions to date, of which three have involved game testing by both co-authors.

These experiments show that the moderating variables include: (1) the presence of circulatory zones between rooms; (2) the number of available switch-room connections; (3) the ratio of switch-rooms to WCs; and (4) the ratio of dwellings to common stairs. We find key dependent variables to be voids and ‘orphan rooms’: voids being leftover spaces that can only be used as shared community rooms or additional ‘spillover-rooms’ (e.g. workspace, guest rooms, etc); and ‘orphans’ being unwanted switch-rooms that become isolated. One important finding is that by strategically placing an extra margin alongside each switch-room (we suggest 6m² or a

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half-bedroom), the frequency of voids, overcrowding and under-occupancy is reduced. This suggests that an investor's risk is lowered - and the spatial and material circularity improved - through a relatively modest investment in additional floor space. Our discussion refers to some practical implications of the findings, as developed through interviews with planners and developers in the UK and Finland.

ARC - an online "Atlas of Reused Concrete"

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Reusing structural concrete elements carefully extracted from buildings deemed for demolition into new structures is a strategy that preserves the technological and historical value of existing components while avoiding the carbon emissions caused by new cement production and reducing the extraction of natural resources. Yet, despite its environmental potential, concrete reuse remains a little-known and underutilized approach, primarily due to logistical challenges, a lack of design standards, and the scarcity of easily accessible design references. Documentation on existing applications is often fragmented across time, languages, and formats, making it difficult for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers to access a clear overview of existing practices and design opportunities.

In response to this gap, this contribution presents ARC, the "Atlas of Reused Concrete", an open-access online platform that gathers, structures, and disseminates international case studies of built projects reusing concrete components structurally. ARC aims to support knowledge transfer related to concrete reuse practices by making past experiences more visible and accessible. The platform supports interactive visualisation and encourages external contributions to ensure long-term growth and relevance. Its four main intended features are: (1) interactive case-study browsing, (2) dataset download options (under development), (3) submission form for new entries, and (4) short FAQs on concrete reuse.

Each case study listed in ARC corresponds to a completed or permitted project in which reused concrete elements serve a structural role. Research prototypes are also included, but clearly marked. The data covers general project information, key characteristics of the donor and receiving structures, reused component types and quantities, and, when available, economic and environmental assessments. Data is sourced from literature, archives, and direct exchanges with project stakeholders, who are, whenever possible, invited to review and validate the information.

ARC is being developed at EPFL by researchers of the Structural Xploration Lab in collaboration with data scientists from ENAC-IT4Research. Its beta version features over 50 documented case studies and is available at <https://concrete-reuse.epfl.ch>, with the first full release planned for late summer 2025. Overall, ARC offers a structured overview of documented built examples of concrete reuse, providing a basis for further research, practice, and considerations on circular approaches in construction.

Keywords: concrete, database, case study, structural reuse, circular design.

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Architectural Reuse of Precast Concrete Systems: Adaptive Transformations at the Building, Room, and Element Scale

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Keywords: Precast concrete reuse, architectural potential, design solutions.

ABSTRACT

With approximately 60% of a building's embodied carbon concentrated in its structural frame, salvaging precast concrete elements from obsolete structures and reusing them in new buildings presents a significant opportunity to mitigate the environmental impact of new construction. While factors such as remaining service life, material quality, structural integrity and deconstructability are critical in assessing the suitability of individual elements for reuse, the reuse potential of reclaimed elements is ultimately determined by their usability—that is, their ability to meet the spatial and functional requirements of the intended new receiver building. The types and configurations of elements in a precast concrete system are typically determined by the spatial requirements of the original building's intended function (Hernández Vargas & Stenberg, 2024). Since buildings slated for demolition often differ significantly from those required in contemporary construction, achieving a perfect match between donor and receiver buildings is rare, thereby complicating reuse efforts (Huuhka et al., 2023). Consequently, the reuse of precast concrete systems represents not only a technical and logistical challenge, but also an architecturally transformative process, in which disassembled elements typically must be adapted and reconfigured to accommodate new building forms and spatial arrangements.

Although approximately 50 projects involving the reuse of precast concrete elements have been documented since the 1980s (Küpfer et al., 2023), the specific design strategies that enabled their successful implementation remain largely undocumented and underexplored. Efforts to assess the architectural reuse potential of existing precast concrete stocks at a more systemic level are limited. Notable among them is a study by Huuhka et al. (2015), which evaluates the potential of Finnish mass housing from the 1970s to meet contemporary spatial, acoustic, and thermal requirements in new housing developments.

To advance knowledge on designing with reclaimed concrete elements, this study examines architectural transformations between donor and receiver buildings in completed reuse projects, focusing on interventions at the building, room, and element scales. The objective is to deepen the understanding of the architectural potential of existing precast concrete systems and to document the design strategies that enable their successful adaptation across diverse building functions and typologies. The findings reveal that precast concrete systems offer a degree of flexibility that allows them to be repurposed in ways not originally intended. With appropriate design interventions, changes in building type, function, and even structural typology can be successfully achieved. Key strategies observed in the studied projects include the resizing of elements, the creation of new openings, new connectors, and the integration of complementary components—all of which play a critical role in enabling the effective incorporation of reused elements into new architectural configurations.

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A novel method for early-stage evaluation of adaptive reuse potential through functional division matching

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Keywords: Adaptive reuse; Building conversion; Early-stage evaluation; Functional division matching; Programme structuring; Typological compatibility.

ABSTRACT

The building sector accounts for a significant portion of global final energy use and greenhouse gas emissions, demonstrating the need to find low-carbon alternatives to new construction. Adaptive reuse offers a sustainable alternative to new construction, yet early-stage assessments of reuse potential often rely on surface-level metrics, failing to consider a building's internal spatial logic. This paper presents a novel method for evaluating adaptive reuse potential by comparing functional divisions – operationally linked clusters of rooms – across existing and proposed building functions. The method was developed in close collaboration with industry stakeholders to ensure practical relevance and applicability in real project contexts. It proceeds through four steps: comparing spatial requirements, identifying adjacency relationships, grouping rooms into functional divisions, and comparing these across programmes. It enables structured, early-stage screening of spatial compatibility before design development. The method was tested through a workshop on the potential conversion of a pre-school to an elderly care facility. The case demonstrated how spatial mismatches and economic infeasibility, such as insufficient living units for operational viability, can be identified early, avoiding costly redesigns. The method also supports reversible planning by highlighting flexible spatial nodes and fostering long-term adaptability.

INTRODUCTION

The building industry accounts for approximately 30% of global final energy use and 26% of greenhouse gas emissions during both construction and operation phases [1]. Notably, the embodied energy from construction activities alone typically accounts for approximately 3% and 35% of lifecycle energy demand, depending on building type, lifespan, and geographical context. Similarly, embodied carbon generally represents between 37 % and 68% of total lifecycle carbon emissions over a 60-year building lifespan, further emphasising the substantial environmental benefits achievable through adaptive reuse [2].

In response to climate targets and resource constraints, adaptive reuse, the practice of converting old buildings to new functions, has emerged as a key strategy to reduce the environmental impact of buildings by extending their service lives and reducing the need for new construction [3,4]. At the same time, changing demographic needs, evolving welfare provision, and urban restructuring have created increased pressure to find new uses for underutilised buildings, particularly in Nordic countries, where ageing populations, migration patterns, and school closures intersect with growing demand for care facilities and housing [5].

While adaptive reuse is widely recognised as a sustainable practice, assessing the suitability of a specific building for conversion remains a challenge [6]. Early-phase decisions are often

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made without structured analysis, relying instead on surface-level indicators such as total floor area, building age, or location [7]. These indicators, while helpful, do not account for the internal functional organisation of the building or the spatial demands of the intended new use. Consequently, buildings that appear suitable on paper may prove unworkable in practice, leading to costly redesigns, inefficient layouts, or project abandonment [8].

This gap in early-phase evaluation highlights the need for methods focused on programme structure: how spaces are functionally organised, how rooms relate through adjacency, and how these groupings align between building typologies. Recent methodological advancements include multi-case spatial mapping, where adaptability was systematically assessed by matching apartment layouts with assisted-living requirements [9], and configurational methods such as SAGA, which quantify adaptability through spatial permeability and connectivity using weighted graph analysis [10]. However, these approaches primarily emphasise spatial and theoretical dimensions, without explicitly addressing practical considerations such as reversibility of interventions, technical constraints, or economic viability.

In contrast, this study proposes a method for evaluating the adaptive reuse potential at an early stage, based on an operational comparison of functional divisions between existing and intended uses. Rather than focusing on building form or physical condition, the method analyses spatial programmes through adjacency relationships and functional clustering, explicitly integrating technical feasibility, economic viability, and reversibility of spatial interventions. The method thus provides practitioners, planners, and researchers with a transparent and scalable framework to assess spatial compatibility across building typologies prior to detailed design or significant investment. The method was developed in collaboration with industry partners to ensure its practical applicability in real project contexts.

METHOD

The proposed method supports early-stage evaluation of adaptive reuse potential by comparing the internal spatial structures of existing and proposed building functions. It is intended for contexts where both functions, such as care, education, or office use, can be described through spatial programmes: structured lists of required spaces with associated area demands and adjacency relationships. The method focuses on functional organisation rather than form or condition, aiming to estimate spatial compatibility before design development.

The method proceeds through four sequential steps. These steps mirror established architectural design practice for new buildings, where spatial requirements, adjacency logic, and functional groupings are systematically examined step by step to ensure operational coherence.

- Comparing spatial requirements
- Identifying adjacency logic
- Grouping rooms into functional divisions
- Comparing these divisions across the existing and target programmes.

In the first step, the existing and intended operational specifications are described in terms of their required rooms or premises. A room in this study is defined as an enclosed space bounded by walls, regardless of whether these are structural or non-structural. Each room type is associated with a minimum floor area derived from design standards, operational benchmarks, or client requirements. This results in two structured programme lists, independent of any specific building geometry. These serve as abstract representations of functional demand and are treated as the conceptual basis for subsequent spatial reasoning.

The second step involves identifying the relationships between different functions within each programme. These adjacency logics describe which spaces should be co-located or spatially separated, depending on operational, accessibility, or privacy considerations. Professional practice, institutional guidelines, or user interviews typically inform these relationships. In cases where adjacency is critical, such as between staff areas and care rooms

or between kitchens and dining rooms, these relationships guide the grouping logic used in the next stage.

In the third step, rooms are grouped into coherent higher-order units referred to here as functional divisions. Each division is composed of rooms that are operationally linked and should be located in close spatial proximity to one another. For example, in a care facility, a division might consist of private rooms, shared sanitary spaces, and a small staff area. In a school, it might include classrooms and adjacent group rooms. The total floor area of each division is calculated, and its internal structure, namely, the types of rooms and adjacency patterns, is recorded. These divisions form the core unit of analysis for the next step.

The fourth step is the comparative analysis of divisions across the two building uses. The aim is to identify whether any division in the existing building function corresponds, in both scale and structure, to a division in the proposed function. Compatibility is assessed on quantitative (total floor area) and qualitative (similarity in room types and spatial relationships) levels. The result is not a binary 'fit/no-fit' judgment, but a spectrum of alignment: some divisions may match fully, others only partially, and some not at all. These findings are typically recorded in a table or diagram showing potential mappings, overlaps, or gaps between functions.

This division-level approach helps identify buildings with adaptive reuse potential that are structurally embedded in space organisation, as opposed to those where conversion would require major reconfiguration.

The method does not account for technical systems, structural grids, or legal compliance. It is intended as a conceptual screening tool in the early stages of a project to support prioritisation and decision-making before architectural design or detailed feasibility studies are undertaken.

ANALYSIS

The proposed method was tested through a full-day workshop to assess its usability in a real-world setting. The case study focused on a building currently operating as a pre-school in an urban area where demographic changes have led to a decrease in the number of children requiring pre-school facilities, and an increase in the need for elderly care facilities. This shift in local needs provided a relevant scenario for applying the method. The architecture firm FOJAB, based in Malmö, initiated the workshop and brought together a multidisciplinary team consisting of representatives from a well-established Swedish property owner, architects with expertise in pre-school and elderly care design, and researchers specialising in adaptive reuse and circularity in technical systems. One architect led the workshop to ensure structured progression through the method's stages.

The first step involved specifying the spatial programmes for both uses. Architects with domain-specific expertise listed the required room types and associated minimum floor areas for pre-school and elderly care operations. These programme items may be derived from plan evaluations, room function plans, or, as in this case, from the experiential knowledge of specialists familiar with designing both building types. For reversible transformations, such specialists have full knowledge of the operational demands of the existing and the intended functions. The resulting programme table, alongside the floor plan of the current building, is shown in Figure 1.

In the second step, relationships between rooms were analysed. Using movable sticky notes representing each room and its area, participants clarified critical adjacencies, such as the proximity required between home rooms and common areas. Degrees of adjacency tolerance were discussed to distinguish between rooms that require strict co-location and those that can be separated within a shared zone. Grouping spaces in this way generated clusters that reflect the operational need for adjacency during use. Functions with minimal dependencies appeared as solitary or standalone elements, offering greater flexibility when fitting into a fixed spatial layout.

Figure 1. Programme requirements and floor plan of the existing pre-school building, illustrating spatial distribution and available area in relation to the proposed new use.

In the third step, rooms were grouped into functional divisions based on operational logic. Sticky notes were clustered into circles representing functional entities such as staff zones, service cores, or user-specific environments. The internal structure and total floor area of each division were noted, forming the basis for the comparative analysis in the next step. Clusters can also be organised into thematic categories to support legibility and analysis, e.g., support areas, user-oriented areas, or staff areas.

Finally, the functional divisions of the existing and proposed uses were compared to assess the feasibility of the building's adaptive reuse. The analysis considered both quantitative matches, primarily floor area alignment, and qualitative matches, including room types and adjacency relationships. While strict one-to-one correspondence was not always necessary, a reasonable deviation in area was acceptable provided that the regulatory and functional requirements of the intended use could still be met. In some cases, parts of a division from the proposed function were distributed across multiple clusters from the current function. This matching logic allowed the method to accommodate imperfect alignments without dismissing the reuse potential outright. The combined process of adjacency mapping, clustering, and division-level comparison is illustrated in Figure 2, which visually summarises all analytical stages and highlights the resulting spatial compatibility and transformation potential.

Figure 2. Combined analytical stages of the method: adjacency mapping, functional clustering into operational divisions, and comparative analysis showing spatial compatibility.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduced a method for early-stage evaluation of adaptive reuse potential by comparing functional divisions between existing and proposed building uses. The approach provides a structured alternative to surface-level assessments, focusing on room types, area requirements, and adjacency relationships.

The method's key strength is its focus on internal spatial organisation, which enables comparison across building types with differing functions but similar structural logic. The use of functional divisions as the analysis unit supports precision and flexibility, making the method applicable to institutional and service-oriented settings. It also proved effective in participatory settings, helping stakeholders evaluate spatial compatibility through shared analysis. This is particularly useful in public-sector projects with diverse and shifting needs.

The case study demonstrated not only spatial limitations but also revealed a fundamental economic barrier: the proposed elderly care function would require around 50 living units to achieve economic viability, while the existing pre-school building could accommodate only about 10. Additionally, critical adjacencies could not be achieved without major reconfiguration of support systems, further reducing feasibility. These results highlight the importance of integrating economic and operational viability into early-stage assessments, thereby preventing costly investments in conversions that may be technically feasible but financially unsustainable.

While promising, the method remains conceptual, as it does not yet integrate technical systems or structural constraints, nor does it account for modifications to room boundaries, such as the addition or removal of non-load-bearing walls or doorways. The decision to exclude potential additions or removals of walls is deliberate; the method prioritises preserving existing spatial configurations to enable reversible conversions in the future. By maintaining the original room boundaries, technical systems such as ventilation and services, which are designed for specific occupancy patterns, can remain largely intact. While this conservative approach may underestimate the adaptability of certain buildings if modifications were allowed, it aligns with a long-term strategy of minimising intervention and maximising future flexibility. Considering selective modifications as an additional analysis layer represents an important direction for future methodological development.

The case study highlighted the importance of technical reversibility in adaptive reuse. Future development will address whether building services, such as ventilation, plumbing, can support reversible transformations with minimal intervention. Ongoing work will refine the matching logic, incorporate technical infrastructure, and test broader applicability across reuse scenarios. The method could also benefit from further formalisation to improve consistency and uptake, as it currently relies on professional judgement.

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Algorithms for design based on a Database of Reused Concrete Elements

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Keywords: algorithm, database, ReCreate, element reuse, structural design

ABSTRACT

In the ReCreate project, a design application named ReCreate Studio has been developed to assist both architects and structural engineers in the design of building structures with an optimum use of available precast concrete elements used previously in deconstructed structures. The starting point of the application is that available elements are described in a database that is available to the designer. The database, whose development is part of work package 1 of the ReCreate project, describes the geometrical and material properties of floor elements, wall elements, beams and columns. Additional information about the present location of elements is also included. The design application is a plug-in for Autodesk Revit.

When designing for the optimum use of available reused elements, fixed dimensions should not be the starting points. The chance that suitable elements will be found in that case is rather small. On the other hand, when a database containing thousands of elements is available, it is hard to get a productive start on the design. Hence, there is a need for algorithms to assist the designer in the selection of available elements and to evaluate the several possible design solutions.

In ReCreate Studio, an algorithm has been applied that assists the designer in creating floor plans from the available floor elements to create a given number of storeys with a given specified floor area. The algorithm is based on logical structural design principles, where successive floors should be identical as far as possible. Using ReCreate Studio with a fictitious data base, learned that through interactions, several feasible collections of elements to create the floors can be found. The collections can then be evaluated on several different aspects. After choosing a particular collection of elements, the designer is free to shape the floor plan based on a collection of proposed elements by moving or rotating groups of elements around.

After the design of the floors, the vertical load-bearing elements must be selected. Algorithms to help with this process are not yet implemented in ReCreate Studio. The designer can indicate the position of solid walls, wall openings and gridlines for beams and columns. The gridlines for vertical load-bearing elements should be above each other. However, they do not have to consist of identically shaped elements over the full height. A design starting point is that the top level of the several floor elements differs as marginally as possible. Such an algorithm can assist the designer by selecting suitable vertical load-bearing elements from the database.

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Applying time-value of carbon to adaptable versus optimised structural design decision-making

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Keywords: Adaptability, circular design, circular economy, embodied carbon, optimisation, time-value of carbon

ABSTRACT

When designing buildings for the circular economy, a balance must be struck between structural optimisation and design for adaptability (DfA); balancing the needs for immediate carbon reductions with the desires for long-term sustainability. Traditional structural optimisation (or '*lean design*') approaches prioritise immediate material efficiency through minimising upfront material usage. However, these approaches may inadvertently reduce building lifespans, increase demolition and rebuild rates, and ultimately exacerbate long-term construction emissions. Conversely, DfA, through providing versatile spaces, selective overdesign and a separation of layers, aims to extend building lifespans and promote material reuse, aligning with the principles of the circular economy. This project therefore investigated the design opportunities for producing longer-lived buildings without the need for significant upfront carbon overinvestment.

To evaluate this balance, a number of theoretical structural design briefs were developed to cover a range of typical building use typologies, and each brief was taken through to concept level, twice; once with a lean design mindset and once with a DfA approach. The material requirements, and associated embodied carbon values, for each design pair were then compared to determine the upfront carbon costs of DfA versus lean design. To assess how these designs would perform in the long-run, various future scenarios were considered, including changing climates, usage requirements and decarbonisation pathways. The material requirements for any resulting structural retrofit gives an indication of the emission saving opportunities of DfA. These results therefore provide a novel insight into the balance between lean design and DfA. However, comparing these two absolute values neglects to capture the temporal nature of the emissions; how can we compare the relative value of a tonne of carbon emitted today versus a tonne of carbon saved tomorrow (or any number of days, years or decades in the future)? As such, a novel decision-making framework was developed that incorporates a '*time-value of carbon*' (TVoC).

There are various factors that influence TVoC, such as anticipated decarbonisation pathways for electricity and material production, reduced cumulative impacts and avoided climate tipping points, and the relative uncertainty of the future emissions compared to the certainty of the present. Considering these TVoC levers, weighting factors were derived to determine the

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equivalent '*net present value*' (NPV) of future emissions (or emission savings). As these factors generally promote immediate carbon reductions, TVoC suggests that not only must the long-term savings of DfA be greater than their immediate costs, these long-term emission savings must first be discounted to their NPV. Nevertheless, the research does highlight aspects of structural design where an only marginal increase in upfront embodied carbon affords the opportunity for significant carbon saving in the future through structural adaptability.

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Better Utilisation of Sawmill Residues: A Pilot Study on Biobased Insulation

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Keywords: Biobased insulation; Carbon sequestration; Circular upcycling; Resource loops; Sawmill residues; Thermal performance

ABSTRACT

The rapidly growing interest in sustainable construction principles has positioned biobased building materials as a critical component of low-emission construction. This study examines the conversion of wood waste from sawmills, including chips and sawdust, into insulation materials that offer competitive thermal performance while extending the carbon storage timeline in buildings. By transforming residues that would otherwise be relegated to low-value uses or disposal, this study aims to demonstrate a viable path toward circular resource flows in the forestry and construction sectors, it aims to demonstrate a viable path toward circular resource flows in the forestry and construction sectors.

Pilot experiments are currently being conducted to develop and evaluate three to four insulation prototypes derived from sawmill byproducts. Each prototype will undergo standard laboratory testing for thermal conductivity (Heat-flow meter and TPS) and simplified life cycle assessments (LCAs). The LCAs will focus on quantifying carbon sequestration, energy inputs, and end-of-life scenarios to identify optimal design pathways and highlight the potential for climate mitigation.

Preliminary findings suggest that wood-fibre insulation sourced and refined from sawmill residues can achieve performance comparable to conventional solutions, such as mineral wool, while reducing energy consumption and carbon footprint. However, key challenges include balancing processing intensity, determining how much the raw fibres must be treated to meet insulation standards, and maintaining a viable economic and sustainable model. The results of the experiments, which will be completed during the summer, will illustrate the trade-offs between different processing approaches and their corresponding impacts on insulation properties and overall circular performance.

Beyond validating technical feasibility, this project acts as a catalyst for broader industry transformation. By showcasing a practical reuse pathway for sawmill waste, to promote cross-sector collaboration among sawmills, material and house manufacturers, and policymakers, ultimately nurturing new business models rooted in resource efficiency and carbon reduction. The insights gained from this pilot study will shape guidelines for future large-scale implementation, contributing to advancing circular bioeconomy strategies in construction and beyond.

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Circular Renovation Practice of Aged Educational Buildings: A Case Study of Neuron Building

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Keywords: Aged educational Buildings, Circular renovation, Renovation process

ABSTRACT

In Europe, cities are largely built, and the central focus of building-related CO₂ emissions is less on the design of new buildings, but on the renovation and transformation of the existing building stock (EPRS, 2021). In the European Union, approximately 17% of non-residential buildings are educational buildings (Österreicher & Geissler, 2016). Many of them were built in the 1960s-1970s. These buildings are typically characterized by high occupancy rates and substantial energy use (Hu, 2020). As such, the renovation of educational buildings plays a crucial role in reducing the environmental impact of the built environment. Compared to demolition and new construction, renovation offers considerable environmental benefits, including reduced material consumption, lower embodied carbon emissions, and the preservation of existing structural resources (Dragonetti et al., 2025). Therefore, prioritizing the circular renovation of educational buildings is essential to achieving climate goals and advancing circular construction practices in the EU.

Despite growing attention to circularity in architectural design research and practice, significant gaps remain, particularly in the context of circular renovation (Circle Economy Foundation, 2024; Carbonell-Alcocer et al., 2022; Transitieteam Circulaire Bouweconomie, 2018). There is a lack of documented case studies and clear methodological frameworks that demonstrate how circular principles can be effectively applied in the circular renovation of existing buildings. This paper presents a comprehensive analysis of the Neuron building, which is an award-winning renovation project. The original building, completed in 1972, was designed by Jacques Choisy (OD205); renovated by Team V Architecture (2019-2023), an education building (of 12,330 m²) for TU/e in Eindhoven, the Netherlands. In renovation practice, the challenges of circular renovation, zero energy renovation, and architectural design to create attractive future learning environments are entangled, thus explored in interrelation in this paper, and focus on circular renovation. Through the analysis of this building case, the study discussed the applicability of circular strategies in renovation processes.

A framework based on three analytical questions guided the research:

- How have the key stakeholders of the design team defined circularity and formulated related design goals in the renovation design process?
- Which circular renovation strategies have been applied in Neuron (Structure, Materiality)?
- What conflicts, compromises, and innovations emerged during the circular renovation process?

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Unlike frameworks that often remain theoretical, this research provides a practice-based account of how circularity is interpreted, negotiated, and operationalized among diverse stakeholders.

This research project builds on a mixed-methods approach, combining case study, document analysis, drawing analysis, and conversations with key stakeholders. A total of 5 conversations were conducted with key stakeholders involved in the Neuron renovation project, including the client (TU/e Real Estate), the architect (Team V Architecture), structural engineers (Royal Haskoning DHV), the sustainability consultant (DGMR), and the contractor (Heerkens van Bavel Bouw). Collected data was analysed through content analysis to identify patterns, tensions, and the application of circular strategies.

Neuron exemplifies a paradigmatic shift in architecture, emphasizing circularity and integrated design. This paper explores the collaborative renovation process and transformation strategies of Neuron, with an emphasis on how circularity was embedded into both design strategies, construction, and materialization, which contributes to a growing body of knowledge on circular renovation. A key contribution of this study lies in the systematic categorization of results across thematic dimensions such as stakeholder definitions of circularity, applied strategies, and emergent challenges and innovations. The findings support future policy development, design practice, and stakeholder collaboration by illustrating how circular strategies can be effectively integrated into complex, multi-actor renovation projects.

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Conceptual Framework for an AI-Supported Design Tool: Enabling Re-Use through Data-Driven Recommender Systems

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Keywords: AI, circular construction, reuse, structural verification, structural design, sustainability

ABSTRACT

The construction sector is a major consumer of natural resources and generator of waste, creating an urgent need for circular construction strategies. One promising approach is the reuse of structural components, although practical implementation faces barriers related to data quality, structural verification, and integration into design processes. This paper presents an AI-supported recommender system developed within ReCreate project in collaboration with DFKI and Concular within the Green-AI Hub initiative, enabling designers to match reused building elements to new design requirements. The system integrates demand, offer, and tolerance data layers and incorporates capacity-based structural verification for key element types, including walls, slabs, beams, and columns. Implemented within Concular's platform, it allows dimension-based matching with flexible cutting options and structural safety checks. Initial results demonstrate strong functionality for individual components but highlight significant challenges when assembling whole-building reuse solutions, primarily due to data incompleteness. Despite these limitations, the system shows considerable potential for material and carbon savings, supporting a scalable pathway towards a circular built environment. Future work should focus on improving data quality, leveraging machine learning, and expanding database coverage to maximize impact. This work represents a first step in embedding rule-based AI within reuse-focused workflows and lays the groundwork for future integration of learning-based methods.

1 Introduction

The construction sector is one of the most resource-intensive industries worldwide. In Germany alone, around 90% of mineral raw materials [1] are used in construction, generating over half of the country's total waste [2]. This reality presents a significant opportunity to improve sustainability and resource efficiency by shifting towards circular construction practices, such as the reuse of structural components. However, integrating reused elements into new building designs poses major challenges.

The conventional design process typically assumes standardized components and linear workflows. Reuse challenges this logic by requiring flexibility, iterative planning, and adaptability to available reclaimed components. To support this, digital tools can help designers explore multiple options and adjust plans efficiently.

Our tool responds to this need by automating the element matching process, allowing for streamlined evaluation of reuse options throughout early design phases.

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Further challenges include inconsistency and incompleteness in the data, such as missing geometry, unknown materials, or vague product categories in BIM models and offer inventories.

To address these issues, a pilot project was launched within the German Green-AI Hub initiative, involving Circular Structural Design, Concular, and the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence. The project aimed to develop a data-driven recommender system capable of suggesting suitable reused structural elements for new building projects while ensuring their structural capabilities. This paper outlines the AI-driven methodology, implementation, and results of the pilot, providing insights into enabling reuse at scale.

2 Methodology

This paper introduces a pilot-stage implementation of rule-based AI in a real-world reuse scenario. It is intended as the foundation for a broader research stream that will progressively introduce data-driven learning, adaptive ranking, and predictive capabilities as more training data becomes available.

Prior to integration, Concular applies AI-based preprocessing to BIM demand models. Using NLP techniques, material types and environmental properties are inferred and matched to EPDs. This classification forms the basis for circularity scoring and GWP baselines. The recommender was developed during a six-month pilot under the Green-AI Hub initiative. Early phases included stakeholder workshops, system scoping, and data audits, followed by iterative prototyping and testing with real and synthetic data.

The development of the AI-Supported circular structural design Tool is based on a modular architecture integrating three primary data layers: Demand, Offer, and Tolerance Data. This structure was identified during early project definition phases and validated through pilot testing. It reflects the practical necessities of matching reused components under real-world uncertainties, balancing operational flexibility with structural safety.

2.1 Data Model

The system processes three types of input data:

Demand Data are extracted from BIM models and describe the required components for new construction projects, including geometry (length, width, height), material properties, load-bearing classifications, timeline and location metadata. Preprocessing steps included standardization of units, handling of missing values through default assumptions, and classification mapping using DIN codes where available. Default assumptions were based on statistical norms in the dataset or physical inference (e.g., deriving volume from dimensions or filling missing material based on product name patterns).

Offer Data represents available reused components listed in Concular's database. These records varied in completeness, particularly regarding material and structural attributes. Normalization routines focused on geometric information and basic material classification. Where information was missing, conservative default assumptions were employed to avoid unsafe suggestions.

Tolerance Data defines acceptable variations between demand and offer elements. A structured JSON schema was developed to describe permissible absolute or relative dimensional deviations per product category, allowing the recommender system to consider flexible matches without compromising usability.

2.2 Recommender System and Matching Logic

In this project, we use a rule-based form of AI. This means the system follows clearly defined rules, like checking whether a beam is long enough or if materials are compatible, rather than learning patterns from large amounts of data. This method is especially useful when the available data is incomplete or not standardized, which is often the case in reuse projects.

A rule-based recommender approach was selected due to the heterogeneous and often incomplete nature of the data. Matching priorities were hierarchically structured along the following criteria:

- Product category equivalence (primary key matching, such as wall, beams, ...)
- Dimensional fit within defined tolerances
- Material compatibility (where verifiable)
- Load-bearing capability (structural verification where possible)
- Optional prioritization based on geographic proximity

Fallback mechanisms were introduced to allow partial matching when full attribute matches were not achievable, maximizing the usability of the available supply without compromising essential requirements.

To summarize, AI in this project helps automate and organize decisions that would otherwise require manual review—such as comparing thousands of reuse options. It doesn't replace design work but supports it by making the reuse process faster and more consistent. In future versions, this logic could evolve into learning systems that improve over time.

2.3 Structural capacity check

To ensure that matched components could fulfill structural functions safely, a structural checking layer was incorporated. Simplified engineering models based on Eurocode standards were applied to major structural element types (walls, slabs, beams, columns). Key mechanical properties such as concrete compressive strength, steel yield strength, reinforcement ratios, and cross-sectional dimensions were either extracted directly from the offer data or conservatively assumed.

Components were verified for normal force, bending, and shear capacity using analytical calculations. If key parameters were missing or unverifiable, elements were either downgraded to non-structural matches or flagged for further manual assessment.

3 System Implementation

Following the definition of the data model and matching logic, the recommender system was implemented within a modular, scalable architecture suitable for integration into existing digital platforms. The system is designed to support users in identifying suitable reused building elements efficiently and reliably, incorporating structural verification to ensure the applicability of suggested elements. As shown in Figure 1, the IT-architecture allows for both, a matching on the element level and an optimization on the building level. This version of the system prioritizes interpretability and robustness, making it suitable for early-stage deployment where training data remains limited.

Figure 1. System architecture of the AI-assisted matching process for reused building elements

3.1 Platform Integration

Although initial plans considered integration into Autodesk Revit through a plugin, technical constraints associated with plugin environments led to the decision to embed the tool within the digital marketplace's web-based platform. This approach offered greater flexibility for data handling, system updates, and user interface design. The recommender system was containerized using Docker technology. The integrated structural capacity computation is open-access and is made available through the Green-AI-Hub git-hub account.

Users interact with the system through an intuitive interface where they upload project-specific demand data (typically exported from BIM models). The system processes the uploaded demand against the offer database and presents a ranked list of potential matches based on defined matching rules and tolerances. Filtering functionalities allow users to refine results based on material type, geometry, structural verification status, or sustainability potential.

3.2 Structural Verification Module

The structural verification of load-bearing elements was embedded in the matching process. For each proposed match classified as potentially structural (i.e., walls, beams, slabs, and columns marked as load bearing), the system automatically performs a simplified structural verification.

The verification procedure extracts necessary mechanical parameters either from offer data, directly or applies conservative assumptions when data are incomplete. Structural checks are executed based on established engineering formulas aligned with Eurocode standards, evaluating:

- Axial force capacity
- Bending moment resistance
- Shear force resistance

Components that pass the verification are explicitly labeled, providing users with additional assurance regarding their structural suitability. Elements with missing critical parameters are either flagged or excluded, depending on user-defined risk tolerances. Conservative values followed Eurocode minimums or were set using lower-bound estimates from domain expertise.

3.3 Advanced Functionalities

To increase the likelihood of finding usable matches, the system implements several advanced functionalities:

- **Virtual Cutting of Elements**
Walls, beams, slabs and columns can be “virtually” cut to adapt their dimensions to the demand element. Logical constraints are enforced, such as maintaining a specified minimum distance from any wall opening when cutting wall segments.
- **Tolerance Flexibility**
Users can adjust tolerance levels manually, allowing for broader or stricter matches depending on project needs.
- **Sustainability Metrics**
Elements can be ranked by estimated carbon footprint savings based on reuse, supporting environmentally informed decision-making. These values are derived from proxy EPD data mapped to common material classes (e.g., CEM I concrete, softwood framing) and are not based on element-specific declarations. Ranking is currently based on rule-based scoring (dimensional fit, material match, structural feasibility), with plans to incorporate ML-based adaptive ranking in future iterations.

4 Results

The system was evaluated based on two primary dimensions: (1) the technical feasibility and reliability of matching individual reused components, and (2) the systemic potential for supporting whole-building reuse strategies under realistic data conditions. Additional scenario-based assessments were conducted to estimate the potential environmental benefits of applying the system at scale.

Extensive internal testing was conducted using both synthetic datasets and real-world project data. Results indicated that while individual element matching performed reliably, whole-building reuse proposals faced significant challenges due to the high incompleteness and inconsistency of the underlying offer and demand datasets. Synthetic datasets were created by modifying geometry and metadata in real BIM exports to simulate edge cases and test robustness.

4.1 Matching of Individual Components

Testing the system against both synthetic and real-world datasets demonstrated that the rule-based recommender could reliably identify suitable matches for individual building elements when sufficient data quality was available. Matches were successfully validated through geometric and material criteria, as well as through structural verification for load-bearing components. The system was evaluated using a combination of synthetic benchmarks and BIM datasets from four Concular projects, each run through the full matching and verification process.

The virtual cutting functionality significantly expanded the pool of viable matches, particularly for walls and beams, by allowing flexible adaptation to dimensional requirements while adhering to logical and structural constraints. Structural verification procedures identified load-bearing capacities accurately when all necessary parameters were present; however, missing structural data in the offer database remained a major bottleneck.

Overall, the matching process showed high reliability, with over 85% of matched elements passing structural verification checks under standard tolerance assumptions.

4.2 Whole-Building Reuse Proposals

Developing whole-building reuse solutions, where an entire demand model is matched against a supply of reused components, proved more complex than individual component

matching. The variability and incompleteness of real-world data introduced challenges in achieving full coverage across all required elements. However, the pilot demonstrated that even partial matching is feasible and can provide meaningful reuse opportunities. By incorporating tolerance adjustments and allowing for flexible data handling, the system can adapt to varying project needs and data conditions. These insights point to the considerable potential of AI-driven tools in enabling circular practices at scale, particularly as data quality and standardization improve over time.

4.3 Resource Efficiency Potential

To evaluate the broader environmental impact potential, a scenario-based resource efficiency (RE) assessment was conducted, extrapolating reuse effects across typical building element categories [5]. Two contrasting scenarios were analyzed:

- **Minimal Scenario:** Assumes the reuse of 30 windows, 2 exterior doors, and 50 luminaires in a small commercial building. Estimated savings compared to new production include approximately 35 metric tons of material and 9 metric tons of CO₂-equivalent emissions.
- **Maximal Scenario:** Hypothetical reuse of all similar offer elements from the database. Projected savings amount to approximately 4.6 million metric tons of material and 1.2 million metric tons of CO₂-equivalent emissions.

While the maximal scenario remains largely theoretical given current data limitations, it illustrates the significant potential gains if systemic barriers to reuse can be addressed. These savings would range around 15–25% reduction in embodied carbon compared to typical commercial mid-rise buildings, based on benchmarks of 500–800 kg CO₂e/m².

5 Discussion and conclusion

The results of the pilot project demonstrate that AI-assisted systems can significantly support the integration of reused components into the design process of new buildings, addressing one of the critical barriers to the broader adoption of circular construction practices. The modular architecture developed - combining demand, offer, and tolerance data layers with a rule-based recommender system and embedded structural verification - proved effective in matching individual building components under real-world conditions.

However, several challenges emerged clearly. The incomplete and inconsistent nature of available data, particularly on the offer side, limited the system's ability to propose whole-building reuse solutions. Furthermore, while the structural verification module allowed safe load-bearing checks when parameters were available, its full potential could not be exploited due to frequent data gaps. These observations emphasize that technical solutions alone are insufficient; parallel improvements in data acquisition, standardization, and quality assurance processes are necessary to unlock systemic reuse potential.

From a resource efficiency perspective, even minimal reuse scenarios yielded substantial material and carbon savings. This finding underscores the strategic importance of reuse initiatives for climate mitigation and resource conservation. Scaling up such impacts, however, will require coordinated efforts across the construction industry, involving digital platforms, designers, contractors, and policymakers.

The system uses simple AI rules to compare many reused elements at once and suggest which ones might fit a new design. It helps find the best matches quickly and consistently; something that would be very difficult to do by hand or with basic filtering tools.

In conclusion, the pilot confirmed the technical feasibility and environmental potential of AI-supported circular structural design. While the current solution provides a functional foundation, future developments should focus on: This pilot marks the beginning of a longer-term research effort aimed at evolving from static rules toward adaptive and intelligent reuse systems.

- Enhancing data completeness through automated enrichment and standardized data protocols,
- Expanding the use of machine learning methods for improved matching in the presence of incomplete information,
- Increasing the breadth and diversity of offer databases to better support whole-building reuse strategies.

In this project, AI is used not to design, but to support design. The system applies rule-based AI logic to automate the complex process of matching reused building components to new design demands. This includes checking geometric compatibility, filtering based on material and load-bearing potential, and structuring recommendations. As more project data becomes available, this logic can evolve into adaptive systems and learning from user input and improving reuse proposals over time.

The broader application of AI-supported reuse systems has the potential to transform construction practices towards a truly circular economy, substantially reducing environmental impacts while maintaining design quality and safety.

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Design Method for Generating a Stock of Segments for Reusable Concrete Slabs

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Keywords: concrete reuse, concrete slab, design for reuse, stock optimization

By recovering and later reusing concrete components, it is possible to drastically reduce the environmental impact in concrete construction. A key technical challenge for the future reuse of concrete components is the integration of design for reuse in the design process of new structures. Slabs constitute the largest mass share in conventional concrete buildings and a potential strategy to allow for their future reuse are prefabricated, demountable slab segments.

The present work proposes a design method that facilitates the generation of a stock of segments that can be flexibly reused in multiple concrete slabs with various boundary conditions and use scenarios. The design method decomposes one-way spanning concrete slabs with prescribed span widths, static systems and load conditions into segments. Simultaneously, the resulting segments are clustered by their geometric and structural properties to form a stock of segments that can be flexibly reused within the prescribed boundary conditions. The segmentation was approached through the formulation of a multi-objective optimization problem, with the objectives to minimize the ecological footprint of the segments, minimize the number of connection points and minimize the number of different segment types.

The application of the design method and a comparative analysis are presented on a case study. The case study demonstrates that the proposed method facilitates a quantitative assessment between the choice of more types and shorter segments, which increases adaptability and material efficiency, and less types but longer segments, which increases the probability of reuse and minimizes the number of connection points. Similarly, the case study illustrated the potential of integrating design for reuse into the conceptual design of concrete slabs.

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Enabling Architectural and Structural Design with Reused Concrete Elements: Insights from the ReCreate Studio

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Keywords: Circular economy, BIM structural design tool, precast concrete, ReCreate, reuse

ABSTRACT

The circular reuse of precast concrete components challenges the conventions of architectural and structural design. Traditional workflows assume element geometry and structural capacity are determined during the design phase. In contrast, the reuse process requires designers to work from a set of existing, predefined components—each with specific spatial, mechanical, and environmental characteristics. This inversion of the conventional design logic introduces new levels of constraint but also opens avenues for more sustainable design practices.

This contribution presents key insights into the development and testing of “ReCreate Studio” [1], a prototype digital design tool created within the EU-funded ReCreate project, specifically under Work Package 5 (WP5): Redesign and Reassembly, which will lead to a Design Manual by the end of the project. The software functions as an add-on for Autodesk Revit and allows architects and engineers to assemble building designs using reclaimed precast concrete elements, which are described in a database. It enables users to browse available components, visualize and import them into a 3D BIM environment, and assess both structural feasibility and environmental impact in real time. The element database is typically built from deconstruction audits and reviewed documentation, with material tests or reinforcement scans used as needed.

A core innovation of ReCreate Studio lies in its object-oriented digital model, which encodes each building element’s geometry, structural properties, material properties, and lifecycle data. The tool introduces a structural analysis engine and environmental impact calculator directly within the design interface. These enable iterative checking of design scenarios - supporting users in selecting, arranging, and evaluating reused elements according to load-bearing requirements and global warming potential (GWP) savings.

Additionally, the application supports automatic floor slab layout generation, simplifying early design stages while optimizing reuse rates. The tool provides feedback on environmental impact, incl. geographical location, (new vs. reused GWP) and flags any components that exceed their structural thresholds. By embedding design constraints directly into the architectural workflow, ReCreate Studio operationalizes the core principles of design for reuse and design for disassembly, bridging architectural intent with structural performance and environmental responsibility.

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Environmental evaluation of recycling waste concrete

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Keywords: Concrete fines, recycling, urban mining

ABSTRACT OR SHORT PAPER

There is a large amount of concrete waste from demolished buildings and infrastructure, which, in Finland, was about 10Mtons in 2022 (StatFin), and it is mainly used for infrastructure such as noise reduction walls and roads.

There are two major ways of bringing the concrete waste back to a building, and hence closing the material loop. The more established way of recycling is using crushed concrete as aggregate in concrete. This is already widely in use in some countries, and in Finland the end of waste has been defined, allowing the sales of recycled concrete aggregates (466/2022). However, the concrete aggregates increase the water intake in concrete mixture, and therefore more cement is needed to reach the wanted result (de Brito, et Kurda, 2021).

Another, so far more a research topic is using the fine fraction produced during crushing in new concrete as a cement substitute. There are several open questions remaining within this topic as the chemistry in concrete is complex and the concrete fines are not yet well known. Many of the earlier studies have focused on studying artificial fines produced in laboratories from pure cement paste or examined different activation methods, such as carbonation of fines (Poon et al. 2023). However, the initial composition of recycled concrete and the history of the structure for example, the time and the environmental conditions of the structure's life cycle, causes variation in the chemical and mineralogical composition of recycled fines. Consequently, there is a need to understand the characteristics of recycled fines in more detail. In this project, new understanding of the characteristics of different fine fractions are achieved, for the benefit of both the scientific and the industrial communities.

One aspect that has received relatively little attention is the environmental footprint of fines. Also, the associated emissions regarding the fines are evaluated for the process, including crushing, sieving, milling, and transportation. Emission evaluation for the concrete aggregates includes the crushing and transportation.

LCA evaluation was conducted with Sulca-tool (<https://www.simulationstore.com/sulca>). Comparing the LCA of these recycling options indicate that the benefits in recycling crushed concrete as recycled aggregates in concrete instead of in infrastructure is dependent on the transport means and distances and thus not necessary bring any environmental advances. On the other hand, if concrete fines are used in the production of new concrete, the environmental benefits depend on the effect on the cement amount needed to bring the desired strength to the final product.

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Evaluation of Spanish Esparto Fibers as a Natural Alternative to Synthetic Fibers for Concrete Reinforcement: Mechanical and Physical Properties

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Keywords: natural fibers; fiber-reinforced concrete; sustainable concrete; mechanical performance; circular construction.

ABSTRACT

This work aims to study the incorporation of esparto fibers (*Stipa tenacissima L.*) as natural reinforcement in concrete, evaluating its potential use as an alternative to synthetic fibers towards more sustainable building materials. For this, three mixtures were considered: (i) polypropylene fiber-reinforced concrete (PPFC), (ii) esparto fiber-reinforced concrete (EFRC), and (iii) a reference concrete (RC) for comparative purposes. Before incorporation, esparto fibers underwent an alkaline treatment to improve their interfacial compatibility with the cement matrix. Fundamentally, this treatment consisted of immersing the fibers in a 3% NaOH solution for 4 hours, soaking them in water for 10 hours, removing the residuals by rinsing, and finally oven-drying at 85°C for 24 hours. The mechanical behavior was determined by compressive strength (CS), flexural strength (FS), and indirect tensile strength (ITS) tests. In addition, physical properties, including density, water absorption, and porosity, were evaluated, along with ultrasonic pulse velocity (UPV), to assess the internal homogeneity of the composites. Results indicated that both PPFC and EFRC exhibited enhanced mechanical performance compared to RC. Particularly, PPFC presented increases of 9.5%, 23.9%, and 17.7% in CS, FS, and ITS, respectively. Conversely, EFRC showed a rise of 0.3% in CS, 6.9% in FS, and 9.2% in ITS compared to the reference concrete. In terms of physical parameters, PPFC exhibited a slight increase in water absorption and porosity of 5.5% and 4.3%, respectively, similar to the 10.4% and 6.5% increases observed in EFRC. Furthermore, while UPV indicated a reduction in the fiber-reinforced mixtures of 3.1% for PPFC and 1.2% for EFRC, the outcomes remained within the classification of “excellent concrete” for the three materials, confirming consistency in homogeneity after fiber incorporation. These findings highlight the potential of esparto, an abundant grass native to the Mediterranean region, as a plant-based substitute for synthetic fibers, enhancing the load-bearing capacity of concrete without significantly affecting its overall technical performance. This contributes to the valorization of local natural resources and seeks to align with circular construction principles.

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Experiment testing of a new RC application with re-integrated reclaimed precast concrete panels

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Keywords: Reclaimed Concrete, Structural Reuse, Structural Testing, Precast Concrete.

ABSTRACT

The art of structural reuse by re-integration is currently gaining significant interest in research environments as a promising solution to meet the requirement for green transition, driven by public interest. Some building materials are by nature better suited for re-integration than others, e.g. non-load bearing elements such as windows or insulation materials, or load-bearing materials with achievable connections by screwing or welding. However, reuse of concrete for structural purposes poses a significant challenge, as connection design typically must be designed for by reinforcement layout prior to casting. This limitation, combined with uncertainty of the material properties of reclaimed concrete materials dating several decades back, makes reuse of recycled structural components in new structures a challenging task that requires careful consideration. This contribution presents a distinct solution, where a reclaimed unreinforced concrete component is cast in a structural system where the new parts comply with current standards and design guidelines. The reclaimed concrete is placed as in-fill in a conventionally reinforced RC (Reinforced Concrete) frame, hence saving concrete while also providing significant lateral in plane stiffness to the load bearing element. The design philosophy of this particular solution entails that the load bearing capacity can conservatively be calculated as the capacity of the new RC frame alone, while the integration of unreinforced concrete provides stiffness if needed in a system of several similar wall elements – or provides flexibility to remove the center part of the individual elements in case change in the usage of the building in future scenarios requires an adapted layout. Experimental test have been conducted at the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) on a full-scale wall element subjected to in-plane forces, demonstrating a superior shear capacity of the new design compared to the frame itself. The solution appears promising and contains a significant reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to a similar best practice solution.

Figure 1. Picture of experimental setup.

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Freeze-Thaw Resistance of Steam Cured Slag Concrete with Low-grade Recycled Coarse Aggregate

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Keywords: concrete, freeze-thaw, low grade recycled aggregate, slag, steam curing

ABSTRACT

In cold regions with lots of snow, the use of the lowest quality (L grade) recycled aggregate in recycled concrete is challenging. In this study, the freeze-thaw behavior of the recycled concrete with combined use of L grade recycled coarse aggregate and natural crushed stone was investigated. To target the application to precast recycled concrete, steam curing was adopted. Additionally, blast furnace slag cement was used to reduce the total alkali content associated with the risk of alkali silica reaction. It was found that the relative dynamic modulus of elasticity for the steam-cured recycled concrete met satisfactory criteria after 300 cycles of the freeze-thaw test. However, the volume change of the steam-cured recycled concrete during the freeze-thaw cycles was not negligible. This implies further research required to understand the effect of the volume changes in cold regions.

INTRODUCTION

With the aim of promoting a circular economy, recycled aggregates are being actively used in the construction field ¹⁾. To implement practical uses of recycled aggregates for concrete, many studies have been conducted to clarify the characterization of recycled concrete ²⁻⁶⁾. However, practical uses of recycled aggregates have been still limited for mainly non-structural concrete members. This is partially because they are diverse in quality and cannot always represent a unified idea. Besides, the allowable criteria for the property of recycled aggregate such as impurity amount and physical property are different from country to country. Therefore, it is necessary to accumulate success stories of recycled concrete one by one, while clarifying applicable standards such as the quality of recycled aggregate, properties of other materials used and mix proportions for recycled concrete.

In Japan, recycled aggregate for concrete needs to meet the JIS standard ⁷⁻⁹⁾. It is classified into

Table 1 Oven dry density and water absorption for different grades of recycled aggregates

Grades	Related standard	Oven dry density (g/cm ³)	Water absorption (%)	Recommended application of recycled concrete
High	JIS A5021 ⁷⁾	≥ 2.5	≤ 3	No limitations.
Medium	JIS A5022 ⁸⁾	≥ 2.3	≤ 5	/ No frost attack and drying ^{*1} / Freeze-resistant products ^{*2}
Low	JIS A5023 ⁹⁾	-	≤ 7	/ Nonstructural members ^{*3} / No frost attack environment

*1: Standard products that are no freezing and drying shrinkage resistant, *2: Some conditions need to be satisfied,

*3: For example, backfill concrete and filled concrete that do not require high strength and durability

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three grades of High, Medium and Low according to their quality. Limited properties described in these standards are given in Table 1. Among them, low grade recycled coarse aggregate (LGRA) which is of the lowest quality, provides benefits in terms of environmental impact because of less treatment and energy necessary during its production. However, recycled concrete Class L with LGRA is limited in use and unusable in the environment of freeze-thaw actions. Recently, the use of LGRA has been promoted, and its usage range is expanded to the equivalent application of M grade recycled aggregate (MGRA) if it meets the requirements of the recycled concrete Class M. To do so, low grade recycled coarse aggregate is mixed partially with a natural coarse aggregate that conforms to JIS A5308: Ready mixed concrete ¹⁰⁾. In other words, the corresponding standard of recycled concrete Class M has been revised so that more use of LGRA will be encouraged. Then, it is expected that the application opportunities of LGRA will increase by mixing with natural coarse aggregate. Thus, if recycled concrete with combined use of LGRA and natural aggregate exhibits resistance to frost damage, its application in a snowy cold region will be possible.

In this study, the freeze-thaw resistance of recycled concrete (RC) with combined use of the lowest grade recycled coarse aggregate and natural crushed stone was investigated. The RC was steam-cured with the aim of applying to secondary product concrete such as precast concrete. Furthermore, the blast furnace slag cement was used as the binder to reduce the total alkali content. In this way, the freeze-thaw resistance of the steam-cured recycled concrete made from the lowest quality of recycled aggregate and the slag cement as the binder is investigated in this study.

RESEARCH MATERIALS and METHODS

Materials. Low grade recycled coarse aggregate used in this study was supplied after the demolition of the University building located in the City of Sapporo after about 40 years in service. LGRA was prepared by cutting and crushing concrete waste with a jaw crusher machine so that the maximum particle size (20mm) and the size distribution can follow the JIS A5023 ⁹⁾. The oven dry density and water absorption rate were 2.26g/cm³ and 6.59%, respectively. Natural coarse aggregate is crushed stone of the surface dry density of 2.74g/cm³ and the water absorption rate of 1.04%. Fine aggregate is sand of the surface dry density of 2.75g/cm³ and the water absorption rate of 1.74%, respectively. The recycled coarse aggregate was replaced by 50 % to the total volume of coarse aggregate in the recycled concrete.

Binder is a blast furnace slag cement -type B that conforms to JIS R5211 ¹¹⁾. The reason to use the slag cement is partially due to the countermeasure against the alkali silica reaction as recommended in the corresponding standard. Water reducing and air entrained (AE) agent was used as the chemical admixture to meet the target air contents ranging from 4 to 7 %. Water to cement ratio was 45% and the fine aggregate ratio was 45.5%, respectively.

Pre-curing before steam curing was carried out for 2 hours after mixing, and then the temperature was raised to 50°C over 2 hours in a steam curing tank and held for 3 hours. After that, the temperature naturally decreased. After demolding, the specimens were cured in water until the age of 7 days. Afterwards, the specimens were wrapped in wet cloth in a constant temperature room at 18 to 22°C to prevent the surface from drying out.

Compressive strength test. To confirm strength development before starting the freeze-thaw test, in accordance with JIS A1108 compressive strength tests ¹²⁾ were conducted on cylindrical specimens of the diameter of 10 cm and height of 20 cm at 14 days and 28 days.

Freeze-thaw test. Based on Method A of JIS A 1148 ¹³⁾, which means both freeze and thaw in water, freeze-thaw tests started at an age of 14 days for the recycled concrete and 28 days for

normal concrete, respectively. Temperature in specimen was decreased from 5 °C to -18 °C and then increased from -18 °C to 5 °C during one cycle of 3-hour periods. The freeze-thaw test has completed at 300 cycles. Rectangular shape specimen of 10 cm width, 10 cm height and 40 cm length was tested and periodically the resonance frequency was measured based on JIS A1127¹⁴⁾. A strain gauge was installed inside the center of the specimen. Thus, the expansion and contraction of the recycled concrete during freeze-thaw cycles were monitored.

Microstructure evaluation. To measure the air content and spacing factor in hardened recycled concrete, ASTM C457 based linear traverse method was employed. The cross section of the recycled concrete was carefully polished and then photographed using a high-performance camera and the air bubbles were identified with a special device. In addition, X-ray CT¹⁵⁾ was carried out to visualize the distribution of air bubbles in the hardened mortar. The mortar was prepared by wet screening of the coarse aggregates during fresh state and cured in the same way to concrete. A cube of one side of 2.67 mm of the central region in the mortar specimen was extracted as the volume interest and analyzed. The resolution was 5.33 μm/pixel.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Air content and spacing factor. As given in Table 2, the calculated air contents and spacing factors for hardened concrete are within 3.2 to 3.9 % and less than 200 μm, respectively. The recycled concrete (RCG50) exhibited a relatively large amount of air as compared with the normal concrete (NCG). This may be attributed partially to the fact that the source material for the recycled aggregate was air entrained concrete used in the University building in the cold region. Similarly, the steam curing concrete (-S) resulted in a large amount of air than that of the standard curing concrete (-N). There is a possibility that microcracks were generated due to the temperature increase during steam curing, and it is thought that they were taken into consideration as air content. In any case, it can be said that irrespective recycled aggregate and curing methods, concretes are freeze-thaw resistant based on the standard test.

Figure 1 shows the visualization of air bubble distribution in the hardened mortar by X-ray CT. To a limited extent, it can be visually seen that the bubbles are evenly distributed. In addition, it was considered that the entrained air was introduced properly in the recycled concrete. Furthermore, it seems that there are many bubbles with larger diameters overall.

Freeze-thaw test results. As shown in Table 2, all types of concrete under study completed 300 cycles of freeze - thaw test at more than 90 % of the relative dynamic modulus of elasticity. Thus, these concretes indicated little difference depending on recycled concrete and curing methods. According to JIS A1148¹³⁾, concrete is considered to be frost-resistant if its dynamic modulus of elasticity is 60 % or more after 300 cycles of freeze-thaw tests. This agrees with the air content results mentioned above.

Table 2 Entrained air and RDME after freeze-thaw test

Concrete name ^{*1}	Air content Hardened (%)	Air content Fresh (%) ^{*2}	Spacing factor (μm)	RDME at 300 cycles (%)
NCG-N	3.2	5.7	178	99.1
RCG50-N	3.5	6.2	171	94.4
NCG-S	3.7	6.1	169	91.3
RCG50-S	3.9	5.5	168	98.1

*1: NCG: Normal concrete without recycled aggregate, RCG50: Recycled concrete with replacement of 50 % of recycled coarse aggregate, -N: Standard curing, -S: Steam curing

*2: Aggregate modification coefficients were used for the calculations.

Figure 1. Air bubble distribution visualized by X-ray CT.

Figure 2. Volume change during freeze-thaw cycles.

Volume change during freeze-thaw cycles. Expansion and contraction of the recycled concrete during freeze-thaw cycles were monitored with an embedded strain gauge as shown in Fig.2. Figure 2 also shows the relationship between the internal temperature and strain change of RCG50S. The maximum strain was found to vary between approximately minus 250μ for contraction due to freezing and 300μ for expansion due to thawing. This range of variation cannot be ignored as compared with that of standard-cured ordinary concrete. The internal microstructure of the steam-cured recycled concrete may have loosened and cracked. Nevertheless, this range of stretching behavior was hardly reflected in the relative dynamic modulus results. This may require some precautions as a result of further research.

CONCLUSIONS

The followings were revealed within the scope of this research.

- (1) It can be said that the influence of the lowest quality recycled coarse aggregate on the freeze-thaw behavior of steam-cured recycled concrete is not so significant. One of the reasons may be due to the properly distributed entrained air within the recycled concrete.
- (2) A non-negligible volume change was observed in steam-cured recycled concrete during freeze-thaw cycles. Further studies are required to clarify the effect of this volume change.

This study is limited to understanding the durability against freeze-thaw actions and needs further investigation on other performance such as drying shrinkage in a given condition and alkali silica reaction for longer periods. In addition, it is noted that the impurity amount associated with the recycled aggregate tested in this study is almost none because of being treated and processed in laboratory room.

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From Precast Structures to reusable components: Processing and reconditioning of reclaimed precast concrete elements

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Keywords: building information modelling (BIM), circular construction, digital, precast concrete, reuse, retrofit

This research outlines the processes and methods applied in the ReCreate project for transforming deconstructed precast concrete elements into reusable secondary products. Drawing from real-life pilot projects in four countries, the task was to examine and test procedures for stripping, cleaning, cutting, and retrofitting reclaimed components, such as with new connectors, to meet the requirements of new structural designs. These processes are implemented and evaluated across the project's pilot cases in Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany, using a variety of wall, slab, beam, and column types that were not designed for deconstruction and reuse.

The processing steps include the removal of surface layers such as plaster, paint, wallpaper, adhesives, and wiring, as well as surface cleaning with mechanical and chemical methods. Health, safety, and environmental considerations guide the selection of techniques, including dust control and the responsible handling of solvents and equipment. Refurbishment tasks such as cutting and retrofitting with novel connectors are discussed in terms of digital workflows, leveraging interoperable formats like the IFC, supported by optimization algorithms that solve the optimal cutting problem. The goal is to minimize waste and maximize reuse potential.

Some of the processing tasks were conducted at factory premises or directly on-site, depending on logistical and technical feasibility. Data from pilot projects document the process, from stripping and refurbishment to element handling, protection during transport, and final reuse. The findings demonstrate the viability of converting structural components from existing buildings into re-certified elements for new construction and contribute to scaling reuse within circular construction practices.

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Increasing flexibility in building design with used precast concrete elements by combination with virgin structural concrete, bricks, steel and timber

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Keywords: REUSE, CIRCULAR CONSTRUCTION, BUILDING DESIGN, USED PRECAST CONCRETE, HYBRID CONSTRUCTION, FLEXIBILITY.

ABSTRACT

When designing a building with used precast concrete elements one is presented with structural constraints of said elements primarily due to fixed dimensions. To circumvent these constraints the inclusion of virgin structural elements such as new concrete, bricks, steel or timber is suggested. Each of those materials presents different advantages for the design of buildings that are envisioned to be made primarily from reused concrete elements.

Based on the case study of a planned two-story youth center consisting primarily of used precast concrete elements the application of additional new/virgin structural elements in the design process is laid out. New concrete (containing RC aggregates) is used for the ground plate instead of used precast slabs to facilitate the placement of connections for water, electricity and heating. A layer of bricks is introduced on which the used precast wall elements are placed to increase room height in comparison to the donor building and accommodate for floor insulation and installations for building services. Steel columns and beams allow for the support of used precast ceiling slabs which were originally placed only on wall elements. This hybrid construction method allows for the employment of the used slabs with their relatively short span while enabling the realization of larger spaces than those found in the donor building. Finally, the introduction of load bearing timber stud walls which are constructed on site after the installation of their neighboring used concrete wall elements allows to react to potential variations in measurements due to historic tolerances in the used precast elements. Additionally, the timber stud walls which are not relying on a strict structural grid can absorb irregularities in the placement of the concrete elements and therefor allow for the concrete elements to be placed where they are needed based on the placement of window or door openings.

The combination of used and virgin construction elements doesn't only facilitate the utilization of used precast concrete elements, but it also results in new hybrid structural construction methods that would generally not be utilized in buildings that are planned entirely with virgin construction materials and products.

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Information is key to successful reuse of precast concrete elements

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Keywords: BIM, Information, Concrete, Reuse, Circular economy

ABSTRACT

The reusability of precast concrete elements in new building structures is contingent on the condition and configuration of the elements, as well as the availability of pertinent structural information, such as material properties, joint configurations, and reinforcement detailing. This structural information is especially needed to demonstrate compliance with building regulations of new building structures in which the harvested elements will be reused. In the absence of structural information, conducting structural analyses becomes a challenge. The information on old donor buildings is usually documented and archived as paper design drawings and calculations of the structure and elements. The accessibility of this information is often problematic; if it is available at all, it is often difficult to find. The donor building and the elements themselves can provide some information by carrying out measurements and tests. The latter is also an effective way to complement and/or verify data.

The process of gathering information commences at the stage of preparing the deconstruction of the donor building. In order to ensure the effective and safe execution of deconstruction, it is imperative to ascertain the manner in which the elements are interconnected, how the stability of the donor building is assured, and the weight and size of the elements. It is evident that the process of information gathering is not complete at this juncture. Following the dismantling of the elements, further needed data becomes available, including specific dimensions and types of connectors, as well as the status of these joints. This and subsequent testing for material properties underscores the necessity to establish a correlation between data and discrete elements, a task that necessitates the utilisation of a database. The advantages of integrating existing work processes and databases, such as Building Information Models (BIM) and 3D modelling, are evident. This approach also facilitates the continuous addition of new data, as new information essentially arises throughout the life cycle of precast concrete elements. Furthermore, there is no reason to assume that the application of these elements will be limited to one or two buildings. The reuse of concrete elements is not limited to one cycle, and each instance necessitates the availability of pertinent information.

Further information may be obtained from a variety of perspectives, including but not limited to a) material properties, b) quality inspection of elements, c) changes to elements through refurbishment and/or strengthening and d) damage repair of elements. These aspects constitute an integral component of the ReCreate initiative, with the overarching objective of fostering the widespread adoption of precast concrete elements within contemporary construction practices, thereby catalysing the transition from a linear to a circular economy.

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Informing Building Concept Design with Circular Economy Principles: State-of-the-Art

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Keywords: adaptability, building reuse, circular building design, circular built environment, circular economy design tool, circular economy design workflow

ABSTRACT

SDG 12 Responsible Consumption and Production calls for the adoption of sustainable production and consumption patterns as a critical pathway to sustain the livelihood of current and future generations. If the design, building and construction industry is determined to contribute to the achievement of this important goal, practitioners and decision-makers need to change the current approach to building design, based on the linear take-make-dispose model, shifting design thinking and practice in favour of the circular economy (CE).

A circular building is conceived, designed, developed, used, and reused without unnecessary resource depletion, environmental pollution, and ecosystem degradation. It is constructed in an economically responsible way and contributes to the long-lasting well-being of people and the biosphere.

An effective transition to a sustainable built environment implies informing design thinking and supporting decision-making with CE principles from the early stage, as the most impactful phase of the whole design process, vis-à-vis desired functionality, performance, cost, time, aesthetics, and overall sustainability outcomes.

Despite promising advancements characterising the contemporary sustainable design scenario, evidence shows that practitioners still lack integrated frameworks and tools supporting circularity, especially in early-stage decision-making and concept design.

The proposed contribution will illustrate the state-of-the-art of approaches, frameworks, methods and tools supporting circular building design, focusing on the early stage of the process. The authors, targeting a variety of audiences including but not limited to researchers and practitioners, will present the results of a systematic review on the subject, currently being finalised. The goal is to highlight latest advancements for circularity informed decision-making as well as barriers and research gaps in order to facilitate effective design processes, and ultimately mainstream CE strategies and solutions at the building scale.

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Integrating Circular Economy Principles in Building Design: Synergies and Tensions Between Durability, Adaptability, and Design for Disassembly

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Keywords: Adaptability, Building design, Circular economy, Design for Disassembly, Durability, Interdisciplinary design.

The study investigates the interaction of circular economy principles — Durability, Adaptability, and Design for Disassembly — within the context of building design. As the construction sector moves toward more resource-efficient, and circular practices, a deeper understanding of how these principles interrelate is essential to facilitate systemic transformation across the built environment. The study develops a framework for integrating circular economy principles into building design through interdisciplinary collaboration.

The research adopts a dual-methodological approach, combining an extensive literature review with an iterative, design-oriented expert collaboration. This collaboration was conducted through several design workshops and the analysis between them, where design decisions aimed at promoting circular economy principles were critically examined. The collaboration involved experts in building physics, structural engineering, HVAC systems, and architectural design, representing both academic and industry sectors. Central to the study is a hypothetical building design, developed through design workshops, which functions as a testbed for the simultaneous and integrated application of selected circular economy principles. The iterative and multidisciplinary design-oriented collaboration (through which the hypothetical building design is developed) allows for the identification of both synergies and tensions among the circular economy principles, providing a lens through which to assess their real-world applicability.

The research delivers a process-oriented framework of the holistic alignment of circular economy principles in practical building design contexts, enriched with concrete design strategies to guide their integrated application in future construction projects. Findings not only provide actionable knowledge for practitioners and policymakers navigating the complex opportunities of circular construction, but also support future interdisciplinary collaboration and research that approaches circularity in the built environment as a whole — from the durability of individual materials and structures to the adaptability of spaces and the reusability of building components. Yet, it should be noted that the construction phase and contractor involvement were not within the scope of this study, and future research should further address these dimensions to fully encompass the systemic whole.

The findings are relevant also in light of recent legislative developments across Europe — including updated national regulations in Finland — that increasingly emphasize building longevity and reuse.

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Mechanical Interlock System for Reversible Precast Slabs

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Keywords: Circular economy, Demountable connection, Design for disassembly, Hollow core slabs, Interlock mechanism, Precast concrete structures.

ABSTRACT

As sustainability and resource efficiency gain prominence in the construction sector, there is an increasing push for design strategies that enable structural flexibility and promote circularity. Hollow core slabs, commonly used in flooring systems, typically rely on cast-in-place mortar joints or concrete toppings to ensure the slabs work together structurally. However, these conventional methods permanently bond the elements, limiting their potential for disassembly and reuse, and thereby compromising the principles of circular construction. This research proposes an alternative removable connection system using mechanical interlocking steel connectors combined with local reinforcement within the slabs. The solution enables efficient force transfer without the use of cast-in-place materials, enhancing demountability and allowing the recovery and reuse of structural components with minimal damage.

A prototype is presented in Figure 1. It is a metallic element with a total height of 126 mm. The upper portion is cylindrical, with a diameter of 100 mm, while the lower part has a conical shape, narrowing to 57 mm. This bottom section includes openings that function as an interlock system. The device is intended to engage with two 10 mm steel rebars placed inside the slabs, ensuring effective load transfer.

A finite element model was created to represent the slab's behaviour in a two-level building subjected to horizontal wind actions. The simulations were carried out using the ANSYS software package and evaluated the connector's strength and deformation under service and ultimate conditions, and its contribution to overall structural behaviour. An example of the finite element model is shown in Figure 2. The preliminary evaluation of the FEM analysis, Figure 3, fall within a range of promising results that confirm the steel connector combined with localised reinforcement can withstand the applied forces. This supports the feasibility of the proposed system for enabling the reuse of hollow core slabs in circular construction. More operability checks and structural analysis are ongoing to optimise the connection system.

Figure 1. Prototype of connector. Figure 2. Components of FEM. Figure 3. FEM analysis.

On-site reuse of façade products: case studies on the benefits of 1:1 mock-ups

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Keywords: circularity, decision-making, façades, feasibility studies, mock-ups, reuse

1. INTRODUCTION

Uncertainties hindering the reuse of façade products

In accordance with the hierarchy of R-strategies, after façade retention, product reuse will become an important strategy in a resource-conscious (i.e. circular) façade renovation practice. For this, the existing façade forms a primary source of reclaimed products [1]. The process of demounting, reconditioning and reinstalling the products on the same façade is called ‘on-site reuse’. Depending on the type of product, its condition and the expectations, reconditioning might range from cleaning to remanufacturing (i.e. reapplying one of the sub-components in a new product), with or without intermediate transportation and storage [2]. However important, today there are still few examples of reuse of façade products. Research on the Belgian market [3] has shown that even when a façade renovation project has circular ambitions, often they are dropped throughout the study process due to (among others) technical, financial and organizational uncertainties.

Feasibility studies using mock-ups as a potential lever

When it comes to dealing with risks and uncertainties in design decision-making, we can learn from pioneering projects from the past applying novel construction techniques. As an example of a way to deal with this, in 1981 the design team and management contractor of the Lloyds’ building in London organized an iterative mock-up programme with 25 meetings over 2 years. In his book *Lloyds 1:1* [4], Michael Eidenbenz offers insights into the variety of advantages of using one-to-one mock-ups during a pioneering design process. The experimentation process not only informed the client and design team towards decisions through unexpected insights, but also enabled a discussion with external actors, created new questions for the design process, reduced the risks during construction and helped to foster a sense of mutual trust among all collaborators, including the suppliers and façade contractor.

As the complexity and demands of façades have increased, today mock-ups have become a common practice in façade commissioning. Depending on the application, Knight et al. [5] differentiate between off-site laboratory, on-site stand-alone, integrated or detail mock-ups. Depending on the assessment goal, they distinguish aesthetic from functional mock-ups. Despite this possible range of uses, in today’s Belgian context, the authors mainly observe façade mock-ups being used for final design validation, including only minor aesthetic decisions on e.g. colours of the joints. While Pietroforte and Tombesi [6] also focused on the value of physical mock-ups as a verification of field conditions, they also showed how they allow to trigger and capture tacit knowledge of different actors involved. As such, mock-ups could be seen as a means for co-creation, in addition to evaluation. Building on these and other examples, the use of 1:1 mock-ups might be a potential lever to deal with the uncertainties on reusing façade products, as detected by Geboes et al. [7].

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Research goal: exploring the benefits of 1:1 reuse mock-ups

Some key references on reuse in construction include examples of reuse mock-ups. For example, Addis' [1] cases show that mock-ups serve purposes beyond validating performance and aesthetics. Also the cases from the 'Design for Reuse Primer' [8] show glimpses of the use of 1:1 mock-ups as a means for dialogue within an iterative reuse design process. However, as these works mainly focus on the overall reuse process, the benefits of reuse mock-ups remain only implicitly discussed. Therefore, this paper aims to investigate the potential of using full-size mock-ups as a lever to overcome uncertainties hindering the on-site reuse of façade products.

Research method: case study analysis

This paper uses three recent case studies (from Switzerland, Germany and Belgium) which employed mock-ups to study the on-site reuse of façade products. To collect information on the projects, semi-structured interviews were organised with two key actors involved in the study phase. During these interviews we discussed the project goals, the involved actors (and their knowledge) and the role of mock-ups throughout the study phase. By putting the results from each case in its particular context, we aim to provide deeper insights on the benefits, enriching the list of added values from the discussion section.

2. RESULTS: CASE STUDIES

Basler Kantonbank: exposing qualities, developing reconditioning processes

To explore possible improvements on their carbon footprint, in 2019 the Basler Kantonbank asked David Vaner to conduct a feasibility study on the 500 m² of façades of their office building in Basel (Switzerland). These were originally constructed in 1966 and renewed by the same façade contractor Schmidlin in 1994. Although the client asked for comparative renovation strategies including a complete façade renewal, the architect did not make a new design. Instead, he conducted a thorough investigation on the existing façade, exposing qualities and developing extensive reconditioning processes.

From the start of the one-year long feasibility study, the architect involved an advising façade planner and the original façade contractor to study the existing products and explore possibilities for reconditioning. Among others, they studied the cleaning of the aluminium panels and the steel parapet elements, and the refurbishment of the aluminium windows and external aluminium blinds. During the audit, they contacted the technicians from Roto (i.e. the original manufacturer) on the window fittings and hinges to know the exact types, their max. load for reglazing and their availability for punctual replacement. For the blinds, they contacted Schenker (i.e. the original manufacturer) to retrieve the exact RAL-colour and explore the refurbishment options (an idea to which they were not open, yet). At this stage the project team made a mock-up proposal, describing the zone of the façade, the general processes ("cleaning", "possibly re-anodizing", ...) and the questions to be answered (thicker glass possible?, fittings replacement?, ...). Also they made a mock-up planning of five weeks (incl. four weeks glass delivery), starting the next month.

The client was convinced that the early 1:1 mock-up played a central role in the study phase: "Without the findings from the model, the refurbishment would not have been possible." The dismantling immediately provided important insights on the existing construction. For example, the parapet elements proved to be powder coated steel, instead of anodized aluminium, which was previously assumed. Moreover, as they continued over two windows and fully supported them, the parapets could not be removed. Hence, the cleaning of these elements needed to be executed in-situ. The reuse process of the anodized aluminium panels was more extensive: dismantling, numbering, vertical transport to the basement, storage,

scratching (to remove dirt), cleaning agent, rinsing, vertical transport to the right floor level, storage, adding insulation, reinstalling, osmosis rinsing (to remove the dirty fingers of reinstallation) and finally sealer coating. Different cleaning processes were executed on different samples to compare the aesthetic results and verify requirements, e.g. if the cleaning water could be drained in the basement via the public sewerage.

Also one window was refurbished for the mock-up. This included reglazing of both the fixed and opening part, which had different glass fixation concepts. The mock-up process proved that the application of a thinner sealing rubber allowed to install triple glazing and uncovered the necessary renewal of the plastic glass clamps which had become too fragile. In addition, all seals were renewed to increase the airtightness between the fixed and opening parts. Based on this test, the team estimated that two workers could dismantle, refurbish and reinstall 7 windows per day, an important insight for the cost estimation. Finally, a detailed measurement of the groove allowed Roto to find a compatible fittings system for the window. The entire mock-up process allowed to gather knowledge on the existing products, design refurbishment strategies and test their logistical, technical and financial feasibility. To evaluate these aspects, the mock-up phase ended with an on-site discussion between the architect, client, façade contractor and façade planner.

Commerzbank / Hotel Ruby Luna: collecting knowledge, facilitating discussion

The office tower of Commerzbank in Düsseldorf (Germany) was designed by Paul Schneider-Esleben and finished in 1962. Due to its innovative curtain wall façade, constructed by Josef Gartner, the building was protected as heritage in 1998. More specific, the façade is characterized by its 1,7m x 3,1m aluminium sandwich panels with a 3-dimensional shape and round-cornered windows whose production technology originated from the Douglas Aircraft Company. From 2016 until 2021 the building was reconverted into a hotel. To preserve its historic appearance and upgrade its thermal efficiency, thermal comfort and acoustics, the 689 original panels were refurbished. This labour-intensive process consisted of the removal (numbering, dismantling and transporting to the façade contractors workshop), the actual refurbishment (removing windows, separating the two anodised aluminium sheets, removing non-fire resistant insulation, cleaning by hand, adding mineral wool, reassembling the two matching panes, adding a new back-structure, adding new windows, temporary storage at contractors workshop) and reinstallation (adding new mounting system on façade, transporting, installing on same position, adding insulation at interior side).

From the start of the study process the façade engineer from Bollinger+Grohmann advised the client to involve the original façade contractor. Their knowledge on the existing façade (thanks to their extensive project archive) proved crucial to develop the elaborate refurbishment process of the E6/EV1 anodised aluminium panels. Through a workshop with the 80-year-old dr. Fritz Gartner, who collaborated on the Commerzbank project himself at the very start of his career, they designed a first renovation concept. Next, a dismantling test verified the original drawings, showing a thinner cavity than expected. This led to an (expensive) point cloud measurement, uncovering tolerances in the structure of 13 cm, which the refurbished façade would follow. The dismantled panel was used to execute first cleaning tests. After this first mock-up phase, the façade contractor refined the design. Already 6 months after their involvement, they made an off-site corner mock-up which convinced the client of its feasibility and the resulting looks. Its main goal was to discuss the visual results of the cleaned panels and the colour differences between the milled rounded corner connectors and the other aluminium components. The Gartner engineers explain how they are used to these discussions, even for new façades, as colour differences might always occur due to slight changes in alloy or anodization process (i.e. the timing, type of acid or amount of electricity). “In the end, it’s art.” After the discussions at Gartner’s workshop, they integrated the mock-up in the façade, combined with a new glazed plinth, to also be approved by the heritage department. Soon after,

the fire of the Grenfell Tower raised concerns on fire safety of façade insulation, which led to a fire safety test on the mock-up. As a result, the honeycomb insulation of the sandwich panels needed to be replaced by a non-combustible material. Therefore, the contractor tested the removal of the insulation and conducted chemical tests on the glue, but also took the occasion to measure the anodization thickness, before the final design was made. Next to the aesthetic and technical tests, the different mock-ups were also used to develop and test the refurbishment process itself. For this, Gartner has a separate mock-up hall where their most experienced artisans are at work, providing feedback on the safety, efficiency, simplicity and quality of the design. The mock-up process also allowed to capture the knowledge of their fixed partners (which were often previously in-house departments) for transportation, cleaning and surface treatment. After a simplification of the final design by the Bollinger+Grohmann, the client organized a tendering and awarded the works to another contractor. After the engineers expressed doubts on the quality, a renegotiation took place between the client and Josef Gartner, who finally executed the works. Despite several mock-up discussions, the client's expectations still did not fully match the in-situ results, leading it to have additional façade cleaning brought in by another company.

Merlo: assessing feasibility, enthusing actors

At the end of 2020 the social housing company BinHôme launched a competition to, among others, upgrade the energy performance of their 1980s Merlo building. During these works the 310 rental apartments would remain occupied. As a public building owner in Brussels (Belgium) they have the obligation to reach an operational energy target of 150 kWh/m²y by 2040. In addition, they want to create exemplary buildings in terms of circular material use, an effort which is also stimulated by the region. Doing so, they recognize the embodied impact of construction in addition to the operational targets. To stimulate reuse, the project description included (only) two sentences on circularity. These referred to several levels of circularity and the explicit possibility of local reuse of materials from the existing building. More importantly, as the client points out during the interview, the project brief did not demand a new image for the building. As an answer, the architects of V+, CLN and Bureau Bouwtechniek proposed to dismantle, treat and reinstall 6.000 m² of profiled aluminium panels with an existing single-face powder coating in order to insulate the façade. By questioning certain demands throughout the study process (e.g. the need to recoat the panels), even today, the labour-intensive reuse processes become equally or less expensive than façade renewal, strengthening the reuse argumentation. In addition, while exploring the possibilities of the existing panels throughout the mock-up process, their proven technical quality (as they are thicker than new panels) and their aesthetic qualities became respectively appreciated by the client and the architect.

After the competition, the design brief demanded an extensive feasibility study in 2 stages, which took place over a period of 16 months. In addition to using reference projects, most knowledge on the reuse processes was created through three individual mock-ups, each testing different aspects or ideas based on progressive insights. These tests were executed by the same façade contractor, each documented in a report by the executive architect and presented to the entire project team at the end of each phase. The first test involved dismantling and reinstalling some panels to verify if this could be done easily and without damaging them. The second test phase explored possibilities of on-site treatment, in order to avoid transportation and intermediate storage and hence limit the related costs and environmental impact. It proved that cold high-pressure cleaning was too abrasive for the existing powder coating. At this stage two manufacturers were consulted, in particular on pre-treatment processes before (re)coating the aluminium panels. This led, among others, to the suggestion of a 'cross-cut' test, a simple but effective coating adherence test.

A third mock-up phase, which took place in parallel with the preliminary design, was used to study different aspects of inverting the aluminium panels, showing their uncoated back to front.

To evaluate the aesthetics, the mock-up was spread across different sides of a rooftop volume. Based on this, the architects refused this option based on a lack of uniformity and what they called a ‘tin-can-like appearance’. As the aging of the aluminium might increase the uniformity and reduce the shiny appearance, these aspects of the mock-up were re-evaluated after 6 months (including a winter period), but with unsatisfactory results. The mock-up report also discussed the watertightness of the joints, the fixation, the safety and the ease of processing, but also defined new questions to be investigated such as the influence of a cavity between insulation and aluminium on dotted corrosion. According to the architect, one of the more challenging aspects was the cost estimate. As the mock-up contractor did not want to provide this (for unspecified reasons related to other projects), offers were asked to other façade contractors, using the mock-up reports as a lever to convince them of the feasibility. Finally, other crucial elements of the feasibility studies were the implementation planning and the compatibility of the logistics with continuous occupation of the appartements. These benefitted indirectly from the mock-up processes through insights from the contractor.

3. DISCUSSION: BENEFITS OF 1:1 REUSE MOCK-UPS

In all three case studies, the early 1:1 mock-up programs on in-situ reuse processes were conceived as experiments to learn from. In addition to the project partners, they involved other actors such as the (original) façade contractor, subcontractors, manufacturers, or experienced colleagues. By facilitating a discussion and knowledge exchange between these different actors, the mock-ups allowed to:

1. gather detailed knowledge on existing products and construction techniques, to the level of every material finishing and connection;
2. develop possible reuse strategies for complex façade products, including non-conventional cleaning, refurbishment or remanufacturing processes;
3. assess the feasibility of reuse strategies on different aspects:
 - financial: testing the entire implementation procedure allows to make a more detailed cost estimation (e.g. based on insights on implementation time of certain processes) and reduce the uncertainty margins;
 - technical: tests on individual samples and/or full-size mock-ups allow to evaluate different technical criteria before and after reconditioning (e.g. durability of finishings, fire safety, water tightness, etc);
 - logistical: testing the practical feasibility of the dismantling, transportation, storage and reconditioning allows to verify the availability of (local) craftspeople with the right expertise and tools, but might also lead to lessons on how to organise the process for subsequent implementation;
 - aesthetics: a transparent conversation on visual expectations could help to avoid discussions during the implementation. Without these discussions, mock-up results might create false expectations and hence be misleading. For example, the average result of a final cleaning or refurbishing process might differ from the aesthetics of a mock-up due to an above-average condition of the mock-up sample or increased effort (to convince the project team) and skill of the artisan executing the mock-up. For the same reasons, also the other aspects (e.g. the timing and hence the costs) might differ between the mock-up stage and the final implementation, as observed in some case studies. In addition, the heterogeneity of the results (due to different labourers, existing patina, etc.) should be discussed, as they might be difficult to interpret based on a limited amount of mock-up samples;
4. inform contractors and prove the feasibility of the developed reuse processes during the site visits of the tendering phase. Mock-ups might also help to enthuse other project partners or colleagues within the same firm on renovation and reuse;

5. build mutual trust between possible future collaborators (clients, architects, façade engineers, contractors, manufacturers, ...) which is key for collaboration.

While the project team clearly benefits from the contractor's knowledge during the study phase (among others, to make a cost estimation), also the contractor is likely to benefit from this. For example, their employees acquire handling skills (i.e. tacit knowledge) which they might valorise during the actual implementation. Also, the experience from the mock-up might allow them to make a better cost estimation for their offer. The overall cost-benefit balance for each actor influences who pays what during the mock-up programs, and depends (among others) on the overall procurement strategy.

4. CONCLUSION: MOCK-UPS CAN BE MORE THAN REALITY CHECKS

The three case studies showed a range of benefits of full-scale mock-ups beyond their general use as reality checks (i.e. the final validation of a façade renovation strategy). First, the mock-ups allowed to reduce technical uncertainties on the existing and reconditioned products by gathering knowledge from different actors and executing tests. Second, they reduced financial uncertainties by informing cost estimates on unconventional dismantling and reconditioning processes. Third, aesthetic uncertainties could be dealt with by facilitating transparent discussions on expectations, but pitfalls were detected concerning both the average result and the overall heterogeneity. Fourth, the mock-up programs could reduce the procedural uncertainties (i.e. who does what, when?) on the final implementation by allowing for more unpredictability during the study phase. Indeed, on the one hand, the mock-ups allowed to develop and assess clear reuse processes and the actors involved. On the other hand, the experimental nature of the mock-up processes themselves (based on progressive insights) included a certain range of unpredictability during the study phase. To conclude, when conceived as experimental co-creation processes instead of one-shot validation tests, 1:1 mock-ups have several potential benefits in reuse processes of façade products.

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Recycled Quarry Sludge as a Sustainable Approach for Mitigating Alkali-Silica Reaction in Aggregates from İstanbul

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Abstract

Alkali-silica reaction (ASR) remains a significant durability issue for concrete structures in regions where reactive aggregates are used. On the European side of İstanbul, sandstone aggregates derived from the Thrace Formation have been widely used in infrastructure projects, yet they exhibit high ASR potential. This study proposes a localized and circular solution by valorizing the sludge waste generated from fine aggregate washing processes at the same quarry site in the Cendere region. The aim is to assess whether this sludge, previously identified as a viable supplementary cementitious material (SCM), can also serve as an effective ASR mitigation agent when used with the reactive aggregates from the same geological source.

The sludge waste, rich in clay and silt-sized particles, was dried and calcined at 800 °C for 2 hours to activate its pozzolanic potential. Mineralogical characterization by XRD revealed the presence of clinocllore, muscovite, albite, and calcite in the raw sludge. Thermal analysis confirmed major structural transformations in the 500–800 °C range. Mortar mixtures were prepared by replacing 20 wt.% of Portland cement with calcined sludge. ASR expansion tests were performed in accordance with ASTM C1260 using reactive aggregates from the same quarry.

The reference mortar exhibited an expansion of over 0.30% at 28 days, indicating high ASR susceptibility. In contrast, the sludge-containing mixture showed significantly reduced expansion, reaching only 0.12% at 28 days—well below the ASTM-defined deleterious limit. Petrographic analysis supported these findings, revealing a clear reduction in ASR gel formation and absence of visible cracking in quartz grains or lithic fragments. Gels in the treated mortars were sparse, micron-sized, and confined to the binder matrix.

These results demonstrate that thermally activated sludge waste can simultaneously serve as a cement substitute and ASR mitigation agent. The study provides a site-specific approach that couples a known SCM with a known reactive aggregate, enhancing concrete durability while promoting sustainable waste reuse within the same production environment.

Keywords: Alkali-silica reaction (ASR), calcined sludge, circular construction, pozzolanic activity, supplementary cementitious materials (SCM).

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1. Introduction

In megacities such as İstanbul, the demand for high-quality construction materials has significantly increased due to the development of new urban areas and the need for earthquake-resistant urban transformation projects. In this context, the quality of aggregates used in the production of durable and long-lasting concrete is of utmost importance. On the European side of İstanbul, crushed aggregates derived from the sandstone-dominated Thrace Formation are commonly utilized in ready-mixed concrete and infrastructure projects.

Since aggregates derived from the sandstone-dominated Thrace Formation—particularly those quarried in the Cendere region—are widely used in İstanbul’s infrastructure and exhibit a high risk of alkali-silica reaction (ASR), it is crucial to evaluate mitigation strategies specific to this geological source. According to accelerated expansion tests conducted in accordance with ASTM C1260, aggregates obtained from a quarry located in the Cendere region of İstanbul exhibit expansion values exceeding 0.30% after 28 days, indicating a high risk for alkali-silica reaction (ASR).

During the aggregate production processes in the Cendere region, clayey-silty sludge waste is generated as a by-product, especially from the washing of fine fractions (<4 mm). These wastes are typically disposed of or stockpiled in open areas. However, recent studies have demonstrated that these wastes can be valorized in the production of construction materials. For instance, Ozkan and Kabay (2022) produced sintered lightweight aggregates by mixing sludge waste with GGBFS and reported satisfactory physical and mechanical properties in the final aggregates. Ozkan et al. (2022) further demonstrated that both cold-bonded and sintered sludge-based aggregates could be successfully used in structural concrete without significant strength loss. Bilici et al. (2023) confirmed the chemical suitability of sludge as a secondary precursor in alkali-activated slag systems. Avci et al. (2022) highlighted that the same sludge waste may undergo significant expansion under thermal conditions, indicating its structural transformation potential.

The use of pozzolanic supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) such as fly ash, slag, metakaolin, and silica fume is one of the most effective strategies for controlling alkali-silica reaction (ASR). These materials have been shown to reduce the concentration of alkali ions (Na^+ , K^+ , OH^-) in the pore solution and limit their interaction with reactive silica, thus suppressing ASR expansion (Figueira et al., 2019; Tapas et al., 2021). Moreover, SCMs enhance the alkali-binding capacity of calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) phases, which further contributes to ASR mitigation (Chappex & Scrivener, 2012a). Certain aluminum-rich SCMs can also reduce the solubility of amorphous silica, thereby inhibiting ASR through alternative mechanisms (Chappex & Scrivener, 2012b; Jin et al., 2024).

Although several studies have explored the valorization of sludge waste from the Cendere region in İstanbul, their focus has primarily been on mechanical and environmental performance. For instance, Miyan et al. (2024) demonstrated that calcined sludge waste could achieve over 75% of the control mortar strength at 28 days when used as a partial cement replacement. Similarly, Bilici et al. (2023) reported satisfactory strength development in alkali-activated slag systems containing the same material. While these findings confirm the material’s viability as a pozzolanic SCM, neither study addressed its potential to mitigate ASR—a critical durability issue in aggregates derived from İstanbul’s Thrace Formation.

In this study, clayey-silty sludge waste generated during aggregate washing operations was thermally activated at 800 °C for 2 hours and used to replace 20% of Portland cement by weight in mortar mixtures. The ASR mitigation performance of the calcined sludge was evaluated using accelerated expansion tests in accordance with ASTM C1260. The results highlight the potential of this local industrial waste to serve not only as a sustainable SCM but also as an effective strategy for enhancing the durability of concrete incorporating ASR-

susceptible aggregates. This site-specific, circular approach aims to address both environmental and performance-based challenges in concrete production.

2. Materials and Methods

The reactive fine aggregate and sludge waste used in this study were obtained from an aggregate quarry in the Cendere region of İstanbul. The clayey-silty sludge was first dried under ambient conditions and then calcined at 800 °C. The heating rate was set at 10 °C/min, and the material was held at the target temperature for 2 hours before being cooled inside the furnace.

Thermal analysis of the untreated sludge waste was performed using simultaneous differential thermal analysis and thermogravimetric analysis (DTA-TG). Approximately 20 mg of dried powder was placed in an alumina crucible and heated from 20 °C to 1100 °C at a constant rate of 10 °C/min under a continuous flow of nitrogen gas.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed prior to calcination to determine the mineralogical composition of the sludge. Measurements were conducted using a Panalytical X'Pert Pro instrument with a Cu anode, scanning in the 2θ range of 5° to 70°.

The particle size distribution (PSD) of the sludge waste was measured using a Mastersizer Hydro 3000 laser diffraction analyzer. Prior to analysis, the samples were dispersed in isopropyl alcohol (IPA) to prevent agglomeration and ensure stable suspension.

Two mortar mixtures were designed for this study: one with 100% cement (Ref-MB) and the other with 20 wt.% of the cement replaced by calcined sludge waste (SCM-MB). Both mixtures used the same reactive aggregate and followed identical procedures. The detailed composition of each mix is presented in Table 1.

To assess ASR performance, mortar bars were prepared in accordance with ASTM C1260. All mixes had a constant binder content and a water-to-binder ratio of 0.47. In the experimental series, 20% of the Portland cement was replaced by weight with calcined sludge. All mixes used the same reactive aggregate. The mortar bars were cured for 24 hours and then immersed in 1M NaOH solution at 80 °C for 28 days. Expansion measurements were taken at 7, 14, and 28 days using four replicate specimens.

Thin sections were also prepared from both reference and SCM-containing mortars to observe ASR gel formation at the microstructural level. These sections were analyzed under a polarizing microscope.

Table 1: Mix design and properties of mortar bar specimens.

Mixture ID	Binder Type	Cement Type	Description
Ref-MB	100% Cement	CEM I	Reference mortar bar
SCM-MB	80% Cement + 20% Calcined Sludge	CEM I	SCM-added mortar bar

3. Results and Discussion

The chemical composition of the sludge waste used in this study has been previously reported by Avcı et al. (2022), based on samples collected from the same washing sludge source in the Cendere quarry. The XRF analysis showed high contents of SiO₂ (53.35 wt.%), Al₂O₃ (17.84 wt.%), and Fe₂O₃ (7.66 wt.%), with moderate levels of CaO (3.57 wt.%) and MgO (3.69 wt.%). The total alkali content (Na₂O + K₂O) was 4.45 wt.%, and the loss on ignition (LOI) was 7.66 wt.%, indicating the presence of both reactive oxides and volatiles suitable for thermal activation. Similarly, Miyan et al. (2024) reported comparable oxide compositions for

sludge waste derived from the same geological formation, confirming its potential as a pozzolanic material after calcination.

A major endothermic peak is observed between approximately 500 °C and 800 °C, accompanied by a significant mass loss (Figure 1). This thermal event is attributed to the dehydroxylation and breakdown of clay minerals such as muscovite and clinocllore, which are present in the untreated material as confirmed by previous XRD analysis. The absence of any further pronounced thermal activity beyond 800 °C suggests that the structural transformation is largely completed by this point. Therefore, calcination at 800 °C was considered sufficient to induce the formation of amorphous phases, which are potentially reactive in cementitious environments.

Figure 1: DTA-TG curve of raw sludge waste

The results of ASTM C1260 tests revealed that the reference mortars exhibited expansion values exceeding 0.30% at 28 days, indicating high ASR risk. In contrast, mortars containing 20% calcined sludge showed significantly reduced expansion, reaching only 0.12% at 28 days. These findings confirm the ASR mitigation capability of the calcined sludge (Figure 2).

The particle size distribution of the sludge waste before calcination confirms its fine-grained nature. The median particle size (D_{v50}) was 11.17 μm , with D_{v10} and D_{v90} values of 2.03 μm and 55.79 μm , respectively, indicating that 90% of the particles were below 56 μm . The specific surface area was calculated as 434.1 m^2/kg .

Figure 2: Expansion rates of mortar bars (R-MB: Reference mortar bar, SCM-MB: Calcined sludge containing mortar bar).

The pozzolanic reactivity of the sludge waste used in this study has been previously confirmed by Miyan et al. (2024), who applied Frattini testing to the same material and reported clear pozzolanic behavior after calcination. The ASR mitigation observed here is thus consistent with the chemically verified reactivity of this sludge waste.

The effectiveness of this mitigation is attributed to the pozzolanic reactivity developed through calcination. XRD analysis revealed that the raw sludge contained clinocllore, muscovite, albite, and calcite (Figure 3). Previous studies have shown that calcination of such aluminosilicate phases within the 700–900 °C range leads to partial amorphization and enhanced pozzolanicity (Fernandez et al., 2011; Ferreiro et al., 2019; Chang et al., 2022). This pozzolanic behavior promotes secondary C-S-H and C-A-S-H formation by reacting with portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), thereby densifying the matrix and reducing pore solution alkalinity.

Additionally, calcined alumina-bearing phases from muscovite and clinocllore can bind alkali ions and participate in the formation of Al-incorporated C-A-S-H gels, thus contributing to ASR suppression by both chemical and physical means (Chappex & Scrivener, 2012b; Chang et al., 2022).

Figure 3: XRD pattern of sludge waste (Q:Quartz, Clc: Clinocllore, Ms: Muscovite, Cal: Calcite, Ab: Albite)

Petrographic analyses provided further evidence of ASR mitigation. In reference mortars, ASR gels were predominantly observed in the binder phase, with gel accumulations reaching up to millimeter scale. In contrast, SCM-containing mortars exhibited only sparse and micron-scale gel formations. Importantly, no visible cracking was observed in quartz grains or rock fragments in either series. The localization of gels within the binder matrix suggests that the calcined sludge limited the progression of ASR by suppressing ion mobility and silica dissolution early in the reaction process (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Thin sections of the mortar bars (a: reference mortar bar, Plane-Polarized Light (PPL); b: reference mortar bar, Cross-Polarized Light (XPL); c: calcined sludge containing mortar bar, PPL; d: calcined sludge containing mortar bar, XPL)

These results indicate that calcined sludge waste can serve as an effective SCM for mitigating ASR in reactive aggregates. This approach not only prevents the disposal of quarry waste but also enhances the durability of concrete through a locally sourced, circular solution.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrated that sludge waste generated during aggregate production in the Cendere region of İstanbul can be effectively valorized through thermal activation and used as a partial cement replacement in mortar mixtures containing ASR-susceptible aggregates. Upon calcination at 800 °C for 2 hours, the sludge material contributed to a substantial reduction in expansion values, lowering the 28-day ASR expansion from over 0.30% in reference mortars to 0.12% in the sludge-containing series.

Petrographic analysis confirmed this mitigation effect by revealing a marked reduction in ASR gel formation and an absence of visible cracking in both quartz grains and lithic fragments. The gels observed in sludge-containing mortars were sparse and limited to micron-scale regions within the binder matrix.

These findings highlight the dual benefit of using calcined sludge waste not only as a supplementary cementitious material, as previously demonstrated in other studies, but also as an effective agent for ASR mitigation. The proposed approach offers a localized and practical solution that promotes both durability and circular construction practices in regions where reactive aggregates and sludge waste co-exist.

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Adaptive re-use for ex-Soviet mass housing: open building strategies for a new housing demand in post-war Ukraine

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Keywords: Housing Demand, European Green Deal, Prefab Concrete Systems, Adaptive reuse, Design for adaptability (DfA), Open Building

ABSTRACT

Once the conflict has ends, Ukraine's reconstruction will require extensive regeneration of its surviving buildings and urban areas. This process must meet a significant housing demand not only from displaced residents but also from newcomers attracted by the country's expected social and economic development. Ideally, this urban and environmental renewal should follow Circular Economy principles, aligning with EU policies risen to face the urgent ecological crisis, meeting the standards and goals of the European Green Deal.

The reuse of undamaged or repairable buildings is seen as a strategy to reduce demolition, materials needs, reduce emissions, while preserving urban identity that communities value. A large share of Ukraine's housing stock originates from the Soviet era, marked by modernist-functional principles. A large portion of this building stock was developed using prefabricated concrete systems and large-scale settlement models. These approaches have often shown functional, environmental, and technological shortcomings and are prone to early obsolescence. This architectural legacy, which still defines much of the Ukrainian urban landscape, requires upgrades in both performance and architectural quality.

This paper presents the results of an ongoing research project focused on the reuse of the II-57 building series, constructed between 1971 and 1978 in the Saltivka district of Kharkiv. The research goal is to develop a catalogue of design strategies of "reuse" focused on the circular principles of "design for adaptability" and "design for disassembly" applicable at different scales and levels of complexity, testing their effectiveness through design experiments on real case studies. Although tailored to the II-57 typology, the proposed approach may also be extended to other precast concrete housing types found across Ukraine.

This ongoing research project carried out between the School of Architecture and Design of Camerino the National PhD Programme in Scientific, Technological and Social Methods Enabling Circular Economy carried by the University of Padua,

proposes a methodology based on the principles of Open Building applied to the reuse of the II-57 building series. The concept of Open Building was theorized by N.J. Habraken in the 1960s as a response to the early decline of mass housing built across Western Europe during the post-World War II reconstruction. Despite the typological and technological rigidity of prefabricated concrete systems, Habraken's theory recognizes the systemic nature of these constructions as a valuable feature that enables targeted interventions on specific subsystems, functional reorganization of interior spaces, and substantial improvements in energy and environmental performance.

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Reuse-oriented Infrastructure Management Plan: A Reinforced Concrete T-beam Bridge Case Study

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Keywords: component reuse, bridge management, plan optimization, sensitivity analysis.

ABSTRACT

Traditional infrastructure management aims to maximize the use of components within their existing service life, resulting in aged components becoming waste. These components can be reused in other structures to extend their service life and enhance circularity. This study addresses the limitations of existing research, which focuses mainly on preventive maintenance and reactive repair or replacement after severe damage, by emphasizing proactive replacement and considering the second service life of components.

In this paper, we build upon traditional bridge maintenance plans and conduct a comparative analysis of the economic and environmental benefits by considering the extra costs and carbon emissions associated with replacing components, as well as the savings incurred from the components' second lifecycle. The case study focuses on an existing reinforced concrete T-beam bridge, the Colorado Highway Bridge L-18-BG. It considers the corrosion of reinforcing steel over time and the consequent reduction in its tensile strength. The objective is to minimize total costs and carbon emissions while ensuring structural safety. The study develops dynamic replacement plan optimization and compares the generated optimal plans with other standard maintenance strategies, including enlarging section method, pasting steel plate method, and pasting carbon fiber method, exploring the impacts of replacement frequency, timing, and ultimate service life of bridge on optimization results. A sensitivity analysis investigates the impact of the time value of money, the calculation methods for the benefits of the component's second lifecycle, and the extra costs of different replacement processes on the final benefits of replacement.

The results demonstrate that considering the components' second lifecycle benefits, proactive replacement can extend the existing structure's lifespan while reducing total costs and carbon emissions. Combining repair with replacement can further enhance these benefits, depending on a suitable optimization problem setting. However, the economic benefits are highly sensitive to the time value of money, the reuse pathways for second-hand components, and the technology of component dismantlement. Future benefits from component replacement will depend on the market acceptance of second-hand components and the development of a robust market for trading these components. This, in turn, is likely to enhance the mechanisms for assessing second-hand components and promote a positive feedback loop, advancing a circular economy in infrastructure management.

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Scaling Circularity in Architecture: From Digital Tools to Built Realities

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Keywords: circular design, digital tools, interior reuse, large-scale reuse, material flows

The transition to a circular built environment demands not only a shift in material practices but also systemic innovation across architectural workflows. This contribution presents White Arkitekter's evolving approach to circular architecture, combining custom-developed digital tools, targeted reuse strategies, and built projects that model scalable reuse implementation.

A central innovation is ReCapture, a proprietary digital method that transforms the reuse process from static documentation into an integrated design workflow. ReCapture allows reuse inventories to be conducted directly within 3D models using a combination of point cloud scanning, BIM, and expert analysis. This creates a data-rich, visual catalogue of reusable elements—accessible across all planning phases and stakeholders. ReCapture not only documents quantities and qualities of building components but embeds traceable material data into the design process, linking potential reuse directly with spatial and architectural decision-making. This method has been successfully implemented in projects such as Läkarhuset in Stockholm, where early-phase reuse inventories using ReCapture informed design priorities and facilitated dialogue between demolition planning, client ambitions, and architectural intent.

Complementing these tool-driven approaches, our experience with built projects such as LUMI in Uppsala—one of Sweden's most ambitious realized reuse initiatives—demonstrates that large-scale material reuse is achievable through collaborative processes and strategic sourcing. Though developed without ReCapture, LUMI exemplifies the environmental, aesthetic, and narrative potential of architectural reuse when embraced from project inception.

On a finer scale, interior architecture projects such as the office for Higab in Gothenburg explore circularity through reclaimed furniture and custom components, showing how design intent can be grounded in ecological ethics even at the detail level.

Together, these projects show how architects can act as enablers of circular transformation: developing digital tools, advocating material continuity, and constructing built environments where reuse is not a constraint but a creative resource. By embedding reuse potential into the earliest design phases and ensuring its traceability throughout construction, our work provides a replicable blueprint for integrating circularity into mainstream practice.

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Short-Loop Circularity Solutions in Academic Workplace Changes

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Keywords: academic workplace adaptation, reuse, shared use, short-loop circular design, reconfiguration, spatial layout analysis

ABSTRACT

This paper investigates short-loop circularity solutions in academic workplace transformations, focusing on both reuse and shared use perspectives. In line with global trends, knowledge-intensive organizations have been downsizing their rented office spaces to enhance efficiency while striving for the effectiveness of newly implemented solutions. Office buildings are typically structurally adaptable, allowing for layout modification to accommodate changing user-needs in a short cycle.

This study posits that reusing (i.e., refurbishing) existing layouts without altering non-load-bearing walls can reduce material waste. In the post-pandemic context, office spaces must support increasingly diverse user activities, which potentially can be facilitated through various shared use strategies aimed also at optimizing layout utilization.

The study has a twofold objective in examining transitions from one office configuration to another. First, it compares workplace layouts before and after refurbishment to assess the extent of layout reuse and nature of any modifications. Second, it evaluates the refurbished layout in relation to the previous spatial solution used by the same user group(s), to identify potential changes in activities and the degree of shared use of the premises.

This paper compares three organizational units within a case faculty, operating across two campuses in the same city. Each unit has recently relocated to new premises in two separate buildings. Each workplace change entailed also institutional incentives aimed at reducing rented office space and promoting more efficient spatial utilization.

The data for this study consists of office layouts drawings in CAD format. The analysis was conducted using ArchiCAD and Excel, employing descriptive statistical analysis. The analysis consists of two stages. First, the extent of refurbishments, measured as e.g. changes to non-load-bearing walls, are compared before and after refurbishment. Second, the office layouts of the units' original buildings are compared with those of the refurbished buildings, focusing on metrics such as the gross-net ratio, types and variety of workspaces, and the number of spaces in shared use.

The findings explore how office layouts have been adapted, with particular attention to reuse and shared use. The results indicate that the layouts have undergone significant adaptation, incorporating both reuse strategies and shared-use models. Despite notable differences among the units within the same organization, the study illustrates the potential for short-loop circulation in office layout design across the three sub-cases. While this paper focuses on academic contexts, the insights gained are applicable to workspace adaptations more broadly.

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Slashing the Burden: Inductive ethnographic observation followed by deductive surveys, towards an initial proposal for a Stadium focused carbon reduction and circularity design toolkit

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Keywords: Carbon Reduction, Circular Economy, Design Tools, Stadium Design.

ABSTRACT

The construction industry contributes over 39% of carbon emissions, almost 50% of raw materials and 62% of waste worldwide, making it a key contributor to the climate crisis. Existing stadium benchmark data indicates the stadium building as the most carbon-intensive typology, estimating construction stage embodied carbon ranging 3000-5000 kgCO₂-eq/m², primarily due to its semi-external nature, increasingly extreme climatic conditions related to user comfort, low usage and enormous spectator draw. With over 30 stadia under construction in the Middle East alone, the circularity and materials carbon intensity of this building typology is critical to address.

Without a bespoke stadium carbon reduction or circularity design tool in existence, this paper draws upon general building classifications to reveal current UK industry sustainability, decarbonisation and circularity design guides, assessments and toolkits, to inform a proposed design approach for the stadium building.

The research method comprises a three-phase approach. Phase 1 begins with qualitative inductive ethnographic observation to facilitate immersion within building design professional practice, industry or government think tanks and principal construction industry sustainability exhibitions within the UK. This aimed at deciphering the key building design sustainability, decarbonisation and circularity guides used in industry whilst identifying their limitations as viewed in industry. Following, phase 2 proceeds to conduct a quantitative and qualitative deductive study using structured cross-sectional surveys targeted at elite sustainability and stadium-focused design professionals to assess the relevance, efficacy and constraints of the observed sustainability toolkits. Advancing, to use statistical and thematic analysis to corroborate the phase 1 theory and reveal stadium professional opinion related to industry toolkits applied to the stadium-specific use category. Phase 3 conducts a desktop study to map the findings from the previous phases into 4 classification sets: the RIBA Plan of Work application framework; tool typologies; decarbonisation or circularity building design aspects; and navigation interface methods. This stage uses thematic analysis to interpret data results attributed to efficacy and limitations pertaining to stadium buildings, to inform a proposed preliminary bespoke stadium decarbonisation and circularity design toolkit.

This investigation provides new knowledge towards facilitating carbon reduction and circularity of stadia buildings by industry designers, through the compilation and development of a proposed bespoke baseline toolkit. The following outputs are developed: 1) a categorisation of the design support tools used for design sustainability, decarbonisation and circularity of the stadium per design phase and per design aspect, and 2) a mapping of design tools organised in families according to tool purpose. Recommendations are included for the expansion of RIBA in-use stage 7 to correspond with the new Net Zero Building Standard to facilitate more regular assessments during the stadium operational stage which require

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specialist design input, as well as a new RIBA end-of-life stage 8 to facilitate disassembly and reuse for circularity promotion.

Conclusions draw upon numerous opportunities for further research towards the development of the baseline stadium design decarbonisation and circularity toolkit.

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Steel cylinder connectors for reversible precast concrete floors: the CCN case study

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Keywords: Demountable connections, Diaphragm behaviour, Innovative design strategy, Precast Concrete Floors.

Abstract. A comprehensive remodelled design strategy has been applied to transform the *Prinsenhof* office building, a structure which had become outdated, into the Circular Centre Netherlands (CCN), a new representative structure for circular construction. The entire project is part of the ReCreate research programme, which is aimed at fostering knowledge about reuse and circularity in the built environment. The new design approach looks at temporary facilities, such as a mock-up and the Inspiration Pavilion, which will be built to provide a realistic representation of the final design of the main building, to assess the construction process and design details, as well as, to facilitate visitors and stakeholders to explore the site and the innovation behind it. The main building of the CCN and all the collateral structures will consist entirely of refurbished façade elements and hollow core slabs (HCSs) from the same donor building. The study represents a further advancement within the research investigation on demountable connections, to showcase a practical solution adopted to connect reclaimed HCSs to achieve a monolithic floor behaviour. The solution proposed herein is specifically designed and developed to meet the requirements of the CCN pilot project. Combined steel cylinders and threaded rebars will assure the diaphragm action on floors against horizontal actions. Preliminary results and remarks from the Finite Element Model (FEM) analysis of the connection system are reported.

1 Introduction

One of the primary objectives in the ReCreate project is to generate knowledge about the deconstruction process of precast concrete components from six existing donor structures originally slated for demolition [1]. Each of the six real-world deconstruction projects serves as a method for acquiring hands-on experience relevant to the learning process concerning the recovery and reuse of precast concrete components. The building stock comprises apartment buildings, offices, and industrial buildings, located in the project partner's countries, offering various possibilities to deal with different typologies and needs [2]. The selected donor building in the Netherlands was the *Prinsenhof* office building, particularly suited for deconstruction and reuse because of its rather simple structural design and high repetition of precast concrete elements. The structure scheme was the same for each floor, and the number of different types of precast elements was limited to load-bearing façade elements, floor slabs and precast concrete inner walls (**Figure 1**). The well-preserved state of the entire structure enables the extensive reuse of its structural components as new elements. Specifically, the refurbishing process for hollow-core slabs covered visual inspection for damage detection and geometry deviations. Additionally, dimension adjustments have been made to reduce the original span from 13 meters to 10.8 meters. The sawing works to adapt the span of HCS are assured using a workbench specifically designed to shorten the element at both ends simultaneously. A strategic arrangement for the entire dismantling, refurbishing, and storage phases allows for an

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efficient use of space at the main site, and a well-planned logistics has been used to reduce risks, minimise costs, and enhance the overall quality check of the project.

Figure 1. Prinsenhof donor building (a) to the CCN pilot project (b).

The scope is to design a novel connection system to allow precast concrete structures to be demountable and adaptable without sacrificing safety or quality, ensuring elements can be removed and reused efficiently with minimal material waste. To date, a substantial number of studies and technical insights have been consolidated in an attempt to identify design methodologies and strategies that facilitate the implementation of selective demolition and design for deconstruction (DfD) [3][4]. In this framework, the mock-up design with demountable connections will serve as a development stage for a practical demonstration of limits and opportunities. It consists of a two-floor building with a total plan surface of 10.8 m x 22.8 m, which will be covered using nineteen HCSs with a width of 1.2 meters. To facilitate the connection of the slabs to each other and secure the entire floor along the perimeter, a double system of tension ties and cylindrical steel connectors will be used. The connection system has been designed with the intention of ensuring the horizontal load transfer, e.g. due to wind loads, so as not to use grouting materials in the interest of reversibility of both the connectors and precast components. The connection herein analysed is specifically adapted for the pilot project as part of an effort to evaluate the structural behaviour of the cylinder connection system already under evaluation [5][6]. The cylinder is designed to work as a dowel-type shear connector applied in the longitudinal joints between adjacent HCS to transfer horizontal shear forces. At the same time, peripheral chords anchored on external cylinders will run in the transversal direction to ensure the diaphragm behaviour of the floor (**Figure 2b**).

Figure 2. Mock-up (a) and its plan view with connection scheme (b).

Once the slabs are set in their intended layout within the new structure, the dowel positioning process begins by drilling a bedding hole across the longitudinal joints between two slabs, and in the middle of the slabs for the peripheral chord, matching the dowel's diameter. One of the

specific issues related to elements coming from *Prinsenhof* is the presence of the original concrete topping, which, due to the strong quality of the mortar, is an integral part of the slabs. The necessity to incorporate the topping layer has turned into a benefit, considering this thickness useful for cylinders and rebars' settlement.

2 Conceptual design

Dimensions and geometry of cylinders have been established by previous research studies [5][6] according to the specific requirements of the connection system [7]. The study will examine the cylinder designed for peripheral chord application, aiming to simulate the structural response under an applied tensile force of 71 kN in the chord. This value has been determined based on the floor system's reaction to horizontal wind loads, as outlined in the mock-up design. In this configuration, the cylinder sticks out 35 mm above the floor, and the rebar is connected to the cylinder with a washer. In this particular application, the wall thickness of the cylinder has been adjusted to 10 mm, as opposed to the 6 mm thickness used for cylinders in the longitudinal joints. The chord to be effective is dimensioned as a Ø16 threaded rebar, giving a hole with a diameter of 18 mm into the cylinder. The distance from the upper border to the hole's centre is equal to 26 mm. The conceptual design is shown in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3. Isometric (a), section (b) and top (c) views of cylinder connection.

The initial consideration lies in determining the washer's ability to distribute the load onto the cylinder wall. The load distribution depends significantly on the washer size; therefore, both 60×60 mm and 80×80 mm washers were analysed for comparison (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4. Washer dimensions and load distribution: 60x60 mm (a); 80x80 mm (b).

The analysis indicates that approximately 96% of the load is distributed within a radius of 22 mm around the hole in the 60x60 mm washer (**Figure 4a**). The remaining 4% is transmitted beyond this region. The percentages are around 80% and 20% respectively, for the 80x80 mm washer (**Figure 4b**). Findings from the load distribution analysis led to the decision to apply a 60x60 mm washer.

3 Finite Element Model analysis

To better understand the capacity response of the cylinder, the FEM has been created using Diana software [8], as reported in **Figure 5**. The presented analysis refers to the cylinder connectors anchored on the peripheral chord. The 3D model consists of a cylinder given the properties of a regular curved 2D shell element. To include the effect of the washer (60x60 mm), a secondary element is created and modelled as a 2D regular curved shell element. Both the cylinder and washer are assumed to be made of S235 steel. The cylinder and the washer are connected via a rigid link in the x-direction (direction of the load of the tension tie). The cylinder is supported in both horizontal directions up to a height of 100 mm, to simulate the contrast effect of the slabs. The bottom edge of the cylinder, as well as the edges of the holes in the cylinder and the washer, are supported in the vertical direction. Following the load distribution analysis, load values reported in Table 1 have been used within the FEM to simulate the chord action.

Figure 5. Finite Element model of the cylinder.

Table 1. FEM load values.

Name	Target	Type	Direction	Value	Unit	Washer 60x60
Load 1	washer	force	X	62	N/mm ²	96% of 71kN
Load 2	washer	force	X	1.35	N/mm ²	4% of 71kN

Using the Von-Mises yield criterion to analyse combined stresses, a maximum stress of 164 N/mm² has been obtained, while the horizontal deformation is limited to 0.06 mm. The deformation and the stress distribution are presented in **Figure 6**. The analysis of the model shows consistent stress concentration between the washer and the cylinder wall. Due to slab confinement, the maximum stress concentration is around the hole at a height of 100 mm. In the course of more evaluations, the impact of the simple hole position and dimension will be investigated, as well. In the first attempt, to facilitate the operational work on the construction site and to ensure the ease of mounting and dismantling, a different design has been modelled, considering a recess instead of the hole. In this manner, the rebar, the washer, and the nut can be accommodated within the cylinder with minimal effort (**Figure 7**). The presence of a slotted

hole in the cylinder is advantageous in some practical respects. Nevertheless, it must be noted that this also results in the removal of a portion of the reacted area of the cylinder. It is therefore reasonable to assume that this will have a considerable effect on the overall resistance. Most of the stresses perpendicular to the pulling direction now must be resisted by the washer alone (Figure 8).

Figure 6. Stress pattern (a) and deformation (b) under a tension force of 71 kN, simple hole configuration.

Figure 7. Assembly of the cylinder with a slotted hole.

Figure 8. Stress pattern (a) and deformation (b) under a tension force of 71 kN, slotted configuration.

Applying the same tension force, equal to 71 kN, the FEM demonstrates that the maximum stress achieves a value of approximately 370 N/mm², while the deformation is nearly double, reaching 0.13 mm. According to the von Mises yield criterion used for the analysis of combined stresses, based on computations from the FEM analysis, it is evident that only the simple hole configuration is capable of withstanding the intended resistance. Indeed, the presence of a recess in the slotted hole configuration contributes to a significant reduction in the structural performance of the connector.

4 Final remarks

The paper presents recent advances in demountable connections for precast concrete floors, focusing on a pilot project within the ReCreate research programme. Using refurbished hollow-core slabs from the Prinsenhof building demonstrates a practical, sustainable approach to circular construction. The development of the cylinder connection system marks a step forward in achieving monolithic floors, with steel cylinders and ties strategically placed. The FEM analysis confirms the efficacy of the strategy, showing that the designed connection can withstand the necessary tensile forces. Additional insights were gained by modelling different configurations, revealing higher stresses in the cylinder with a slotted hole, making it unsuitable for the CCN project. As the mock-up has been developed with the intention of testing the structural configuration for the final design, dimensional and shape deviations will be addressed, and practical experience will be acquired regarding the application of various solutions. Concurrently, laboratory tests are evaluating the system's structural reliability in several scenarios, including the longitudinal joint configuration. Furthermore, the study emphasises the effective reuse of existing structural components by integrating them into a new design framework that supports both structural integrity and environmental sustainability.

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Toward Active Urban Mining: A Contextual and Systemic Reframing of Circularity Strategies for the Built Environment

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Keywords: systemic sustainability, circularity, urban mining, reusability, recyclability, circularity strategies

ABSTRACT

In the general circular economy hierarchy, “reuse” is rightly prioritized over “recycling” due to its superior preservation of material resources and embodied energy, providing a re-utilization scenario for all materials and components in the product [1]. However, in the context of the built environment, this principle cannot be applied without critical reflection. Buildings are long-lasting products, and elements extracted after decades of use often no longer comply with updated regulatory, safety, or performance standards—even when geometrically and materially intact—making direct reuse impractical or even impossible.

When reuse is not feasible, it is essential to ensure that all invested materials can be recovered and introduced into a high-quality, low-loss recycling processes, and reintroduced into state-of-the-art products. If this is not possible, valuable resources are permanently lost, undermining the core objectives of circularity and urban mining. This highlights the importance of designing for material recoverability and high-efficiency recycling, but also of recognizing that this is only one of many necessary considerations in achieving effective circularity.

Driven by the reuse narrative, certain measures—such as disassembly, modularization, or material passports—are often promoted as silver-bullet solutions to circularity. However, a closer look reveals that while these strategies may be highly effective for some materials and product types, they can have little to no impact on others. For instance, modular design that disregards components and materials separability, or lacks standardization in dimensions and future use cases, may neither support reuse nor enable recycling, resulting in little to no circularity benefit despite its modular structure. [2],[3].

This paper argues that there is no one-size-fits-all solution. Instead, circularity must be approached systemically, taking into account the specific properties of the materials and products, their integration and utilization in the building, and the building’s lifecycle context. A wide range of circularity strategies and combinations thereof are observed and compared in order to identify which approaches provide the highest circularity potential for specific groups of materials and products.

Using prominent building materials with significant climate and resource impact like timber and concrete as examples, the paper demonstrates that circularity strategies must be material-, utilization-, and context-specific.

Overall, the paper advocates for a differentiated, systemic and evidence-based approach to circularity in the built environment, challenging generalised solutions and aiming instead for targeted strategies that can realistically enable active urban mining and true resource circularity.

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Trusted Service Layer for Circular Infrastructure: Establishing Reliable Reuse of Bridge Components

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Abstract

The transition to circular construction in infrastructure projects is hindered by a critical lack of trust and transparency in reusable component information. This paper presents a Trusted Service Layer approach that addresses this challenge by facilitating verified information exchange for reusable infrastructure components. By integrating with Digital Product Passports and blockchain technology, the service layer provides reliable component history, characteristics, and performance data, enabling confident reuse decisions. We outline a proof-of-concept implementation focused on bridge components in the Dutch infrastructure sector, demonstrating how this approach can increase circular material adoption while reducing verification costs and risks. The proposed system creates value through enhanced trust in component provenance, standardized information exchange, and data-driven insights for future standardization efforts. This research contributes to circular construction by addressing the fundamental trust barrier that currently prevents widespread adoption of component reuse in infrastructure projects.

Keywords: Circular Construction, Digital Product Passports, Infrastructure Reuse, Service Layer, Supply Chain Transparency, Trusted Information

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1 Introduction

Infrastructure projects face mounting pressure to adopt circular economy principles, with the European Green Deal and national policies like the Dutch Circular Economy program setting ambitious targets for material reuse and waste reduction [1]. However, the practical implementation of circularity in infrastructure remains challenging, particularly for complex structures like bridges. A primary barrier is the profound difficulty project owners and constructors face in sourcing reliable, reusable infrastructure components with verified characteristics and history [2].

Current practices for component reuse are fragmented and inefficient. Finding suitable components involves laborious manual searches across disparate sources, with limited standardized data formats and, crucially, lacking trusted verification of components' history, quality, and performance characteristics [3]. This inherent lack of trust and transparency acts as a major barrier to the widespread adoption of reused materials, even when potentially suitable components exist. As noted by Eberhardt et al. [4], the perceived risk associated with reused structural components often outweighs potential sustainability benefits, leading to default choices of virgin materials.

The Province of North Holland (PNH) exemplifies this challenge in its efforts to implement Industrial, Flexible, Demountable (IFD) principles in bridge procurement. While standardization offers clear benefits

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for future reuse, the broader industry often fails to see the immediate value proposition, hindering uptake. This is compounded by technical challenges in decomposing complex Building Information Models (BIM) into meaningful, reusable component-level data [5].

Previous research has explored various technological solutions, including blockchain for supply chain transparency [6], digital twins for component tracking [7], and ontologies for semantic interoperability [8]. However, these approaches often focus on specific technical aspects rather than addressing the fundamental trust barrier in a holistic manner. Additionally, existing marketplace platforms for construction materials typically lack robust verification mechanisms, limiting their effectiveness for critical infrastructure components [9].

This paper presents a focused solution: a Trusted Service Layer that facilitates verified information exchange for reusable infrastructure components. We concentrate on establishing trust through reliable component information, enabling confident reuse decisions. The approach integrates with Digital Product Passports (DPPs) and blockchain technology to provide immutable records of component characteristics, history, and performance.

Our research contributes to circular construction by addressing the critical trust gap that currently prevents widespread adoption of component reuse in infrastructure projects.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Research Approach

This research employs Design Science Research (DSR) methodology to develop and evaluate the Trusted Service Layer as a solution to the trust barrier in circular infrastructure. DSR is particularly appropriate for this work as it focuses on creating innovative artifacts to solve real-world problems while simultaneously contributing to scientific knowledge [10].

Following Hevner et al [11], our approach consists of three main phases:

1. **Problem Identification and Definition:** Through literature review and analysis of current circular infrastructure practices, we identified the trust barrier as a critical challenge preventing widespread component reuse.
2. **Solution Design and Development:** Based on the problem definition, we designed the Trusted Service Layer architecture and component information model, integrating blockchain and Digital Product Passport concepts.
3. **Evaluation:** The solution is being evaluated through a proof-of-concept implementation with bridge components, focusing on the three validity types proposed by Larsen et al. [10]: criterion validity (does the solution meet specified requirements?), causal validity (does the solution address the identified problem?), and context validity (under what conditions does the solution work?).

This methodological approach ensures that the Trusted Service Layer is not only technically sound but also addresses the practical needs of stakeholders in the circular infrastructure ecosystem.

2.2 System Architecture

The Trusted Service Layer follows a multi-layered architecture designed to connect various actors and data sources within the circular infrastructure ecosystem. Figure 1 illustrates the system's architecture and operational flow, showing how information moves through the layers and the key verification processes that establish trust in component data.

As shown in Figure 1, the architecture consists of five interconnected layers:

Figure 1: Trusted Service Layer architecture and operational flow.

- **User Interface Layer:** Provides a simple component browser and search interface, allowing users to discover and view verified component information.
- **Trusted Service Layer:** The core innovation area, providing verification logic, trust mechanisms, and orchestration between users, data sources, and assurance providers. It acts as the central hub, coordinating both the verification of component information through blockchain technology (step 1) and the structuring of this information via ontologies in the Knowledge Layer.
- **Knowledge Layer:** Utilizes ontologies to structure information, translating between different data formats (e.g., from IFC to URI-based identifiers) and ensuring semantic consistency across the system.
- **Digital Product Passports:** Contains verified claims about components that have been validated through blockchain (step 2), providing a standardized format for component information that can be integrated with supply chains (step 4).
- **Data Layer:** Manages raw data from suppliers, configurators, and IFC files, forming the foundation of the information pyramid and providing the source data (step 3) that flows to material supply chains.

The verification process (steps 1-2) ensures that information stored in Digital Product Passports is tamper-proof and reliable, creating a trusted foundation for reuse decisions. The blockchain verification mechanism provides immutable records of component verification, while maintaining flexibility to accommodate multiple levels of assurance based on component criticality and available information.

The data flow (steps 3-4) enables integration with material supply chains, making verified component information available for reuse decisions. This bidirectional flow ensures that both technical specifications and verification status are accessible to potential users of reused components, addressing the trust barrier that currently limits circular practices.

2.3 Component Information Model

The Trusted Service Layer utilizes a component information model that captures essential characteristics for infrastructure reuse decisions. Based on literature in circular construction and digital product passports [12, 9, 3], we identified key information categories required for confident reuse:

- **Physical characteristics:** Dimensions, material composition, weight, connections
- **Structural properties:** Load capacity, fatigue performance, remaining service life
- **Provenance information:** Original project, manufacturing date, standards compliance

- **Usage history:** Previous applications, loading conditions, maintenance records
- **Verification status:** Level of assurance, verification methods, certifications
- **Logistics data:** Current location, availability date, transportation requirements

This information model is implemented using standardized data schemas compatible with existing Building Information Modeling (BIM) frameworks and Digital Product Passport specifications, ensuring interoperability with industry tools and processes. As highlighted by Abreu et al. [12], DPPs require the integration of multiple segments of the product lifecycle, necessitating an innovative architecture capable of capturing information throughout the process.

2.4 Proof of Concept Implementation

To validate the Trusted Service Layer approach, a proof-of-concept implementation focused on bridge components is being planned in collaboration with the Province of North Holland. The implementation follows an incremental approach with four key elements:

1. **Component Record Creation and Verification:** Establishing a system for recording and verifying information about reusable bridge components, focusing initially on standardized elements from PNH's IFD bridge program.
2. **Simple Interface for Component Discovery:** Developing a basic user interface that allows stakeholders to browse and search for components based on key parameters and view their verified characteristics and history.
3. **Process Mapping:** Documenting the end-to-end process of component reuse, from design to marketplace listing, identifying key integration points and information flows.
4. **Value Demonstration:** Using a simulation approach to demonstrate the value added by the trusted information layer in terms of transaction efficiency, risk reduction, and material reuse rates.

The proof of concept utilizes blockchain infrastructure for component verification while maintaining an open architecture that can integrate with multiple assurance providers. This approach allows for testing the core trust mechanisms without requiring the development of a complete marketplace platform. As noted by Jensen et al. [13], blockchain technology can clear "areas of interoperability and data governance and facilitates multiple levels of access" in digital product passport systems.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Addressing the Trust Barrier

The Trusted Service Layer directly addresses the fundamental trust barrier in circular infrastructure by providing verified component information with clear assurance levels. By making this information transparent and trustworthy, the service layer enables stakeholders to make informed decisions about reuse, potentially increasing the percentage of circular materials in new projects. Literature suggests that this approach could significantly reduce the perceived risk associated with reused components, particularly for standardized elements like bridge beams, columns, and deck sections [4, 2].

The system's flexibility in accommodating multiple levels of assurance is particularly valuable for the infrastructure sector, where component criticality varies widely. For primary structural elements, the highest level of blockchain-backed verification might be required, while secondary elements might use simpler

verification methods. This aligns with the design principles for blockchain-based digital product passports proposed by Abreu et al. [12].

3.2 Value Creation Mechanisms

The Trusted Service Layer creates value through multiple mechanisms:

- **Risk reduction:** By providing verified component information, the system reduces the perceived and actual risks associated with reused materials.
- **Transaction cost reduction:** Standardized information exchange reduces the time and effort required to assess component suitability.
- **Material value preservation:** Enhanced trust in component quality helps maintain value across multiple use cycles.
- **Data-driven insights:** Component usage patterns provide valuable metadata for future standardization efforts.

For clients like PNH, this means being able to quantify the value of materials that can be reused, providing a clear business case for standardization efforts. For suppliers and contractors, it offers a way to demonstrate the quality and reliability of their reusable components, potentially commanding better prices.

Recent research by King et al. [14] emphasizes that digital product passports require an ecosystem approach integrating suppliers, partners, and third-party auditors. The Trusted Service Layer facilitates this integration by providing a common verification framework that can be adopted across the infrastructure sector.

3.3 Integration with Existing Systems

A key advantage of the service layer approach is its ability to integrate with existing systems rather than replacing them. The layer acts as a bridge between component suppliers, verification providers, and potential users, enhancing information flows without disrupting established workflows.

This integration capability is particularly important for the infrastructure sector, where large investments in existing systems and processes make wholesale replacements impractical. By focusing on the specific trust gap rather than attempting to create an entirely new ecosystem, the Trusted Service Layer offers a pragmatic path to increased circularity.

As noted by Abreu et al. [12], blockchain-based digital product passports contribute to environmental sustainability by promoting transparency, reducing counterfeiting, enhancing recycling efforts, and encouraging responsible consumption through increased product awareness. These benefits align directly with the goals of circular infrastructure initiatives.

4 Conclusion

This paper has presented a focused approach to addressing the trust barrier in circular infrastructure through a Trusted Service Layer that facilitates verified information exchange for reusable components. By integrating with Digital Product Passports and blockchain technology, the service layer provides reliable component history, characteristics, and performance data, enabling confident reuse decisions. The system's value creation mechanisms include risk reduction, transaction cost reduction, material value preservation, and data-driven insights for future standardization efforts.

Future work will focus on expanding the component types covered by the system, enhancing integration with design tools for a seamless workflow, and developing metrics to quantify the impact on circular material adoption rates. By addressing the fundamental trust barrier, the Trusted Service Layer contributes to making circular construction a practical reality in infrastructure projects.

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Återhus 3.0: Building new from old

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The construction sector is a major contributor to Sweden's climate impact, largely due to its reliance on virgin materials and the high volume of demolition waste. Återhus 3.0 is a Swedish innovation project aimed at advancing the circular economy in the construction and real estate sector by reusing heavy, load-bearing components such as concrete and steel as well as wood from existing buildings. Coordinated by RISE Research Institutes of Sweden, the project includes 14 partners from academia, municipalities, and the construction industry. It runs from December 2023 to January 2026, with a total budget of approximately SEK 51 million. Återhus 3.0 builds on previous project phases that developed methods for reusing structural building elements. This third phase focuses on scaling up and implementing these methods in real-world projects, with the aim of significantly reducing environmental impact and aligning with national and international sustainability targets.

The project is organized into work packages covering: Business models and digitalization; Technical quality assurance - developing standards to ensure reused materials are safe and durable; Design for reuse; Policy and regulation: Proposing regulatory adjustments to facilitate large-scale reuse.

The goal of Återhus 3.0 is to:

- Increase reuse of structural elements that would otherwise be demolished.
- Reduce the climate impact of the building sector by at least 25% by 2030.
- Decrease construction and demolition waste volumes by 10%.
- Strengthen the competitiveness of companies through circular business models.
- Enhance the sector's capacity for innovation and talent attraction.

These approaches are tested and validated in six demonstration projects across Sweden and they include different topologies and types of materials.

Återhus 3.0 marks a critical shift towards a more sustainable construction industry in Sweden. By combining cutting-edge research, innovative business strategies, and practical pilot projects, it aims to mainstream the reuse of heavy building materials. The project is a model for reducing climate impact and preserving resources.

Keywords: Concrete, Beams, Hollow core, Steel, Reuse, Wood.

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Circularity in the Built Environment 2025

Circularity and environmental assessment in the built environment

Applying a multi-cycle life cycle assessment framework to circular office tables and partition walls

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Keywords: Built environment, Circular economy, Environmental life cycle assessment, Multi-cycle assessment framework

1. INTRODUCTION

Buildings are responsible for approximately 50% of resource extraction and consumption, 40% of the energy consumption in the European Union (EU), 36% of energy-related greenhouse gas emissions, and over 30% of the EU's annual waste [1]. Of this waste, only about 40% is recycled or reused. Therefore, the built environment has great potential for lowering its resource consumption and decarbonisation by implementing circular economy (CE) principles [2]. Circularity or CE principles, focus on retaining the value of materials for as long as possible through strategies like rethink, reduce, reuse, repair, and recycle – collectively also known as the R-strategies [3]. However, while these R-strategies promote sustainability, they do not offer an assessment of the potential reduction in greenhouse emissions or any other environmental impacts.

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a widely used, science-based method for quantifying the environmental impacts of products [4]. LCA evaluates the environmental aspects and potential impacts related to a functional unit throughout a product's life cycle, which starts from raw material acquisition, goes through to production, use and end-of-life (EOL) treatment, and ends with final disposal [5]. The result of an LCA is an environmental profile of the product assessed that includes quantified environmental impact indicators. However, the EN 15804+A2:2019 [6], which is the current European standard for conducting LCAs of construction products, is intended to assess linear life cycles rather than multi-cycle or circular life cycles.

Within the Horizon Europe research project Drastic [7], a sustainability assessment framework has been developed that incorporates multi-cycle LCA (MLCA) while also considering circularity and sufficiency aspects [3]. Five pilot projects that will demonstrate varied circular solutions are currently under development and their level of sustainability will be validated with the developed multi-cycle sustainability and circularity assessment framework by March 2027. To already test and further improve the assessment framework, the Drastic assessment framework has been applied to two circular case studies taken from the Flemish Living Lab project MASCO on circular materials [8]. This paper presents some of the results of the MLCA and circularity assessment of the two MASCO case studies.

2. METHODOLOGY

As described above, the Drastic sustainability assessment framework [3] has been applied to this study. The framework defines a multi-life cycle approach as “*an approach that enables cascading scenarios based on the R-strategies regarding a circular economy to preserve and*

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prolong the service life of buildings, components, and materials, thereby reducing resource demand (water, energy, and materials)”. The modular structure of the EN 15804+A2:2019 forms the basis for the MLCA in which cascading scenarios based on the R-strategies are included in the different life cycle information modules, as visualised in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Mapping of the interaction between the R-strategies and information modules [9].

The core and additional environmental impact categories as included in the EN 15804+A2:2019 (e.g., the impact category climate change expressed in the unit kg CO₂ equivalents, and particulate matter expressed in disease incidence) are used to calculate the characterised life cycle impact assessment results. All 19 categories have been considered to minimise burden shifting. Furthermore, normalisation and weighting have been applied to allow aggregation of the assessed impact categories into a single score. While the uncertainty level associated with a single score is greater than that of the individual indicators, it facilitates better univocal decision-making compared to presenting several individual indicators side by side.

The EN 15804+A2:2019 standard does not provide guidelines for normalisation or weighting. Therefore, the Environmental Footprint (EF) weighting approach [10] developed by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission is used, as the impact categories and impact assessment methods of EN 15804+A2:2019 align with those of the EF method. The normalisation and weighting in accordance with the EF method results in a single score expressed in environmental milli-points (mPt). This article presents only the single score results. To calculate the environmental impacts, the LCA software SimaPro Craft, version 10.2, and the generic life cycle inventory database ecoinvent 3.11 are used. Furthermore, the components from the Drastic assessment framework related to multi-cycle life cycle costing and circularity from a sufficiency perspective are excluded from the scope in this paper.

3. CASE STUDY DESCRIPTIONS

This paper presents two circular case studies: an office table remanufactured and sold by NNOF, and a demountable, reusable internal wall solution by JUUNOO. Both case studies consider an office building located in Brussels, Belgium as the location of the client.

3.1 NNOF

NNOF (Nearly New Office Facilities) is a Belgian company specialising in sustainable design and transformation of professional workspaces [11]. They offer relocation services for companies, including remanufactured or reused furniture to fit the new office space. For this case study, an office table is selected, made of a particle board panel supported by powder-

coated steel legs. The panel, measuring 0.9 by 1.8 meters, is covered in melamine and finished with PVC edging. During the remanufacturing process, NNOF mechanically removes the melamine and PVC edging from the table surface, before applying new melamine and PVC edging. Additionally, a new powder coating is applied to the steel legs. When a table is suitable for reuse, it only requires a manual cleaning with water and soap. Both the remanufacturing and reuse process include transport from the client to the NNOF warehouse and from the NNOF warehouse to the client of the next use cycle. For remanufacturing, there is also transport between the NNOF warehouse and the NNOF workshop.

3.2 JUUNOO

The Belgian company JUUNOO designs and develops modular and reusable internal wall systems for workspaces [12]. Their BaseClick wall is an alternative to conventional non-load-bearing internal walls, which generally use a metal framework and gypsum board finishes. The BaseClick consists of a clickable metal frame that allows for endless reuse. It is filled with glass wool insulation and covered with fibreboard panels, which are secured using nylon tapes. The insulation, fibreboard panels, and nylon tape can be reused twice. When these components are disassembled for a third time, they will need to be replaced, i.e., a refurbish activity in terms of the R-strategies.

4. RESULTS

The next sections describe the results per case, addressing the environmental impacts per scenario, cycle, and information module. While the net impacts in module D –representing the potential benefits and loads beyond the system boundaries that result from waste processing in module C– are included in the graphs for completeness, they are not discussed in the next sections. This exclusion is to ensure clarity and prevent any double counting of potential avoided impacts.

4.1 RESULTS NNOF

Figure 2 illustrates the MLCA results of the NNOF case study. It shows the environmental profile based on the single score (mPt) of an office table for four different scenarios. Each scenario is separated with a thick vertical line, and each scenario considers three cycles separated with a dotted line. Each scenario starts with a first business-as-usual (BAU) production (A1-A3), transport (A4), and installation (A5) in cycle 1, and ends with a final EOL (C2-C4) in cycle 3. The first scenario represents the traditional linear “take-make-waste” economic model, where each cycle ends with an EOL (C2-C4), and each cycle begins with a full product and construction process stage (A1-A5). This BAU scenario serves as a baseline for comparison for the remaining three scenarios that reflect NNOF’s approach, incorporating the R-strategies remanufacture and/or reuse in cycles 2 and 3.

One BAU module A, including production, transport to and installation at site, account for 2.09 mPt, while a BAU EOL (module C) accounts for 0.78 mPt. In the first scenario, these impacts occur three times, once per cycle, totalling to 8.62 mPt. The second scenario considers one BAU module A (2.09 mPt) followed by two remanufacturing cycles at NNOF (0.50 mPt each), and a final EOL (0.78 mPt), resulting in a total environmental impact of 3.87 mPt over three cycles. This corresponds to a 55% reduction in environmental impact compared to the BAU baseline scenario. The third and fourth scenarios consider one and two reuse cycles, respectively. The environmental impact of one reuse cycle is 0.05 mPt. Therefore, in the third scenario still with one remanufacture cycle, the total environmental impact over three cycles is 3.42 mPt, while in the fourth scenario with two reuse cycles, the impact is reduced to 2.96 mPt. These correspond to reductions of 60% and 66%, respectively, compared to the BAU baseline scenario.

Figure 2. Comparative MLCA of a BAU office table and NNOF table for three cycles, environmental profile expressed as single score [mPt].

Figure 3. Comparative MLCA of a BAU internal wall and JUUNOO BaseClick wall for six cycles, environmental profile expressed as single score [mPt].

4.2 RESULTS JUUNOO

Figure 3 presents the MLCA results of the JUUNOO case study. It outlines the environmental impacts, expressed in mPt/m² of wall area, for two scenarios: the BAU baseline scenario, which considers a gypsum metal stud wall, and the JUUNOO BaseClick wall. Both scenarios are assessed over six cycles. The chosen number of cycles allows for a complete assessment of the JUUNOO wall's circular potential.

The BAU scenario involves six identical cycles, each comprising of production, transport to site, and installation in module A, followed by deconstruction, waste treatment, and disposal in module C. The impact of one BAU module A is quantified at 2.93 mPt/m², while one BAU module C accounts for a significantly smaller impact of 4.87×10^{-4} mPt/m². The relatively minor effect of module C is so small that it is almost not visible on the graph. The BAU scenario results in a total impact of 17.85 mPt/m² when assessed over six cycles.

The first cycle of the JUUNOO scenario comprises of the production, transport, and installation of the BaseClick wall, which accounts for an impact of 3.96 mPt/m². Cycles 2 and 3 represents reuse cycles, where the wall installed in the previous cycle is manually disassembled and transported to JUUNOO (C2 reuse/refurb. –which is too small to be visible on the graph), followed by transport (A4 reuse/refurb.) and installation at another office location (A5 reuse/refurb.), resulting in a relatively small impact of 0.20 mPt/m² per reuse cycle. Cycle 4 is the refurbish cycle, in which the insulation, fibreboard panel, and nylon tape need to be replaced, while the clickable steel frame can still be reused. This refurbish cycle has an environmental impact of 2.02 mPt/m². Cycles 5 and 6 are also reuse cycles like cycles 2 and 3; however, at the end of cycle 6, an EOL is considered with an impact of 0.45 mPt/m². Overall, the JUUNOO scenario results in a total impact of 7.21 mPt/m² when assessed over six cycles, which corresponds to a 60% reduction compared to the BAU scenario.

5. CONCLUSION

The MLCA results of both cases highlight the environmental benefits of transitioning from a linear economy to circular strategies such as remanufacturing and reuse. In both cases, the BAU baseline scenarios leads to the highest environmental impact due to repeated full-cycle production and EOL stages, emphasising the inefficiencies of the conventional "take-make-waste" model.

The NNOF case study demonstrates how integrating remanufacturing and reuse strategies can significantly lower environmental burdens. The comparison between the different scenarios demonstrates that reducing the need for new materials and extending the lifespan of existing furniture leads to meaningful environmental savings. In this specific example, a reduction ranging from 55% to 66% is feasible over three cycles. Moreover, increasing the number of remanufacturing or reuse cycles would further enhance sustainability gains, reinforcing the value of circular design principles.

Similarly, the JUUNOO case study shows the possible effectiveness of reusable non-load-bearing internal wall systems. Despite a higher initial impact in the first cycle, total environmental impacts can be reduced across multiple cycles with refurbishing and reuse processes. The break-even point between the assessed BAU gypsum wall and the JUUNOO system is reached by cycle 2, demonstrating possible gains of circular construction practices. These findings emphasise the importance of designing demountable, long-lasting products that minimise waste and optimise material use across multiple cycles.

It is important to acknowledge that this assessment assumes BAU products remain unchanged throughout different cycles. However, future advancements in technology, production methods, and energy infrastructure—including decarbonisation efforts—could lead to lower environmental impacts over time. Therefore, incorporating prospective LCA approaches into multi-cycle assessments would provide a more dynamic and forward-looking perspective on the MLCA framework.

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Are Bio-based Insulation Systems in Net-zero Carbon Building Renovations Inherently Circular?

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The UK and Europe have committed to reducing emissions to as close to zero as possible by 2050 to avoid catastrophic climate change. Reaching net zero means tackling all sources of emissions, and heating for homes and workspaces makes up almost a third of all carbon emissions. So, improving the energy efficiency of buildings is a priority, ensuring they require less energy to heat, making them cheaper to run and more comfortable to live in, while reducing our dependence on imported energy. At the same time, governments have fully engaged in transitioning to a circular economy to boost the economy and reduce dependency on raw materials while protecting the environment and accelerating to net zero. However, there is no clarity on the role that net-zero carbon building renovations in construction and operation have in the transition to a circular building environment.

The study consists of practice-oriented case study research aiming at contributing to practitioners' knowledge in the building sector by investigating the level of circularity of bio-based insulation systems applied in net-zero building renovations to define the potential of this intervention in the implementation of a circular built environment. Firstly, an analysis of existing bio-based insulation systems was implemented through a literature review, and a taxonomy of 6 system types was developed and compared in terms of materials, application features, advantages and disadvantages. Secondly, the study analysed existing tools available in the literature to assess the circularity of building components and selected the CBC-generator developed by van Stijn & Gruis (2019) as a design framework suitable for evaluating the circularity of identified insulation systems. Thirdly, the selected method was applied to the analysis of the taxonomy of bio-based insulation systems through case study research to assess their degree of circularity and understand the role played by this type of intervention for net-zero building renovation in the transition to a circular built environment.

The study showed that a limited degree of circularity is achieved by focusing on bio-based insulation materials only. In net-zero carbon building renovations in construction and operation, considerations are limited to carbon emissions associated with the building's production and construction stages up to practical completion of the renovation, and to carbon emissions associated with the building's operational energy used annually. This approach does not consider carbon emissions associated with waste generated by the inefficient maintenance, refurbishment and limited final recovery of building materials and systems applied in net-zero building renovations. Among the 6 types of bio-based insulation systems, the vapour-open internal insulation system resulted in the most circular system because of its whole bio-based nature, combined with only mechanical connections, which facilitate slowing and closing the material loop. Based on findings, recommendations for improving the circularity of bio-based insulation systems were formulated to support the transition to a circular built environment.

Keywords: carbon-neutral renovation, circular building, circular design, circular economy, net-zero carbon building.

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Beyond Measuring Resource-Flow - a Holistic Approach for a Framework to Assess Circularity in the Built Environment through all Life Cycle Stages

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Keywords: Circular Construction, Circular Economy, Circularity Assessment, Sustainable Construction

ABSTRACT

The transition to a circular economy in the built environment demands more than recycling materials – it requires a rethinking of how buildings are planned, used, and valued. This paper presents a conceptual framework for a circularity index that integrates strategic planning, resource flows, and systemic impacts across environmental, social, and economic dimensions. Developed through literature review and stakeholder analysis in Switzerland, the conceptual framework includes six indicators: strategy and goals, resource flows, information transmission, and social, ecological, and economic impact and value. It provides a comprehensive yet flexible foundation for assessing circularity in construction projects. While the framework currently lacks an operational measurement system, it sets the groundwork for future development of a practical tool. This work contributes to efforts in making circularity measurable and actionable across the built environment.

INTRODUCTION

The building-and-construction-sector is one of the most resource- and emissions-intensive industries globally. According to the United Nations Environment Program (2024), the built environment accounts for approximately 37% of global energy-related CO₂ emissions and over 50% of extracted raw materials (Linde et al., 2022). This makes the transition toward a circular economy (CE) in the sector not only necessary but urgent. Circular economy principles aim to decouple economic growth from resource consumption and environmental degradation through strategies such as reuse, refurbishment, recycling, and extended product lifetimes (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017; Kirchherr et al., 2017).

Despite a growing consensus on the value of circular construction, its implementation has been hindered by the lack of standardized operational tools for evaluating circularity. While numerous approaches exist – ranging from the Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) (Ellen MacArthur Foundation et al., 2019) to Cradle-to-Cradle (C2C) certification – many remain fragmented or too narrow in scope. Recent reviews (Benachio et al., 2020; Ossio et al., 2023; Pomponi & Moncaster, 2017) have pointed out that most methods either focus exclusively on material flows or lack integration with spatial and social dimensions. Moreover, tools developed for product or material level often fail to scale up effectively to the complexity of buildings or districts.

Emerging concepts such as Circular Ecosystem Innovation provide a more integrated vision, emphasizing value creation across multiple life cycle stages, cross-sector collaboration, and feedback-based learning loops (Konietzko et al., 2020). These align well with systems thinking

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and sustainability transitions theory, which highlight the importance of adaptive governance, network dynamics, and multi-level interactions in shaping circular transitions (Bocken et al., 2016; Loorbach et al., 2017).

Further, scholars such as Blomsma & Brennan, (2017) and Ghisellini et al., (2016) have stressed that circularity assessments must move beyond technocentric metrics and engage with institutional, behavioral, and societal dimensions. In the construction context, this implies the need for frameworks that evaluate not only what materials are used and how, but also the underlying planning strategies, information structures, and value distribution across stakeholders.

Against this backdrop, the present study outlines a concept for a structured framework for a circularity index in the built environment. Rather than introducing yet another set of isolated metrics, it synthesizes key dimensions from existing circularity models and incorporates input from stakeholders across the Swiss construction sector. The goal is to develop a tool that combines theoretical soundness with practical relevance – supporting decisions in design, procurement, and policy while promoting circularity across environmental, societal, and economic dimensions.

Importantly, the framework also aims to recognize the systemic value of the R-strategy Refuse – understood as not building or retaining existing buildings and structures. Since this strategy results in the absence of resource flows, it cannot be captured using flow-based assessment tools. The framework therefore seeks to expand measurement logic to account for strategic non-action as a valid and high-impact circular decision, acknowledging the environmental benefit of avoided material and energy use.

The remainder of this paper presents the outcomes of the stakeholder and the literature analysis, the methodological development of the framework and its core components. It concludes with a discussion of the framework's potential applications and current limitations, outlining the next steps toward a fully operational assessment tool.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The development of the framework is based on the synthesis of a stakeholder analysis and a literature review and analysis of existing methods and concepts.

STAKEHOLDER ANALYSIS. The stakeholder analysis formed a central component in the development of the framework for a circularity index, ensuring that it reflects not only theoretical robustness but also practical relevance. The analysis was based on a comprehensive online survey conducted between December 2023 and March 2024, which gathered responses from 158 professionals operating in the Swiss built environment sector. The total population of the sector is ~514'700. The confidence level of the sample size is therefore 95% with a margin error of 8%.

Participant Composition. Respondents came from a wide range of fields: 53% were architects and engineers, 18% were from real estate business, 14% came from construction companies, and the remaining 15% represented public administration, academia, and material manufacturers.

Interest and Motivation. The survey revealed a clear demand for a practical circularity assessment tool. A total of 81% of respondents expressed high or very high interest in the

development and use of such a framework. Their primary motivations included resource conservation (89%), climate protection (88%), and innovation potential (78%). Additionally, 69% highlighted technical optimization as a key driver for supporting circularity. As further medium relevant topics new business models and attractiveness for expert personnel and employees (both 56%) were voted for.

Influence and Decision-Making Power. Only 8% of respondents indicated that they hold sole decision-making authority for circularity-related topics within their projects. However, 48% reported that they could significantly influence project outcomes through collaboration. Furthermore, 32% felt they had a high to very high influence on broader developments within the sector, reflecting a notable capacity for systemic impact.

Collaboration and Implementation Potential. Stakeholders expressed a strong willingness to work together across disciplines. Up to 79% said they were open to collaborating with professionals in other areas to promote and implement circular strategies. Key partners identified for collaboration included sustainability consultants, digital planning experts, and project developers.

Expectations for the Framework. Participants emphasized the importance of a framework that is adaptable to project specifics, digitally integrable (e.g., through Building Information Modelling (BIM) or resource passports), and aligned with both ecological and economic performance indicators. There was a clear call for non-prescriptive, strategy-enabling guidance rather than rigid checklists.

Overall, the stakeholder analysis provided a strong part of the foundation for shaping the six-indicator framework, confirming the relevance of the proposed impact categories and the need for a tool that supports both strategic planning and measurable action in circular construction.

LITERATURE REVIEW. A comprehensive literature review was conducted, analyzing academic systematic overviews, including international standards (ISO 59020 - Circular economy - Measuring and assessing circularity performance, 2024), European proposition for indicators for the built environment (European Commission et al., 2023) design frameworks (Cradle-to-Cradle, Braungart et al., 2007), sector-specific rating systems (Deutschen Gesellschaft für Nachhaltiges Bauen – DGNB e.V., 2024), and practical indicators (Ellen MacArthur Foundation et al., 2019). Key gaps were identified: limited social integration, poor alignment across scales, and insufficient metrics for design quality or resource planning. These gaps informed the development of the proposed concept.

Comparative Academic Analyses. Recent reviews by Khadim et al. (2022), Benachio et al. (2020), and Ossio et al. (2023) provided a systematic overview of circularity indicators across scales. These works identified recurring limitations, including:

- A predominant focus on material flows, especially recycling, while neglecting early-phase strategies such as design for disassembly or shared use.
- Minimal coverage of societal dimensions, such as user well-being, job creation, or participatory planning.
- Weak representation of spatial and temporal dynamics, limiting adaptability across building types and life cycle stages.
- Lack of integration between material tracking (e.g., passports, digital twins) and performance indicators.

Conceptual Frameworks and Models. The concept of Circular Ecosystem Innovation complements traditional linear-to-circular transition models by emphasizing systemic collaboration across industries and life cycle stages (Konietzko et al., 2020). It focuses on creating value through integrated stakeholder ecosystems, digital resource transparency, and feedback-oriented innovation loops. Unlike conventional models that concentrate on materials or product design, this concept calls for coordinated strategies involving planning, ownership, use, and end-of-use across the entire built environment. It helped inform the development of indicators that link design strategy with societal and economic value creation. The MCI developed by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation was one of the most influential sources for circularity assessments (Ellen MacArthur Foundation et al., 2019). It measures the degree of material circularity based on input and output flows, particularly focusing on recycled content and recovery rates. While methodologically sound, MCI was found to overlook critical aspects such as service life extension, modularity, or socio-economic impact. The C2C design framework, with its regenerative philosophy, introduced important principles like material health and continuous reuse, but lacks operationalized metrics for the building scale (McDonough et al., 2003).

The R-strategies (Refuse, Rethink, Reduce, Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Repurpose, Recycle, Recover) formed the conceptual basis for prioritizing circular interventions (Kirchherr et al., 2017). Despite their comprehensiveness, they often lack project-specific application logic or measurable performance criteria.

Standards and Certification Systems. ISO 59020 (2024) served as a key reference for defining boundaries, indicator structures, and integration levels across the product and system scale. It emphasizes harmonization of measurement methods and flexibility in applying circularity metrics depending on data quality and decision context. ISO 14044 (2006) and SIA 2032 (2020) provided relevant frameworks for aligning circularity assessment with environmental life cycle analysis without conflating the two.

Existing green building rating systems like DGNB, BREEAM, and LEED include circularity as a subtopic, mostly through recyclability, material sourcing, or end-of-life waste indicators. However, they tend to treat circularity as an add-on feature rather than an integrated planning strategy. These systems typically underrepresent design adaptability, socio-economic co-benefits, and upstream avoidance measures.

Gaps and Implications for Framework Development. The review concluded that a meaningful circularity framework must bridge multiple gaps:

- It should combine qualitative assessments (e.g., strategic intent, adaptability) with quantitative data (e.g., resource flows, environmental, social or economic impacts).
- It must extend beyond building components to include planning processes, use-phase efficiency, and end-of-use scenarios.
- It should reflect all three dimensions of sustainability – environmental, social, and economic – in balanced ways.
- It must enable application at different project stages and spatial scales.
- It must allow the assessment of measures independently from resource flow.

These findings were directly used to structure the six-indicator model proposed in this paper, ensuring that it addresses conceptual, technical, and operational shortcomings observed in prior approaches.

FRAMEWORK DEVELOPMENT

The framework for a circularity index was developed to address the conceptual, technical, and practical gaps identified through literature and stakeholder analysis. It operationalizes circular-economy-principles through six overarching indicators that reflect both strategic intent and measurable impact across the life cycle of the built environment. It is strongly based on the ISO 59000 series to ensure international compatibility. The framework shall enable informed decision making for owners, architects, engineers, construction companies, material suppliers and legal authorities through all life cycle stages. Nevertheless, the significance and informative value of each indicator varies according to the stage it is used.

The indicators are not intended to prescribe specific solutions but to offer a consistent structure for evaluating diverse circular strategies. As approximately 80% of stakeholders report to have shared decision-making power, the framework must support multi-actor decision-making processes. It therefore avoids reducing complex information to single scores and instead maintains a clear distinction between qualitative assessments and quantitative measurements, allowing for transparent and context-sensitive evaluation.

Each indicator is designed to integrate qualitative reasoning with quantitative potential, ensuring that the framework is both adaptable across scales (material, component, building, and district) and applicable across all project stages: design, building, use, and valorization. The term *valorization* is deliberately chosen, as it refers not only to post-use activities such as refurbishment, disassembly, and resource recovery, but also to the pre-design phase, where existing buildings, components, or land are assessed for their potential value before initiating a new project. Valorization thus operates at both ends of the project lifecycle – as the beginning and a conclusion of one loop (Fig.1).

Figure 1: Life cycle Stages, with valorization referring to post-use and to pre-design

The six core indicators of the conceptual framework are as follows:

1. Qualitative Assessment of Strategy and Goals

This indicator evaluates how circularity is embedded in the strategic intent of a project, focusing on whether early-phase decisions and overall project goals are guided by circular thinking. It emphasizes avoidance-based approaches, such as achieving project goals without building (e.g. reorganization of floor plans), extending the use of existing structures (e.g. shared use or multifunctional spaces), or reducing material demand through spatial efficiency and sufficiency (e.g. reduced space use per person). These strategies are most influential during the valorization and design phases, where long-term impacts are shaped and the influence on the project outcome is the highest.

The indicator is aligned with ISO 59020, which supports evaluating circular actions in relation to project goals, and ISO 59010, which emphasizes design for circularity. It builds on the upper levels of the R-strategy framework, which prioritize prevention over resource recovery. It is also informed by the Circular Ecosystem Innovation model, which calls for minimizing and regenerating resource flows. The importance of this indicator is supported by stakeholder input, which highlights strong motivation for resource conservation, climate protection, and innovation potential.

2. Quantitative Measurement of Resource Flows

This indicator measures material inputs and outputs throughout the building lifecycle. It accounts for the use of primary materials, pre-use secondary materials (reused or recycled), and the potential for post-use materials to be reclaimed. Resource flows are tracked across material types – biogenic, fossil, mineral, metallic – as well as energy and water, within clearly defined temporal and spatial system boundaries. The indicator distinguishes between end-of-use strategies (reuse, repair, refurbish) and end-of-life scenarios (recycling, composting, incineration, landfill), enabling a differentiated assessment of material pathways. It is most effective during the design and construction phases, where material choices and supply logistics are defined.

The indicator is directly aligned with ISO 59020, which places resource flow measurement at the core of circularity assessment. It further builds on the Material Circularity Indicator and reflects principles from the Circular Ecosystem Innovation model, particularly slowing and closing resource loops. It also responds to stakeholder priorities, particularly the need for technical optimization in material planning and life cycle performance tracking.

3. Qualitative Assessment of Information Transmission

This indicator assesses the availability, quality, and accessibility of information related to materials, components, and building structures used in a project. It accounts for the presence of tools such as resource passports, material and building cadasters, and integration with Building Information Modeling. By ensuring transparency and traceability, the indicator supports information transition to the next loop of the life cycle. It is particularly important during the design and building stage, where data structures for material documentation and digital workflows are established and determines the quality of the transition from one cycle to the next in the valorization stage.

The indicator aligns with principles defined in ISO 59004, particularly those concerning systems thinking, resource traceability, and ecosystem resilience. It also reflects the concept of cross-sector collaboration outlined in the Circular Ecosystem Innovation model. Stakeholder insights further emphasized the importance of collaborative processes and digital integrability, underlining the need for structured and interoperable data as a foundation for scalable circularity.

4. Qualitative and Quantitative Assessment of Social Impact and Value (Performance)

This indicator assesses the social implications of circular strategies applied throughout a project. It accounts for aspects such as user health and comfort, neighborhood quality and participation, social inclusion, and accessibility, fostering a sense of identification with the built environment. In addition, it considers whether design and construction processes contribute to broader societal benefits, such as job creation, skill development, and workplace safety including physical and mental health. The indicator is most impactful during the valorization phase, where key strategic decisions have a strong influence on the project process and outcome.

This indicator is compatible with ISO 59020, which includes provisions for measuring and assessing sustainability impacts, including social dimensions. Its development addresses a key gap identified in the literature review, namely the limited integration of spatial and social factors in existing circularity metrics. Stakeholder responses further reinforced its relevance, particularly through the emphasis on attractiveness for employees as a driver for circular practices in planning and construction.

5. Qualitative and Quantitative Assessment of Ecological Impact and Value (Performance)

This indicator assesses the environmental impact of circular strategies beyond life cycle assessments. It considers the reduction and remediation of harmful substances (e.g. asbestos, PAH polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, PFAS Per- and polyfluorinated alkyl substances, ...), biodiversity preservation (flora and fauna), water efficiency (e.g. ground water, rainwater retention, ...), and avoidance of ecosystem degradation. By linking ecological performance with circular objectives, it supports the identification of regenerative design potentials. It is most effective during the design stage where the material specification takes place.

The indicator aligns with ISO 59020 for sustainability impact assessment and draws on ISO 14044 and SIA 2032 to ensure compatibility with environmental life cycle analysis. Influences from Cradle-to-Cradle and the Circular Ecosystem Innovation model – particularly the principle of regeneration (‘make clean’) guided the focus on ecological health and effectiveness. Stakeholders emphasized its relevance through strong support for climate protection and its alignment to both ecological and economic performance.

6. Qualitative and Quantitative Assessment of Economic Impact and Value (Performance)

This indicator assesses the economic implications of circular strategies from both a socio-economic and user/investor perspective. It captures socio-economic contributions such as job creation and local economic development (trades and crafts), while also accounting for project-specific factors like life cycle costing, adaptability to future needs, and exposure to price volatility. Importantly, it enables comparative assessment of interventions – including the option not to build – by the economic evaluation of scenarios of a site or building before and after the project. It is most effective during the valorization phase, where the potential for value creation or preservation is strategically assessed.

The indicator aligns with ISO 59020, which defines methods for assessing sustainability impacts in economic terms. It draws from the literature’s critique of poor alignment across spatial and stakeholder scales, and the need to clarify how circular value is distributed. The Circular Ecosystem Innovation model reinforces this by framing circularity as a driver of long-term economic resilience. Stakeholder input further emphasized the importance of aligning circularity with measurable economic performance and innovation potential.

RESULTS

The framework consists of six indicators structured in two functional groups. The first group – Strategy and Goals, Resource Flows, and Information Transmission – provides the foundation

Figure 2: conceptual framework for a holistic circularity index with six indicators

for assessing circularity. These indicators focus on intent, material logic, and documentation, and can be applied independently depending on the project stage. The second group – Social, Ecological, and Economic Impact and Value – captures the systemic effects of circular strategies and is most informative when the three are assessed together. Their performance depends strongly on the decisions evaluated in the first group. The framework’s logic is sequential: strategy and material/resource planning must be assessed first, followed by performance indicators (Fig. 2). Assessing not building as a circular strategy requires combined evaluation of strategic intent with its social, ecological, and economic implications.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a holistic conceptual framework for a circularity index designed to operationalize the principles of the circular economy within the built environment. Developed through rigorous literature analysis and stakeholder analysis, the framework captures six interconnected indicators essential for assessing circularity.

However, it is important to acknowledge key limitations. The framework is based on stakeholder input and sectoral conditions specific to Switzerland, reflecting the current state of circular construction practices in that national context. While the structural logic of the framework is designed to be broadly applicable, its successful transfer to other countries requires a contextual review. It is recommended to assess similarities and differences between national construction practices and regulatory environments to ensure relevance and adaptability.

At present, the framework offers a well-structured and holistic foundation for assessing circularity, but does not include operational metrics, neither measurement, nor scoring system. The development of such metrics must consider each country’s regulatory structures and data standards. Operationalization should rely on metrics that are compatible with existing planning procedures to ensure practical integration. For example, required calculations – such as for floor area – should align with nationally established rules to minimize additional effort for project stakeholders. Ensuring alignment with national systems can help avoid duplication, reduce complexity, and increase acceptance of circularity assessment methods across the construction industry.

Future work should focus on translating the framework into a functional assessment tool with clear criteria, data structures, and evaluation methods for each indicator. Including:

- Defining operational metrics for qualitative and quantitative evaluation.
- Developing a transparent and flexible scoring methodology.
- Testing and validating the approach through pilot projects.
- Ensuring digital integration with tools such as BIM and material passports.

Ultimately, the concept lays the groundwork for a consistent and holistic approach to measuring and assessing circularity in construction, while highlighting the need for continued development to move from theory to implementation.

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Circular Bio-based Construction: Guidance for assessing future environmental impacts

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Keywords: Bio-based construction, Circular construction, Environmental assessment, Future scenarios

ABSTRACT

The built environment is a major contributor to global environmental pressures, accounting for 40% of total greenhouse gas emissions. Circular and biobased construction are two emerging approaches that can potentially reduce these impacts. Circular construction focuses on improving resource efficiency by reusing materials and reducing waste. Biobased construction, by contrast, uses renewable materials such as timber that can temporarily store carbon during a building's lifespan.

Environmental assessment methods support sustainable design and policymaking in the built environment. However, most focus on current impacts and overlook future changes. This limits their usefulness for circular and biobased solutions, whose impacts may shift as they respond to societal and technological changes. Future-oriented methods are needed to capture both potential benefits and unintended consequences. While future scenario modelling is common in environmental sciences, its application to assessing future impacts in the built environment remains limited and is mostly confined to a few specific cases. We address that gap by reviewing methods, tools, and data for future-oriented assessment, with a focus on circular and biobased construction.

We assess how future-oriented environmental assessment methods can be applied to circular and biobased construction across five scales: material, product, building, regional, and global. Our approach combines a literature review of existing methods with workshops involving AEC (Architecture, Engineering, Construction) sector experts to identify key external factors and research questions at each scale. The result is an overview of relevant methods, tools, and data requirements, aligned with a sector specific research agenda.

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Comprehensive circularity: Assessing social performances for the growing application of reuse in construction

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Keywords: Circular economy, Reuse, Social Life Cycle Assessment, Social Sustainability

ABSTRACT

The built environment accounts for 40% of greenhouse gas emissions and global construction and demolition waste (CDW). While the circular economy (CE) offers a promising path toward ecological transition, current approaches remain technocentric, prioritizing material and economic efficiencies. The social dimension of sustainability is often overlooked, raising key questions about the inclusiveness and long-term viability of circular strategies in the built environment.

In response to this gap, the research aims to develop a robust and operational methodology for integrating social aspects and indicators (e.g., social innovation, and inclusion) into circular construction strategies. The main hypothesis is that incorporating social dimensions into evaluation methods can make the social value of CE more tangible, thereby fostering broader stakeholder acceptance and increasing practices related to this emerging concept. Among this, reuse appears as a particularly promising application. It offers cost and material savings, creates new types of employment, improves working conditions, and supports innovative collaboration across the value chain, while contributing to ecological benefits.

To test this hypothesis, the research adopts a mixed-method approach. Top-down (quantitative) and bottom-up (qualitative) strategies are combined to better address the complexity of Social Life Cycle assessment (S-LCA). Guided by the UNEP/SETAC guidelines, the study will develop and refine social indicators through both theoretical dimensions and empirical fieldwork. The Cross Impact Balance (CIB) method will enable scenario development by exploring systemic interactions, complemented by participatory workshops, interviews, and in-situ observations. This approach will then be quantified within the broader Life Cycle Sustainability assessment (LCSA) framework and will leverage Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Cost assessment (LCC) tools. In parallel, socio-economic evaluation methods like Social Return on Investment (SROI) will align technical indicators with local design contexts and social economy.

The resulting framework will provide decision-makers with concrete metrics and flexible tools to recognize and amplify the social dimensions of circularity. By promoting inclusive jobs, fair value sharing, and active stakeholder engagement, this research supports a just, scalable and socially embedded transition in the construction sector.

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Do Reuse Ambitions Meet Reality? Assessing the Availability and Embodied Carbon Reduction Potential of Reclaimed Precast Concrete Elements in Sweden

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Keywords: Circular construction; Embodied carbon; Life cycle assessment (LCA); Material flow analysis (MFA); Precast concrete; Reuse

Structural elements account for a significant share of a building's embodied carbon. Conventional demolition practices not only generate substantial waste but also lead to the loss of high-value materials. Meanwhile, the global demand for construction materials continues to grow, posing major challenges for achieving climate targets. Reusing structural elements, rather than downcycling or landfilling, has emerged as a promising strategy to extend the lifespan of embodied carbon and reduce emissions associated with new construction.

Among structural materials, precast concrete plays a dominant role, representing the largest share in the Swedish building stock and carrying high carbon intensity. Its modular design and characteristics also make it comparatively easier and safer to deconstruct and reuse, positioning it as a key target in circular construction strategies. However, the availability of reusable precast concrete elements remains unexamined.

This study aims to explore the supply dynamics of structural precast concrete elements through demolitions in Sweden. It further assesses the potential embodied carbon savings that could be achieved through their reuse, providing insights into the climate benefits of scaling up structural reuse practices at the stock level.

The study consists of two main components: a stock and flow analysis of precast concrete elements over time and a life cycle assessment (LCA) to estimate the potential embodied carbon savings through reuse. The analysis spans from the 1950s, marking the introduction of precast concrete in Sweden, up to 2050, in line with the EU net-zero climate target. The analysis includes both residential and non-residential buildings. Estimation methods differ between these categories due to variations in data availability. Precast concrete intensity is calculated per flat (residential) or per square metre (non-residential) and multiplied by the respective estimated numbers of constructed and demolished flats or square metres. Embodied carbon performance is modelled dynamically, accounting for technological advancements over time.

The results indicate that while the reuse of precast concrete elements can contribute much to reducing embodied carbon at project level, the overall impact remains modest. This is primarily due to a persistent imbalance: future demand for construction materials is estimated to exceed the available supply of reusable elements, given the relatively low demolition rates. Moreover, increasing demolition rates will not necessarily improve reuse potential; on the contrary, it may accelerate the need for new construction, further amplifying material demand and associated emissions.

This study contributes to climate mitigation efforts by offering a data-driven understanding of how structural element reuse can be strategically scaled within the building sector. By combining prospective material flow analysis with LCA, this study advances tools for evaluating future reuse potential and embodied carbon savings in structural materials. The findings offer practical value for urban planners, policymakers and industry stakeholders aiming to align construction practices with long-term sustainability and climate goals. Additionally, the analytical framework developed here is adaptable and can be applied to other structural materials, supporting broader transitions toward circularity in the built environment.

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Enhancing Social Value: Circular, Relocatable Classroom as Testbed for the Value Chain Actors

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Keywords: circularity, relocatable building, social value, temporary building, testbed, value chain.

ABSTRACT

Buildings demand significant resources and long-term commitment, while user needs rapidly change. The use of educational technology (EdTech) in schools is a prime example of fast-changing, short-term needs. EdTech refers to digital tools to support learning. Teachers face barriers using EdTech, such as time constraints and a lack of skills or support. Not all schools can invest in dedicated EdTech classrooms.

A circular solution that supports temporality, flexibility, multifunctionality, and serviceability while enhancing learning is needed. This paper aims to analyse the social life-cycle impact of a circular, temporary classroom from the perspective of its value chain actors. This single case study focuses on a relocatable container called Tekla. Tekla serves both as a classroom for schools and as a testing environment (testbed) for EdTech companies, allowing them to develop products in real-life settings. Tekla, including the container, hosts, and support services, moves between schools every two to four weeks in Helsinki, Finland.

The ongoing analysis is based on Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) guidelines (UNEP 2020), with specific adaptations for the built environment as suggested by Lundgren (2023). It includes sector-specific indicators such as accessibility, participation, psychological comfort, usability, fulfilment, and stakeholder management. The value chain actors include EdTech companies, teachers, principals, learners, city employees, and the city. The framework was applied in an initial qualitative content analysis of project documentation related to the development and use of Tekla. Data sources for this analysis include participant data, meeting notes, reports, communications with value chain actors, and administrative records.

The analysis shows Tekla's social impact stems from technology and city-aligned management practices. Initial results demonstrate high value for end-users—learners, teachers, and EdTech companies—via proximity-based accessibility and multifunctionality. Tekla's relocatability provides access without user travel, promoting equal access to new technologies, especially in urban regeneration areas and remote schools. The analysis also shows that Tekla enables value chain actors to benefit from ecosystem collaboration and shared infrastructure. For example, EdTech companies engaged with a more diverse and inclusive group of learners during product development, and students from vocational schools gained real-world work experience by

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moving Tekla from school to school. However, the impact on workers is mixed. The concept requires continuous facilitation and fast-paced stakeholder collaboration, while also offering limited physical working conditions. Despite these challenges, workers express pride in their work and experience increased professional status and skills development.

The study contributes to the development of new S-LCA indicators tailored to the characteristics of temporary, circular learning environments. Although the findings are based on a single, context-specific case, they offer valuable insights on mobile classrooms supporting social sustainability in education. Future research will refine these and expand data collection through interviews with key stakeholders.

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Environmental benefits of reusing precast concrete elements: case study of hollow-core slabs

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Keywords: building component reuse, circular construction, life cycle assessment (LCA), precast concrete

ABSTRACT

Concrete is the most used construction material, simultaneously being highly carbon intensive. In conventional demolition the carbon investment is lost while concrete is crushed and downcycled. As a part of the ReCreate research project (EU H2020), this study investigates reuse of precast concrete elements (PCEs) as whole units - an act of circular economy that has been inadequately researched. Through life cycle assessment (LCA) the study determines the environmental impacts of reused hollow-core slabs that have been harvested from a case study building located in Tampere, Finland, and are repurposed in new construction projects. Data for the LCA was collected by documenting input and output flows of deconstructing, transporting and refurbishing the elements, forming a cradle-to-gate analysis. The environmental impacts of the reused hollow-core slabs are compared to corresponding newly manufactured PCEs. The results show that environmental benefits can be gained by substituting new PCEs with reused PCEs. Transportation is the most significant contributor, which highlights the importance of optimizing the distance between the donor building and the element factory where the refurbishment takes place.

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From potential to reality: Advocating for an evidence-based circularity assessment framework

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Keywords: Built Environment, Burden of Proof, Circularity Assessment, Circular Economy, Evidence-based.

ABSTRACT

Circularity is often treated as a design principle or strategic ambition to improve resource efficiency, but in practice, many of its claims remain unverified and untraceable. Existing assessment methods typically focus on intended design strategies or modelled impacts, rather than demonstrating real-world outcomes. This paper introduces the concept of evidence-based circularity assessment as an alternative approach for shifting from intention to actionable outcome. Drawing on an analogy of two contrasting ‘circular’ coffee pod systems, it illustrates how the credibility of circularity claims depends on the presence of verifiable evidence, coordinated infrastructure, and traceable processes. Building on these insights, the paper proposes a conceptual framework for assessing circularity, structured around three interdependent elements: proof, process, and persuasion. Finally, the paper explores how these principles can be applied in the built environment, where supporting systems are needed to track, evaluate, and realize circular material flows. The approach aspires to support more transparent, accountable, and adaptive forms of circularity assessment in complex real-world settings.

INTRODUCTION

In the early years of the 2020s, one global coffee company was fined with more than one million dollars for misleading consumers and investors about the recyclability of its plastic coffee pods. The company claimed that its pods are “100% recyclable” and that extensive testing has shown that they “can be effectively recycled”. In response, the recycling operators explicitly told the company that processing the pods was not commercially feasible. The design of the pods and the material choices were viewed as too costly and impractical to process, which was expected to result in significant amounts of waste to landfills. This wide gap from the coffee pod case questions the discrepancies between claimed recyclability and actual recycling outcomes: to what extent claimed recyclability guarantees recycling? Does this mean that recyclability could be treated as a reliable proxy for circular performance? In essence, it leads to the sanity check of what is really meant when circularity-related claims like materials, products or assets being (fully) recyclable or reusable are made.

The circular economy is based on a regenerative and restorative approach to production and consumption systems. It promotes waste management strategies such as reuse, repair, remanufacturing, and recycling, which are often referred to as the R-strategies (Morseletto & Haas, 2023). Within this paradigm, circularity is commonly described as the degree to which a product, material, or system remains in use, regenerates value, or avoids waste over time (EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy, 2020). But despite its appeal, circularity remains

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a contested and often vaguely defined concept (Dominko et al., 2023; Nikolaou et al., 2021). This ambiguity becomes especially problematic when circularity is treated as something that can be simply claimed, rather than something that must be demonstrated. When circularity becomes just an unsubstantiated claim, the consequences may be profound. For example, it can lead to misguided investments, poorly informed policies, and false consumer confidence (Kurnaz, 2021; Pölkki, 2024). Circularity is not simply a feature of what something is made of, instead, it is about what happens to it and can be proven to happen to it. This probes deeper question for the underlying circular reality, as to how can circularity be assessed not for its desired outcome (e.g., intended reuse after end-of-life) but proven outcome, beyond a reasonable doubt?

The gap between circularity as intention and circularity as outcome calls for a reassessment of how such claims are evaluated. Existing assessment methods in the built environment operate across different levels, ranging from products and materials to assets and broader systems, and address various aspects of the circularity landscape, including design strategies, policy frameworks, and operational practices (Feizollahbeigi et al., 2025; Khadim et al., 2022; Peng & Cao, 2025). Examples include Level(s) (Dodd et al., 2017, 2020a, 2020b, 2021; Donatello et al., 2021), Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) (Ellen MacArthur Foundation & Granta Design, 2019), Building Circularity Indicator (BCI) (Verberne, 2016), Material Flow Analysis (MFA) (Tanzer & Rechberger, 2019), and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) (Lei et al., 2021). They provide valuable insights into circular potential or modeled environmental impacts. However, these methods often focus on intended design strategies or predicted performance rather than on demonstrating whether circular outcomes are actually achieved in practice. As a result, they may lack transparency, traceability, and clear mechanisms to verify the real-world realization of circularity claims.

In this article, we argue that circularity claims, much like public declarations in legal settings, should be treated as assertions that carry a burden of proof (Stein & Allen, 2013). When a stakeholder, whether a developer, designer or contractor, makes a circularity claim, such as “this product is 100% recyclable” or “this building is 100% designed for disassembly”, they are, in effect, making a public assertion that should be answerable to others. Drawing inspiration from principles of legal accountability, they bear the responsibility to substantiate such claims with credible and verifiable evidence (Stein & Allen, 2013). Methodologically, this paper adopts a conceptual approach, using narrative review to explore how evidentiary logic can be adapted for circular construction in the built environment. The review process involved identifying and synthesizing insights from literature on circularity assessment, evidence-based practices, and legal reasoning, in order to trace gaps in current methods and inform the development of a new conceptual framework. The result is a set of conceptual building blocks that form the basis of an evidence-based assessment framework. These include the foundational elements of proof, process, and persuasion, which together offer an alternative lens for evaluating circular performance, not as a promise, but as a demonstrable reality.

This article questions the current ways in which circularity is assessed in both practice and academic work. It highlights that drawing on the principle of legal accountability can help to arrive at a different approach that treats circularity not as an assumption or a claim, but as something that must be demonstrated through proof, process and persuasion. In this way, stakeholders that wish to pride initiatives with a circularity claim would benefit from following a court-like synonym through which they carry the burden of persuasion to convince a jury or judge (e.g., regulators, clients or the public) that the evidence provided is strong enough to warrant belief and action. This adds to credibility of the actual circularity

that is desperately needed in our built environment. Just like a legal judgement is not made on possibility but on proof, circularity assessment must move beyond potential to documented reality with circularity claims being substantiated to demonstrate how circularity plays out over time. Without such a shift, circularity risks becoming a rhetorical gesture which sounds convincing but cannot be verified or trusted.

EVIDENCE-BASED CIRCULARITY: AN ANALOGY

The notion of “evidence-based” is not new. It originates from medicine, where it emerged as a corrective to expert-driven decisions that lacked systematic justification (Sackett et al., 1996). It quickly spread to policy, education and management, where it was seen as a way to improve transparency, accountability, and the quality of decision-making (Baba & HakemZadeh, 2012; Head, 2016). Over time, scholars have questioned the neutrality of evidence, emphasizing that what counts as valid evidence is shaped by social, political and institutional contexts (Greenhalgh & Russell, 2009; Reay et al., 2009). In such contexts, to act in an evidence-based way means that action must be guided by transparent, reproducible, and verifiable knowledge, not intuition or intent (Baba & HakemZadeh, 2012). Transposed to the context of circularity, the term marks a similar shift: from promises to proof, from intent to traceable result. Evidence-based circularity, in our view, could refer to the assessment of circularity claims based on verifiable outcomes, supported by credible documentation and transparent processes, not just design intentions or material properties. It asks not whether a product could be circular, but whether circular strategies, such as reuse, repurpose and recycling, actually occur and can be shown to occur.

To help ground this abstraction, let us return to a more relatable example. While the aforementioned coffee company failed to substantiate its recyclability claim, another coffee company operating in the same market took a more systematic and transparent approach. This company uses aluminum for its coffee pods, a material with a feature of indefinite recyclability (Bulei et al., 2018). However, this company also realized that technical recyclability was only part of the equation. To support its claim, it implemented a comprehensive take-back system by providing consumers with prepaid return bags, establishing thousands of collection points, and building dedicated facilities where used pods could be sorted, processed, and reintegrated into material cycles. The company also communicated openly about the outcomes, publishing what percentage of pods were actually returned and how the recovered materials were reprocessed. As we can see here, the circularity of the pods was not just implied by its material, instead, it was enacted by a network of commitments: consumer instructions, reverse logistics, processing infrastructure, and communication with stakeholders. This analogy offers a simple but crucial insight for how evidence-based circularity could be: the material itself is not the sole determinant of circular outcomes; what matters equally is the system that surrounds it, e.g., the network of responsibilities, actions, and follow-up mechanisms that allow circularity to occur and to be seen to occur.

EVIDENCE-BASED CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENT: A LEGAL ACCOUNTABILITY

The example of coffee pods systems is relatively contained because of a single-use product with a short lifecycle and a centralized actor responsible for closing the loop. The built environment, by contrast, is a vastly more complex ecosystem, where circularity claims, such as reuse potential, recyclability, or disassemblability, span decades, involve multiple phases and dozens of actors, and unfold across shifting regulatory, economic, and spatial conditions (Geldermans, 2016; Guo et al., 2024; Ofori, 2015). Claims made at the design stage can often disappear into the noise of execution.

At present, many circularity claims in the built environment remain more aspirational than operational. As Kanters (2018) observes, despite the presence of deconstruction principles and design-for-disassembly principles, less than 1% of buildings are actually constructed to be fully demountable. Similarly, although several modular systems claim to be relocatable and reusable, only a limited number of buildings have been successfully disassembled, relocated, and reinstalled in real-world conditions (Ling, 2023). Design for disassembly do not guarantee effortless disassembly and subsequent reuse. Yang et al. (2025) further emphasize that critical factors such as client ownership, digital material tracking, and the retention of component value play pivotal roles in enabling actual building reuse. The absence of these enabling conditions often results in circularity remaining a theoretical design ambition, rather than a realized outcome. This is not simply a technical shortfall but it reflects a deeper systemic accountability gap. Even when advanced tools such as Building Information Modelling (BIM) or material passports are used, they often serve as one-time records rather than evolving and verifiable sources of truth (Markou et al., 2025; Munaro & Tavares, 2021). These tools frequently fall short of functioning as instruments of accountability. They document what could happen, but they do not confirm what did happen. They may capture intended recyclability or reusability but not realized ones. Without institutional arrangements to update, audit, and enforce these records, the tools become static, like testimony without cross-examination. In such an environment, circularity claims lack both traceability and consequence. They can be made with ease but rarely carry the burden of proof or the expectation of follow-up. This is where an evidence-based circularity assessment, anchored in accountability, becomes not just preferable but necessary.

To address this accountability gap and explore how evidence-based circularity assessment could work in the built environment, we turn to the logic of legal proceedings. When a claim is made in court, the party making the claim carries the burden of proof. It is not enough to state something, instead, verifiable evidence that holds up under examination should be provided. The burden of persuasion is meanwhile equally important. Even if one has evidence, it must be presented in a form that jury or judge (i.e., regulators, client, the public) can evaluate and trust (Schauer, 2006). This means that circularity assessment must be not only accurate but also legible and verifiable. A material passport that lists components as “recyclable” means little unless it is kept up-to-date and linked to measurable outcomes after use (Markou et al., 2025). As with a testimony, clarity, transparency and traceability matter. The aim is not to penalize ambition but to reward accountability to support circularity claims that can be substantiated through documented processes and demonstrable results. To move toward an evidence-based framework, we propose an assessment structure inspired by courtroom reasoning. Rather than assuming that circularity happens because it was intended, we ask whether it can be demonstrated across the three interdependent dimensions of proof, process, and persuasion.

The first dimension, *Proof*, addresses the question of whether a circularity claim can be substantiated with verifiable evidence that circular outcomes have actually occurred. This can include audits, tagging systems, verified material transfers, or post-demolition tracking. Proof mirrors the burden of proof in legal reasoning, whether party making the claim must produce evidence that supports their assertion. In the context of circularity, proof corresponds to verifiable documentation that circular strategies were executed, not merely designed or intended.

The second dimension, *Process*, focusses on whether there is a functioning system in place that enables circularity to occur. This involves the availability of supporting infrastructures, regulatory mechanisms, and coordinated procedures that allow reuse, recycling, or other

circular strategies to be executed effectively. This relates to the concept of due process or procedural justice in legal systems, where how something is done is as important as what is done. In circularity assessment, it is not enough to declare that a material is recyclable, instead there needs to be a system that makes recycling actually happen.

The third dimension, *Persuasion*, concerns whether the presented information can convincingly support the circularity claim to those who must act on it, whether they are clients, regulators, or procurement officials. This dimension involves transparency, traceability, and the capacity to transform data into actionable knowledge. It mirrors the burden of persuasion in legal contexts, whether even with evidence, the claimant must present it in a compelling way to convince the decision-makers. In circularity assessment, persuasion is about whether evidence is traceable, clear, and credible enough for stakeholders to trust and act upon.

In the built environment, these three dimensions can be directly translated into practice. Proof relates to tracking materials and verifying that reuse, recycling, or recovery actually occurred. Process concerns whether infrastructures like material passports, deconstruction protocols, and recovery systems are in place to enable circular strategies. Persuasion involves providing traceable and transparent information that not only documents past actions but also clearly indicates the material's readiness for a next life cycle, which gives stakeholders a concrete basis for future decisions.

This conceptual framework with three dimensions shifts circularity assessment from speculative aspiration to accountable practice. It moves the emphasis from what could happen to what has happened, and how we know it. In this way, evidence-based circularity could become not just a concept, but a commitment to traceability, verification, and trust.

CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

This paper has introduced an evidence-based concept for circularity assessment, informed by principles of legal evidentiary reasoning and structured around the dimensions of proof, process and persuasion. Circularity, especially in the built environment, should not be judged on material potential or design alone, but on demonstrable outcomes achieved through credible evidence and supportive systems. The proposed evidence-based circularity assessment framework with three dimensions shifts the focus of circularity assessment from making claims to cases whether claims that must be substantiated, contextualized, and legible to others. In doing so, circularity moves from idealism toward institutional accountability.

Nonetheless, challenges remain. Current tools, such as LCA and circularity indicators, often focus on potential or modeled outcomes rather than observable results. Data on material reuse or recycling in construction projects is often fragmented or unavailable. Institutional incentives may reward declarations rather than verification. These challenges point to a need for further development in both research and practice.

Our next steps will be focusing on constructing and operationalizing this approach. There is also a need to better understand how evidence-based assessment interacts with certification schemes, procurement criteria, and policy instruments, many of which currently prioritize intentions over implementation. Future research will also explore how these systems can evolve to support more verifiable claims and facilitate adaptive learning across projects.

In conclusion, circularity assessment must evolve in both method and mindset. The move toward evidence-based circularity is not about perfection, but about progress that can be

demonstrated and improved upon. It asks not only whether something is circular in principle, but whether it is circular in practice and whether we have the evidence to show why, how, and to what extent.

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Life cycle assessment and cost analysis of circular timber vs. conventional building solutions: a case study of the Nydalen Factory, Oslo

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the environmental and economic performance of a circular renovation project in Nydalen, Oslo, where reclaimed timber and designed for assembly and disassembly components were used in place of conventional materials. Using an extended LCA and LCC system boundary that includes reuse and recycling (Module D), the analysis reveals substantial carbon savings, driven primarily by avoided impacts from biobased and reused materials, and highlights key cost trade-offs. Despite higher upfront costs, the circular solution showed long-term environmental benefits. The study demonstrates a practical application of LCA/LCC in capturing reuse potential, addressing methodological gaps in assessing circular construction.

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable construction is increasingly guided by circular economy principles, but evaluating circularity in practice remains methodologically challenging. This paper presents a case study of a renovated factory in Nydalen, Oslo, transformed into a circular hub using reclaimed timber provided by Omtre AS (Figure 1; Omtre AS, 2025). While Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) are standard tools for evaluating environmental and economic performance, their application to circular construction reveals methodological limitations.

Key challenges persist in integrating circularity indicators such as adaptability, reuse potential, and longevity into LCA and LCC frameworks (Lam et al., 2022; Larsen et al., 2022; dos Santos Gonçalves et al., 2025). In particular, the frequent omission or inconsistent treatment of reuse, recovery, recycling potential (Module D) undermines the ability of LCA to reflect material reuse or recycling benefits (Van Gulck et al., 2022). This is especially critical when reclaimed biobased materials like timber are involved, as current LCA methods struggle with accounting for biogenic carbon flows, storage, and substitution effects (Andersen et al., 2021; Rasmussen et al., 2023).

Rather than proposing new metrics, this paper extends the system boundary of traditional LCA/LCC to include reusing scenario at the end of life, offering practical insights into how reclaimed wood and circular construction practices can be evaluated more meaningfully. Drawing on recommendations from the EU-funded DRASTIC project (2025), the study illustrates a pragmatic approach to bridging methodological gaps in the sustainability assessment of the built environment (Rajagopalan et al., 2021; Buyle et al., 2019).

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Figure 1. Nydalen project design sketch by Malene L. Grimsgaard (left) and photo by Sebastian Larsson during the installation of the wooden structures and furniture (right).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Nydalen project features two main circular construction solutions: partition walls using Grape’s lock system designed for easy dismantling and reuse, and walls and benches made from Norsk Massivtre panels with reclaimed timber (Fig. 2). The functional unit for the LCA and LCC is the 310 m² of internal partition elements and furniture constructed with these solutions. The assessment focuses on these components and compares them to business-as-usual alternatives, steel stud walls with gypsum boards and benches made from virgin wood, to evaluate their relative environmental and economic performance.

Figure 2 Walls developed by Grape without glue and screws for easy disassembly, maintain and reuse (left). Walls and benches built using Norsk Massivtre product in Nydalen project (right) (Photos by Grape).

The LCA followed a cut-off allocation approach, where environmental burdens are assigned only to processes beyond the point of material collection. This reflects the material’s previous life and avoids double counting of embodied impacts (Van Gulck et al., 2022). Reclaimed timber was used instead of virgin wood, significantly affecting the carbon profile. The analysis was performed using openLCA 2.1.1, with environmental impacts assessed according to the EN 15804+A2 methodology. In line with EN 15804+A2, biogenic carbon is considered neutral at the point of reuse, and no new sequestration is credited.

The system boundary of this study is defined based on a cradle-to-end-of-life approach in accordance with LCA methodology. It includes the following life cycle stages: Product stage (A1–A3), covering raw material supply, transportation, and manufacturing of the materials and products used. For reclaimed materials, this also includes the reclamation process, such as on-site sorting during demolition, transportation, and off-site cleaning and sorting (Table 1, see RT*);

Construction process stage (A4–A5), encompassing the transportation of materials to the construction site and their installation; and End-of-life stage (C1–C4), which involves demounting, waste disposal, and waste handling processes. The Use stage (B1–B7) is excluded. The hub has a defined lifespan of 10 years, due to its temporary status. Therefore, long-term operational and maintenance factors are omitted. The future reuse and recycle potential of these materials are considered in Module D, which quantifies the avoided impacts due to production and waste treatment/disposal of equivalent virgin materials beyond the current system boundary.

Module D is calculated using the next formula, which was developed based on the substitution method according to EN 15804+A2: **Impact module D** = $I_{reuse/recycle} - I_{new\ materials} - I_{waste\ treatment}$ where $I_{reuse/recycle}$ is the impact associated with preparing materials for reuse or recycling (e.g., transportation to storage, repair, maintenance, cleaning, sorting, melting, or crushing); $I_{new\ materials}$ is the impact of producing the equivalent virgin materials and $I_{waste\ treatment}$ is the impact that would have occurred from the end-of-life treatment or disposal of those virgin materials. It is important to clarify that biogenic carbon regarding $I_{new\ materials}$ is not accounted for in the calculation, because carbon sequestration never takes place, but biogenic emissions generated due to waste treatment are included. For instance, the avoided climate change – biogenic from incineration process is included.

In the Nydalen case, 90% of the components are assumed to be reused in the next cycle based on supplier estimations. In contrast, for the BAU scenario, it is assumed that 90% of steel waste and 20% of gypsum board waste are fully recycled into new equivalent products (Table 1), consistent with typical Norwegian construction waste management statistics (Statistics Norway, 2020).

Table 1 Inventory Data

	<i>Nydalen project</i>	<i>Business as usual scenario</i>
	4 h labour	
RT*	90 t*km lorry 16ton, EURO 6 5.0E-7 item sawmill construction, EUR	Not applicable
A1-A4	16.1 m ³ – reclaimed timber, NO 3.7 m ³ – virgin timber, NO 57 kg screws, GLO 18 pcs metallic sliding door fitting, GLO ~ 70 km – lorry 16ton, EUR 6	324 kg – light steel frame 216 m ² gypsum plasterboard 28 kg – screws 6.7 m ³ virgin timber 18 pcs metallic sliding door fitting ~ 5 km – lorry 16ton, EUR 6
A5	60 h labour 2 h machine operation, diesel	155h labour 2 h machine operation
C1-4	46.5 h labour 2 h machine operation, diesel ~ 30 km lorry 32ton, EURO 6 1.98 m ³ waste wood, incineration 5.7 kg scrap steel, landfill	120h labour ~ 30 km lorry 32ton, EURO 6 6.7 m ³ waste wood, incineration 172.8 m ² gypsum board waste, landfill 53.2 kg scrap steel, landfill
D	-17.82 m ³ wood elements, reused -51.3kg screws, reused -18 pcs metallic sliding door fitting, reused	-478.8 kg steel, recycled -43.2 m ² gypsum board, recycled

*RT= Reclaimed timber, 1 m³

The LCC followed the same system boundary as the LCA and was carried out using an Excel-based model, aligned with the principles of EN 16627. A real-term approach was used, where prices exclude inflation and only a 4% real discount rate, as recommended by the Norwegian Ministry of Finance, was applied. Currency conversion from NOK to EUR was based on the exchange rate on

the day of calculation (April 3, 2025). Most cost data, including materials, labor, transportation, installation, and waste disposal, were informed by contractor feedback, previous project experience, and reference prices from local service providers.

Table 1 presents a detailed overview of material quantities and sources. Datasets were sourced from Ecoinvent 3.10 at the unit process level, representing European markets for steel and gypsum boards, global markets for specific fitting parts sourced out of Europe, and regional markets (Norway/Sweden) for timber products. Transportation distances for Module A2 are included in the data sets. In addition, primary data was provided by OMTRE AS, the project manager, along with components supplier Norsk Massivtre, and Grape AS. Their input enabled accurate modeling of both environmental and economic aspects, including real-world data on demounting time, transport, and storage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The life cycle assessment of the Nydalen project (Table 2) reveals a clear environmental advantage over the conventional BAU scenario, primarily driven by the substantial emission savings in Module D. By incorporating the reuse potential of the circular building components, the project achieves a net carbon benefit of $-10,138.79$ kg CO₂-eq, in contrast to a net emission of $3,343.50$ kg CO₂-eq in the BAU case. These avoided impacts, especially in biogenic carbon emissions, highlight the importance of extending system boundaries beyond end-of-life to include the benefits of material substitution. The BAU scenario, despite initially sequestering carbon through virgin timber use, ultimately results in higher emissions when this carbon is released at the end of life without substitution. This contrast underscores the importance of reuse strategies, particularly when using biobased materials, to mitigate climate change impacts in the construction sector.

Table 2 Results LCA (kg CO₂ eq)

<i>Project</i>	<i>Impact Category</i>	<i>A1-A3</i>	<i>A4</i>	<i>A5</i>	<i>CI-C4</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>Total</i>	
Nydalen	CC, Total	5838.70	137.44	8.69	1860.70	-17984.32	-10138.79	
	CC, Biogenic	4590.76	0.13	0.02	1785.54	-16069.71	-9693.26	
	CC, Fossil	1245.90	137.25	8.67	75.08	-1907.93	-441.05	
	CC, LULUC	2.04	0.06	0.00	0.08	-6.68	-4.48	
	CC, Total	-	2031.23	6.13	9.49	6406.97	-1047.86	3343.50
BAU	CC, Biogenic	-	4114.99	0.01	0.05	6042.16	-14.86	1912.36
	CC, Fossil	2079.80	6.12	9.44	364.45	-1032.67	1427.13	
	CC, LULUC	3.96	0.00	0.01	0.36	-0.33	4.01	

*CC= Climate Change; LULUC= Land use and land use change

Table 3 Results LCC (EUR)

<i>Project</i>	<i>A1-A3</i>	<i>A4</i>	<i>A5</i>	<i>CI-C4</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>Total</i>
Nydalen	43078.73	792.00	3379.20	3232.42	-16763.65	33718.70
BAU	10615.13	176.00	8395.20	7383.46	0.00	26569.80

Although the product stage (A1–A3) in Nydalen has higher impacts due to labor and energy intensive processing of reclaimed timber, the fossil-related emissions in this stage are still 60% lower compared to BAU. This is attributed to the replacement of energy and emission intensive virgin materials with reclaimed timber. The results also show marginal benefits in climate change–

LULUC, reflecting slight reductions in land-use change through avoided extraction of primary timber resources. The most decisive contribution comes from Module D, which offsets emissions from both fossil and biogenic sources and reinforces the value of substitution accounting in circular construction assessments. Additionally, the lower end-of-life impacts in Nydalen (C1–C4) reflect its design for disassembly and simplified material separation, contrasting with the higher disposal burdens seen in the BAU approach.

In terms of life cycle cost (Table 2), the Nydalen solution incurs substantially higher costs in the product stage, driven by manual sorting, cleaning, and preparation of reclaimed timber, and the lack of industrial processing infrastructure. High labor rates in Norway further exacerbate these expenses, making A1–A3 the dominant cost contributor. However, this disadvantage is partially compensated by lower installation costs in A5, resulting from the use of modular and easy assembly components, which simplifies on-site assembly. Transportation costs (A4) are slightly higher due to the logistics of handling reclaimed materials from a further source. At the end-of-life stage, Nydalen again performs better, with reduced costs due to recoverable materials and fewer disposal burdens compared to BAU.

The most significant economic advantage for Nydalen emerges in Module D, where a credit of –€16,763.65 reflects the avoided cost of virgin materials, disposal savings, and potential residual value of reclaimed components. The BAU scenario, by contrast, lacks these savings and produces limited or depreciable returns from material recovery and recycling. Despite the higher initial investment, Nydalen’s total life cycle cost is only 27% greater than BAU, which may be justifiable considering its substantial environmental benefits, policy alignment with circular economy targets, and potential future cost internalization through carbon pricing or material scarcity.

CONCLUSION

The Nydalen project demonstrates that integrating circular design strategies and reclaimed materials into construction can lead to substantial reductions in life cycle carbon emissions. While the approach entails higher initial costs, particularly in material processing and labor-intensive preparation of reused elements, these are partially offset by downstream savings in installation, end-of-life, and material substitution stages. The results highlight the critical role of Module D in capturing the environmental benefits of reuse and recycling, which are often excluded in conventional cradle-to-grave assessments. However, the project also reveals the economic challenges of current circular construction practices, particularly the lack of industrial infrastructure for handling reclaimed materials. This underscores the urgent need for further development and scaling of industrial processes to improve the cost-effectiveness, efficiency, and accessibility of material reuse in the building sector, but also to explore the impact of different business models enabling multiple use cycles on the LCC and LCA results. While focused on low-performance requirements, the findings provide a valuable foundation for expanding circular strategies into more demanding renovation contexts, supporting both climate goals and the transition to a more resource-resilient built environment.

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Modelling life cycle impacts of recycling and reuse of building components

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Keywords: Case study, Circular Economy, Construction, Design for Deconstruction, Life Cycle Assessment, Reuse

ABSTRACT

In life cycle assessments (LCA), the environmental impacts of the different stages of a building's or building product's life cycle are evaluated in the Modules A, B and C. Module A includes the product stage, as well as the construction stage, Module B describes the use stage and Module C the end-of-life stage according to EN 15978 and EN 15084. Module D summarizes the positive and negative impacts beyond the system boundaries of the studied life cycle.

Our study focuses on Module D1, which shows the potential of reuse and recycling of construction components and materials in their next life cycle. Although the general approach to modelling such impacts has been introduced in the new EN 15804+A2:2019, its application to scenarios with multiple recovery options (such as recycling and reuse), and to materials with specific LCA features (such as open/closed loop recycling or carbon sequestration) needs to be further clarified. The study is based on the methodology developed in the ADVANCE project for assessing Module D1 of constructional steel [1]. A building component made from three material options, which are timber, reinforced concrete and steel, is evaluated for different reuse and recycling scenarios to show the method's applicability. The selected building component is part of a preliminary design of the Finnish "Circular Drifter" building by VTT and Aalto University [2], developed to promote Design for Disassembly (DfD) and simplified reassembly. In this study it is shown that the methodology given in EN 15804 and further developed in the ADVANCE project can be applied to commonly used structural materials and it shows the environmental potential of their reuse and recycling accordingly.

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Reducing environmental impact with advancing circularity: conceptual framework for sustainable construction

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Keywords: circularity, circular economy, environmental impact, LCA, sustainable construction

ABSTRACT

The built environment significantly affects resource consumption and environmental burden, in terms of large share of natural resource depletion, greenhouse gas emissions, and waste generation. As construction demands continue escalating, it becomes essential to adopt approaches that reduce environmental impact while prioritizing circularity. This reduction can be supported by life cycle thinking of construction projects, which involves evaluating the environmental impact through the lifespan, followed by the optimization of designs and plans with consideration of circularity. This study explores the potential of integrating environmental impact and circularity to promote sustainable construction practices. Frameworks such as life cycle assessment (LCA) and circular economy (CE) models serve as useful tools to achieve this target. However, implementing these frameworks within the built environment involves multiple aspects such as optimizing design, material selection, construction methods adoption, operational plans, and rethinking decommissioning. In addition, the implementation may take place across different types of construction projects: buildings to be built, existing buildings in need of renovation, and buildings to be decommissioned or repurposed. Therefore, the implementation and relevant evaluation criteria should be tailored to meet specific requirements, depending on e.g., the type of construction project, stakeholders' emphasis on smart building design, and regional policies promoting timber material. To foster a systemic shift towards sustainable construction, the study proposes a conceptual framework integrating circularity into LCA. LCA serves as the primary evaluation criterion, and the CE model works as a supporting tool. The LCA is simplified by aligning with the Finnish low-carbon assessment method. The CE model is tailored to specific construction project types and provides guidance for design and subsequent LCA analysis. Multiple scenarios, such as modular design, adaptive design, material recycling and reuse plan, are generated for each project type using the CE model. LCA is then performed under these scenarios, with results informing decision-making and optimization of the project. Furthermore, to ensure the framework's effectiveness, collaboration among architects, engineers, developers, and policymakers is essential for addressing feasibility issues and refining the approach. In summary, this study highlights the imperative of creating a resilient and low-carbon built environment, also proposes a framework to achieve this target by minimizing environmental impact and advancing circularity.

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ResourceRevival: Redefining the urban mine to close local loops and move toward resource-neutral districts

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Keywords: Brick-Recycling, Circular Deconstruction, Material-Flow-Analysis, Nature-Based-Solutions, Resource Mapping, Resource-Neutrality, Social-Urban-Mining

ABSTRACT

The reuse of building materials is widely discussed in the context of urban mining. However, a truly circular district approach goes far beyond this. The exploratory project *ResourceRevival* aims to transform the *Werk Möllersdorf* - a 24,000 m² former industrial site in Traiskirchen, Austria - into a resource-neutral mixed-use quarter, including subsidized housing. As part of a co-creative concept development process, the project brings together previously separate strands all heading towards circular economy. It identifies synergies between the availability and demand of resources such as building materials, rainwater, greywater, and renewable energy, and aims to close local loops in an integrated and interdisciplinary way. The project explores a new application field for secondary raw materials, strengthening regional material cycles. Emission and cost analyses will quantify the ecological and economic added value of the resource-optimized planning. The development of modular tender criteria and a template for resource inventories for material flow analyses will support transferability and implementation in future projects. While the preservation and reuse of existing structures is the preferred strategy under circular economy principles, six industrial halls have proven incompatible with the site's future use. Their circular deconstruction will yield over 2,000 tons of predominantly post-war brickwork, which will be assessed for technical suitability and ecological integrity in nature-based solutions, such as substrate or drainage layers in green roofs and filling material for stormwater infiltration systems. *ResourceRevival* exemplifies circular district development that sees materials, energy, and water as interconnected assets - redefining the urban mine and advancing the transformation toward a circular built environment.

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The Environmental Benefits of Relocation and Renovation of Heritage Wooden Buildings versus New Construction

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ABSTRACT

Relocating underused heritage buildings offers an opportunity to recover their cultural significance, residual material value, and utility, thereby reducing environmental impact and promoting a circular economy in the built environment. While several studies have compared the potential environmental benefits of renovating an existing building versus replacing it with a new one, there is a notable absence of case studies examining the environmental impact of building relocation. Therefore, this study aims to address the following question: Are the total emissions from building relocation and renovation still environmentally favorable compared to those from new-building construction? To address this question, a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is employed. The results indicate that the building relocation and renovation have a lower environmental impact. However, the emissions from building relocation are influenced by variables such as road characteristics, the technology utilized, and the standards adopted.

Keywords: Building Relocation, Renovation, Life cycle assessment

1. INTRODUCTION

Reusing existing buildings can lead to substantial reductions in greenhouse gas emissions. For instance, adaptive reuse of a historic building can result in an 82% reduction in global warming potential compared to new construction [1].

In areas undergoing socio-spatial changes that preclude renovation and rehabilitation of a building on the original site, building relocation serves as an alternative reuse strategy to prevent demolition [2]. This method involves either relocating the building intact or through disassembly and reassembly, thereby facilitating its renovation and rehabilitation at a new site. Building relocation is practiced as a preservation technique, but as a last resort [3-5]. This approach proves advantageous for circular reuse [2] and waste reduction [6].

In evaluating the environmental impact of buildings, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a standardized tool that addresses the environmental burden throughout a building's life cycle [7]. This method quantifies the environmental load from various stages—production, construction, use, and end-of-life—and can be employed to compare the impact of different choices of materials and designs at each stage [8].

Research on the LCA of existing buildings has primarily focused on improving building performance for rehabilitation and energy efficiency, as well as the benefits of embodied energy and materials, e.g., [1, 7, 9-12]. However, there is a lack of research quantifying the greenhouse gas emissions (GHGe) associated with building relocation, encompassing the stages of preparation, transportation, and the construction of a new foundation at the new site. This study aims to expand LCA calculations to include GHGe from building relocation, preparation, and construction of new

foundations, in addition to renovation. It will determine whether the environmental impact of building relocation and renovation outweighs that of demolition and new construction.

2. CASE STUDY DESCRIPTION

In 2012, the Norwegian Defense Estates Agency (Forsvarsbygg) decided to establish a combat aircraft base in Ørland for the Royal Norwegian Air Force [13]. This development will affect many vernacular buildings due to high noise levels from airplanes. Among these, 26 heritage-listed buildings are in the noise red zone [14]. To protect them, Forsvarsbygg has decided to relocate these buildings to a new urban site in Brekstad (Figure 1).

Among these buildings is Grande A, a farmhouse built in 1923 with log walls. It is a two-story structure on a stone masonry basement, with a gabled roof supported by purlins and rafters, covered with slate. The facades are clad with vertical wood panels. Grande A is listed as heritage Grade C in Ørlandet municipality (more info in Table 3). According to Norwegian conservation regulations, for this Grade, the exterior characteristics of the building's form, design, and materials must be preserved, while the interior layout can be redesigned to better fit new uses [15]. Retrofitting measures for this case study comply with previous research [13], as specific measures are proposed for this typology to preserve the cultural values associated with the buildings while ensuring that the renovation meets the necessary energy standards.

A new base foundation is required to install Grande A after relocation. At the new site, in Brekstad, the first floor must be constructed no lower than +3.5 meters above sea level. Consequently, a concrete slab-on-grade foundation with a stem wall is assumed [13]. The construction and thermal requirements of the new foundation adhere to current Norwegian regulation TEK17.

Figure 1. Ørland Municipality, showing the areas affected by red noise zone due Ørlandet airport expansion [14]. The original location of Grande A building (red star) and planned new location in Brekstad (green triangle).

3. METHODOLOGY

The LCA calculations adhere to NS-EN-ISO 14083: 2023 [16] for relocation and NS 3720: 2018 [17] for renovation and subsequent life cycle. For existing buildings, the system boundary is defined using the cut-off allocation method, where the remaining service life and end-of-life are independent of the first life cycle [17]. The impact assessment is limited to Global Warming Potential (GWP) expressed in carbon dioxide equivalents (CO₂e). This assessment examines GHGe arising from (1) building relocation, (2) disposal of remaining building parts at the original

site, (3) building renovation, including the construction of a new foundation at the new site, and (4) use of the building for 50 years.

The relocation process emissions account for the GHGe of the transport chain operation according to [16]. This standard is adopted due to the heavy load transport (the weight of the building) and the machinery needed for building separation, bracing, lifting, transportation, and placement. This standard requires the inclusion of GHGe from the transport operation and processes at sites (“hubs”) from energy use and provision that enables the transfer of the freight (the building) and activities [18]. Transport chain includes all activities from a point of origin to destination and is specified by sequence of transport chain elements (TCE), which divide the process into similar section based on activities, e.g., load transshipment, passenger transportation, or type of vehicle. Building relocation from the original site to the new site in Brekstad occurs once during the building’s entire life cycle. The emissions calculation considers the weight of the building, the vehicle technology, the traveled distance, the road characteristics, fuel type and the operation duration (Table 1). Building relocation emissions are calculated in MS Excel with related emission factors adopted from [16].

The building energy consumption for both renovation and new building is modeled for space heating connected to the district heating system. The energy performance of renovation scenario is calculated using building energy simulation software OpenStudio [19] with the energy improvement measures from Table 3. For the new building scenario, the calculation is according to the Norwegian standard for the net energy requirement limits which is (100 + 1600/m² heated floor area) [20]. The GHGe from renovation and energy demand is analyzed using Reduzer software [21] with data from Environmental Product Declarations.

Demolition waste such as concrete, masonry, bricks and tiles can be repurposed as filler material, reducing landfill use and conserving natural resources [22], generally not harmful to the environment [23]. In this analysis, the emissions from the disposal of remaining building parts are calculated based on their use as filling material for the original basement. However, this application is subject to safety checks to ensure the absence of hazardous substances.

The results are compared to the reference emission value according to the Norwegian Agency for Public and Financial Management [24] for a similar new building, limited to the emissions from material use [25], Table 2.

The scope, life cycle stages, system boundaries, and building systems are shown in Figure 2. The present condition of the building, materials and assemblies, and the renovation measures are presented in Table 3, where Table 1 describes the details of the relocation operation.

Table 1. Information for relocation process based on [16].

Route characterization	Road transport + Ferry Transport	Crane Truck	68 tonnes **
Total traveled distance	230 km*	Emission control technology	Euro VI
Topography/Road type	Hilly/Motorway	Fuel Type	Diesel
Temperature	Ambient	Operation Time	40 hours

* Including 5 km building transportation and 225 km machinery transportation. ** Lifting capacity.

Table 2. The GHGe reference values for a similar new construction [24].

Module	Upper Ground Strc. (Timber)	Foundation (Concrete)	Total CO ₂ e/m ²
A1-A3	136.3	71.2	207.5
A4	15.8	3.1	18.9
A5	13.9	0	13.9
B2, B4	34.4	0	34.4

Figure 2. Assessment steps and system boundaries.

Table 3. The building materials and assemblies and the proposed measure for renovation.

Grande A		Typology: Residential / farmhouse
	Construction year: 1923	Structure: Log wall & half-timbered.
	Gross Floor Area = 210 m ²	Stories: two floors, original basement is excluded from the building relocation,
	Heated Floor Area = 181 m ²	Heating system after renovation: the crawl space under the gable roof is not headed.
	District heating	
	Building weight = 64 tonnes	Energy use after renov.: 129.8 kWh/m ²
Building Parts	Description	Upgrading Measures and improved U-values
Roof top	Slate is in good condition.	Reusing slate, 20 % replacement of deteriorated wooden structure, installation of 200 mm mineral wool in the attic.
Roof structure	Partial decay in structure.	
Attic	Insulation in attic.	U_{Roof} = 0.162 W/m²K
External wall	Load-bearing logs	The bearing logs are in good condition and will be reused with no extensive treatments, replacement of façade cladding, and installation of 150 mm mineral wool insulation for exterior.
Internal wall	Load-bearing logs	U_{External wall} = 0.158 W/m²K
Floors	Wooden & vinyl covering with post-insulation.	Replacement of floor covering with 90% wooden and 10% ceramic.
External doors and Windows	Wooden doors from the 90s.	Replacement of external doors and adding secondary glazing for windows to comply with energy efficiency requirements and airtightness.
		Air tightness (q50) = 3 h⁻¹, U_{Doors} = U_{Windows} = 1.5 W/m²K
New Foundation	100 mm reinforced concrete mat foundation, 200 mm EPS, and vapor barrier/radon barrier.	U = 0.164 W/m²K
Existing Found.	The existing basement and foundation, along with the fireplace, and chimney are assumed to be used to backfill the existing basement cavity and level the ground.	

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results indicate that the renovation of Grande A, including its relocation, is less emissions intense compared to the target new building values (Fig. 3). In total, the renovation and relocation of Grande A emits 46.5 tonnes CO₂e, which represents a 56 % reduction compared to the new building (82.9 tonnes CO₂e) over 50 years. The consumption of new material for renovation and energy upgrades, and the construction of the new foundation, accounts for the majority of initial emissions for Grande A.

The emissions from the building relocation, which account for the emissions from the transport operation and the processes at the site, contribute 1.5 tonnes CO₂e, representing 10% of the initial renovation process impact (Fig 4). It is important to note that, based on NS-EN-ISO 14083, the emissions from labor (passenger) transport should be included. However, NS 3720 exempts this requirement. To align with the building LCA standards, the emissions from this activity are excluded from the calculation.

Figure 3. The total GHGe from Grande A renovation in contrast with the target new building values.

Figure 4. GHGe emissions related to the production, operation and maintenance of Grande A relocation, renovation, and use for 50 years, compared with target GHGe values for new building, per life cycle stages. The green arrows show the percentage of avoided GHGe, and red arrows show an increase in GHGe from the renovation scenario in comparison to the reference values.

The resulting GHGe from the energy demand for space heating for Grande A is 149 kg CO_{2e}/m²/year, which is 17.2% higher than the missions from the standard energy use for a residential building, coupled with the same district heating system, which is 120 kg CO_{2e}/m²/year (Fig. 4). This higher impact is due to lower airtightness, measured at 3 h⁻¹. Yet, this has been significantly improved through energy measures, reducing it from the original 10 h⁻¹ [13].

As depicted in Figure 4, the life cycle stages present varied environmental burdens. The main contributors to avoided emissions are the reuse of the existing log structure of Grande A, resulting in a 78.7% lower emission in the production stage (A1-A3), followed by a 76.6% reduction for future maintenance and replacement (B2, B4), and a 63.9% reduction for construction transportation (A4). The emission loads from the two life cycle stages, construction (A5) and building operation (B6), are higher compared to the reference GHGe values, but these are dwarfed in magnitude by the significant avoided emissions from the other stages. The impact from building relocation—building transportation and on-site activities—is allocated to the building renovation stages A4 and A5, respectively. The resulting impact from the demolition of the remaining building parts at the original site is minimal, as the remaining parts are assumed to be used to fill in the basement cavity.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The primary objective of the study was to examine the additional GHGe associated with the building relocation process and the construction of a new base foundation, alongside the emissions from the renovation process. The findings indicate that the renovation of Grande A, including its relocation and its projected energy use, saves overall 56% of emissions compared to a new, similar building.

The significant role of reusing existing resources accentuates the environmental benefits of renovation, even when the building is relocated to a new site and meeting the additional construction requirements, in contrast to new building construction. However, this is heavily dependent on assumptions about achievable energy standards for relocated buildings and energy generation systems.

The relocation of the heritage wooden buildings in Ørland is currently in the development stage, and there is limited information on the primary data, which will be available in the near future. This introduces certain limitations to this study. To adequately calculate the GHGe loads and allocate the impact, the following measures need to be improved:

- It is more effective to develop the new building scenario to better align with the technical measures of Grande A when making comparisons.
- The energy upgrade measures adopted need to be critically assessed for their impact on the aesthetic features of the building, which contribute to its cultural significance.
- GHGe from the relocation process is calculated based on the actual building details and geographical data, but the utilized technology is assumed. As the type of technology—their energy use, and provision of the energy—are core criteria for the transportation environmental impact; it is important to adhere to primary data for the building relocation process.

Additionally, this study's innovative application of transport chain LCA standards to building relocation requires further research to enhance its applicability for such scenarios. It is also important to evaluate the trade-off between the potential environmental and cultural benefits versus the additional costs that come with the relocation process.

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Circularity in the Built Environment 2025

Circular construction and real estate business

A Circular Early-Design Strategy for Deutsche Bahn's Real Estate Assets

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ABSTRACT

This paper outlines a strategic framework for circular construction strategy within the real estate portfolio of Deutsche Bahn (DB). A specific case study at the Mühldorf station demonstrates how such a reuse strategy for in-situ and pre-cast concrete elements can be operationalized in practice. The approach includes the identification and assessment of reusable components, on-site evaluation of structural quality, and the development of a reuse catalogue aligned with current standards. By integrating structural assessment, digital material passports, and quality assurance protocols, the strategy supports DB in transitioning from linear construction to circular value creation. The resulting methodology offers scalable potential for embedding reuse practices across DB's real estate assets.

1. Circular Strategies for Real Estate Portfolios

The construction sector is one of the most resource-intensive industries, consuming around 90% of all mineral resources [1] and generating more than half of Germany's annual waste volume [2]. For large property owners like Deutsche Bahn (DB), this presents both a challenge and an opportunity: how to manage an extensive and aging real estate portfolio in a way that aligns with climate and resource-efficiency goals.

The ReCreate project [3] offers valuable insights into the reuse of structural building components, including the development of supporting workflows, validation methods, and references to evolving legal and normative conditions. Drawing on these experiences, this paper outlines a tailored reuse strategy for DB's real estate assets. It focuses on how reusable elements can be identified, assessed, and integrated into new projects and will be demonstrated through a case study at the Mühldorf station.

While the potential for reuse in building projects is widely acknowledged, there is a lack of tested frameworks for integrating reuse audits, quality assurance, and design coordination within large public real estate portfolios. This paper addresses this gap by demonstrating how a structured reuse approach can be embedded into DB's planning and project workflows.

2. Foundations of a Reuse Strategy

In recent years, several core principles and methods have emerged to support such reuse strategies:

From a technical perspective, these include the definition of key parameters for the structural validation of concrete and reinforcement-steel components, and the handling of incomplete historical data through assumptions based on typical construction practices at the time. These are complemented by quality control measures and matching procedures that take into account geometry, structural capacity, material, and dimensional tolerances.

On the organizational side, early integration of reuse considerations in planning has proven essential, supported by structured workflows and digital documentation. Newly developed standards such as DIN SPEC 91484 “Procedure to record building materials as a base to evaluate the potential for a high-quality reutilization prior to demolition and renovation work (pre-demolition audit)” [4] offer a useful reference point for consistent evaluation and traceability, while the limited availability of BIM-based data remains a practical challenge. From an ecological perspective, substantial carbon savings can be demonstrated when reusing structural components; clearly exceeding the performance of newly produced alternatives, including those made from recycled concrete or low-carbon materials. This confirms the relevance of reuse as a key lever in reducing the environmental impact of the built environment.

3. Mühldorf Station as a case study

3.1 Project description and activities

The Mühldorf station served as a pilot case to explore how reuse strategies could be applied within Deutsche Bahn’s real estate portfolio. The building, a reinforced concrete skeleton structure from 1976, features a combination of in-situ concrete and prefabricated exposed-concrete façade elements. The project investigated both the technical feasibility and practical implementation of component reuse based on the building’s current condition and documentation.

The scope of activities included:

- A detailed on-site inventory and inspection of the precast façade elements, including the identification of connection details and surface conditions,
- A preliminary structural assessment of the precast elements as well as selected in-situ components such as walls and slabs,
- The development of a reuse catalogue aligned with DIN SPEC 91484, including material specifications and classification of reuse scenarios,
- Development of a procedure to guarantee a reliable quality assessment approach
- An evaluation of both the technical feasibility and economic implications of reuse, including demolition logistics, reprocessing needs, and potential re-integration into future planning.

The Mühldorf railway station is an in-situ concrete skeleton structure from 1976. The station comprises three buildings of different heights: The larger office wing, the station entrance hall, and the smaller gastronomy area. The modern design is characterized by a terraced, horizontally structured façades, the distinctive stairwell and the projecting entrance hall roof. The materials most visible are concrete, brickwork, natural stone and aluminium.

The non-load-bearing exposed concrete façade elements were designed as prefabricated elements with a rough-sawn textured formwork surface. The prefabricated façade elements do not envelop the entire building. Parts of the building (e.g. stairwell) were constructed in in-situ concrete without additional curtain wall elements. The cantilevering roof of the entrance hall is a wooden structure.

Figure 1. and Figure 2.
left: Mühlendorf railway station, office wing;
right: close up of the surface structure of the façade elements

For the railway station with adjoining office wing, a review of the potential reuse of load-bearing components in a new building has been commissioned. The initial situation here was based on previous cost and demand estimates, which suggested that refurbishing the existing building would not be economically feasible and that more floor space would be required than is covered by the existing building. For this reason, several reports documenting the state of the structure were made available at the beginning of the project, e.g. the quality of the façade elements had been investigated on two sample elements.

As shown in the following images, sample elements were deconstructed during those investigations and reinstalled later.

Therefor the practicability of deconstructing and reinstalling for the façade elements has already been proven. For those elements where no damages are visible and where the carbonation has not yet reached the reinforcements a strategy for (adaptive) reuse will be outlined. During the first on-site visit, it also became apparent that the damage to the in-situ concrete main structure was largely limited to the upper stories. For this reason, reuse scenarios and a possible reuse strategy are also being developed for in-situ concrete elements of good quality.

Figure 3. and Figure 4.
left: Mühlendorf railway station, deconstructed façade element for inspection,
right: façade with deconstructed element reinstalled

3.2 Outcome of pre-demolition audit

The building was inspected on site as part of a PDA (pre-demolition-audit) in accordance with DIN SPEC 91484. The façade elements are in a reusable condition, except for the elements on the south side of the building, due to carbonation. The remaining service life for the elements has yet to be determined.

On the upper floors, some moisture damage has been identified on the main supporting structure due to leaking roof surfaces. This moisture damage can be repaired with a certain amount of effort. The lower floors are free of damage.

However, the audit also highlighted challenges typical of legacy buildings, including inconsistent documentation, variable material quality, and difficulty identifying connection types. These issues emphasize the need for standardized digital records and flexible assessment methods to support future reuse efforts.

Excerpt of PDA stage 1 (preliminary assessment):

Nr.	Betrachtungsebene	Bezeichnung	Verortung	Verbindungstypen	Menge	Höhe	Gebrauchszustand	Funktionen	Potential für Anschlussnutzung
	Gebäude Bauteil Bauelement Komponente Material					[m m]		Tragstruktur	ja / nein / keine abschließende Bewertung möglich
1	Bauelement	Fassaden	N	Gewindestangen, Edelstahl	36	div.	gut	Fassaden	ja
2	Bauelement	Fassaden	S	Gewindestangen, Edelstahl	34	div.	verwittert	Fassaden	nein
3	Bauelement	Fassaden	O	Gewindestangen, Edelstahl	5+6	div.	gut	Fassaden	ja
4	Bauelement	Fassaden	W	Gewindestangen, Edelstahl	5+6	div.	gut	Fassaden	ja
5	Bauteil	Decken	-	monolithisch	div.	18cm 20cm	div.	Decken	ja

Excerpt of PDA stage 2 (detailed testing):

Nr.	Einbaujahr	Bestehende Unterlagen	Spezifische Attribute	Verbindungsart	Demontierbarkeit	Potenzielle Anschlussmöglichkeit
		CE-Kennzeichnung Ü-Kennzeichnung Typenschilder Datenblätter Leistungs-/Konformitätserklärung	durch: Datenblätter Produktnormen Proben	nachDGNB Gebäude-ressourcenpass	nachDGNB Gebäude-ressourcenpass	nach DGNB Gebäude-ressourcenpass
1	1977	n.v.	C30/37	geschraubt	Geringer Aufwand / Zerstörungsfrei lösbar	
2	1977	n.v.	C30/37	geschraubt	(wie 1)	

3	1977	n.v.	C30/37	geschraubt	(wie 1)	
4	1977	n.v.	C30/37	geschraubt	(wie 1)	
5	1977	n.v.		festverbaut	Hoher Aufwand / reparable Schäden	

4. Towards a Circular Strategy for Deutsche Bahn

To implement a scalable reuse strategy across Deutsche Bahn’s real estate portfolio, a coherent system of technical processes, data standards, and regulatory pathways must be established. Building on the findings from the Mühlendorf pilot, the proposed strategy comprises several interdependent components that collectively enable reuse as a viable, verifiable, and repeatable practice.

4.1 Early Phase Planning and Component Audits

At the core of the approach lies early integration within planning workflows. Structured component assessments, based on pre-demolition audits as defined in DIN SPEC 91484, allow for the systematic documentation of materials, connection types, geometric properties, and dismantling potential. In parallel, tools such as the DGNB building material passport and the DGNB circularity index provide structured criteria to evaluate the reuse potential of elements and support decision-making in early design phases.

4.2 Reuse-Oriented Deconstruction Planning

Deconstruction is approached not as demolition but as a carefully staged process tailored to the recovery of high-value components. This includes assessments of cut lines, planning of crane access and temporary structural supports, and the systematic labelling and cataloguing of elements to maintain traceability. The cleaned elements must be protected during intermediate storage to retain their usability, requiring logistical planning and coordination between deconstruction and potential reuse sites.

4.3 Multi-Level Quality Assurance

A robust, multi-stage quality assurance process supports structural integrity and regulatory acceptance at every step. Initial evaluations in the built state combine visual inspections with archive and BIM-based documentation. Suitability testing of selected components includes non-destructive assessments of carbonation depth, reinforcement layout, and material strength. After removal, further visual and technical inspections confirm the absence of critical damage, with supplementary tests employed as needed to verify long-term storage stability. If minor deterioration is present, repair techniques such as re-alkalization of concrete may be applied to restore functional performance.

4.4 Regulatory and Approval Pathways

Structural reuse must align with national and sector-specific regulatory frameworks. Especially for load-bearing elements, approval procedures may involve multiple actors, including the Eisenbahn-Bundesamt (EBA) for all DB projects. The strategy therefore requires early clarification of regulatory responsibilities, the use of standardized templates for documentation, and traceable evidence of quality and condition for each reused component.

4.5 Technical and Economic Evaluation

To ensure practical viability, reuse scenarios must be evaluated from both technical and economic perspectives. This includes assessing the feasibility of adaptations (e.g. cutting, drilling, surface preparation), estimating costs for testing, transport, and reprocessing, and comparing these with new production. Adaptive reuse options, for example, reusing slabs as walls or foundations, can increase flexibility and overall material yield.

4.6 Design integration into new projects

To fully realize the reuse potential of reclaimed components, integration into the design phase of new construction projects is essential. This requires early coordination between planning teams and material inventory databases, enabling architects and engineers to incorporate available components as functional and aesthetic elements from the outset. Reused elements should not be treated as constraints, but as design drivers that inform geometry, detailing, and material expression. Standardized digital representations, e.g. BIM objects enriched with reuse metadata, can support seamless integration, while adaptive design approaches allow flexibility in accommodating component variability.

4.7 Strategic Integration into DB Processes

To scale reuse beyond individual projects, the strategy must be embedded in DB's planning systems and digital infrastructure. Reuse audits should become a standard step in project development, ideally supported by digital twin environments for lifecycle tracking. Procurement and approval workflows need to incorporate reuse criteria and streamlined verification protocols. Reuse-matching capabilities within DB's databases could further support cross-project material allocation, provided they align with DB's specific regulatory and operational requirements.

This approach is not only technically feasible but also strategically aligned with DB's sustainability goals. As part of its corporate strategy, DB aims to achieve climate neutrality and establish a circular economy by 2040. Binding targets for 2030 include significantly increasing recycling rates and integrating circular practices across the full asset lifecycle - from procurement through use to eventual dismantling.

5. Conclusion and Next Steps

The Mühlendorf station pilot validates a practical reuse strategy informed by ReCreate's methods. To scale this across DB's portfolio, next steps include embedding reuse workflows into early planning and building a centralized reuse platform. The result: a railway infrastructure network that values and systematically reuses its structural assets.

While the proposed approach is robust, its effectiveness depends on data completeness, stakeholder coordination, and regulatory flexibility. Limitations include challenges in material traceability and the variability of site conditions. Nonetheless, the pilot demonstrates a replicable method that integrates pre-demolition audits, structured quality assessment, and design-phase coordination to enable circular construction at scale.

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A stakeholder-Issue mapping of reuse of residential buildings.

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Keywords: Circular economy; Circular built environment; Building reuse stakeholders, Reuse of buildings, urban regeneration.

ABSTRACT

The reuse of buildings offers a sustainable alternative to demolition and new construction, extending the lifespan of structures and promoting a more circular built environment. However, the decision-making process involves stakeholders from diverse disciplines with often conflicting interests, creating significant challenges. Identifying these stakeholders, defining their roles and scope of action, and mapping their interrelations with reuse challenges are crucial steps in determining where and how the reuse process can be accelerated to enhance circularity in the built environment.

Accordingly, this study addresses the question: Who are the stakeholders involved in the challenges and conflicts of interest that hinder the reuse of buildings? Using a semi-systematic literature review followed by thematic analysis, five key stakeholder groups are identified: (1) Property owners, (2) Investors, (3) Government representatives & Regulators, (4) Building professionals, (5) Users, community & civic society. The findings highlight the pivotal role of building professionals, who engage with most challenges and can act as mediators beyond their expected technical roles. Additionally, government representatives, regulators, and investors are identified as key initiators of the reuse process. Furthermore, while users, community, and civic society are not always directly involved in decision-making, they influence the process indirectly, and their inclusion is essential for the long-term success of reuse projects.

Existing research on building reuse often adopts a single-disciplinary perspective, overlooking interdisciplinary dynamics and offering limited focus on residential buildings. This disciplinary approach risks overlooking key stakeholders and their roles in the reuse process. To address this gap, this study takes a holistic, multidisciplinary approach to identifying stakeholders and mapping their influence on reuse challenges. By enhancing the understanding of stakeholder dynamics, the findings provide valuable insights for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners seeking the advancement of circular reuse practices in the built environment.

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Addressing System Challenges and Driving Change: Leveraging Stakeholder Collaboration in Developing Innovative Solutions for Wood Waste

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Keywords: stakeholder collaboration, system challenges, system changes, wood waste

Abstract

The pressing need for climate change mitigation and global timber shortage underscores the importance of addressing efficient and sustainable resource use. Better use of wood resources is gaining support from legislative bodies, especially in Europe, where the reuse and recycling of materials often take precedence over incineration for energy production. A recent study revealed that one-third of wood recovered from buildings is suitable for high-value recycling, indicating that the potential amount of waste wood for recycling is significantly higher than the current utilization (Höglmeier et al., 2017).

Yet, in Norway, an estimated 805 000 tons of wood waste were generated in 2022; still, only 3.5% underwent material recovery, with the remainder being directed to incineration (SSB, 2023), indicating a large potential for wood waste utilization. However, developing innovations, business strategies, and new value chains for wood waste requires new ways of thinking and a mindset shift, as the wood and construction sectors are well-established in the current existing infrastructures, practices, norms, and standards. Yet, such a development compels collaboration between various stakeholders, including businesses, government agencies, and communities (Berardi & de Brito, 2021; Sudusinghe & Seuring, 2022). We strive to understand this by investigating a case study on the wood construction sector in Norway. The main data input for this study comes from two stakeholder workshops and 16 semi-structured interviews. We organized the two workshops, approximately 30 participants representing designers, architects, builders, industry associations, and researchers, in the form of the World Café in September 2023 and in October 2024. By bringing together the stakeholders in direct and mutual dialogues, we intend to stimulate a joint discussion of common challenges in wood waste management and how the stakeholders could collaboratively tackle these challenges. We also carried out the semi-structured interviews with relevant actors between the first and the second workshop in the period February-August 2024.

This study sheds light on several challenges. Virgin wood and building materials in Norway are cheap, making disposal inexpensive and recycling unattractive. The disassembling and sorting process is resource-intensive and entails high costs, requiring specialized skills and knowledge. Regulatory barriers include restrictions on the use of reclaimed wood and unclear policies on recycling. There are no clear standards concerning sorting criteria and requirements, encompassing uncertainties about which elements of wood waste to consider, how the mapping process should be conducted, and who will be responsible for reusing, testing, and declaring reused materials. Furthermore, there is a lack of consensus on methods, and industry interest in supporting standardization is limited. Insufficient market demand for products derived from recycled wood, coupled with the weak economic viability and incentive to invest in the new value chains, is another obstacle. Utilizing wood waste efficiently requires advanced technologies in all phases, from mapping, disassembling, and sorting wood waste to testing and categorizing wood qualities, which are not currently in place. There is also limited awareness among stakeholders about the potential value and opportunities associated with wood waste, and the absence of a well-developed infrastructure for efficient collection and transportation systems.

Addressing these challenges involves a multi-faceted approach that includes raising awareness, improving infrastructure, revising regulations, stimulating market demand, and fostering collaboration among stakeholders. Stakeholders' discussion points to solutions such as establishing a "quality stamp" that can enhance resale value and instil consumer confidence in their purchases, incentivizing contractors to boost the demand for recycled materials, coordinating transport for the waste return with

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as few intermediate stations as possible, and especially elevating public procurement concerning wood waste.

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Business Model Canvas for Residential Adaptive Reuse

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Keywords: adaptive reuse, business model, circular business model, contractor

ABSTRACT

The construction industry is affected by several ongoing crises, derived from e.g. the climate emergency and geopolitical challenges. Thus, new thinking and novel business models are much needed. The major role of the construction industry in the climate energy and resource depletion calls for sustainable and circular business models specifically. Consequently, this study aims to develop a sustainable business model for one construction process, namely, adaptive reuse of existing buildings to housing ('residential adaptive reuse'). The business model is created with the help of a strategic management tool, Business Model Canvas. The traditional elements of the canvas are complemented with two new elements, eco-social costs and benefits. The developed business model is based on two expert workshops held online in June 2024. The participants comprise 12 industry professionals representing contractors, developers, and public sector clients. The findings are synthesized into one circular business model canvas. The findings reveal that the business model differs from that of new construction, most significantly in the eco-social elements included in the canvas. Avoiding greenfield development and the use of existing infrastructure and buildings deliver the most benefits. The largest cost savings in both economic and environmental terms derive from existing foundations and the building stem. On the other hand, the typical tendency of adaptive reuse projects to use environmentally sound, aesthetically pleasing and high-quality materials was identified as an extra cost. In addition to the cost structure and revenue streams, the customer segment and customer relationships for adaptive reuse projects also differ somewhat from new construction. Speciality housing, such as student housing or elderly care, were seen as potential clients. Traditional contracting forms, such as the full-cost model, are not seen as suitable. Instead, adaptive reuse projects should favour long-term, partnering type commitments. The developed business model canvas with the distinctive elements may work as inspiration and guidance to contractors looking to venture into adaptive reuse projects.

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Circular management of residential stock: needs, approaches and calculations

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Keywords: Carbon accounting; circular stock management; lifetime extension; new construction; renovation; sustainability.

ABSTRACT

The awareness that the throw-away society must be turned into sustainable reuse is growing. Due to climate change and the consequences for nature and the environment, governments have become aware of their responsibility for policy measures towards a circular economy. The Dutch government has declared that the Netherlands has to be fully circular in 2050 - that is that raw materials retain their value - and has started the implementation of that target; and the construction and real estate sector is preparing for this.

But change does not happen overnight. The transition to circularity is a complex process. The concepts, goals and guidelines that are used are not clear and the possibilities have largely yet to be discovered. How, where and with what to start, which approach and at what level? Greenwashing is lurking.

This contribution deals with those questions, focused on the housing stock. Although the number of construction projects (NL) labelled as circular is steadily growing, they concern most of all new construction. But new construction is only a limited part of the task. The annual new construction volume is less than 1% of the existing stock. New construction is therefore certainly not the highest form of circularity, even if it makes maximum use of sustainable and/or reused materials.

Lifetime extension through continued use by means of renovation and retrofit covers the entire existing stock and therefore has a much greater potential to achieve true circularity. Our paper is focused on renovation. It starts with an exploration of the concept of circularity. Next, it is discussed how this can be applied on the existing housing stock and housing needs (NL). We will address the question of how the constantly changing quality of new homes relates to the quality of existing homes, and what that means for the concept of circularity in the housing stock. The results of a recent study into the sustainability (in terms of CO₂ footprint) and costs of the most important intervention variants at home level subsequently provide insight into the effects of choices made from a circular management perspective.

Enablers of Material Reusability in Urban Infrastructure Renovation: Insights from Amsterdam

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Keywords: Material Reusability, Circularity, Construction Industry, Reusability Assessment, Sustainability

Abstract

In response to the growing need for renovating aging urban infrastructure, this study investigates the key factors influencing material reuse within circular renovation practices. Focusing on multiple projects in Amsterdam, four critical enablers of reusability were identified through expert interviews: material quality, willingness to reuse, reuse policy, and early stakeholder engagement. By highlighting these factors, the study advances understanding of circular renovation strategies and contributes to achieving the Sustainable Development Goal for sustainable cities and communities.

Introduction

In historic city centers like Amsterdam, aging bridges and quay walls require urgent renovation due to overdue maintenance and increasing urban activity, particularly freight traffic. This has led the municipality of Amsterdam to launch a comprehensive program to assess and restore approximately 200 kilometers of quay walls and 800 bridges. Aligning with broader societal goals such as climate adaptation, energy transition, and circularity, this initiative has fostered collaborations between public institutions, researchers, and market parties. Among these, the "Urban Bridges and Quay Walls" (Urbi quay) program, supported by the Dutch Research Council (NWO), is dedicated to developing sustainable and circular solutions to enhance the resilience of urban infrastructure. Within this program, the Logiquay project focuses on circular logistics and multi-project control to accelerate renovations, improve oversight, and enhance sustainability through material reuse and emission reduction.

Several research endeavors addressed reusability assessment of construction materials ((Bellini et al., 2024; Coenen et al., 2021; Mollaei et al., 2023; Rakhshan et al., 2020). Rakhshan et al. (2020) identified six primary categories of factors that influence component reuse: economic, environmental, organizational, regulatory, social, and technical. Among these, economic considerations were found to be the most influential, followed by technical and organizational aspects. In a more recent contribution, Bellini et al. (2024) proposed eight information-based criteria for evaluating the reusability of construction products. These include environmental impact (e.g., greenhouse gas emissions), technical specifications, expected lifespan and quality, ease of disassembly, logistics and storage needs, placement within the project, risk assessment, and cost analysis.

Mollaei et al. (2023) emphasized the influence of regional conditions, such as public perception, the maturity of the secondary materials market, regulatory frameworks, and landfill fees, in shaping material recovery practices. Meanwhile, Coenen et al. (2021) suggested that reusability can be assessed through three indicators: disassemblability, transportability, and uniqueness. Disassemblability and transportability relate to individual components, while uniqueness pertains to the asset as a whole. Components that are easier to disassemble and transport are considered more reusable. This method offers a quantitative assessment of reusability for each component but demands detailed input data, which may not be consistently available. Moreover, it does not consider the material's quality when determining its reuse potential.

Supporting the aims of the Logiquay project, this research investigates how different factors impact the reusability potential of materials and can contribute to circular renovation practices in urban infrastructure. By analyzing multiple projects, this study will identify key data and people factors influencing reusability potential. This research investigates the key factors that contribute to successful material reuse in renovation projects. In exploring these dimensions, this research contributes to Amsterdam’s overarching ambition to develop sustainable, reusability methodologies that can serve as scalable models for other municipalities facing similar infrastructure pressures. By advancing our understanding of reusability potential in renovation projects, this study supports the broader goals of sustainable urban development and future-resilient infrastructure. The research is structured around the following questions:

1. What factors impact material reusability in the construction industry?
2. Which factors most significantly influence material reuse in the circular renovation of urban infrastructure?

Materials and methods

To address the first research question, a literature review was conducted. This review identifies and synthesizes factors that influence the effective management of materials across the renovation lifecycle. Table 1 shows an overview of the factors impact the material reusability. 49 factors are identified and are classified into six classifications, Technical, Functional, Environmental, Financial, Organizational, and Stakeholder. In the third column, the relevant sources are listed. According to the table, the functional group contains the highest number of factors, followed by the stakeholder-related group, with 14 and 11 factors respectively. This highlights that, in addition to technical and material-related considerations, human and project-related factors also play a significant role in enabling material reuse.

Table 1 Factors influencing material reusability

Classification	factor	Source
Technical	Standard materials	(Charlotte et al., 2022; Condotta & Zatta, 2021; Matrai, 2019; Ottosen et al., 2021)
	Component uniqueness	(Coenen et al., 2021)
	Technical requirements (structural)	(Bellini et al., 2024; Matrai, 2019)
	Material condition	(Bellini et al., 2024; Devenes et al., 2024)
	Life expectancy	(Bellini et al., 2024)
	Material inspections	
	Product documentation	
	Design phase standardization	(Hradil et al., 2019; Silva, 2023)
Functional	Infrastructure	(Coenen et al., 2021)
	Component interfaces and connections	
	Transportability	
	Storage capacity and location	(Almeida et al., 2022; Bellini et al., 2024)
	Ease of deconstruction	(Bellini et al., 2024)
	Availability and scheduling of materials	
	Storage duration and preservation	
	Transportation logistics	

	Sorting and storage facilities	
	Design for disassembly	
	Economic risks	
	Technical risks	
	Uncertainty due to limited data	
	Risk management	
Environmental	Carbon-saving potential	(Bellini et al., 2024)
	Hazardous material identification	
	Energy consumption	
	Recyclability of materials	
Financial	Landfill and incineration taxes	(Freire-González et al., 2022)
	Market creation for reusable materials	(Banias et al., 2022)
	Financial benefits	(Nußholz et al., 2020; Schützenhofer et al., 2022)
	Cost evaluation	(Bellini et al., 2024)
Organizational	Pre-demolition audits	(Condotta & Zatta, 2021; Spišáková et al., 2022)
	Mandatory regulations for material reuse	(Condotta & Zatta, 2021)
	Knowledge sharing platforms	(Christensen et al., 2022)
	Stakeholder awareness and collaboration	(Christensen et al., 2022; Matrai, 2019; Yetunde Adenike Adebayo et al., 2024)
	Reuse in Design Process	(Rakhshan et al., 2020)
	Reuse in Contract	
	Components management coordinator	
Experience with reused materials	(Densley Tingley et al., 2017; Rakhshan et al., 2020)	
Stakeholder	Early engagement	(Heuvel, 2024; Yetunde Adenike Adebayo et al., 2024)
	Collaboration	(Bellini et al., 2024; Yetunde Adenike Adebayo et al., 2024)
	Trust	(Matrai, 2019)
	Willingness to compromise	
	Transparent communication	(Yetunde Adenike Adebayo et al., 2024)
	Information exchange	(Bellini et al., 2024)
	Risk-sharing	(Matrai, 2019; Rakhshan et al., 2020)
	Reputation	(Van Remmerden et al., 2025)
	Visual appearance concern of architects and contractors	(Rakhshan et al., 2020)
	Public awareness of reuse	
Willingness to reuse		

In addition to the various parameters presented in Table 1, other factors may also play a crucial role in determining material reusability. One such factor is the method of material harvesting. Selective deconstruction typically offers a higher potential for material reuse compared to sudden demolition (Assefa & Ambler, 2017). Adopting a multi-project perspective can further enhance reusability potential (Ashrafi et al., 2025). In this approach, projects are viewed as part of a broader system where material supply and demand are made transparent. Within multi-project environments, early-stage collaboration and joint planning among stakeholders can facilitate material sharing and project synchronization—ultimately promoting greater circularity and material reuse.

The second research question is addressed through semi-structured interviews with experts. The interviewees—stakeholders involved in the renovation of Amsterdam’s bridges and quay walls—represent a range of roles within the projects, including contractors, engineering firms, and municipal experts. To gather insights, five interviews were conducted. During the interviews, participants were asked to evaluate the reusability factors presented in Table 1. They rated the importance of each factor on a scale from 1 to 5. The average score for each factor was then calculated, and the four factors with the highest ratings were identified. The findings from these interviews are discussed in the following section.

Results and discussion

Building on the insights gathered about data, information, and stakeholder dynamics, this section identifies the factors that stakeholders consider most important for enabling material reusability in projects. During the interviews, stakeholders ranked both technical and non-technical factors. The role of each interviewee and their score for each factor are represented in the Table 2.

Table 2 Four factors with the highest score

		Material Quality	Willingness to Reuse	Reuse Policy	Early Engagement
Interviewee 1	Project Lead	4	4	4	3
Interviewee 2	Project Lead	5	4	4	3
Interviewee 3	Contract Manager	5	5	3	4
Interviewee 4	Project Lead & Technical Manager	5	5	4	3
Interviewee 5	Project Controls Manager	4	4	5	4
	Average score	4.6	4.4	4	3.4

The four factors that emerged as the most critical for supporting material reuse are as below:

- **Material Quality:** This factor received the highest average score of 4.6 out of 5. According to the interviewees, materials must be in good condition and suitable for reuse—particularly structural elements like beams and columns.
- **Willingness to Reuse:** This factor, categorized under stakeholder-related aspects, received the second-highest score with an average of 4.4 out of 5. This indicates that stakeholders involved in the projects should actively promote and integrate material reuse throughout both the design and execution phases.
- **Reuse Policy:** This factor represents the average of two related aspects from the organizational category—reuse in contracts and mandatory regulations for material reuse. With a score of 4 out of 5, it ranks third in importance. The findings suggest that making reuse a mandatory requirement in contracts or municipal guidelines can significantly enhance circularity within projects.
- **Early Engagement:** Ranking fourth, this factor falls under the stakeholder-related category and received a score of 3.4 out of 5. The findings highlight the importance of involving all key stakeholders from the early stages of the project. In particular, early

engagement of contractors and secondary material providers during the design phase is considered crucial.

The findings reveal that while technical and material-related factors—such as material quality—are crucial for enabling reuse, stakeholder involvement and supportive organizational measures play an equally important role. High scores for factors like willingness to reuse, reuse policy, and early engagement underscore the need for an integrated approach that combines physical feasibility with institutional commitment. This suggests that successful implementation of material reuse in urban infrastructure renovation requires alignment between technical capabilities, stakeholder motivation, and regulatory frameworks.

Conclusion

Circularity is essential for creating a more sustainable construction industry, with material reuse playing a central role. This study first identified key factors influencing material reuse based on existing literature. It then focused on the circular renovation of urban infrastructure in Amsterdam. The identified factors were evaluated through expert interviews with professionals involved in these projects. Four top-rated factors emerged as the most critical enablers of circular practices: material quality, willingness to reuse, reuse policy, and early stakeholder engagement. These findings emphasize that, in addition to technical and material-related aspects, stakeholder involvement and human-centered factors are fundamental to successfully implementing material reuse in urban infrastructure renovation.

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Estimating the National Scale Economy of Reusable Building Components Through Simulation

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Keywords: circular economy, market behavior analysis, recycled building components, re-use markets, simulation modeling

ABSTRACT

Climate change requires more sustainable and regenerative practices in industries, including construction. Strong incentives are being proposed for the construction and planning of buildings to increase the re-use of materials and building components. However, even though showcase examples of materials and components being re-used successfully in individual projects, large scale markets to supply and deliver good quality re-usable components have not yet developed.

In this work, we aim to increase understanding of market behavior of re-usable components in different scenarios, and, to this aim, we developed a simulation tool to assist researchers in market analysis and modeling. In the simulation, we model the supply of recycled materials and the purchasing logic of second-hand material customers. The simulation environment enables the study of the effects of supply and demand trends and assesses the influence of intermediate storage and upcycling facilities on the purchasing logic of customers. A large number of controls are provided to the user to generate market scenarios.

Our preliminary results are based on two different types of materials, one being a larger component with a higher requirement of upcycling before reinstallation and the other a bulk component with high throughput. Varying the costs of disassembly, upcycling and reinstallation and the availability of storage spaces, market behavior is analyzed in volume, commercial value, logistical requirements and carbon emissions. The AnyLogic based tool is shared for wider use contributing to market and policy research.

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Evaluating the financial viability of building material reuse: Insights from a contemporary case study

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Abstract: The construction sector significantly impacts environmental degradation, consuming nearly half of the world's raw materials. Adopting circular economy principles, such as material reuse, can enhance sustainability. However, in the absence of reliable cost data on material reuse, a dual perception persists: on one hand, reuse is considered cost-effective due to the avoidance of material production costs; on the other hand, the labor-intensive nature of dismantling and processing—combined with high labor costs—can render it more expensive than purchasing new materials. This study examines the financial viability of reclaiming materials from a contemporary dwelling, not designed for disassembly. It quantifies the costs of reuse based on interviews with experts in practice and compares this to different market values and new material prices.

Findings show that labor-intensive deconstruction and material processing drive reclamation costs, while transportation and storage contribute minimally, except for high-volume materials like insulation. Glulam is the most financially viable material for reuse due to its high market value and relatively low cost for reuse. Timber frames, doors, windows, façade bricks and faience will tiles can be financially viable under specific market conditions. Conversely, hollow clay bricks, concrete and insulation are consistently unprofitable to reclaim due to high processing costs and low resale values. The study concludes that, within the current financial context, prioritizing high-value materials with low deconstruction and processing costs is essential to ensure the financial viability of material reuse.

Keywords: Case study; Financial costs; Housing; Reuse; Urban mining

1. Introduction

The construction sector, a cornerstone of human progress, has paradoxically become a harbinger of environmental degradation. It is responsible for consuming nearly half of the world's raw materials and stands as one of the main consumers of natural resources [1]. Yet, within this crisis lies an extraordinary opportunity: the circular economy. By embedding principles of reuse in practice, the sector can pivot towards sustainability [2]. In this study 'reuse' denotes the process of disassembling materials, processing and reimplementing them. However, in North-Western Europe, currently only 1% of the materials from a demolition site are reused [3]. Financial costs are a decisive factor to opt for a material and currently there is a dual perspective regarding the financial implications of reuse [4, 5]. On one hand, there is a perception that material reuse is more cost-effective due to the absence of production costs [6, 7]. On the other hand, reclamation processes—such as dismantling, cleaning, transport etc. — are necessary to facilitate reuse and are often time-consuming and labor-intensive [5, 8]. In regions with high labor costs, such as Western countries, these processes can make reuse more expensive than new materials. Furthermore, logistics for collecting, transporting, and storing reused materials generate additional financial costs [9]. The financial viability of material reuse remains insufficiently understood, primarily due to the absence of high-quality datasets on associated costs [10]. Addressing this research gap, the present study gathers cost data through expert interviews, enabling an analysis of the financial viability of reclaiming materials from an existing contemporary dwelling in comparison to both new material prices and market values.

2. Methodology

The methodology of this study consist of two parts: (1) description of the case study and (2) determination of the financial costs of reuse.

2.1 Case study

The IbSN house, designed by BLAF Architects and located in Sint-Niklaas (Belgium), has been selected as case study for this research (Figure 1). Although the dwelling was constructed as recently as 2017, it was expropriated in 2025 due to urban planning considerations. As this situation makes it impossible to preserve existing materials on site, a research project ‘Build, DE-Build & RE-Build’ is established to investigate the reuse potential of the available materials. The project aims to maximize the reuse of all materials, while this study only focuses on the available building materials and excludes the foundation, fixed furniture and technical installations.

Figure 1. Visuals of the IbSN house by BLAF Architects.

The first step of this study involves identifying the materials that are predominantly present in the case study. This is achieved through a detailed analysis of primary construction documentation, such as architectural plans and the bill of quantities. The mass and volume of materials are critical factors in material reuse. The mass primarily affects the deconstruction process, whereas volume plays a key role in the transportation and storage of materials [11]. Consequently, both parameters are investigated for this dwelling.

2.2 Financial costs of reuse

Due to limited literature regarding costs of reuse, information to determine the costs of deconstruction, processing (e.g. cleaning, sawing, planing etc.), packaging, transport and storage is gathered through interviews with experts in practice. In total, representatives from eight reuse companies, six contractors, two logistical companies and three material manufacturers are interviewed. The financial viability of reuse is then investigated using the cost-benefit analysis (Formula 1) [12]. The difference between the total costs and the market value represents the profit margin; the greater this difference, the more financially beneficial reuse of a material becomes. The formula considers only upfront and direct costs associated with reuse and excludes value-added tax (VAT) and potential subsidies. All cost costs are reported in euros (€).

$$(C_{dec} + C_{proc} + C_{pack} + C_{tran} + C_{stor}) * F_r < V_M \quad (1)$$

The costs of deconstruction (C_{dec}) and processing (C_{proc}) are estimated based on the required labor time and multiplied by the average hourly labor cost in Belgium (€48 per hour [13]). The interviews indicated that the labor costs for construction workers are broadly in line with the national average, justifying the use of this rate. The costs of packaging (C_{pack}) are limited to the costs of EURO pallets and big bags, no other materials are included. Based on the interviews, the transportation costs (C_{tran}) are estimated at €90 per hour, assuming a vehicle load of 75% over a 100 km distance and storage costs (C_{stor}) are anticipated at €2 per square meter per month for a six-month period. Transportation and storage costs are assumed to be outsourced to external logistics providers. Due to the absence of relevant data on the risk factor (F_R), it is assumed to be equal to 1, neutralizing its impact. The costs of reuse are weighed against different comparison values. The first one is the market value of the reused materials

(V_M), determined through two distinct methods: (1) interviews with reuse companies (data only available for some materials), and (2) a 20% reduction to the new price of the material. Additionally, the costs of reuse are compared against new material prices with and without waste processing costs. The new material prices are derived from the project's original building information, updated to current values using the ABEX index [14]. The costs of waste treatment are sourced from the Public Waste Agency of Flanders (Belgium) [15]. In this study, material losses from damage during deconstruction and processing are accounted for by reducing the remaining material quantities used to calculate new material prices and market values. The financial viability is analyzed at both the material and building levels, with the former assessing individual materials and the latter evaluating the overall potential of reusing all available materials collectively.

3. Results

Based on mass, façade and hollow clay bricks collectively account for 48% of the total material composition, while concrete represents 34% (Figure 2). However, when assessed by volume, their proportions decrease, while low density materials -such as timber and insulation- become more significant, accounting for 16% and 41% of the total volume, respectively.

Figure 2. Share of materials available in the case study when addressing the mass and volume.

The highest costs associated with material reuse are primarily attributed to materials that dominate in both mass and volume, namely bricks, concrete flooring, and timber frames (Figure 3). In contrast, insulation materials, while occupying a substantial volume, contribute relatively little to the overall costs. In general, reclamation costs are predominantly influenced by deconstruction expenses, which range from 20% for cellulose to 95% for concrete flooring. However, some materials incur substantial processing costs, such as the removal of nails from timber frames (up to 53% of the total reclamation costs), the assessment of thermal conductivity in insulation materials (up to 40%), and the extraction of mortar from bricks (31%). In contrast, expenses related to transportation, packaging, and storage are generally minimal compared to other cost factors. Nevertheless, for insulation materials, these costs can reach 10%, 15%, and 16%, respectively. These high logistical costs associated with insulation materials are due to their large volume, which significantly increases logistical expenses.

When evaluating the total cost of material reclamation in relation to their market value, certain materials demonstrate financial viability for reuse. Using the market value established through interviews -the most stringent criterion- only the glulam structure is found to be financially viable for reuse. This is attributed to glulam's relatively high market value, which allows it to be sold at a premium price, in combination with limited processing costs. When comparing the costs of reuse to the market value determined by a 20% reduction to the new material price, additional materials, including timber frames, doors and windows, also become financially viable for reuse. For timber frames, the costs are associated with both dismantling and processing (nail removal and planing), whereas for doors and windows, the primary cost only arises from the deconstruction process. Finally, when the reclamation costs are scaled against the new material price (with and without waste processing costs), façade bricks and faience wall tiles also become financially viable for reuse. For façade bricks, the combined costs of deconstruction and mortar removal are high; however, the price of new ceramic bricks slightly

exceeds these costs, making reuse viable. For faience wall tiles, the new price compensates the reclamation costs, which are mainly caused by dismantling and mortar removal.

The reclamation costs of hollow clay bricks, concrete and insulation materials consistently exceed the comparison values, making them financially unviable for reuse. In the case of concrete and hollow clay bricks, the high costs of the labor-intensive deconstruction combined with the relatively low cost of new concrete materials, contribute to its lack of financial viability. For insulation materials, the disparity between reclamation costs and comparison values is less pronounced. However, the requirement to test the thermal conductivity for reuse as thermal insulation significantly increases the associated costs, making financial viability challenging. Though, it can be questioned whether testing is required, since the material did not exceed its service life. Furthermore, insulation materials can be repurposed as noise insulation minishing the need for testing and providing a more cost-effective reuse option.

Figure 3. The total financial costs (expressed in euros) for reusing the materials in the dwelling (per weight). The bar charts indicate the share of different reclamation processes. The scatter plots provides the new material price with (New+waste) and without costs of waste processing (New) and market value of the materials based on a reduction of 20% to the new price (MV: 20%) and interviews with reuse companies (MV: RC).

An analysis of the total costs associated with reusing all materials from the case study (Figure 4) reveals a total expense of €65 201. The most beneficial comparison value for reuse is the combination of the material new price and waste processing costs. This equals €66 966 for the entire building en generates a slight benefit of 3%. However, when waste processing costs are excluded from the comparison, the equivalent cost of new materials decreases to €64 767, nearly offsetting the reclamation expenses. Hollow clay bricks and concrete flooring incur high reclamation costs but have a relative low new material price. In contrast, glulam elements, windows, and doors exhibit the opposite trend, with lower reclamation costs and higher new material prices.

Nonetheless, in current market conditions, it remains unfeasible to sell reused materials at the same price as their new equivalents. When the reclamation costs are assessed against a market value that reflects a 20% reduction from the new material price (€51 183), the result is a financial deficit of approximately 21%. A more conservative estimate, the price determined by reuse companies, suggests a potential market value of €36 873 for the entire building, which corresponds to a financial shortfall of 43%. This substantial disparity suggests that, under current financial conditions, the reuse of all available materials is not financially feasible. To

achieve financial viability, it is essential to prioritize the selective reuse of materials that possess high market value and incur relatively low reclamation costs.

Figure 4. The bar chart provide the total cost of reusing the materials (Reclamation costs), the market value, determined by a reduction of 20% to the new price (MV: 20%), a combination of a reduction of 20% to the new price and interviews with reuse companies (MV: RC+20%) and the total new price, with (New+waste) and without waste processing costs (New). The share of materials within each bar is indicated. The costs are provided per weight and expressed in euros.

3.1 Limitations of the study

Given the limited availability of cost data for reused materials in existing literature, this study relies on interview-based data, which introduces certain limitations. While a comprehensive dataset is compiled and average values are used for analysis, the data remains case-specific, influenced by material conditions, construction methods, and the expertise of the dismantling contractor. Moreover, the interview outcomes are generalized and adapted to fit the study's scope, and deviations from these values may occur in practice.

Furthermore, transportation and storage costs are estimated as external expenses, potentially leading to cost overestimations compared to internally managed logistics. Packaging costs are limited to pallets and big bags, excluding other materials that could affect the overall cost analysis. The study focuses exclusively on direct costs and omits indirect costs (e.g. costs of standard equipment), which may result in an underestimation of the actual costs. Another limitation of this study is that, while a risk factor was included in the cost-benefit formula to account for uncertainties in material reuse [12], it was not quantified or applied due to a lack of reliable data. These limitations may impact the comprehensiveness of the financial assessment and highlight opportunities for future research.

4. Conclusion & discussion

This study contributes to the existing literature by providing an exploratory analysis of the financial viability of reusing materials from a contemporary dwelling, using practice-based data to address the lack of reliable cost information. The analysis shows that the costs of reuse are primarily driven by labor-intensive processes such as deconstruction and processing, whereas transportation, packaging, and storage generally contribute less, except for high volume materials like insulation.

This study evaluates the total cost of material reclamation against multiple reference values to highlight different perspectives on financial viability. Reuse costs are compared to the market value of reclaimed materials, which is particularly relevant for reuse companies or contractors aiming to resell those materials. These prices result in the most stringent criteria, under which

only glulam, timber frames, doors and windows are financially viable. Additionally, the analysis considers the combined cost of waste processing and new material acquisition, offering insights for project owners weighing reuse against conventional demolition and new construction. Within this analysis, also façade bricks and faience wall tiles become financially viable. In contrast, hollow clay bricks, concrete, and insulation materials consistently show poor financial returns due to high processing costs and low resale value.

This findings highlight that in the current financial context, strategic selection of high-value materials with low costs for processing and deconstruction is essential to make reuse financially viable. To improve the financial viability of material reuse optimizing dismantling and processing methods is required. This can be achieved through strategies such as employing social economy initiatives for labor-intensive tasks, adopting more efficient reuse approaches (e.g. reuse at element level) and leveraging automation technologies (e.g. automated cleaning). Furthermore, regulatory changes and market adjustments such as reducing testing requirements (e.g. thermal insulation) and implementing supportive policy measures (e.g. VAT reductions or subsidies for reuse) could facilitate material reuse in the future [16]. By integrating both technological advancements and policy interventions, the cost-effectiveness of material reuse can be enhanced, promoting its broader adoption in the construction industry.

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From Theory to Practice: Mapping Institutional and Stakeholder Theory Pathways for Sustainable Construction

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Keywords: Sustainable Construction; Circular Business Model; Sustainable Business Model

ABSTRACT

The construction sector is undergoing a fundamental shift toward circular and sustainable business models that foster resource efficiency, environmental resilience, and social value creation. This study examines the role of institutional and stakeholder theories in explaining the drivers and implementation pathways of these models. Institutional theory elucidates how external regulatory, normative, and cognitive pressures—such as environmental legislation, certification systems, and industry norms—influence the adoption of circular models emphasizing material loops, reuse, and design for disassembly. Meanwhile, stakeholder theory focuses on how clients, communities, regulators, and other actors shape firms' commitment to sustainable models integrating environmental, social, and economic dimensions.

A qualitative comparative analysis was conducted, based on case studies of European construction firms implementing either circular or sustainable business models. Data were collected through document analysis (e.g., sustainability reports) and semi-structured interviews with Latvian construction companies. Each case was assessed using a framework derived from the two theories to evaluate how institutional pressures and stakeholder dynamics affect model selection and execution.

Findings reveal that institutional drivers—such as regulatory mandates, market incentives, and certification criteria—are key to enabling circular business models, which yield tangible benefits like reduced waste, lifecycle cost savings, and increased flexibility via modular design. In contrast, stakeholder engagement is more prominent in sustainable business models, where long-term viability, social acceptance, and cross-sector collaboration are central. These models generate wider systemic outcomes including climate resilience, social inclusion, and reputational advantages.

The comparative insights suggest that while both model types pursue efficiency and sustainability, circular models concentrate on material and process optimization, whereas sustainable models reflect a more holistic and stakeholder-oriented shift. Many firms adopt hybrid approaches to align with regulatory expectations and diverse stakeholder needs.

This study contributes to the theoretical integration of business model innovation with institutional and stakeholder perspectives. It presents empirical evidence from the construction industry and proposes a framework for designing models that respond to shifting regulatory landscapes and evolving stakeholder priorities. By connecting theory and practice, the research demonstrates that circular and sustainable business models are complementary strategies for fostering systemic transformation in construction.

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From Waste to Worth: Stakeholders' Interpretation of Value in Circular Construction Projects

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Keywords: circular construction, value creation, value proposition, circular projects, sensemaking

ABSTRACT

Circular construction has emerged as a sustainability paradigm aimed at reducing environmental impacts, improving resource efficiency, and generating economic benefits. Central to this paradigm is the concept of value, which can be interpreted differently by various groups of project actors. While previous research in circular construction has primarily explored value from business model and industrial ecology perspective, focusing on environmental and economic dimensions, limited attention has been given to how practitioners themselves make sense of the value of circularity in everyday project contexts. This subjective appraisal can significantly influence stakeholder involvement and decision-making processes in circular construction. Our study addresses this gap by drawing on data from 103 semi-structured interviews with project actors involved in three circular construction projects in the Netherlands, supplemented by a co-creation workshop. Using an inductive Gioia method, we investigate how circularity's value is interpreted and contested within these projects. Our analysis identifies six distinct value themes, which are aggregated into two overarching dimensions: *Values-as-Beliefs* (moral, personal, and symbolic), which relates project values to individuals' abstract beliefs about ideal modes of conduct and desirable end-states, and *Values-as-Outcomes* (instrumental, economic, and environmental), which defines project values in terms of the tangible outputs, benefits, or worth generated by a project.

In relation to *Values-as-Beliefs*, our findings show that project actors perceive circularity as a moral obligation, largely driven by climate concerns. Larger organizations and civil servants are regarded as bearing a particularly strong moral responsibility in this regard. Personal values, shaped by culture, experience, and education, are often endorsed in professional settings, fostering intrinsic motivation and dedicated engagement with the circular transition. Finally, symbolic values provide recognition and identity to individuals and organization but also pose a risk of *greenwashing* if not supported by concrete actions. Actors emphasized the need for positive framing of circularity to enhance its symbolic value.

With regards to *Values-as-Outcomes*, we found that project members interpret circularity as a practical instrument for innovation and resource efficiency. Furthermore, circularity is understood as a means of achieving economic benefits and as an environmental lever for reducing ecological footprints and generating broader social returns. However, several tensions were identified, including the challenge of balancing short-term economic pressures with long-term circularity goals, and the uneven distribution of value among stakeholders.

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This research offers valuable insights for practitioners and policymakers in the construction industry by highlighting how actors differently value circularity, and how these subjective evaluations shape the adoption of circular construction. It also contributes to the broader understanding of value in circularity transitions and projects, offering implications for future research and practice aimed at fostering circular construction.

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How circular economy innovations emerge in the construction sector

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Keywords:

Circular economy, co-creation, construction, innovation, production, transformative learning

Introduction

The construction sector is a significant contributor to global climate emissions. In 2021, the buildings and construction sector accounted for approximately 37% of energy and process-related CO₂ emissions (UNEP, 2022). This consists of material production, operational emissions, embodied carbon, and the energy consumption of operation of buildings. (Joensuu et al., 2020; Bajzelj et al., 2013, Zhou et al., 2012). Adopting and advancing circular economy practices is identified as a key remedy to this (Brandão & Verissimo, 2024). Moreover, as Joensuu et al. (2020) advocate, there is a need to move the emphasis from simple recycling of materials, which often involves energy-intensive material processing, towards reuse of products and components and new kinds of design-out-of-waste strategies (Joensuu et al., 2022).

Circular economy (CE) innovation refers to a novel solution e.g. product, business model, manufacturing method or design solution, which advances efficient use of resources. There is an urgent need for novel circular innovations and openings in the construction sector. However, implementing circular economy in the construction industry comes with several challenges. Lack of awareness, regulatory and policy barriers, the high cost of the required upfront investments, supply chain complexity, limited market demand, and cultural resistance all complicate the effective adoption and operationalization of circular economy principles and practices. (Brandão & Verissimo, 2024; Abdul-Hamid et al., 2020; Poon et al., 2001). Collaboration, cocreation and diffusion of new innovations are recognized as focus points when studying innovation in the construction sector (Xue et al. 2014). Construction industry ecosystems are complex, and the adaptation of individual players in the sector often hinge on various variables. The expectations and involvement of project owners, contractors, designers, suppliers, consultants, material producers, and investors vary and depend on each other. Scharmer (2007) categorized these different types of complexity into dynamic and social complexity. Moving from novel ideas to actual value creation calls for recognition and appreciation of stakeholders, as well as supportive and guiding regulations and policies.

This paper explores the innovation processes and interdependence in the construction industry value chains. The goal is to gain a better understanding of how circular economy innovations are developed, matured, and operationalized in the Finnish construction sector and identify drivers and bottlenecks of the innovation processes.

Methodology

We organized a workshop for construction industry stakeholders, as well as interviews with businesses and organizations involved in circular economy innovations in the construction sector. Based on the need for industry-wide collaboration, the co-creative workshop included conversation and tasks. Workshop participants were split into three groups and challenged to

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determine the desired benefits and challenges to achieving these benefits of new innovations. The time span of these challenges was also addressed, and stakeholders were asked to define the interdependencies of each other's challenges. Asking to state the relations and connections between different challenges and stakeholders and comparing the results of the different groups helped to form a consensus.

The four interviews conducted were semi-structured and seek to grasp hands-on experiences from the industry. The people interviewed had experience in developing circularity on the project level, researching circularity in the construction industry, developing a new circular innovation and creating and publishing professional information and instructions.

The comments and experiences of these professionals were analyzed, and an initial and complementary consensus was formed. We base our discussion on these initial observations from the workshop and the interviews. These observations are interpreted through a theoretical lens consisting of Scharmer's (2007) Theory U change management theory, combined with the theory of transformative learning (Mezirow 1991).

Theoretical frameworks of innovation

Anderson & Tushman (1990) present their cyclical model for technological development where dominant designs and industry standards emerge from the competition created by a changing environment. Population growth and demand for new construction was high after the World Wars. Solutions in industrialized construction that were created then dictate the ways buildings are built even today. Productivity in construction has stood still while societies have demanded more quality and safety (Eurostat). The demand for sustainable construction has not been high enough to create major competition for new technologies. Rogers (2003) has explained the diffusion of new innovations and technologies. After an innovation emerges, rather than staying still, it evolves when users with different characteristics adopt the new technology. Novel methods, like co-creation, try to harness this information from the stakeholders to guide the development process. Most users require significant proof of the superiority of new technology to change their habits. Research data alone is not always enough to convince a user. According to Rogers (2003), most users are most influenced by their own assessment of peers using the product or technology. Rogers' theory applies not only to individuals, but also organizations. Frontrunners take risks and create their advantages by adapting to new technologies early. Most companies adjust to new technologies only when they have become industry standards.

Theory U is a change management method developed by Otto Scharmer, which focuses on leading profound change by shifting awareness and attention. The phases of change are illustrated on the U-curve, starting from moving down the U which involves opening up and dealing with resistance in thought, emotion, and will – redirecting and letting go - and eventually moving back up again through a process of bringing new insights and innovations into practical application. This takes place through the bottom of the U, which is the crucial phase where transformation occurs. At the bottom of the U, old, usual ways of thinking are suspended, allowing new possibilities to emerge. The steps are illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Phases of Theory U. (Adapted from Scharmer, 2007)

Transformative Learning Theory, developed by Jack Mezirow, is a framework for understanding how adults change their perspectives through critical reflection and new experiences (Mezirow, 1991). This theory emphasizes the process by which individuals question and revise their existing beliefs, assumptions, and worldviews. Transformative learning is often triggered by experiences that challenge an individual's existing beliefs and assumptions. These may include encountering disorienting dilemmas and situations that disrupt normal routines, or exposure to new ideas and perspectives that challenge existing knowledge and processes. In recent years, the link between sustainability and transformative learning has been receiving increasing research interest (Aboytes et al., 2020), making it a viable model for interpreting circular economy innovation processes.

From an engineering perspective, the innovation process has been traditionally viewed as quite straightforward: First, potential customers are identified, and their needs are clarified. Second, conceptual designers recognize a bundle of customer needs that can be satisfied with one product or service. From this bundle the characteristics of the product, i.e. what it should be able to do, are derived. In some cases, this can mean a combination of products and services, which forms a product family or ecosystem. Third, technological solutions are developed to make the product function as it should. The result of this phase is technical designs and specifications. Finally, production technology, e.g. an assembly line, is designed to make products according to technical specifications within optimal tolerances. (Taguchi, 1986; Akao, 1990)

We would like to point out two notions of this traditional innovation process perspective: First is that it does not consider design or development task as inconveniently challenging problems or dilemmas, as Mezirow's (1991) description of transformative learning would suggest. Second is that the innovation process can be divided into two parts: the earlier part that focuses on the product and the second part that focuses on the production, which slightly overlaps in the technological solution development phase. The problems of these two parts differ from each other as the first part focuses on what should be manufactured, and the second part focuses on how to manufacture.

It might be fair to say that the engineering perspective tries to exclude people from the innovation process and examines it purely from the product and production development perspective. However, there exists ongoing criticism toward forgetting the human perspective. One of the most famous is Deming's (1986) principle that the purpose of any company should be determined by its aspiration to provide benefits to its customers and manage it in a manner that embraces the pride of workmanship. This comprises the human perspective of both customer and worker. Therefore, it is not rational to examine the innovation process without considering the role of brainpower and ability to learn, which are very human features in essence.

The ability to learn together with customers is emphasized also in recent marketing research literature, in which it is called co-creation. The concept of co-creation is based on the idea that the value of the product or service is understood best when customers are engaged in the design process. The idea is to determine the features of the product or service in such dialogue, which enables the producer to learn how the customer wants to utilize the product or service. Along with the dialogue, this perspective embraces the open and transparent information sharing combined with collaborative risk assessment. (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004)

Even though the ability to learn is present in various research perspectives, it is not imminent, what should be learned. Deming (1986) emphasizes the continuous improvement inside the company, and Prahalad & Ramaswamy (2004) embraces learning from customer needs in collaboration with the customers. These perspectives are good starting points, but they do not recognize the fact that construction projects are versatile multi-organizations instead of being single companies or relationships. Therefore, the dilemmas and inconvenient situations that trigger learning processes can be different from those that exist in smaller entities.

Findings and discussion

Current construction industry standards have been formed and developed through several iterations of technological development, following the steps of Theory U (Scharmer, 2007) and the cycles discussed by Anderson and Tushman (1990). However, the observations we have made based on interactions with stakeholders suggest that circular economy innovations of the field are largely still at the initial stages of suspending and redirecting for the first time.

It is also worth noting that the construction sector is a complex ecosystem of interdependent stakeholders, and an individual idea or invention faces significant roadblocks before it can become an innovation leading to sustainable transformation. In the light of our observations, we suggest that investments play a crucial role in construction sector circular economy innovations and, eventually, the green transition of the entire sector. Based on the information gathered we suggest that the following components and their interplay are at the very core of the transition.

Firstly, the timespan of green transition innovations must be taken into consideration. When addressing the timespan of innovations in the workshop, participants pointed out that short-term innovations concentrate on product development and smaller changes in existing production, long-term positive impact on environmental sustainability typically require major changes and investing in production equipment and processes. Therefore, product development is a crucial learning process, not only for enhancing circularity of existing products, but to provide information to guide and support investment decisions. The second

conclusion from the workshop was that political regulation and direction plays a central role in stakeholders' motivation and decisions regarding investments. On the one hand, innovators wait on regulations to provide competitive advantages to environmentally friendly products and processes, which would encourage investments. On the other hand, uncertainty of upcoming regulatory changes impedes investment decisions. As political direction may take the form of "stick or carrots", i.e. regulation by taxation or investment incentives, many are waiting to see what turns regulation takes in fear of expensive, erroneous investments. In making decisions on production investments, there must be alternatives that remain allowed and profitable throughout the lifespan of the investment. A transition period can facilitate investments in green production technologies, provided that the regulatory changes are clearly defined, and the regulation genuinely either supports or impedes decisions through certification and control mechanisms. Transparency of future development of regulatory practices affects the timespan of investments.

New green technologies often face criticism over their higher price and rightfully so. Expecting consumers to voluntarily pay more for sustainable products will probably not solve the climate crisis. Paying more for the same performance attributes of a product will only lower purchasing power. Like Anderson & Tushman (1990) have already presented, new innovations improve significantly when they reach the era of incremental change. Connective technologies and innovations in production do not increase the competitiveness of a product until it has reached a certain status in the market. To put it simply, product development in the context of sustainable building is about creating products that have positive environmental effects. Investments in production on the other hand seek to make the products applied on a major scale by making them cost-effective and applicable.

The processes required in circular economy innovations involve a significant amount of uncertainty and foresight. Companies often fear transformation and losing their current market share. SMEs at the end of the subcontracting chain are surviving rather than leading change. The industry leaders are called upon to lead the change. This calls for tolerance of ambiguity and, in many cases, steps out of the comfort zone. This can be perceived as a transformative learning process, without which the jump to the Theory U curve cannot take place.

Conclusions

Our aim with the current paper has been to illustrate the multifaceted nature of circular economy innovations in the construction sector. Their emergence requires decisive advancement on multiple fronts at the same time. Cleantech innovations of the construction sector are thus not only a question of technological development, as un-learning of old economic logic and processes is equally necessary to enable investments in production technologies.

If cleantech innovations are supposed to save the economy of any given region, they must create a significant number of jobs with high productivity. Investments in novel production technologies are made with aspiration to increase productivity and enable employment. Productivity may sound like unanimously understood and well-defined concept, but the difficulty to increase it suggests that it should be perceived as a more complex and multi-dimensional phenomenon. The increase of productivity is often preceded by an uncomfortable process of unlearning old processes and models of consumption, earning

logic, and production methods. This requires a simultaneous transformative learning process in companies and organizations that form the construction industry value network.

The observations that form the basis of these conclusions were made in a single workshop session attended by construction industry stakeholders, and interviews with selected visionary people placed in key positions in the construction sector. At this early stage, they illustrate the forerunners' perspectives and experiences with construction industry circular economy innovations. In order to understand the involvement of the large majority, wider data collection and content analysis are required.

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How Do Circular Construction Strategies Impact Housing Projects? The Need for Context-Specific Approaches

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Beyond environmental benefits, circular design choices can reduce housing costs through reuse, repair, maintenance savings, and adaptable buildings that extend their lifespans. Despite the existing amount of research, the adoption of circular design strategies in housing projects is hindered by a lack of understanding of the relationship between design choices and socio-institutional parameters, including management and financing. Every project is unique and has its own regulations, stakeholders, and contexts. Particularly in the context of housing, it is crucial to ensure that decisions related to circular design do not negatively impact the project's equitability. Therefore, practitioners and policymakers often find it difficult to decide which circular design choices will actually improve the housing projects.

Goal. Based on twenty-two existing international case studies, we aimed to identify patterns in the characteristics of existing equitable housing projects that applied certain circular design strategies.

Method. Serving as an exploratory instrument, Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) was used to identify these cross-case patterns. Through Boolean logic, QCA can identify which combinations of housing characteristics (conditions) lead to a specific circular design strategy (outcome). QCA requires three inputs: cases, conditions, and outcomes. First, information on the twenty-two chosen cases was gathered using semi-structured interviews, literature reviews, workshops, and site visits. These cases were located in Belgium, Finland, Spain, and Switzerland. Second, the conditions examined in this analysis were obtained from case study mapping. They were chosen for two reasons: certain conditions distinguish housing developments according to their funding sources and ownership types. Other conditions noted by the interviewees presented opportunities for circular strategies, including sustainable building subsidies and environmental ambitions. Finally, for the outcomes, we identified 14 circular design strategies, such as the reuse of building materials and design for adaptability. For each outcome, we performed a QCA to analyze the conditions that led to the circular design strategies. After the QCA, it is key to link the results back to the case study narratives and study the within-case mechanisms, which provide more in-depth information about why a certain pattern emerges. Approaching QCA results in this narrative way allowed us to explore how and why different housing projects can benefit from specific circular design strategies.

Results. QCA provides a comprehensive and exploratory view of the financial, management, ownership, and building contexts in which circular strategies are applied. We found that the project characteristics that lead to the implementation of a circular design strategy vary significantly depending on the strategy. For example, regarding the circular strategy of adaptable building design, our findings show that ownership type significantly influences how adaptability is implemented. While projects that applied another circular strategy, such as the reuse of building materials, were driven by collective ownership and investments, the heritage value of the building, and self-building by residents. The study provides recommendations for designers, policymakers, project initiators, and managers. Furthermore, we identified missed opportunities for linking circular design strategies to the project characteristics. The results can assist in making better-informed design choices related to specific contexts.

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Integrating stakeholders perspectives: the case of circular concrete pavers in the City of Amsterdam

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Abstract

Construction activities in the built environment use a vast amount of resources, making the circular economy an attractive paradigm against the linear take-waste-dispose economy to reduce this resource consumption. Within the built environment, this transition encompasses the use of circular strategies across the product life cycle for materials. This entails efforts from multiple stakeholders across the product value chain. In this study we therefore explore how stakeholders engagement can aid the process to arrive at a common understanding of a public sector circular business model (PSCBM) in the case of a circular concrete paver. We conducted a participatory design workshop aimed to design this PSCBM with all relevant stakeholders across the product life cycle were (re)presented. We conclude that the presence of stakeholder perspectives was observed to be necessary in drafting up a PSCBM for a concrete paver, but caution is needed. Outcome-wise stakeholder engagement was necessary to sharpen the dream, indicating stakeholder value propositions, activities required, value trade-offs and to arrive at a relevant set of indicators. Process-wise, stakeholder engagement in this setting was relevant because stakeholders were enabled to share perspectives and challenge each other perspectives accordingly. This leads to the advantage that the practical feasibility of proposed ideas could immediately be challenged. However, outcomes and assumptions should always be cross-validated and updated according to new insights (e.g., relevant outcomes of tests or regulations, latest insights on reuse and recycling innovations). The outcomes are time- and context-bound and very much reliant on the perspectives shared. The findings of this study contribute to our understanding of how stakeholder engagement in a workshop setting, can potentially be useful to strategize about circular products. We conclude that this for example, could help to improve the functional and esthetical requirements for product procurement.

Keywords: circular economy, circular procurement, public sector circular business models, public space, stakeholder engagement

1. Introduction

Local governments are expected to play a pivotal role in achieving circularity goals in the built environment (Osei-Tutu et al., 2024). For example, public procurement can play a major role in creating circular buildings and constructions (Alhola et al., 2019). In the Netherlands, municipal efforts to create a circular economy (CE) can very well be enacted in the physical municipal outdoor public space. Municipalities are asset owners and consume a vast amount of materials every year to create and maintain their roads, parks, squares, etc. For example, public spaces in Leiden demand an average of 240 million kilos of material every year (PosadMaxwan, 2022). Creating a circular built environment is considered to be a multi-stakeholder challenge (Osei-Tutu et al., 2024). However, we do not yet fully understand how stakeholder engagement contributes to understanding the circularity of a product. Based on the aforementioned studies, we hypothesize that that stakeholder engagement is required to truly understand circularity of a product. Hitherto, this study aims to understand the benefits and limitations of stakeholder engagement in constituting a circular product. To do so, we use a public sector circular business model

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(PSCBM) framework and applied it for a use case in the city of Amsterdam. In the city, a concrete paver with a relatively low environmental footprint was piloted. We invited all stakeholders and gathered all relevant stakeholders perspectives across the concrete product value chain in one workshop session. The aim of the session was to strategize the future use of circular concrete pavers within the municipality, using a PSCBM template. This study synthesizes this experience of stakeholder engagement to arrive at a shared future of a circular concrete paver in the municipality of Amsterdam.

The aim of this paper is to contribute to the understanding of CE by exploring how stakeholder engagement can potentially be useful to strategize about circular products. This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides background information on the circular built environment as a multi-stakeholder challenge and how business models for the public sector can be of use; Section 3 explains the research methodology; Section 4 contains observations of stakeholder engagement in this study; Section 5 discusses these observations and Section 6; provides a summary of the study and conclusions.

2. Background

2.1. Moving towards a circular built environment is a multi-stakeholder challenge

The activities to create a circular economy in the built environment are dispersed among the stakeholders across the product value chain (Ho et al., 2024). To integrate circular economy principles in the built environment many stakeholders are needed with different roles and responsibilities (Osei-Tutu et al., 2024; Schraven et al., 2019). This implies that individual stakeholders need to execute activities (i.e., circular procurement, reuse and recycling activities) taking into account that the circularity of a product is not jeopardized in next product life cycle stages. The lack of stakeholder engagement in the construction industry one of the key barriers to adopt circular procurement (Sajid et al., 2024).

2.2. The use of business models for the public sector in the circular economy

Moving towards a circular economy within the construction industry may require the adoption of new business models for stakeholders involved (Torres Curado et al., 2024). Although in the private sector research is conducted on circular business models, integrating public sector bodies more specifically has not been largely explored in academic literature. Efforts have been aimed at connecting supplier business models to procurers business models (Witjes & Lozano, 2016) and to connect public sector and circular businesses models (Lewandowski, 2018). Since local governments play an important role in accelerating the transition in the construction industry (Osei-Tutu et al., 2024), a PSCBM may be helpful as a tool to conceptualize why and how to operate circular strategies within the city. Especially in the municipal public space this is relevant, as municipalities are responsible for designing, maintaining and retrofitting the public space.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research design

We conducted a participatory design workshop with the aim to design a PSCBM for a circular concrete paver in co-creation. Storvang et al., (2017) find workshops in business model research a useful method to engage multiple stakeholders. Hence, we used a workshop setting to discuss a potential PSCBM too. The pilot innovation discussed was a concrete paver (i.e. “betonstraatsteen” in Dutch) applied in a recent roadwork replacement project (Oct 2024). The low impact of the paver originated from the use of secondary materials, that included 15% residue slag from a waste-to-energy plant (WTE-slag) as a replacement for sand and fine gravel and fly ash and blast furnace cement to replace Portland Cement. For aesthetical reasons, the paver had a red natural stone top layer, partly from waste materials of stone mining operations. We used this exercise as a case study to draw empirical observations on stakeholder engagement.

We prepared the workshop in advance by preparing the content in parts of the template, to use the workshop time most effectively and drafted the participation list together with the initiating municipal innovation manager. The motivation for participants to join was to engage in a discussion on the use of circular concrete pavers within the municipal context. The following workshop participants were invited: innovation manager, project leader, project director, buyer, asset manager (advisor), contractor, product supplier (of the piloted product) and high-grade recycler of concrete pavers. Most stakeholders were present at the workshop, but the contractor and buyer were represented by others. The asset management advisor represented the buyer, being involved in establishing product requirements for procurement as well. The recycler represented the contractor, being familiarity with other contractor activities as well. We conducted one 3.5h workshop on 3rd of Feb 2025. Prior to the workshop consent forms were signed according to GDPR regulations.

The PSCBM template used in this study, is an adaptation of the Business Model Template (Jonker & Faber, 2020). The PSCBM template includes the opportunity to discuss all value propositions for all stakeholders involved across the product value chain. Furthermore, it includes a multi-value perspective on value generation/capture, including sustainable and public value creation. Besides, it concerns activities on both the municipal as the infrastructural project level. The template has been tested as evaluation and ideation tool in several cases within the municipality of Amsterdam. An overview of the building blocks is included in Table 1.

3.2. Data collection and analysis

The session was recorded, audio transcribed and the data coded, using codes that related to the building blocks and content (e.g. scope description, circular strategy, risk, risk mitigation measure etc.) to perform a descriptive analysis of the final business model. All participants were asked for feedback on the final result through email. From the data, observations on the process and outcome were drawn on the use of stakeholder engagement. We coded these observations inductively from the workshop data.

Table 1. Building blocks of Public Sector Circular Business Model (source: Reijtenbagh et al., (2025) [Manuscript in preparation])

<i>Phase</i>	<i>Building block</i>	<i>Content</i>
Define value	Circular strategy (& Scope Description)	Description of the circular strategy (and the project)
	Motive & Context	Description of the reasons, challenges, and requirements of execution the circular strategy
	The Dream	Description of the common dream that is worked towards when implementing this circular strategy.
	Value Proposition (for each stakeholder separate)	Description of the value proposition for each stakeholder
Deliver value	Core activities, parties involved and resources required	Description of all activities, actors and resources (incl. artifacts) required
	Risks and risk mitigation	Description of risks and possible measure to mitigate them (and who is responsible to mitigate these)
	(Internal) test	Description of conditions to success and factors that influence feasibility
Generated value	Value created	Description of benefits and costs that relate to the value domains: public, social, environmental/circular and financial value
	Impact measured	Description of indicators that measure the impact

4. Findings

The results describe how stakeholders engaged in drawing up a possible future of a circular concrete paver within the municipality of Amsterdam and how this helped in drafting up a public sector circular business model. The results report on the stakeholder engagement in the different phases of the business model: defining value, deliver value and generated value.

4.1. *Define value: Identify value propositions for each stakeholder and shape a collaborative dream*

Drafting a collaborative dream that is agreed upon by each stakeholders worked as a steering wheel in the business model. *If activities were proposed that that did not match the objectives in the dream, stakeholders activated each other to rethink these activities.* The participants discussed the dream, and agreed that it is not a vision or a requirement, but rather a shared idea that can change over time. The subsequent presentation of the stakeholder *value propositions of all stakeholders involved, opened up a discussion on what product's properties are needed to maintain circularity across the value chain.* This increased awareness on the different stakeholder perspectives. The question was asked: who's value proposition is not met? Only the recycler responded with a 'no' as he would face problems in his recycling process. This led to suggestions on how to change the product design such that it could be reused and recycled in the future ahead and the possible feasibility of doing so.

4.2. *Deliver value: creating a comprehensive co-created overview of activities and requirements*

The identification of risks and risk mitigation measures were helpful in reshaping activities of stakeholders and requirements, like rules, regulatory measures and contracts. A collaborative discussion on conditions for success and feasibility factors further helped (re)shaping these. *Because stakeholders could immediately react to each other, proposals on requirements and activities could be challenged.* For example, according to the recycler the use of WTE slags impedes the recycling process involved in producing cement powder from concrete. Then a discussion unfolded by the asset manager adviser, supplier, innovation manager and recycler on the implications of replacing these slags by other materials.

4.3. *Value generation: debating value trade-offs between stakeholders and evaluating the practical logic of impact indicators from different stakeholder perspectives*

Discussing value generation with different stakeholders provided insights into *possible value trade-offs between stakeholders.* During discussions on the value created anecdotes were shared upon possible value trade-offs. These did not concern only concrete pavers, but nevertheless gave clear illustrations on value trade-offs. For example, in the past, granite curbs have been used, but they cause slipperiness problems. From an aesthetic point of view, it is a 'good' choice, but the slipperiness led to many claims. Another value trade-off was mentioned: during execution of a project you often experience a choice between nuisance and ease and quality of the execution. A short and intense execution with more workspace was considered better, but it creates more nuisance/obstruction for local companies and citizens. In addition, *collaboratively debating impact indicators made the participants aware of which indicators do (not) make (practically) sense.* For example, local employment was not considered important, since labour shortages force contractors to work with people nationally and even internationally.

5. Discussion

In this study we observed stakeholder engagement in a workshop setting to discuss a circular concrete paver with a PSCBM lens. The recycler (also in his contractor role) was able to explain how the piloted products affects the concrete recycling and reuse process, meanwhile the supplier was able to explain the potential pitfalls of changing the product design. Because of the workshop set-up, perspectives could immediately be challenged. Municipal officials contributed their ideas on aesthetics, functional quality

and low environmental footprint to the discussion and provided relevant examples from their experiences and daily practices. Stakeholder engagement in this setting facilitated immediate knowledge exchange, the ability to hear each other perspectives and assessments on feasibility of suggestions during discussion. Hence, the results showcase that the inclusion of all relevant stakeholders across the value chain aids understanding of what is required to reuse and recycle products in later phases of the product life cycle. This can lead to new insights on how products design could be adapted to safeguard future reuse and recycling, in sum *circularity*.

Figure 1. Proposed integration of requirements of all stakeholders responsible for maintaining circularity across the product's life cycle

In the workshop, all stakeholder perspectives were necessary to be able to consider what is required to maintain circularity across the product's life cycle (visualized in Figure 1). As a result, this input can be useful to (re)shape product design requirements. This contributes to the call of Alhola et al., (2019) that shaping better conditions for procurement needs market innovation towards creating novel products and solutions that are improved in terms of recyclability, the use of recycled materials, proven disassembly, and increase in life span. Effective circular procurement includes collaborative capabilities of trust, coordination of supply chain activities, decision-making power, technical knowledge, and information sharing capabilities (Ababio et al., 2025). Stakeholder engagement in this workshop setting, especially enabled information sharing capabilities.

Though, we found benefits of stakeholder engagement in this setting, there are also limitations to the representativeness of the perspectives shared and hitherto to the final outcome of the PSCBM. An inevitable bias is introduced due to that 1) only perspectives from workshop participants are shared and these may not be representative or not congruent with sectoral positions or other market parties, 2) the perspectives shared can only be argued and challenged during discussion, but not be verified as such, 3) if stakeholders are not present, representation of stakeholders makes the input of these perspectives less reliable 4) participants have only their (limited) technical knowledge and experience and 5) they may have limited ability to express these. As a result, in further research endeavors that include multiple stakeholders, we advocate for taking some time to discuss and evaluate assumptions explicitly. Cross-validation with other sources (e.g. research reports on recycling opportunities) is needed to check validity of outcomes and assumptions. Also, regular updates of the model are needed to the latest insights on reuse and recycling possibilities and regulatory requirements. Lastly, the experience of the co-creative process in this study may not necessarily compare to the development of other road construction products. Hence, further research could follow the same procedure used in this study and compare the findings.

6. Conclusions

In this study we explored how stakeholders involvement can aid discussions in a participatory design workshop aimed to design a PSCBM for a circular concrete paver. In this workshop all relevant stakeholders across the product life cycle were (re)presented. The presence of stakeholder perspectives was observed to be necessary in drafting up a PSCBM for a concrete paver. Outcome-wise stakeholder engagement was necessary to sharpen the dream, indicating stakeholder value propositions, activities required, value trade-offs and a relevant set of indicators. Process-wise, it was relevant *because stakeholders were enabled to share perspectives and challenge each other perspectives*. This leads to the advantage that the practical feasibility of proposed ideas could immediately be challenged. Outcomes and assumptions should always be cross-validated and updated according to new insights (e.g., relevant outcomes of tests or regulations). All in all, we can conclude that shared perspectives from stakeholders across the product life cycle are needed to effectively evaluate the feasibility the product in terms of upcoming reuse and recycling activities across the product's life cycle, which supports our hypothesis. However, there are limitations to stakeholder involvement in a workshop setting with respect to representativeness, that ultimately affect the initial outcome. Further research, could focus on identifying what information or process is needed after a co-creative workshop, that can lead up to a final outcome of an envisioned PSCBM for municipalities.

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Mobile demonstration unit circular construction

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Keywords: Circular construction methods, demountable, environmental impact, mock-ups

ABSTRACT

In the context of the 2nd International Conference on Circularity in the Built Environment (CiBEn 2025), we present an innovative project aimed at conveying future-oriented building methods to designers, contractors and other stakeholders in the construction industry. Central to this project is a mobile unit, a 20-foot container, integrating 45 models. All models of a certain element have similar thermal resistance. The accompanying technical information sheet informs the user about the technical design, the environmental impact, circular properties and points of attention during installation. On this basis an objective comparison can be made between traditional and more circular approved construction methods.

By this project we lowered the threshold for contractors and designers to start working with circular construction methods. By designing and building a mobile unit, it is possible to come to the target group on events, fairs, ... The models make clear which method to apply to achieve a qualitative result. The focus is on sustainability, comfort, reuse and disassembly of the materials. By approaching the methods in a hands-on way, we convince the contractor of the added value of circular construction and let him get started.

The models include both new construction and renovation solutions for walls, roofs, floor packages and joinery. We start with a traditional build and by applying various circular interventions, we design builds with as little environmental impact as possible. The re-use of materials, the implementation of biobased products and the disassembly of the different layers all have an impact. What makes it all very insightful is the use of real materials on scale 1/1. The visitors experience the ‘touch and feel’ of the materials which helps in imaging the practicality of circular construction methods. By doing so, we help people make a conscious choice and accelerate the transition to adopting less environmentally damaging building practices.

The project has already visited several locations, including construction fairs and science festivals in Ghent, Brussels and Aalst. We also host groups of e.g. architects and renovation consultants at our campus stand to make them aware of what circular construction means in practice. This abstract provides an overview of our project and its impact on the construction industry, and we look forward to sharing our findings at CiBEn 2025.

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Navigating Ecosystem Formation in the Norwegian Circular Timber Built Environment: The Role of Intermediaries

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Keywords: Business Model Innovation, Ecosystem formation, Intermediaries, Norway

ABSTRACT: The transition toward a circular built environment necessitates a multistakeholder approach, with an increasing emphasis on ecosystem thinking and strengthened by interdisciplinary collaboration. While scholars have developed rich theoretical frameworks to explore ecosystem formation (Aarikka-Stenroos, et al., 2021; 2022; Konietzko et al., 2024) and circular business models (e.g. Bocken et al., 2016), much of this literature remains conceptual, with limited insight into the operationalization of these models in real-world settings. This paper advances the theoretical lens proposed by Konietzko et al. (2020)—by grounding it in empirical insights from Norway. Focusing on the Norwegian startup Omtre AS, this study explores its role as an intermediary within the Sirktre project, a multi-year, multi-actor initiative involving over 30 stakeholders across industry and academia on establishing circularity in the timber construction (Wuyts et al., 2024) and its expansion through other R&D (timber) projects and commercial activities. As a young, mission-driven firm, Omtre occupies a hybrid position between supply-side actor and system intermediary, raising questions about the boundaries, roles, and competencies required of such actors in ecosystem formation. Drawing on workshop data, including a business model co-creation session held in Oslo in January 2025 with approximately 40 industry and research participants, we examine how intermediaries like Omtre support the emergence and structuring of innovation pipelines in timber circularity. Using a business model canvas inspired by Bocken, 2024, five circular timber-related cases—ranging from manufacturing and storage hubs to architectural reuse practices—were analyzed. Additional workshops in March and April 2025 helped refine both the business model canvas and understanding the roles of intermediaries. The findings illustrate not only the operational dynamics of ecosystem formation but also the tensions intermediaries face in balancing inclusivity with ecosystem coherence, especially in relation to other frontrunners. The paper contributes to the literature on circular ecosystem development by offering practical insights into the evolving, sometimes conflicting roles of intermediaries, their capacity limitations, and their potential to both catalyze and constrain circular transitions.

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Testing Ecosystem and Collaborative Circular Business Model Frameworks for Hemp-Based CNC-Knitted Construction at Low Technology Readiness Levels

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Keywords: digital technologies, fabrication, fast-growing building material, speculative design, value chain.

ABSTRACT

This short paper explores how ecosystem mapping and circular business modeling tools can support early-stage development of hemp-based CNC-knitted construction systems—a low-TRL, bio-based innovation with potential for circular building applications. Focusing on the European Alpine region, the study identifies key structural challenges such as fragmented value chains, limited processing infrastructure, and regulatory gaps. Through stakeholder workshops and speculative modeling, the research highlights the role of digital fabrication, decentralized production, and intermediary actors in enabling more resilient, place-based circular systems. By addressing both technical and socio-economic barriers, the paper contributes to broader efforts in scaling circular bio-based solutions in the built environment.

INTRODUCTION

The built environment remains one of the most materially and energy-intensive sectors in Europe, driving urgent innovation agendas around biobased materials and circular construction systems. The hemp industry is increasingly positioned as a symbolic and material driver of the European Green Transition, due to its regenerative properties and cross-sectoral versatility. Hemp cultivation offers significant ecological co-benefits, including soil regeneration, carbon sequestration, and low input requirements, making it attractive for circular bioeconomies (Crini et al., 2020; The Hempclub Project, 2023). Its utility spans from high-value fibers for composites and textiles to lower-grade applications such as insulation and biomass-based panels, enabling cascading value chains and the profitability of the production (Alex et al., 2015).

While hemp holds strong potential as a circular material, realizing these benefits depends not only on its biological properties, but also on the design of products, business models, and ecosystem governance structures (Bocken et al., 2016). Circularity is not inherent to any material; it must be actively enabled through systemic strategies such as design for disassembly, take-back schemes, and reuse-oriented fabrication (Pomponi & Moncaster, 2016). The circular economy (CE) is increasingly understood as a systemic, multi-actor, and multi-scalar transition that depends on coordinated interactions across diverse stakeholders and stages of material use (Konietzko et al., 2020). In the construction sector, implementing CE principles requires collaboration across the entire building lifecycle—from design and fabrication to operation, reuse, and deconstruction. These transitions introduce new actors

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and practices, reshaping socio-technical ecosystems and demanding new forms of cooperation to embed circularity meaningfully and durably (Evertsen & Knotten, 2024).

This short paper contributes to the development of circular business models and collaborative ecosystem thinking by exploring how early-stage actors can align material innovations—like Computer Numerical Control (CNC)-knitted hemp—with circular principles through participatory mapping and speculative prototyping.

In order to understand how to foster these cascading value chains illustrating hemp's potential to support circular construction systems, the weaknesses and challenges have to be understood - from a multiscalar perspective. Persistent weaknesses and challenges include the lack of agronomic expertise to cope with the inconsistent material quality, lack of processing infrastructure, and unresolved regulatory constraints (Nath, 2023; Sadrmanesh & Chen, 2019). The dynamics of hemp innovation are also deeply geographically uneven, shaped by historical, institutional, and infrastructural differences across regions.

Drawing from economic geography frameworks for circular economy and Technological Innovation Systems (TIS) theory adapted for ecosystem mapping of circularity transitions of the built environment (Vasseur & Lou Kings, 2025), it becomes clear that regions such as France, Belgium, and East Germany benefit from retained expertise and institutional coordination, while Southern Alpine and Italian regions face innovation inertia due to fragmented networks and missing intermediaries (personal communication with experts, 2025). Understanding hemp not simply as a crop, but as a systemic socio-technical assemblage (Wuyts 2025), is crucial for designing effective support mechanisms that are regionally adapted and capable of scaling ecological, social, ethical and economic impact. The EU-funded RAW project, which investigates the use of computational technologies for Resource AWARE architecture, researchers are actively engaging with the natural material variability and supply inconsistencies inherent to bio-based materials like hemp with the aim to integrate these into the material streams, performance demands and scales of the building industry. Noteworthy, inconsistencies of supply cannot be dealt with by computation, but rather by establishing the necessary conditions to support a value chain. Hence, the wider consortium works with actors in the supply chain and socio-technical scientists to identify the reasons for supply inconsistencies and highlight potential avenues for their mitigation.

Within the project's fiber track, CNC-knitting technology is explored for architectural application- next to coreless fiber winding (outside this short paper's scope).

CNC-knitting offers a great potential for architectural construction and scaling up, despite its common use in the garment sector. An additive manufacturing and programmability of CNC-knit permits the creation of architectural textiles with seamlessly graded properties and waste-free in fabrication. The computational design strategies allow for natural material specific allocation strategies, where the uneven yarn qualities and strength can be steered for better structural performance of the constructed textile element. See Tamke et al. (2020) for a wider discussion. Despite the technical benefits of CNC-knit and the high- Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the technology in itself, as proved and widely used within the garment sector, the immediate scalability and wide architectural application of graded CNC-knitted membranes is uncertain, especially in the context of the urgent timelines of the green transition. This keeps the architectural CNC-knit at low-TRL for building sector applications. In this setting, custom developed digital design tools become essential not only for design iteration, and further digital fabrication of those advanced materials. This paper explores speculative methods, such as speculative mapping, which can enable early-stage prototyping of possible futures, helping to identify where architectural experimentation intersects with broader socio-technical constraints. They also serve as communication instruments, allowing insights to be shared across diverse stakeholder groups, including policymakers, industry partners, and regional planners, before lock-ins or inequities become institutionalized

The insights presented in this paper build on technologies and practices developed in the DRASTIC project, where higher-TRL demonstrators were tested with major industry partners. In contrast, this phase of the RAW project deliberately focused on lower-TRL experimentation, working with academic research and startup environments, and fragmented supply chains. In doing so, the research sought to evaluate how ecosystem and business modeling tools can be adapted to early-stage contexts where conventional road mapping is too rigid and slow to be useful. Hence, this short paper pursues two interrelated goals:

1. To test the application of ecosystem mapping and business modeling frameworks developed in the DRASTIC project for circular solutions for higher TRL with prototypes at lower TRLs developed in the RAW project, focusing on how these tools support decision-making around exploitation pathways.
2. To extract insights into the broader structural challenges and leverage points affecting the integration of hemp fibers—particularly CNC-knitted tensile membranes—into construction markets, across European contexts, with focus on the Alpine region.

By combining speculative and practical lenses, the study highlights how structured tools can help small actors (such as startups or research groups) rapidly engage with complex innovation ecosystems without oversimplifying them.

METHOD AND MATERIALS

The research design followed a multi-stage, transdisciplinary approach that combined expert elicitation, participatory ecosystem mapping, and speculative business modeling within the context of the European hemp construction sector. The aim was to explore the integration of CNC-knitting as a niche digital fabrication technology within early-stage biobased architectural construction value chains.

In the six months leading up to a 1.5-day co-creation workshop, the first author conducted exploratory conversations with hemp-focused researchers from the RAW project. These dialogues provided early insights into sectoral dynamics and helped identify key actors in the European hemp ecosystem, particularly on the supply side. A preliminary stakeholder map was created by the first author using an adapted TIS framework tailored to the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) sector (Vasseur & Kings, 2025), and was iteratively developed through desk research, social media outreach (including LinkedIn posts inviting public input), and feedback from RAW consortium members. This mapping process included a geographic and actor-based giga mapping exercise (Sevaldson, 2011) on a Miroboard, visualizing the relationships across farming, processing, fabrication, and intermediary roles. A co-authored participant list of expert stakeholders was assembled, mostly from the supply chain side. One of the co-authors, with an established network in fast-growing architectural materials, curated a shortlist of invitees based on relevance, regional proximity, and active involvement in hemp-based construction value chains. More than 15 experts were invited, spanning diverse roles—from farmers and intermediary processors to machine developers and yarn producers. Ultimately, 9 participants attended, primarily representing the supply side. These included hemp cultivators, integrators, and entrepreneurs developing hemp-based panels. While their perspectives offered valuable insight into upstream challenges and opportunities, the group did not include digital fabrication actors or CNC-knitting industry representatives beyond the RAW researchers themselves. This absence of digital enablers was notable, given the technical focus of the project. Nonetheless, the participants brought rich and contrasting views on business models and political-economic approaches—ranging from cooperative and commons-based strategies to more traditional capital-driven models focused on scaling through machinery investments and logistics optimization.

The workshop design was iteratively developed to reflect both practical insights and theoretical scaffolding. Throughout this period, the co-authors collaborated continuously,

with parallel workstreams focused on technical developments (e.g., fiber processing and prototyping) and macro-environmental scenario planning.

The co-creation workshop itself was divided into two main stages. On the first day, participants engaged in a structured review and discussion of the ecosystem map, evaluating the proposed actor categories, relationships, and blind spots. The first author facilitated and took extensive notes. The second day began with short provocations and insights sharing from industrial actors (notably in farming, machinery, and fiber processing) and was followed by a speculative business modeling session. In this exercise, the first author and one co-author presented two fictional but grounded business cases: one for a design office, offering the consultancy around design, modeling and digital fabrication prototyping for hemp-based CNC-knitted architectural elements, while another company is a “knit-on-demand” CNC-knitting fabrication firm, that has extensive park of CNC-knitting machines and is able to produce complex textile surfaces using hemp yarn. These two fictional companies were situated within a Circular Business Model Canvas, and participants collaboratively mapped their potential relationships with these models—reflecting on opportunities, constraints, and roles from their own sectors. The discussion is documented in notes, which are mapped onto the canvas.

The ***Thematic analysis of the workshop notes*** focused primarily on *pain* and *gain* points identified by the participants regarding the uptake of hemp-based materials in construction, and the feasibility of integrating niche digital technologies like CNC-knitting. Reflections on the DRASTIC ecosystem mapping and business model tools, applied in the RAW research, were guided by a self-reflective and dialogical analysis between the first and last authors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ecosystem map of hemp fibers for AEC anno 2025: In the RAW project, researchers already embedded in the hemp and fiber sectors collaborated with the first author—approaching the industry with a fresh, theory-informed perspective supported by the DRASTIC project and insights from other building materials—to construct a preliminary mapping of key ecosystem actors. This mapping identified a diverse but unevenly connected set of stakeholders. Farmers, often operating at small scale, expressed interest in hemp cultivation but remained constrained by market uncertainty, labor intensity, and limited infrastructure. Processing facilities are largely outdated or absent in Alpine regions, with existing centers often located hundreds of kilometers away, posing significant logistical and economic barriers. Researchers and technologists are advancing niche applications such as CNC-knitting and coreless winding, though their compatibility with current biomass flows remains limited. Intermediary organizations and NGOs play vital roles in connecting the actors, but their influence varies significantly by geography. At the end of the value chain, architects and designers are emerging as innovation drivers, yet struggle with unreliable supply chains, performance validation, and regulatory hurdles. Meanwhile, policy and procurement bodies appear under-engaged, often limited by outdated frameworks and budgetary models that do not yet accommodate bio-based or circular alternatives.

Discussion about possible scenarios for a desirable or likely ecosystem anno 2030: During the workshop discussions on potential ecosystem configurations, participants debated the viability of small-scale, decentralized models versus larger, more centralized approaches to hemp-based construction. This prompted reflection on different business model trajectories, including cooperative structures, commoning practices, and franchise-based replication models. A recurring theme was the importance of knowledge flows and institutional memory, particularly in decentralized systems where technical and organizational know-how cannot be easily centralized or standardized. Several pain and gain points for the wider uptake of hemp in the AEC sector were identified, many of which lie outside the control of researchers and small medium enterprises (SMEs). These include financial bottlenecks, gaps in infrastructure

investment, and the absence of regulatory incentives. As a result, participants emphasized the critical role of financial intermediaries and policy makers in shaping the direction and inclusivity of bio-based innovation systems, particularly through their influence on capital flows, subsidy schemes, and certification frameworks.

Pain points, with focus on the Alpine region: The Alpine region faces a complex constellation of pain points that limit the viability and scalability of hemp-based construction innovations. Foremost among these is the fragmentation of value chains, with cultivation, processing, and fabrication often geographically and institutionally disconnected. This is compounded by a lack of regional infrastructure, particularly decortication and scutching facilities, resulting in high transport costs and inefficient bale logistics. The absence of standards and fiber grading systems further hinders quality assurance, certification, and market integration. Advanced fabrication methods like CNC-knitting and coreless winding are technologically misaligned with currently available hemp yarns, which remain brittle, inconsistent, and prone to breakage. These technical challenges are embedded within broader institutional and policy vacuums, including the absence of support for bio-based construction in public procurement and carbon accounting systems—gaps clearly visible in regions like Tyrol. Beyond technical and regulatory issues, socio-cultural mistrust—such as skepticism toward cooperatives and the persistent stigma around hemp—weakens collaborative models for hemp-uptake, while the high entry costs for specialized machinery and legal compliance exclude many smaller actors. Temporal constraints, such as narrow harvesting windows and processing bottlenecks, exacerbate material inefficiencies. Additionally, both digital and physical disconnects inhibit the integration of locally produced yarns into high-spec fabrication workflows of digital knitting and robotic winding.

Gain Points, with focus on the Alpine region: Despite structural challenges, the Alpine region also presents a number of strategic advantages for advancing biobased construction innovation. There is a notably high level of stakeholder enthusiasm for bio-based materials. This momentum is reinforced by the presence of growing cross-border networks and consortia, which enable knowledge exchange and collaborative experimentation. The cascading value potential of hemp—ranging from high-performance textiles and composites to insulation panels—enhances its economic viability, particularly when value chains are creatively structured. Encouragingly, several yarn producers, along with established flax processors, have shown willingness to experiment with hemp under the right technical and financial conditions. In parallel, digital fabrication methods like CNC-knitting offer significant design adaptability, weight reduction, and reusability, aligning well with circular construction goals. Regionally, political openings are emerging. For example, the Tyrolean government has begun integrating life cycle assessments (LCA) and biobased procurement into public projects, such as regional signage made from hemp composites. Finally, to optimize emerging systems, participants emphasized the role of spatial optimization models for reducing logistics-related emissions and costs. Calls were made for an atlas of CNC-knitting fabrication and decortication facilities, inspired by precedents in urban circularity mapping (e.g., Verga & Khan, 2022), which could serve as critical planning tools for infrastructure and link the actors more efficiently together.

Economic Geography - Lock-Ins and Transition Dynamics: The transition toward a circular, hemp-based construction economy is deeply shaped by economic geography and systemic lock-ins. A clear core-periphery dynamic exists: Eastern European regions such as the Baltic region, Ukraine and East Germany retain large-scale cultivation capacity and processing knowledge, while Western Alpine areas, though lacking infrastructure, are emerging as design and innovation hubs. However, the transition is hindered by bioregional fragmentation, with administrative borders impeding integrated planning. Alternative frameworks, such as watershed-based bioregionalism offer promising pathways for supply chain coordination. Across Europe, knowledge geographies remain uneven: France, Belgium,

and East Germany maintain valuable expertise and machine networks, while regions like Northern Italy and parts of the Alps face discontinuity due to the loss of cooperative models and processing skills. Meanwhile, rising global interest—particularly from China’s expanding hemp industry—poses *perceived* geo-economic risks for Europe if coordinated R&D and material sovereignty strategies are not established. Several systemic lock-ins further constrain this transition. Technical lock-ins arise from the incompatibility between CNC-knitting’s demand for uniform, high-performance yarns and the inconsistent output of current regional hemp processing. Social and cultural lock-ins—including stigma, mistrust in cooperatives, and aesthetic preferences shaped by retting discoloration—affect both farmer engagement and architectural design uptake. Additionally, policy lock-ins, such as regulatory ambiguities around *tetrahydrocannabinol* (THC) content and procurement practices favor conventional materials

Niche Opportunities: CNC-Knitted Hemp Membranes: CNC-knitted hemp membranes represent a compelling niche within a niche of lightweight tensile structures, offering a high-aesthetic, low-volume entry point into the bio-based construction sector. Their unique materiality and digital fabrication potential make them particularly suited for shading devices, indoor spatial structures, architectural pavilions, and high-end retrofits, where visibility and innovation carry strategic weight. In the context of the RAW project, such applications serve as effective proof-of-concept platforms, generating stakeholder interest and legitimacy while facilitating ecosystem alignment. The scalability of this approach lies in its compatibility with digital fabrication networks, enabling a “knit-on-demand” model where decentralized yarn producers and design offices collaborate through shared digital file systems and CNC-knit fabrication operations. However, full deployment remains constrained by materials R&D challenges, particularly the need to improve yarn consistency, tension performance, and brittleness—issues that demand targeted pre-treatment, extensive testing and eventually specific digital design models, dedicated to the use of natural yarns for large-scale application in order to meet architectural and structural standards.

A collaborative circular business model for two imaginary firms ‘design to production service’ and ‘CNC-knitting on demand’: As part of the business modeling workshop, participants engaged in a speculative design exercise using the DRASTIC collaborative circular business model framework, which integrates material cycles with ecosystem relationships. Two fictional companies were prototyped, both situated in the Innsbruck region: Company A, a “design-to-production service” for spatial and acoustic solutions using hemp-based knitted elements and Company B, a “CNC-knitting on demand” firm. Represented by two RAW researchers, these imagined companies were placed within the model’s grey (material flow) and green (ecosystem value) columns, enabling participants to map out phases such as material collection, sale, take-back, and recovery, alongside key relational questions (e.g., who helps whom, with what, and why). The scenario unfolded with Company A offering design services to building owners, while Company B provided knitting-fabrication services, raising questions of supply chain logic, geographic proximity, and economies of scale. Discussion extended into logistical and infrastructural dependencies, such as the number of farmers and hectares required to supply hemp yarn for a building-scale membrane, accounting for rotational farming systems and the need for decentralized knowledge systems. Participants questioned whether digital files might be sent to fabrications in cheaper locations, highlighting geopolitical and economic considerations, including trade tariffs, the role of IP in supply chain optimization, and the possibility of flat-packing or unraveling membranes to reduce transport emissions. Yarn ownership and access to materials sparked further debate, with participants exploring subscription models, adaptive design services, and rental systems, where yarn producers might retain ownership, with textile being returned for unraveling and reuse of remaining yarn for further re-knitting of reiterated designs given the yarn amount. The absence of certification schemes, challenges in material

storage, and the need for open-access CNC-knitting machine parks with custom specifications (e.g. gauge variation to accommodate the variety of hemp yarn thicknesses) were also flagged as critical gaps. While the model helped clarify the relationships and missing actors, especially those responsible for building deconstruction and yarn recovery, were noted, alongside the decentralized nature of existing CNC-knitting research facilities across Europe. A recurring concern was material availability, which remains a limiting factor for scaling up such a speculative business ecosystem before more logistics infrastructure and machine networks are in place.

Discussion of combining and testing the methodological frameworks at Low Technology Readiness Levels: The study explored the applicability of combining and testing established methodological frameworks—particularly the TIS framework and the collaborative circular business model canvas—in contexts characterized by low Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs). While these frameworks had been developed and partially tested within the higher-TRL scope of the DRASTIC project, their application to emerging technologies such as CNC-knitted hemp architectural membranes allowed for a critical examination of their flexibility and limitations.

One key insight was the necessity of clearly defining a tangible product or product range, as services alone were insufficient to anchor stakeholder engagement or support value chain modeling. The TIS framework proved particularly helpful in mapping actor roles and functions, yet during the business modeling phase, participants often defaulted to imagining demand beginning with contractors or product traders, sidelining intermediary roles. Interestingly, while intermediaries received less focus in the initial mapping, pain points related to certification, logistics, and knowledge transfer emerged prominently during the second-day discussions, highlighting their structural importance in enabling or obstructing system-level transitions. This suggests that adapting innovation frameworks to low-TRL contexts not only requires rethinking assumptions about actor behavior and demand pathways, but also foregrounds the fragility of emergent ecosystems still lacking institutional and infrastructural anchors.

Limitations: While the study provides valuable insights into early-stage ecosystem dynamics and circular business modeling, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the findings are context-specific, shaped by the Alpine region's fragmented infrastructure and the participant group's supply-side focus. The absence of actors from the CNC-knitting fabrication industry or digital technology providers limits the breadth of perspectives on downstream integration and technical scalability. Additionally, as the workshop involved a relatively small and regionally situated group of stakeholders, the generalizability of insights to other geographies or industrial contexts should be approached with caution. Finally, the speculative nature of the business modeling exercise, while useful for exploring future scenarios, may not fully capture real-world constraints faced during implementation at scale.

CONCLUSION

This study explored the potential of applying ecosystem mapping and collaborative circular business modeling at low Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) within the emerging field of hemp-based digital construction technologies, with a focus on CNC-knitted architectural membranes. By testing speculative mapping tools in real-world stakeholder contexts, the research surfaced critical insights into the infrastructural, regulatory, and socio-technical barriers that currently inhibit the wider uptake of hemp in the AEC sector.

A key outcome was the recognition that transition processes in bio-based construction systems are deeply interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral—requiring engagement not only with architects and engineers but also with logistics experts, geographers, social scientists, innovation managers, and most importantly, practitioners and operators on the ground. The exercise also highlighted the importance of building inclusive ecosystems that integrate both

supply and demand side actors as well as often-overlooked intermediaries, who play a decisive role in certification, quality control, logistics, and knowledge exchange. As both the DRASTIC and the RAW project are still in its early stages, future iterations will benefit from further integration of environmental impact modeling, particularly life cycle assessments, to align design and material strategies with measurable sustainability targets.

The insights from this study and this *test* will directly inform the refinement and final publication of the ecosystem mapping framework and circular business model for the AEC sector currently under development within the DRASTIC project.

Given the structural limitations faced by researchers and SMEs—especially in Alpine and Southern European regions—policy makers are urged to act. Ten actionable steps are proposed: from investing in regional decortication infrastructure and adaptive machinery, to establishing grading systems, launching performance-based certification pilots, and supporting decentralized, cooperative ownership models. Broader measures should include capacity-building in rural communities, cross-sector innovation platforms, and public procurement policies rooted in LCA logic. Finally, regulatory harmonization around Cannabidiol/THC thresholds and material marketing pathways is essential to unlock a truly circular and just bio-based construction future.

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Circularity in the Built Environment 2025

Regulation, policy and social aspects in a circular built environment

A multidisciplinary Categorization of challenges of reuse of residential buildings.

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Keywords: Circular economy; Circular built environment; Sustainable Urban Development, Reuse of buildings, urban regeneration.

ABSTRACT

The reuse of buildings offers substantial environmental, economic, and social benefits, presenting a circular, sustainable alternative to new construction and urban sprawl. However, the multidisciplinary nature of building reuse, especially in historic residential buildings, involves diverse stakeholders with often conflicting interests, such as heritage preservation, financial viability, and environmental efficiency. These complexities pose significant challenges.

This study aims to identify and categorize the challenges associated with the reuse of residential buildings from a multidisciplinary perspective. Moreover, it maps the relationships between these challenges and their occurrence at various scales. By doing so it addresses the core research question: What are the key challenges and conflicts of interest that hinder decision-making in the reuse of residential buildings?

Through a semi-systematic literature review followed by thematic analysis, the study identifies 75 sub-challenges categorized into 10 overarching themes: (1) economic viability and financial challenges, (2) building conditions, (3) design-technical challenges, (4) location challenges, (5) decision making, (6) policy and regulations, (7) knowledge, capacity, and skills, (8) culture, perception, and awareness, (9) surrounding community, and (10) timeline. The findings highlight strong interconnections among these themes, with financial viability emerging as a critical influence on many other aspects. Existing research on building reuse often adopts a narrow disciplinary focus, lacks a holistic, multidisciplinary perspective, and overlooks the interplay between different challenges, particularly in residential buildings.

This study addresses these gaps by providing a conceptual framework that categorizes and maps interrelations between the challenges of residential building reuse across multiple disciplines. The framework serves as a resource for policymakers, researchers, and educators in understanding the complexities of building reuse. Additionally, it can be utilized to further develop strategies, policies, and decision-support tools to effectively address these challenges.

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An Indigenous Approach to Community Building Longevity Through Retrofits

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Keywords: Circular Construction, Indigenous, Retrofits, Resilience

The Green Building Technology Access Centre at the Southern Alberta Institute of Technology has been leading several projects in partnership with Indigenous organizations and communities in Alberta, Canada. These projects are focused on fostering an understanding of aging Indigenous community infrastructure and developing tools and resources that support Indigenous-led solutions for long-term success and autonomy.

The research team, in collaboration with Indigenous partners, developed an engagement process that is founded on Indigenous community and environmental values blended with current retrofit approaches and building code requirements, resulting in a Two-Eyed Seeing approach. Through development of a Relationship Agreement, project team participants established how parties would work together to listen and learn from each other, acknowledge that Indigenous knowledge belonged to Indigenous peoples, and collaboration decision-making would guide all participants. From there, a series of in-person meetings and community workshops were co-led by the project participants to present ideas and collect feedback from the communities and subject matter experts (SMEs). Effort was made to ensure Indigenous-based SMEs were also included in the activities and all resources and tools developed through the project(s) were created to function according to the long-term needs of the communities.

The community building retrofits comprised of updating an existing building to boost performance, functionality, or safety. This process often involves upgrading systems or components to meet modern standards, improve energy efficiency, or address specific vulnerabilities like climate risks. A major advantage of retrofits is the ability to significantly enhance a building's resilience and sustainability without requiring extensive demolition or rebuilding, rather focusing on extending or improving the longevity of existing infrastructure. Several building-specific analyses were undertaken to support the Indigenous engagement activities and included conducting high-level building assessments, conducting Level II ASHRAE Energy Audits, and working directly with building operations staff through knowledge sharing and learning activities.

Feedback from building operations staff and communities highlighted several stressors that Indigenous and remote communities face more than other areas. They are often the most impacted by climate events—such as extreme heat, prolonged cold snaps, and permafrost thaw—and frequently contend with aging infrastructure and high energy costs. Climate change is expected to accelerate the need for major repairs in these areas, placing additional strain on

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already limited resources. Retrofits of community buildings not only reduces energy use and emissions, and increases the longevity of the infrastructure, but also improves resilience, comfort, and health outcomes.

Critical success factors identified in developing a lasting program within communities were identified as: flexibility in all approaches while maintaining Indigenous perspectives and knowledge in the form of Two-Eyed Seeing; and, seeking comprehensive solutions that encourage local capacity and create lasting safety, training, and economic benefits. Key priorities requiring action include: developing local Indigenous workforces with culturally appropriate, trauma-informed training that remains in the community and is regularly updated; establishing self-determined funding without restrictive requirements that replenishes annually; and addresses gaps in construction practices including culturally sensitive contractor training, rigorous inspection processes, and long-term operations and maintenance planning and implementation. Finally, ensuring adequate follow up to support continuous advancement for Indigenous and remote community infrastructure and local residents.

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Digital Register for Demolition Material and Construction Waste: Improving Circularity in Finnish Building Projects

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Keywords: construction and demolition waste, digitalization, regulation, reporting, reuse

ABSTRACT

During construction and demolition projects, significant amounts of different wastes are generated. EU target to utilize 70 % of construction and demolition waste has not been reached in Finland. The new Construction Act 751/2023 has an emphasis on decarbonization and circularity in the built environment. New regulation (16 § in the Act 751/2023) came into force from the beginning of 2025. It requires submitting reports on produced demolition material and construction waste from all construction and demolition projects that require a building permit, demolition permit or demolition notice. The objective of the report is to provide detailed information regarding the types and quantities of demolition materials and construction waste. The party undertaking the project is responsible for filling an estimate form when applying for the permit or submitting the notice and filling a realization form once the project is completed.

As by the new Construction Act the report must be submitted to a database managed by the Finnish Environment Institute. The reports are submitted through a new national information system called Rapu, which has been developed by the Finnish Environment Institute in collaboration with the Ministry of the Environment and other key stakeholders.

Digitalization of the reporting unifies the information related to demolition materials and enhances the use of it. The objective of the reporting and the new system is e.g., to support bridging the gap between supply and demand of demolition materials and to enable steering and supervision of the authorities. Additionally, the new system and database also aims to improve the statistics on construction and demolition waste which can be used for mandatory reporting on local and European level. The information submitted to the database may as well be used for research purposes. The first version of the new system enables submitting the mandatory reports from projects according to the new Act, and the system will be developed to also enable notifying on availability of construction and demolition materials for reuse and recycling and thus increase the circularity in construction.

Construction Act. 21.4.2023/751.

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Envisioning Circular Futures in Shrinking Cities and Regions: Goal Dependencies Underpinning Transition Drivers

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Keywords: circular economy, goal dependency, governance, shrinking cities, urban shrinkage

ABSTRACT

As the circular economy gains traction as a novel sustainability paradigm, its translation into local and regional policy agendas reveals a spectrum of interpretations shaped by divergent goals. While circularity is often presented as a means of achieving sustainable development, its adoption is highly contingent on context-specific visions and priorities. This paper explores how circular economy agendas are mobilised in two structurally shrinking European regions, Satakunta (Finland) and Parkstad Limburg (Netherlands), and how these policy agendas reflect underlying “goal dependencies” in urban and regional governance. Drawing on Evolutionary Governance Theory and comparative discourse analysis, the study examines how enduring visions of economic renewal, image reconstruction, and institutional legitimacy shape the practical deployment of circular economy initiatives in the built environment. In Satakunta, circularity is aligned with industrial modernisation, growth stimulation, and foreign investment attraction, continuing a long-standing developmental trajectory. In contrast, the policy discourse in Parkstad focuses on circular construction as a tool to combat regional stigma, restore public trust, and reposition the region within national and European circular economy narratives. In both cases, the circular economy vision functions less as a predefined endpoint and more as a strategic instrument for enacting future-oriented governance goals. The findings highlight how governance coalitions in shrinking cities and regions mobilise circular discourses to sustain reinvention, address structural decline, and reassert relevance, underscoring the importance of unpacking local goal orientations in understanding circular transition pathways.

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Hazardous substances in reused concrete elements – legal insights from Sweden

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Keywords: Reuse, Hazardous substances, Precast concrete, Building actor, Legislation

Interest in reusing construction materials is growing, driven by the need to reduce the climate impact of building projects. In particular, the reuse of concrete products show significant potential. However, developers must be confident that reused materials meet quality and safety standards. An essential aspect of the quality assurance is to ensure at a sufficient level that any content of hazardous substances cannot cause problems for the environment and health today and in the future. The ongoing Horizon 2020 project ReCreate explores a wide range of challenges to scaling up reuse of prefabricated concrete elements in construction. Within that project, a review of legislation linked to hazardous substances in buildings was conducted, focusing the Swedish context. Relevant authorities were also consulted about their interpretation of legal requirements related to reuse of concrete elements. The aim was to provide an updated understanding of legal requirements and the need for guidance from both a property owner and developer perspective.

The review highlights the challenges of scaling up reuse, but also clarifies issues of significance for property owners who intend to transfer or sell products for reuse, and developers who wish to take over/buy/use products in new construction projects. One important challenge is the breadth of legislation that those actors need to comply with and the separation of it into product and waste legislation, based on a linear economy model. So far, concrete, authority guidance on how to navigate this regulatory landscape, promoting reuse of construction products, is very limited. For example, a developer in Sweden is responsible for ensuring that construction products meet several requirements, including protection with regard to hygiene, health and the environment. However, no guidance is given on handling of potential risk of indoor emissions when concrete elements are reused as building components. It is desirable that authorities coordinate better for more detailed guidance on which rules property owners and developers should adhere to in order to 1) be able to reuse construction products as construction products again, and 2) be able to temporarily store dismantled construction products without risking legal infringements due to the construction products being classified as waste. Further, it is important that the legislator develops - or the industry agrees on - a reasonable test methodology so that costs and time for testing do not become an obstacle to reuse. Finally, it is important that tests on relevant hazardous substances *are* carried out and subsequently clearly documented. Such test results, along with other quality assurance information, should be documented digitally and follow the reused elements in future applications and locations. The digital information, if also made openly available and searchable, will in addition facilitate scaled-up concrete reuse by increasing the conditions for dismantled products to be put back into use.

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Revitalizing Brickmaking for Industrial Heritage and Ecological Preservation

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Keywords: Brick production, industrial heritage, construction waste, environmental cleaning.

ABSTRACT

This study focuses on a deteriorating, abandoned brick production plant situated in an ecologically significant valley in Ankara. It investigates the potential for revitalizing the facility as a small-scale, continuous production site that not only preserves the region's historical tradition of brickmaking but also supports broader environmental sustainability goals. Central to this proposal is the integration of ceramic waste into the production cycle, contributing to both material reuse and ecological restoration.

The research begins with a comprehensive analysis of the valley's natural and urban development history, emphasizing its environmental value and long-standing industrial role. Results show that environmental decline has intensified and become more evident, overshadowing the gradual disappearance of the region's industrial heritage.

An on-site evaluation of the plant assesses its structural condition and architectural features to determine the feasibility of reactivation. Based on this assessment, a two-tiered material sourcing strategy is proposed. The first involves reclaiming usable ceramic waste—such as clay batches, broken bricks, and roof tiles—from the valley and nearby decommissioned facilities. The second source is the city's construction waste disposal site, which contains significant volumes of ceramic and clay-based debris from ongoing demolitions and excavations.

The proposed production model is illustrated through a diagrammatic scenario, emphasizing community engagement as an integral part of preserving this functional legacy. The study ultimately offers a scalable and adaptable model for linking industrial heritage conservation with environmental regeneration in similarly threatened landscapes.

INTRODUCTION

In contrast to the long-standing recognition of archaeological sites and classical architectural heritage, industrial heritage has only recently been acknowledged as a critical yet complex component of cultural legacy. Its preservation presents distinct challenges, as it intersects with social, economic, environmental, and political dimensions that often fall outside traditional conservation approaches (Cossons, 2016).

Preserving industrial heritage requires more than stabilizing or repurposing abandoned structures. These sites embody key milestones in the history of manufacturing, engineering, and construction (Cossons, 2016). Therefore, a successful strategy must go beyond adaptive reuse and address the full spectrum of industrial legacy. This includes the preservation of intangible values like historical functions, labor practices, environmental roles, and their evolving cultural significance (Leifeste & Stiefel, 2018).

A compelling case is Queen Street Mill in Burnley, Lancashire. This 19th-century textile factory has been preserved as the world's last operational steam-powered weaving shed. Unlike static exhibits, its functioning machinery allows visitors to experience industrial craftsmanship as a living, educational process (Southern, 2016).

Industrial heritage preservation should also consider aspects of sustainability, in reducing environmental impact and reinforcing cultural continuity (Leifeste & Stiefel, 2018;

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Vukmirović & Nikolić, 2023). Key strategies include reusing existing structures to lower material demand and emissions, minimizing demolition waste, and integrating ecological restoration through improved energy performance and greener infrastructure.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study focuses on Imrahor Valley, the Ceylan Tuğla brick plant, and the Tulumtaş disposal area in Ankara. It proposes a modest-scale brick production revival that preserves industrial heritage while promoting environmental regeneration through the reuse of clay and ceramic waste in production line.

Imrahor Valley: A Legacy of Brick Production and Environmental Significance in Ankara

Imrahor Valley, situated in southern Ankara Province, is notable for its distinct geological and ecological features. It forms part of a wider natural system that includes the Eymir and Mogan Lakes—originally a single water body—and Elmadağ, one of the tallest peaks in the area (Figure 01a) (Çevre ve Şehircilik Bakanlığı, 2015). The valley includes water streams, strong airflows, endemic biodiversity, and elevation differences of 70–80 meters (Çevre ve Şehircilik Bakanlığı, 2015).

In the 1920s, German planner Carl Christoph Lörcher designated the area as a protected zone, excluding it from construction as part of Ankara's early urban planning (Tunçer, 2020). This vision was reaffirmed in the 1930s by Hermann Jansen's master plan (Tunçer, 2020). However, the city's rapid population growth prompted changes.

In the 1950s, planners Raşit Uybadin and Nihat Yücel revised the city plan, maintaining the area's recreational status (Tekeli et al., 1991), even as informal housing and small-scale brick kilns emerged.

By the 1970s, about 25 brick production sites were operating in the valley (Tekeli et al., 1991; Şenyapılı, 2004; Sınacı & Özfindık, 2019). During the 1980s, official planning efforts continued to support the protection of Imrahor Valley's greenbelt and natural assets. However, in the 1990s, regulatory changes enabled partial master plans that drastically altered the valley's trajectory. As the area was rezoned for residential use, brick production became legally impermissible, leading to the widespread closure and abandonment of the brick kilns (Tıǧlı & Tuncer, 2023).

Urban renewal initiatives soon followed, prompting significant public protests and legal challenges. Despite this resistance, large-scale construction accelerated. By the 2010s and 2020s, mass housing projects had spread across the valley floor, disrupting ecological flows, reshaping waterways, and degrading soil integrity (Figure 01b). These topographical interventions resulted in profound and potentially irreversible environmental damage (Sınacı & Özfindık, 2019).

Consequently, most brick facilities in the valley were left in disrepair. Some found informal reuses such as waste-sorting sites, photography locations, or recreational spaces, while many continued to decay. One structure was officially renovated into a public library and social center for waste workers (Gaia Journal, 2017; Öztürk, 2017; NTV News, 2021). Another, which remained operational until the early 2020s, was selected as the case study due to its representative scale, typology, and preserved materials (Figure 01c).

Figure 01a: Imrahor Valley on the map (adapted by the author from Yandex Maps, 2025)

Figure 01b: Densified construction activity encroaching upon the valley floor (Author, January 2025)

Figure 01c: Roofs of a former brick production plant in the valley (Author, November 2024)

Ceylan Tuğla: The Last Abandoned Brick Plant in Imrahor Valley

Ceylan Tuğla, officially named Ceylan Earth-Based Products Industry Trade Limited Company, was founded in the 1970s in Ankara's Imrahor Valley. The facility occupied a 50,000-square-meter site and specialized in the production of fired clay bricks, offering both solid and perforated varieties made from heavy and light clay mixtures (Ceylan Tuğla, 2009).

Figure 02a: The abandoned plant in the valley's natural landscape (Author, November 2024)

Figure 02b: The plant, with final products scattered around as waste (Author, January 2025)

Figure 02c: Interior view of the plant (Author, January 2025)

Its location near the city center provided a logistical advantage, minimizing transportation costs and supporting its long-term viability. The main production hall measured roughly 12 meters in width, 120 meters in length, and 3 meters in height (Figure 02a-b-c). The architectural layout reflected a standard brick kiln design, comprising a single vaulted volume with 15 regularly spaced side openings for efficient brick loading and unloading. The building was constructed from solid clay bricks bonded with cement mortar and finished with exterior plaster. The vault

walls were 2 meters thick at the base, narrowing to 1.5 meters toward the ridge. The roof included integrated firing components, with remaining sections clad in traditional clay tiles. Site visits in 2024 and 2025, four years post-closure, showed the building remained structurally sound with minimal settlement. However, the roof had suffered major damage due to illegal removal of steel elements, creating multiple openings. Overall, the structure maintained its integrity despite these impairments (Figure 02a-b-c).

Figure 03a: Destroyed roof tiles of the plant (Author, January 2025)
Figure 03b: Destroyed surrounding walls of the plant (Author, January 2025)
Figure 03c: Extracted clay from around the riverbed (Author, January 2025)
Figure 03d: The open-air stock of extracted clay around the plant (Author, January 2025)

The plant's surroundings suffered from unregulated abandonment, with construction debris including roof tiles stamped from the 1960s, fragmented brick garden walls, and discarded hollow brick batches (Figure 03a-b). Extracted clay stored around the site before closure remains unused (Figure 03c-d). This clay and debris form a large, chemically inert waste mass. About 24 other former brick plants in the valley share similar conditions, though total waste quantities remain unmeasured.

Tulumtaş Disposal Area: Construction Waste Management Facility

Urban development in Ankara has surged over the past two decades, driving frequent demolitions and rapid new construction. Selective demolition often recycles valuable materials like metals, while ceramic and concrete wastes are discarded as inert. These materials are transported to Tulumtaş Disposal Area, the city's largest facility for inert waste management (Figure 04a). Concurrently, new construction—especially residential towers with multi-level underground parking—produces vast amounts of excavated soil, which is also deposited at Tulumtaş, accumulating alongside broken bricks and roof tiles (Figure 04b-c).

Located within 30 kilometers, this facility offers clay-based waste resources that are by far more extensive, providing significant potential for sustainable raw material recovery.

Figure 04a. Roadway between the Tulumtaş Disposal Area and the proposed brick plant site (Adapted by the author from Yandex Maps, 2025).

Figure 04b. Broken hollow bricks scattered in debris at the Tulumtaş Disposal Area (Photograph by the author, December 2023).

Figure 04c. Excavated soil from construction sites deposited at the Tulumtaş Disposal Area (Photograph by the author, December 2023).

Scenario Development for a Circular Approach: Integrating Industrial Legacy and Environmental Protection

Fired clay bricks are valued for their strength, durability, and resistance to harsh conditions, making them among the most enduring building materials—capable of lasting thousands of years, as evidenced by ancient settlements (Fernandes et al., 2010). Even after a building's service life ends, bricks can often be salvaged and reused as intact wall sections or individual units (Nordby et al., 2009).

Recovery from demolished masonry is significantly improved through heat treatment, which breaks down mortar and enables cleaner separation without damaging the bricks. This method is more efficient than traditional hand demolition in preserving material integrity although it increases the embodied energy (Mulder et al., 2007).

When reuse is not feasible, fired clay waste can be crushed and ground to substitute up to 30% of raw clay in new brick production without compromising quality (Demir & Orhan, 2003). Crushed bricks also serve as recycled aggregates in concrete, providing acceptable structural strength (Zhu & Zhu, 2020), or as partial substitutes for cement in geopolymer-based materials, suitable for both precast and cast-in-situ applications (Youssef et al., 2019).

Based on the collected background data, the proposed strategy begins by utilizing the site's existing clay and ceramic waste, then transitions to sourcing materials from the Tulumtaş Disposal Area, establishing a sustainable system.

RESULTS

The preparatory phase emphasizes reusing clean, sturdy tiles and bricks, particularly those stamped with dates from 1966, which carry important historical value. Although many bricks and tiles were found broken during site inspections, this phase still offers significant potential for promoting environmental sustainability, supported by literature indicating that up to one-third of virgin clay can be replaced with recycled content. The proposed model transforms this waste into new material for production, as illustrated in Figure 05.

Figure 05: New raw material obtainment process using the surrounding waste

The proposal suggests preserving the brick plant in its original function, recognizing not only the physical structure but also its operational role as a key element of heritage. By maintaining the production process, the site can become a living museum—an active space that safeguards the legacy of brickmaking while remaining accessible and engaging for the community. This approach preserves both the industrial character, and the pastoral memories tied to the local territory.

CONCLUSION

The proposed approach is adaptable to similar contexts, as small-scale brick production in riverbed areas is common in many regions.

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Towards Circular and Sustainable Housing in Nigeria: The Potential of Circular Building Labels

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Keywords: Circular Building Label, Occupants operations, Nigeria, Decarbonization, Sustainability traits, Sustainable Housing

ABSTRACT

This research investigates the critical opportunity of providing sustainable housing in Nigeria, where a significant deficit is compounded by unsustainable informal construction practices that contribute to environmental degradation and the need for documented residential carbon emissions. The study explores the transformative potential of Circular Economy (CE) principles within the Nigerian residential building sector, proposing the implementation of Circular Building Labels (CBLs) as a mechanism to promote resource efficiency, minimize waste, and reduce the environmental impact of residential buildings. The central research problem lies in the contradiction between the pressing need for housing and the unsustainable nature of current construction methods and occupants' operations; circular construction, facilitated by CBLs, offers a promising avenue by encouraging material reuse, potentially lowering costs, and formalizing sustainable local initiatives. This research aims to understand the transferability of CE principles to Nigeria and how contextual potentials can be integrated into locally appropriate circular construction processes.

Employing a mixed-methods approach, this study synthesized insights from policy documents and academic literature on sustainable construction in Nigeria, alongside international case studies and best practices from Finland and Germany. To understand the specific local context, the methodology incorporated a qualitative investigation, including a case study survey within the Apo-Dutse District, F.C.T. – Abuja Municipal, Nigeria, focusing on the social and psychological factors influencing the adoption of green buildings. This local investigation identified barriers and opportunities for circular construction beyond those evident in literature reviews. Furthermore, the study utilized the EDGE app to estimate potential emissions reductions in a proposed residential estate project in Apo-Dutse, Abuja, providing a quantitative dimension to the analysis of decarbonization pathways. The research also included a comparative study of institutional frameworks supporting CE in the construction industry across

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Nigeria, Finland, and Germany, drawing on a multi-level qualitative literature analysis of 228 relevant documents (norms, regulations, and cultural cognitive institutions).

Key findings reveal that while Nigeria is in the early stages of formal CE adoption compared to Finland and Germany, there is significant potential in the formal sector for integrating circular principles to address the housing deficit sustainably. The local investigation highlighted socio-cultural factors, a need for occupants' sustainability traits, and institutional enhancement as crucial considerations for successful implementation. The EDGE analysis indicated a potential for significant reductions in energy, water, and material-related emissions through efficiency measures. The comparative analysis of CE roadmaps revealed Nigeria's foundational stage, underscoring the need for strengthened policy and infrastructure. The study identified fundamental institutional and behavioral traits that underpin sustainable housing adoption, including a need for nature reciprocity and being humane, as well as cultural norms that favor long-term gains.

This research demonstrates that a cross-country comparative review, combined with local context-specific qualitative investigation and quantitative assessment, provides a more comprehensive understanding of Nigeria's sustainable housing opportunities and challenges. The proposed CBL framework, informed by these findings, offers a pathway to integrate social, environmental, and economic considerations for Nigeria's more sustainable and resilient housing sector. The study contributes to knowledge by providing a context-specific approach to sustainable housing in Nigeria, focusing on CE-led construction decarbonization, behavioral transformation, and robust institutions. It also offers practical implications for policymakers and industry stakeholders by highlighting the need for tailored decarbonization strategies, addressing character flaws hindering sustainable practices, and integrating CE principles. This research ultimately envisions a future where environmentally friendly residential estates become standard practice in Nigeria.

Waste or Building Material? Decision Moments as Catalysts for Circular Construction

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Keywords: waste regulation, permitting processes, participatory governance, deconstruction, reuse

ABSTRACT

It is prohibited in most jurisdictions to build with waste materials. However, there are many cases where waste materials could be used for construction. To reduce waste and to recycle waste the EU has the so-called End-of-Waste (EoW) status to enable the recovery of materials and products from a finality as waste. However, a problem of the End-of-Waste status is that it is rather difficult to agree on criteria (Johansson and Forsgren, 2020). More importantly, for the circular economy in construction, the End-of-Waste status means an enormous obstacle for firms wishing to reuse materials and materials “automatically” classified as waste, because for many of these materials and products there do not exist criteria at the national level. This includes legislation and interpretation of the European EoW regulations as a guideline in absence of legislation (Johansson, 2023) Therefore, having to engage with an End-of-Waste process is costly and time-consuming for firms.

In this context, it appears to be a sensible approach to prevent waste from forming in the first place. In deconstructing a building (as opposed to traditional demolition), there is a pathway to prevent the waste status to be attached to reuseable building materials. However, whereas technically, deconstruction is relatively uncomplicated, the regulatory aspects are multifaceted. In this contribution, examples of regulatory decision moments in Finland, Germany and the Netherlands are examined. In all cases, actors involved in the reuse of deconstructed products/materials have actively engaged with the local authorities to shape decision-making about the waste status of these materials or products. Since local government is usually the permit-issuing authority, such pro-active engagement can help set precedents for other actors. Rather than mechanically applying “the rules”, this kind of interaction with authorities is a form of participatory governance that can strengthen the legitimacy of decision-making (Fischer, 2006).

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Organised in collaboration between TU Delft (the Netherlands), Tampere University (Finland) and the Horizon 2020 project ‘Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy’ (ReCreate) and its partners, CiBEn2025 brought together pioneering researchers from all over Europe and beyond to share knowledge on the state-of-the-art on circular construction. Everyone was warmly invited to contribute their circular construction expertise to CiBEn2025 by submitting their contribution by May 30, 2025, in one or more of the following themes:

Urban mining

- Identification and quantification of urban mines for secondary construction products
- Material Stock and Flow Analysis (MSFA)
- Urban mining as a political issue of economic scarcity and self-sufficiency

Circular decommissioning of buildings and infrastructure

- Smart methods and tools for deconstruction aiming at reuse
- Smart methods and tools for demolition aiming at recycling

Circular supply chain management in construction

- Digital information management tools
- Tracing and tracking technologies of secondary products and materials
- Circularity passports
- Value creation by digitalisation

Quality management of reused building parts and recycled construction materials

- Ensuring performance and durability
- Managing risks for health and safety
- Standards development to support circularity
- End of Waste criteria and process

Circular design, construction materials and products

- Reused building materials and products
- Recycled building materials
- Design for adaptability and disassembly (DfA, DfD)
- Architectural, structural, building services, and other circular design
- Use of Building Information Modelling (BIM) and other digital tools
- Work processes in circular construction

Circularity and environmental assessment in the built environment

- Life cycle assessment of circular construction solutions
- Life cycle costing and life cycle profit of circular construction solutions
- Measuring social impact of circularity in the built environment

Circular construction and real estate business

- Circular value chains and business ecosystems
- Circular business models
- Diverse product, process and service innovations

- Value creation and value capture
- Added value from digitalisation

Regulation, policy and social aspects in a circular built environment

- Challenges and catalysts for circularity in the policy environment
- Policy tensions between circularity and other public policy
- Circularity, national security, and post-war reconstruction
- Circular policy-making and public procurement
- How circularity changes work in the construction sector

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